

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

WORLD CONFERENCE

on

**Contribution of Indian Knowledge
&**

Sanskrit to Humanity - 2023

विश्वसंस्कृतसम्मेलनम् २०२३

मानवतायै भारतीयज्ञानपरम्परायाः संस्कृतस्य च योगदानम्

SRINIVAS YOGA-SANSKRIT STUDIES & RESEARCH CENTRE

विश्वमाङ्गल्यम् - २३

WCCIKSH-23

February 24th To 26th 2023

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

NOTE

All papers presented in the Conference will be published in the Proceedings book after review with ISBN Number

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24th February 2023

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Jagadguru Srimanmadhavacharya Moola matha Samsthanam
Pontiff of Sri Rama Teertha Peetam, Shri kaniyooru Matha,Udupi

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4	The art of designing stable multicomponent alloys	Dr. Srinivas Veeturi

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Paper No. 1.01: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

An exploratory study of Rāmarājya with evidence from Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa: Internal Control Structure and Finance Governance Model

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ABSTRACT

‘Rāmarājya’ is an aspirational benchmark in administration standards as envisaged by Mahātmā Gandhi in his speeches and writings between 1920 and 1947. Its objective of good governance is the triumph of people, planet, and profit, evident during the reign of King Rāma, as described by Sage Vālmīki in the epic Rāmāyaṇa. The science of statecraft a.k.a ‘Arthaśāstra’ which was the basis of the good governance in Rāmarājya is not available today. This paper seeks to reconstruct the finance and related aspects of ancient Arthaśāstra (which existed at the time of Rāmāyaṇa) using practical case studies from Rāmāyaṇa. This would help understand primordial principles of accounting, economics and related legalities which can ensure good governance.

The paper adopts a qualitative inductive research approach using principles of grounded theory and hermeneutics. Data analysis includes textual and contextual analysis with thematic and discourse analysis. Two chapters from Ayodhyā kāṇḍa of Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa viz. ‘Nārājaka-sarga’ (2.67) and ‘Kaccit-sarga’ (2.100) have been considered for the study. Initial findings reveal significant coverage of the internationally recognized Committee of Sponsoring Organizations’ Internal control integrated framework in Rāmāyaṇa, along with other aspects which may potentially enhance the model. Finally, the paper encourages one to explore on having an indigenous framework for Internal controls and Finance Governance which can fit the mindset and ethos of Indian companies and their customers.

Keywords: Finance Governance, Internal control framework, Rāmāyaṇa, Indian Knowledge Systems, Arthaśāstra, Rāmarājya.

Paper No. 1.02: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Metals in Biology

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ABSTRACT

Metal are fundamental elements for the maintenance of lifespan of plants, animals and humans. They control many of our daily functions. Sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, zinc, iron, copper and manganese are some of the metals that are present in our body. Their absence or deficiency can cause growth disorders, severe malfunction, cancer or death. Their presence in excess can be toxic. They are also involved in communication of messages, maintenance of blood pressure, stability and regulation of DNA, genetics, proper functioning of nerve cells, muscle cells, brain and heart, supply of oxygen for digestion of food that provide energy for us to grow, walk, talk, etc. They play important roles in the synthesis of food that we eat every day. Rice, fruits, pulses, etc are prepared by plants through photosynthesis. In this talk, some of these aspects and role of metals will be highlighted.

Paper No.1.03: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Copper materials: From ancient civilization to COVID times

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ABSTRACT

The story of copper and its alloys is virtually a chronicle of human endeavor since man emerged from the Stone Age. The ubiquity of the copper materials contributing to every civilization, from the ancient Egyptians, Romans to modern day cultures around the world is noteworthy in the history of technology. In fact, one of the major "ages" or stages of human history is named after a copper alloy, bronze. Prior to 19th century, copper was used mainly for its mechanical properties, whereas since then its function expanded owing to its exceptional thermal and electrical conductivity. In the twenty first century, however, the antimicrobial properties of copper materials, though recognized in ancient civilization has resumed its importance. The property combined with variations in composition and processing methods has made copper materials versatile in a wide range of applications. In this talk, the speaker will highlight with selected examples how copper materials have evolved over centuries highlighting events including its significance in art and culture, particularly from ancient India to modern times.

Paper No. 1.04: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

The art of designing stable multicomponent alloys

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that the metal based idols (Utchava murthies) are more stable under harsh environment conditions than ceramic idols present in the south Indian temples. For example, the ancient metallic structure like *the iron pillar of the Delhi* that was constructed by Chandragupta II (375–415 AD) is well known for the rust-resistant composition of the metals used in its construction and attracted the attention of materials scientists because of its anticorrosive nature. Further, the ancient *ashtadhatu and panchaloha* idols exhibited excellent mechanical and anticorrosive properties. These materials are quite different from the conventional alloys like Si-steel..etc. Now there is a significant interest in the study of multicomponent alloys such as, bulk amorphous alloys and high entropy alloys. Recently there has been significant interest in equiatomic high entropy alloys that exhibit excellent physical properties. Some of the recent results on high entropy alloys will be presented in this talk, which may be useful in understanding the origin of the mechanical properties of ancient alloys.

Paper No. 1.05: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Applications of artificial machine intelligence learning and recognition technology in Archeology

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ABSTRACT

Archaeology is the scientific study of human history and pre-history where people work with ancient materials and historical places. Today, the discovery and study of ancient civilizations has increased its significance through the recovery and analysis of artifacts and physical remains. Archaeologists can explore and exploit the knowledge from an extensive amount of archaeological data with the use of artificial machine intelligence and recognition technology to analyze textile and natural materials in such a way as to make decisions related to appropriate strategies for the preservation, identification and protection of archaeological elements, as well as to classify them and decide on the most ideal point excavation in a complex cultural landscape.

The literature survey of this paper provides an insight that the applications of artificial machine intelligence are still at the preliminary level in archeological research. The study intends to know more about the archeological benefits to culture and environment when aligned with machine intelligence perception and recognition technology. This study further investigates the history of artifacts and applications of artificial machine intelligence. The *information gathered from secondary resources including scholarly publications, web articles, and other resources*. Based on the findings, it is evident that to enrich high-quality output, digital archeologists use cutting edge artificial machine intelligence learning recognition technologies. This research study gives an overview of machine learning algorithms and applications of machine learning on Archeology, based on a variety of data collected.

Keywords: AI, ML, AMIL, Recognition Technology, Archeology, Rock Art

Paper No. 1.06: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Sundara Vimana as Recommend by Maharshi Bharadwaja: A Conceptual Computer 3D Model

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ABSTRACT

In the advanced and modern aeronautical sector there is plenty of aircrafts with much flight technology. But according to the traditional science and technological texts Indian skies had been outshined by aircraft before 19th century. Several types of Vimaanas (aircrafts) are explained in Bruhat Vaimanika Shastra of Maharshi Bharadwaj, or Bharadhwaja Vimaana Shastra (BVS) which is the world's first aeronautical engineering guide.

BVS explains the various aspects of aircrafts, currently available texts in the area provide only overview of the aircraft, and a clear model of the aircraft is not available. One of the types of vimaana explained in BVS is the "Sundara Vimaana". This Vimaana works on the principle of distributed propulsion system. It makes use of many alternative energy sources in a unique way to drive the vehicle. This vimaana can travel at the speed of 8000 km/hr which can act as interplanetary aircraft. This paper is a report of the effort to come out with a conceptual 3D computer model of the Sundara Vimana which would help future researchers to work more in the area.

Keywords: Bruhat Vaimanika Shastra, Maharshi Bharadwaja, Sundara Vimana, Conceptual model,

Paper No. 1.07: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Varamusha of Vagbhatacharya – The Adventure of its Reinvention

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ABSTRACT

Crucibles are pot like vessels used for heating/melting metals used for the purpose of heat treatment/casting. Several traditional Sanskrit based texts explain about manufacturing of varieties of crucibles. Vaimanika Shastra of Maharshi Bharadwaja, RasaratnaSamucchaya of Vagbhatacharya are some such typical texts. In particular, Vagbhatacharya of the 10th Century in his Rasaratnasamucchaya explains several varieties of crucibles, for melting of metals, aimed at preparation of nanometallic medicines.

However, with current varieties of crucibles like the graphite crucible, alumina crucibles, the crucibles mentioned in the RRS has been absolutely neglected. This paper is the report of an adventure to reinvent one of the types of crucibles; the varamusha mentioned in RRS. Through this adventure it was possible to successfully develop Varamusha, and costed about 1/3rd compared to modern graphite based crucible.

Thus there is enough scope for research on a variety of such crucibles mentioned in the traditional texts.

Keywords: Crucible, Musha, Varamusha, melting of metals, Rasaratnasamucchaya.

Paper No. 1.08: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Analysis of Terms Referring to Metals and Minerals in Vaijayantīkoṣa

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ABSTRACT

Vaijayantīkoṣa is an ancient Indian Sanskrit lexicon written by Yādavaprakāśa in the 11th century. As is the case with ancient Sanskrit lexicons, it is written in verse format. It is comprehensive and voluminous with about 20,000 words encoded in the verses. The koṣa (lexicon) is divided into a total of eight kāṇḍas which are sub-divided into chapters based on the subject matter. Chapters are logically organized based on domains such as astronomy, agriculture, wildlife, metallurgy, agriculture, administration, defence, botany, zoology, medicine and words pertaining to these domains are organized under a single chapter heading.

In this paper, a list of words that appear in śailādhyāya (chapter devoted to mountains, metals, minerals, gems etc.) have been selected and evaluated. About 20 terms referring to minerals and metals have been selected as follows: Red Arsenic; Chalk; Yellow Orpiment & Sulphuret of Arsenic; Sulphur; Myrrh; Mica; Pyrites; Red Chalk; Gold; Artificial Gold; Silver; Copper; Brass; Bell-metal; Black Brass/Pañcalōha; Lead; Tin; Iron; Magnet; Antimony; Mercury. Each word may have many synonyms and all these synonyms (a total of 300) that appear in the lexicon will be listed. Their appearance in standard dictionaries will be evaluated and recorded. Those words that do not have reference in the standard dictionaries will be recorded and presented, providing scope for future research.

Keywords: vaijayantīkoṣa, Sanskrit koṣa, ancient Sanskrit lexicon, ancient Indian knowledge systems, metals and minerals in ancient India

Paper No. 1.09: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

भामती श्रीनिवास विश्वविद्यालयः, मुक्क भारतवर्षम् कृषिपराशरः - सविमर्शावलोकनम्

डा ॥ सोन्दा भास्कर भट्टः
श्रीनिवास विश्वविद्यालयः, मुक्क

ABSTRACT

भारतं कृषिप्रधानं राष्ट्रम् । प्राचीनकालादारभ्य भारतीयाः कृषिकार्यमेव कुर्वन्ति स्म । कृषिः, वाणिज्यं, गोपालनं च भारतीयानां आद्यकार्यमासीत् । 'जन्तूनां जीवनं कृषिः' 'कृषितो नास्ति दुर्भिक्षः' इत्यादि भावः सर्वदासीत् । कृषिकर्म न केवलमुद्योगः जीवनस्य प्रधानकर्तव्येषु अन्यतमः इति ते आमनन्ति स्म ।

वेदकालादारभ्यः कृषिं कुर्वन्ति स्म । कृषिसम्बद्धानि, वृष्टिसम्बद्धानि च बहवः मन्त्राः वेदे सन्तीति कारणतः धैर्येण एवं वक्तुं शक्यते । चतुर्वेदाः, बृहत्संहिता, काश्यपीय कृषिसूक्तिः, वृक्षायुर्वेदः, एतादृश ग्रन्थेषु कृषिसम्बन्धिनः विचाराः बहुवर्तन्ते । ऋग्वेदीयकृषिसूक्तं, पर्जन्यसूक्तं, भूसूक्तं, माण्डूक्यसूक्तं इत्यादीनि सूक्तानि कृषिकर्मपूरकानि सन्ति । 'कृषिपराशरः' ग्रन्थोऽपि कृषिविषययुक्तः एव ।

पराशरविरचिते 'कृषिपराशरे' समग्रतया कृषि विचारः निरूपितमस्ति । कदा कृषिं करणीयम् ? कीदृश वातावरणं परिसरश्चावश्यकः ? बीजवपनकालः कः ? बीजरक्षणं कथं करणीयम् ? रोगनियन्त्रणं कदा तथा कथं करणीयम् ? कीटनियन्त्रणं कथम् ? संस्करणं संरक्षणं च कथं वा कर्तव्यम् ? इत्यादयः विषयाः कृषिपराशरकृतेः प्रधान वस्तु वर्तते । एतादृश कृषिसम्बद्धविचाराः एव सुलभशैल्या संक्षिप्तरूपेण, समग्ररूपेण च ग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् निरूपितं विद्यते । अत एवाधुनिककालेऽपि अस्याध्ययनं अत्यावश्यकमिति मे भाति । यतोऽध्ययनकाले कृषिरपि अन्यतमोद्यममिति परिभावितवन्तः । अधिकाधिकोत्पन्नमेव चरमलक्ष्यम् । अतः सावयवं विहाय रासायनिकोपायाः सर्वत्र दृश्यते । विषमिश्रितौषधप्रयोगोऽपि वर्तते । अनेनैव भूमिः, जलं, वातावरणम् आहारं च विषमयमेव । एतादृशाहारः जीविनामुपरि दुष्परिणामं करोति । इदानीं वयमनुभवन्तः स्मः । अतः निरपायकारी आहार प्राप्यर्थं चिन्तनमिदानीं प्रचलदस्ति संशोधनमपि कुर्वन्तः सन्ति । अनेन सह आर्षेयमार्गान्वेषण प्रयत्नोऽपि सर्वत्र दृश्यते ।

पराशरमहर्षिविरचित कृषिपराशरग्रन्थस्याध्ययनं, प्रयोगः अनुष्ठानं च प्राचीनमतानुसारेण नूतनं मार्गमन्वेष्टुं सहकारी भवेदिति ज्ञायते । अत एव सविमर्शावलोकनार्थं ग्रन्थोऽयं मया स्वीकृतः ।

कृषिपराशरः महान् ग्रन्थः नैव । ग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् २४३ श्लोकाः विद्यन्ते । कृषिशास्त्रमिति नाम तत्र तत्र दृश्यते । कृषिकर्म विवेचनमेवास्योद्देशः । 'कृषिकर्मविवेचनम्' इति प्रथमकारिकायाः पादमेव प्रधानोद्देशं सूचयति ।

कृषिकार्यमहत्त्वं, मेघनिर्णयः, वृष्टिनिर्णयः, अनावृष्टिनिर्णयः, कृषिपरिवीक्षणं, गोपूजा, बीजसंरक्षणं, गोमेयकूटोद्धारः, हलादिदिसामग्रीनिरूपणं, बीजवापनविधिः, मयिकादानं, धान्यकट्टनविधिः, जलरक्षणं एवं रीत्या कृषिकार्यस्य समग्रचिन्तनं विधि-विधानं च अल्पे ग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् निरूपितमस्ति ।

धान्यकृषिमेव प्रधानतयात्र चिन्तितमस्ति । नान्यकृषिचिन्तनं नास्तीति कारणतः ग्रन्थस्य अन्यभागः नोपलब्धो वेति संशयः बाधते ।

Paper No. 1.10: **Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance**

Contribution and Relevance of Hindu Scriptures in the field of Science in 21st century

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ABSTRACT

Modern science is appreciated and accepted globally as a contribution of western world. Hardly any name from ancient India comes up assuming that India has always been a backward country. Even today's Hindus who are the survivors of the most ancient civilisations in India, hardly know about the actual scientific contributions of ancient Indians. The objective of this paper is to throw light on the scientific Hindu scriptures and the essence of their content with actual references along with their relevance in the 21st century.

The research paper uses Exploratory methodology. It deals with the contributions of Rishis, hindu scholars and acharyas who worked extensively on topics like Atomic physics, Matter, Gravity, Astronomy, Astrology, Anatomy, Metallurgy, Surgery, Genetic Engineering etc. After a thorough understanding of each of these fields of science in the perspective of ancient scriptures and modern science, the relevance of these scriptures in the 21st century is discussed followed by the causes and incidents which led to the gap of knowledge between ancient and present times. It ultimately aims to bring credit to the deserving minds of ancient India who had accomplished what even today's modern science finds astonishing. It concludes with how we need to learn from history and preserve our knowledge and self esteem to carry it to next generations.

Keywords: Hindu, Veda, Shastra, Upanishad, Science, Rishi, Samhitha, Purana, Ithihasa

Paper No. 1.11: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

Cognitive hierarchical approach for understanding Shat padartha and their relevance in Ayurved

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ABSTRACT

Ayurvedic education demands an integrative reorientation. Pedagogical research is concerned with finding out about how learning takes place, so teachers can promote good learning practices. Bloom's Taxonomy is one of the most recognized learning theories in the field of education, comprises three learning domains: the cognitive, affective and psychomotor and assigns to each of these domains a hierarchy that corresponds to different levels of learning. The cognitive domain is focused on intellectual skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, and creating a knowledge base. The sages desirous of long life and concerned about the well-being of creatures, visualised the six padartha to achieve life's goals. This is considered as the results of the first research developed on the basis of experiential knowledge of sages.

The six padartha namely dravya, guna, karma, samanya, vishesha and samavaya are the tools to achieve the equilibrium of body components (dhatusamya). Charaka Samhita being a medical text focuses more on the clinical aspect of the concept. Hence there is mention of samanya-vishesha before the dravya. Vaisheshika philosophy states dravya as the foremost padartha. As equilibrium of body components is considered as the ultimate aim of Ayurveda, samanya vishesha principles have been given immense importance amongst the six padartha. Hence proper understanding of Shat padartha with suitable examples from Ayurveda requires a cognitive hierarchical approach (remember, understand, apply, analyse, evaluate and create) as padartha are the basis on which the rationale of treatment of Ayurveda is executed and planned.

Keywords: Cognitive, Padartha, Ayurveda

Paper No. 1.12: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

अर्थशास्त्रे कृषिविद्याविमर्शः ।

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प्रस्तावना

विश्वस्य प्राचीनग्रंथऋग्वेदात् अस्मान् इमं ज्ञातं यत् तस्मिन् समये कृषौ सम्यक्
अभ्युदयम्।मनुष्यानां जीविकोपार्जनस्य कृषिः महत्वपूर्ण साधनम् अस्ति।कृषेः अर्थः किम्?
एतस्य परिभाषा "कर्षणं कृषि" इति। अर्थात् यस्मिन् वपनादिकार्यं भवति सः
कृषिः।आचार्यकौटिल्यस्य अर्थशास्त्रस्य व्याख्यानानुसारं
जलभूमिबीजपरिकर्मवापकालदोहदरोगोपचारपुष्पफलरसगंधादयः कृषिकर्मनिहितम्।
ऋग्वेदे अक्षकितवं कृषिकृतं परामर्शम् –

Paper No. 1.13: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

कौटिल्यस्य अर्थशास्त्रे कृषिः

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ABSTRACT

उत्तरं यत्समुद्रस्य हिमाद्रेश्चैव दक्षिणम् । वर्षं तद्भारतं नाम भारती यत्र सन्ततिः ॥

हिमालयहिन्दूमहासागरयोर्मध्ये विद्यमानायां पुण्यकर्मभूमौ विराजते आर्षपरम्परान्विता कृषिप्रधाना भारतीसन्ततिः । सन्ततिरेषा सम्भाषते संस्कृतादिविधभाषाः सुखेन जीवति च । सम्पर्कसाधनीभूतभाषासु मुख्या मधुरा दिव्या गीर्वाणाभारतीत्यादिनाम्ना प्रसिद्धा प्राचीना च संस्कृतभाषा । किञ्च “भारतस्य द्वे प्रतिष्ठे संस्कृतं संस्कृतिस्तथा” । अगाधेऽस्मिन् भारतीये संस्कृतसाहित्ये विद्यन्ते विजयन्ते च चतस्रः विद्याः । आन्वीक्षिकी त्रयी वार्ता दण्डनीतिरिति । तत्र कृषिः पशुपालनं वाणिज्या च वार्ता । “वार्ता समृद्धौ सर्वाः समृद्धयः” इति कौटिल्यम् । भारतं कृषिप्रधानः, कृषकः आधारः देशस्य । “कृषिमित् कृषस्व” इति च श्रुतिः ।

जनपदनिवेशप्रकरणे अकृषतामाच्छिद्यन्त्येभ्यः प्रयच्छेत्-अनुपयुक्तां कृष्यर्थं सिध्यमानभूमिं न स्वीकर्तव्यम् । ग्रामभूतका वैदेहका वा कृषेयुः । पुनश्च राजा कृषकं धान्यपशुहिरण्यैश्चैनाननुगृह्णीयात् । दण्डविष्टिकराबादैः रक्षेदुपहतां कृषिम् । सेतुबन्धविचारः-सहोदकम् आहार्योदकम् वा सेतुं बन्धयेत् । दृश्यन्तेऽत्यधिकतया प्रस्ताविताः कृषिविचाराः सीताध्यक्षप्रकरणे-अत्र सीता-पदस्य कृषिः इत्यर्थः । सीताध्यक्षः कृषितन्त्रशुल्बवृक्षायुर्वेदज्ञस्तज्ञसखो वा सर्वधान्यपुष्पफलशाककन्दमूलवाल्लिक्यक्षौमकार्पासबीजानि यथाकालम् गृह्णीयात् । सर्वबीजानां तु प्रथमावापे क्षेत्रेषु बीजेषु रोगनिरोधकशक्तिवर्धनार्थं सुवर्णोदके बीजानि वापयेत् सृष्टिकारकप्रजापतिकाश्यपस्तुतिपरकमन्त्रञ्चैनं ब्रुवन् ।

प्रजापतये काश्यपाय देवाय नमः सदा । सीता मे ऋध्यतां देवी बीजेषु धनेषु च ॥

मुख्यपदानि- भारतम्, कृषिप्रधाना, संस्कृतभाषा, कृषिः, पशुपालनं, वाणिज्या, वार्ता, सीताध्यक्षः, कृषिमित् कृषस्व, बीजानि

Paper No. 1.14: Ancient Indian Technologies and their Relevance

वेदकालादारभ्य आधुनिककालपर्यन्तं कृषेः विकासः – एकं विमर्शात्मकं संक्षिप्ताध्ययनम् ।

विद्वान् रवि जोशी

उपन्यासकः

श्री श्रीमाता संस्कृत महाविद्यालयः उम्मचगी, यल्लापुरम्, उत्तर कन्नड

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“भारतस्य द्वे प्रतिष्ठे संस्कृतं संस्कृतिस्तथा” इत्युक्त्यनुसारेण अस्माकं भारतं प्रपञ्चेऽस्मिन् चिरकालात् परिचितं महत्वपूर्णं स्थानम् आरुह्य विराजते इत्यस्य कारणम् अस्माकं संस्कृतं संस्कृतिश्च एतद्वयं मूलरूपेण चिरकालात् संरक्षितमस्तीति कारणात् तत्परम्परा अविच्छिन्नतया प्रवहति । तयोः परम्परयोः अस्माकं भारतीयसंस्कृतौ क अृषिरपि परभागमारुह्य शोभते ।

वैदिकसाहित्येऽपि कृषिमधिकृत्य विषयविचारधारा ऋषिभिः उत्पादिता अधुनापि भारतीय संस्कृतेः (जीवनस्य) – जीवस्तम्भरूपा वर्तते । चरकपराशरप्रभृतय अनन्तरकालीनाः मुनयोऽपि तत् साहित्यमाश्रित्यैव स्वकीयममूल्य-ग्रन्थ-रचनाम् अकुर्वन् ।

एवमेव भारतीयेतिहासे अद्वितीयस्थाने परिगण्यमानः सूक्ष्मदर्शी चाणक्योऽपि स्वकीये अर्थशास्त्रेऽपि कृषिविद्यां सूक्ष्मेक्षणिकया विचार्य स्वकीयं निर्णयं प्रकटितवान् । सोऽपि निर्णयः अधुनापि आधुनिकभारतीयानाम् अत्यन्तमुपयोगाय अकल्पयिष्यत यदि तान् विषयान् अन्वकरिष्यन्त । डा. खादर महाभागाः ‘सिरिधान्यगळे आहार’ इति कर्णाटकभाषायां स्वविरचिते आधुनिकेग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् पारम्परिक-कृषिविद्यामधिकृत्य विश्वजनीने मार्गे जागृतिम् उदपादयन् ।

रुद्राध्याये वेदमन्त्रे नमक-चमकादिभिः व्रीहयश्चमे, यवाश्चमे, माशाश्चमे, तिलाश्चमे, नीवाराश्चमे इत्यादि धान्यादि विषये फलपुरण दूया सम्प्रार्थ्यते ।

पराशर महर्षेः “कृषिपराशर” ग्रन्थे “एकया पुनः कृष्या भूयादेकश्च भूपतिः”॥

इत्युक्तम् ।

मुख्य-बिन्दवः-

◆ अर्थशास्त्रे कृषिविचाराः

◆ कृष्याधिकारिणः पात्रम्

AÉKÉÑIIE Mü iÉIŞÉÉÉIÉxrÉ xÉSÑmÉrÉÉãaÉ:

◆ कृषिक्षेत्रे सर्वकारस्य पात्रम्

रघुवंशादि काव्येषु, शाकुन्तलादि-नाटकेषुच नीवारादिसस्याभिवृद्धिं प्रति प्रमाणानि बहूनि उपलभ्यन्ते । तस्मात् कृषिः भारतस्य जीवनं राष्ट्रस्य अभिवृद्धिकारणञ्च इति न विस्मरणीयम् ।

प्राचीनविचारान् आश्रित्य नूतनसंशोधनविचारान् तन्त्रज्ञानञ्च उपयोक्तव्यम् ।

MùluÉiÉÉIqÉ'ÉÉ- mÉëpÉ×iÉÏIÉÉ M×ùlwÉxÉÉIkÉMüÉIÉÉÇ luÉcÉÉUÉ:AImÉ AÍxqÉIÉÇ mÉëoÉIkÉã mÉëmÉgcÉÏM×üiÉÉ: |

॥ इति शम् ॥

Paper No. 2.01: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Ancient Indian Views in the Teaching-Learning Process Lessons for Management Education

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ABSTRACT

The role of education system goes beyond the expansion in knowledge base and educative skills of the younger generation who seek the education system to build up their future career. Educated people need to contribute meaningfully in the development perspective and become valuable assets to society. The process of teaching-learning activity has to build up the Intelligent quotient, Emotional quotient, and Spiritual quotient of the younger generation. The very purpose of this paper is to highlight the Ancient Indian views in the teaching-learning process and showcase their relevance for management education.

Keywords: Education System, Younger Generation, Teaching -Learning Process, Ancient Indian Views

Paper No. 2.02: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Literature Review on Indian Ancient University in importing Holistic and Multidisciplinary: To Create Indian Knowledge System (IKS)

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Education in ancient India is way back in the 3rd century BC it is a source of knowledge, traditions, and practices focused on the holistic development provided by the ancient university in higher learnings provided by the Nalanda(5th century), Takshashila(6th century BC), Odantapuri (550-1040), Jagaddala, Sharada peeth Valabhi, Varanasi, Manyakheta, Sripadraj Matta ,Kolar Dist in Karnataka, Kanchipuram, Nagarjinakonda focused on Moral, Physical, spiritual, intellectual through Vedas, Brahmanas, Upanishads, Dharmasutras the learning sources are Kavyas, Itihas, Anviksiki(logic), Arthashastra, Mimamsa, Varta(trade), Krida, Shastrartha, Uyayamaprakara, Dhanurvedya, Yogasadhana, music, the system of ancient education was Vedic and Buddhist with the language of Sanskrit and Pali, Produced academic Scholars Panini well-known grammarian, Charaka medical teacher, Chanakya, Jivaka and Swami Vivekananda Ramakrishna Mission in the twentieth century are the hub of learning. The National Education Policy 2020 is the framework of the Indian Knowledge system to provide innovative developments through multidisciplinary linkages with other branches of knowledge contributed by Aryabhatta mathematician, astrologer and physicist he wrote the book Aryabhattiya(summary of Mathematics), Bramagupta book Brahm Sputa Siddantika on mathematical, Ganesha Upadhaya mathematician and philosopher, medical and Ayurveda by Susruta, Patanjali on Yoga and Vagbhata, The education agencies in ancient days are Gurukula, Parishad and Samnelan, teaching methods are verbal and explanatory, lectures, debates and discussions to creating the Three R's Reasoning, Resilience and Responsibility.

Keywords: Indian Ancient University; Multidisciplinary; Academic Scholars; Indian Knowledge System(IKS); NEP2020;3R's

Paper No. 2.03: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Popular Verses from Subhashitam and their Relevance in Management Case Studies.

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ABSTRACT

Subhashitas in Sanskrit are short and wise verses containing moral and ethical advice based on experience and research. They contain practical examples in rhythmic mode conveyed generally in four lines or two lines. They are picked from ancient epics, poetry, writings, and other literary works. Many of the Subhashitha Sukthas and verses contain management principles which are applicable at all times, to all people and to all regions of the universe. This inquisitive study probes in to the origin of various Subhashitha sukthas and verses and analyzes them through literature review. Their meaning interpretations and relevance as per different authors are studied and then attempted to relate them to corporate decision makings, actions and the consequent results. Study also reviews some of the recent corporate events which made news and also some interesting case studies taught in management classes. Thereafter attempt is made to connect the Sukthas to the principles, practices and strategies of the corporate leaders and entrepreneurs. The study is expected to be useful in handling management lessons more effectively backed with Indian ethos and could also help the concerned to take appropriate decisions when confronted with corporate or personal dilemmas.

Keywords: Subhashitha Sukthas and Verses, Ancient Epic Corporate Events, Case Studies.

Paper No. 2.04: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Strategies of Management from the Indian Epics

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ABSTRACT

The concept of Management is from time immemorable. Management principles and practices are used by each of us even without our conscious effort. The Indian epics are one such piece of evidence to understand that Management principles were followed by our great forefathers. The Indian Epics namely Mahabharat Ramayana and Bhagavad-Gita portray what is good and bad. They teach us the essence of life. If read and understood in the right manner a lot of management concepts can be seen in the Indian Epics. Some common concepts like teamwork, Strategic Approach, loyalty, leadership, planning, and formal communication can be understood from the epics. This Paper is a deliberate effort to identify the various strategies and strategic Models that have played a vital role and have had a mention in the epics.

Keywords: Strategies, Management, Indian Epics, Teamwork, Leadership

Paper No. 2.05: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

ಕ್ಷೇಮಕುತೂಹಲದ ಪಾಕರಸಾಯನ

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ABSTRACT

ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಪರೂಪವೆನ್ನಿಸುವ ಪಾಕಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ಕ್ಷೇಮಕುತೂಹಲಮ್ ಕೃತಿಯು ಆಹಾರ ತಯಾರಿಯ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿಕೊಡುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ರಕ್ಷಣೆಯ ಸೂಚನೆಗಳನ್ನೂ ಸಾಂದರ್ಭಿಕವಾಗಿ ನೀಡಿದೆ. ದೀರ್ಘಕಾಲದ ಆರೋಗ್ಯವನ್ನು ಬಯಸುವ ಜನರು ಎಂಥಹ ಆಹಾರವನ್ನು ಸೇವಿಸುವುದು ಒಳಿತು ಎನ್ನುವ ಕ್ಷೇಮಸಮಾಚಾರವೇ ಕ್ಷೇಮಕುತೂಹಲದ ಪ್ರಧಾನ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ನಾವೆಲ್ಲ ಹೊಟ್ಟೆಬಾಕರಂತೆ ರುಚಿಕರವಾದ ಆಹಾರವನ್ನು ತಿನ್ನುವುದರ ಕಡೆಗಷ್ಟೇ ಗಮನ ಹರಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಆದರೆ ಪಾಕ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣದ ವಿಧಿವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ಗಂಭೀರ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಕಾಲಾನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಸರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಿಗತಕ್ಕಂಥ ಖಾದ್ಯ ಪದಾರ್ಥಗಳ ಸವಿವರವಾದ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ಕ್ಷೇಮಶರ್ಮ ಹೆಸರಿನ ಪಂಡಿತವರೇಣ್ಯರು ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಪಾಕ ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ಉದ್ಯಮವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪಾಕಪ್ರವೀಣರಿಗೆ ಈ ಕೃತಿಯು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಯೋಗ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಶೋಧನಾತ್ಮಕ ಕೈಪಿಡಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಖ್ಯಾತ ಭರದ್ವಾಜ ಕುಲದಲ್ಲಿ ದ್ವಿಜರಾಜನೆಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನ ವೈದ್ಯನ ಜನನವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವೈದ್ಯಮಹಾಶಯನು ಪುರಾಣ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾದ ರಾಕ್ಷಸರ ರಾಜಧಾನಿ ಲಂಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಣ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಭೀಷಣರಿಗೆ ಚಿಕಿತ್ಸೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ ಗೌರವಕ್ಕೆ ಪಾತ್ರನಾಗಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಇದೇ ದ್ವಿಜರಾಜನ ವಂಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿರೋರತ್ನಮ್ ಹೆಸರಿನ ಚಿಕಿತ್ಸಕನು ಜನಿಸಿ ಖ್ಯಾತ ವೈದ್ಯ ಸುಶ್ರುತಾಚಾರ್ಯರ ಸಹಚಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ವ್ಯಾಧಿಗಳಿಂದ ಪೀಡಿತರಾದವರಿಗೆ ಶುಶ್ರೂಷೆಗೈದು ರೋಗ ಶಮನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದ್ದ. ಶಿರೋರತ್ನಮ್ ನಂತರ ಧರ್ಮಧರ, ರಾಮ, ಯತಿ, ಯಶೋರಾಜ, ಮಹಾರಾಜ, ಪ್ರಹ್ಲಾದ, ಕಾಮರಾಜಕ, ಹ್ವಾದನಿ ಮತ್ತು ತ್ರಿಪುರಾರಿ ಎನ್ನುವವರು ವಾಗ್ಭಟರ ಅಷ್ಟಾಂಗ ಹೃದಯ, ಚರಕ ಸಂಹಿತಾ, ಸುಶ್ರುತ ಸಂಹಿತಾ, ಆಯುರ್ವೇದ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳ ಆಳವಾದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ವಿಶ್ವದ ವೈದ್ಯರುಗಳನ್ನೇ ಬೆರಗಾಗಿಸಿದ್ದರು.

ಈ ಪುಸ್ತಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಕಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಏಳು ಪ್ರಕಾರದ ದ್ರವ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು, ಭೋಜನಾಲಯ ಮತ್ತು ಭೋಜನೋಪಕರಣಗಳ ವಿಚಾರವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಮುಂದುವರಿದು ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರಕಾರದ ಸಸ್ಯಾಹಾರ, ಮಾಂಸಾಹಾರ ಪದಾರ್ಥಗಳ ತಯಾರಿಕೆ, ಪಾನೀಯ ಮತ್ತಿತರ ರಸಾಯನಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಸರಲವಾಗಿ ಮನಸ್ಸಿಗೆ ಮುಟ್ಟುವಂತೆ ಬರೆದಿದ್ದಾನೆ. 600 ವರ್ಷಗಳಷ್ಟು ಹಿಂದೆಯೇ ರಚನೆಗೊಂಡಿರುವ ಈ ಪುಸ್ತಕವು ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಸಹ ಅದೇ ಜನಪ್ರಿಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ.

Keywords :

ಕ್ಷೇಮಶರ್ಮ, ಕ್ಷೇಮಕುತೂಹಲ, ಪಾಕಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ರಸಾಯನ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ, ಸ್ವಾಸ್ಥ್ಯವಿಜ್ಞಾನ, ಪಾಕವಿದ್ಯಾ, ದ್ವಿಜರಾಜ

Paper No. 2.06: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

City planning in Kautilya Arthaśāstra and its Modern Relevance

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ABSTRACT

Kautilya Arthaśāstra is the well-known book on political administration. His thoughts on every aspect of it are usable in many ways till the date. In the second Adhikaran he has described his thoughts on planning of the city. Today we find - Metro-cities are dense and over populated, Exploitation of all natural and available resources in big cities is the main ecological issue. Some cities in remote area are not well developed and well connected by good roads. So the aim of the paper is to discuss Kautilya's description of city planning and its features addressing some of the problems in modern cities.

Analytical methodology or collecting references from the Kautilya Arthaśāstra and modern planning are used. Kautilya says that Samaharta should laid foundation of the city in the middle of Janapada. It should in rectangular/ circular / in suitable form. Water should be available for the agriculture and domestic use. He also said that the officer should lay foundation of industries, mines, business roads, reserved forests and make proper arrangements for its maintenance. While discussing the land and property, he has discussed about details of house building.

In the nutshell Kautilya suggested to make city completely well planned, independent, having ecological Balance and full of facilities and opportunities.

Keywords: Samaharta, Arthashastra, Urban Planning, Ecological Balance

Paper No. 2.07: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Management Insights from Indian Ancient Scriptures

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ABSTRACT

The paper attempts to study the relevance of Ancient Indian scriptures like Vedas, Upanishads, Shreemad Bhagavad Gita, Manu-smriti/Manav Dharma Shastra, Arthashastra, etc in the today's corporate world. There are so many management principles available in our scripture which we are using nowadays in our day to day life. The scripture alone is our guide in determining what should be done and what should not be done. Knowing this, we ought to perform only such action as is ordained by the scriptures.

The conceptual study will be carried to explore the application of ancient Indian scriptures on present management practices. The various management concepts like planning, decision making, attaining objectives, roles and responsibility, vision, leadership, motivation, ethics, corporate governance, and strategic management observed in various scriptures. The successful organisations are following the ancient Indian scriptures in their corporate actions.

Keywords: Corporate world, Manu-smriti, Scripture

Paper No. 2.08: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

An exploratory study of Rāmarājya with evidence from Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa: Internal Control Structure and Finance Governance Model

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ABSTRACT

‘Rāmarājya’ is an aspirational benchmark in administration standards as envisaged by Mahātmā Gandhi in his speeches and writings between 1920 and 1947. Its objective of good governance is the triumph of people, planet, and profit, evident during the reign of King Rāma, as described by Sage Vālmīki in the epic Rāmāyaṇa. The science of statecraft a.k.a ‘Arthaśāstra’ which was the basis of the good governance in Rāmarājya is not available today. This paper seeks to reconstruct the finance and related aspects of ancient Arthaśāstra (which existed at the time of Rāmāyaṇa) using practical case studies from Rāmāyaṇa. This would help understand primordial principles of accounting, economics and related legalities which can ensure good governance.

The paper adopts a qualitative inductive research approach using principles of grounded theory and hermeneutics. Data analysis includes textual and contextual analysis with thematic and discourse analysis. Two chapters from Ayodhyā kāṇḍa of Vālmīki Rāmāyaṇa viz. ‘Nārājaka-sarga’ (2.67) and ‘Kaccit-sarga’ (2.100) have been considered for the study. Initial findings reveal significant coverage of the internationally recognized Committee of Sponsoring Organizations’ Internal control integrated framework in Rāmāyaṇa, along with other aspects which may potentially enhance the model. Finally, the paper encourages one to explore on having an indigenous framework for Internal controls and Finance Governance which can fit the mindset and ethos of Indian companies and their customers.

Keywords: Finance Governance, Internal control framework, Rāmāyaṇa, Indian Knowledge Systems, Arthaśāstra, Rāmarājya.

Paper No. 2.09: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

A Comprehensive Doctrine for Indian combat readiness; In International Waters by Decoding Gita, Arthashastra and the Art of War

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: India has a vast coast line of 7516.6 kilometers and it needs a comprehensive plan a written document to prevent and knock off various infiltration possibilities. The current Naval doctrine[s] will have to be added and expanded keeping various players in mind; especially the Chinese, Few Island Nations as well as the Pakistani Navy. This is a doctrine for India's preparedness in terms of combat readiness in international as well as territorial waters. The entire doctrine is framed by engaging, adopting, adapting various strategic positioning thought processes from The Gita, The Arthashastra by Chanakya and the Chinese Art of War by Sun Tzu.

Design: This paper is designed to develop a comprehensive doctrine that adopts various treatise and concepts form three classics that have shaped the world. Be it wealth creation, restoration and advancement of the civil society. The gita has 18 Chapters, the arthashatra has 6000 sutras classified in to 15 books, 150 chapters and 180 topics by chanakya himself. The Art of War written by Sun Tzu has 13 chapters. These three books are the guiding path for the entire research.

Findings: India's contribution to the world in terms of administration, philosophy and state craft has been enormous.

Originality: This paper highlights various aspects of Indian original thinking and wisdom from various corners of the learning quarters.

Paper Type: An exploratory research papers for understanding India's contribution

Key words: Strategy, Art of war, Bhagvath Gita, Sutras, Arthashastra, administration, combat readiness, SWOT analysis of international waters, ABCD analysis of the doctrine

Paper No. 2.10: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Leadership is challenging, and it is even more difficult to reduce attrition in a tertiary care hospital.? A Preliminary Study

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Attrition rates in various cadres are a major issue in tertiary care facilities; attrition rates are one of the important factors used by accrediting bodies to assess the efficacy of Quality services provided by accredited hospitals. Tertiary care hospital has recognized the importance of this issue and are making significant efforts to avoid attrition.

Design/Methodology/Approach: A Retrospective study carried out in a tertiary care Hospital. All the Doctors and Nursing staffs who have resigned from the Tertiary hospital in the financial year of the hospital from Jul 2022 and Dec 2022 were taken into the study. The reason for Healthcare workers leaving the hospital was taken from the exit interview form.

Findings/Result: An analysis was carried out based on the Exit interviews conducted over a 6-month period (July 2022 to December 2022) indicated the attrition rate and the reasons for it. A research was conducted to better understand the Tertiary Care Hospital's experience and the reasons for attrition.

Based on the findings, (which will be disclosed) the hospital management made the decision to streamline the HR Management system, which will be extremely beneficial in retaining employees and delivering quality services, as employees are the assets of any organization that enable it to fulfil its goals and establish benchmarks

Keywords: Attrition, Leaders, Tertiary care, Hospitals

Paper No. 2.11: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

“Theoretical assimilation on organization and Management Theory History”

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ABSTRACT

There has undoubtedly been an increase in discussion over the place of history in management research, with some writers offering proposals on how to reunite the two fields and others calling for a "historic turn." In this study, we contend that while history was undoubtedly marginalized by the scientization of management beginning in the late 1950s, it began to reappear in the 1980s and is now more frequently used in a variety of research initiatives. We emphasize that for management scholars interacting with history (or wishing to do so), the most important question is how it relates to theory. First, we provide a systematic account of the ways in which history has been used, distinguishing between "history to theory" and "history in theory," both at the micro (organizational) and macro levels of analysis. In the former, we take into account research initiatives like (neo-) institutionalism, in which hypotheses are developed, modified, or tested using historical data. As an example of "history in theory," we may think of research projects like "imprinting" that use history or the past as a moderator or driver within the theoretical framework itself. A growing number of research, which we refer to as exhibiting "historical consciousness" in the sense of incorporating period effects or historical contingencies into their theorizing endeavors, are also highlighted in our second section. Finally, building on our general review, we offer more detailed recommendations for enhancing history's visibility and impact inside organization and management theory.

Keywords: Organization and management theory, macro levels of analysis, scientization of management, historical consciousness

Paper No. 2.12: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

“Unlocking the Secrets of Success: Management Lessons from the Mahabharata and Bhagavad Gita”

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ABSTRACT

The Mahabharata and the Bhagavad Gita are ancient Indian texts that offer valuable lessons for management. The Mahabharata, specifically the Battle of Kurukshetra, can offer several management lessons such as Leadership, strategy, teamwork, moral and ethical leadership, emotional intelligence, adaptability, resilience, and decision-making. On the other hand, The Bhagavad Gita presents a spiritual perspective on self-actualization and management. The text is a dialogue between Lord Krishna and Arjuna, and it presents the idea that the ultimate goal of human existence is to attain self-realization and liberation from the cycle of rebirth. The Bhagavad Gita teaches that self-actualization can be achieved by following the path of dharma, or righteousness, and by developing devotion to God. This research will explore these management lessons from both texts and will analyze the leadership styles, strategies, and ethical principles that can be derived from the epic and the scripture.

Keywords: Mahabharata, Bhagavad Gita, Management, Leadership, Strategy, Teamwork, Ethical leadership, Emotional intelligence.

Paper No. 2.13: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

Ancient Indian Education: It's relevance and importance in the Modern Education System

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ABSTRACT

India has a rich tradition of education and learning right from the ancient times and during the Golden Age of Indian Culture, the Renaissance period. The three achievements during this period were the decimal system, the great Sanskrit epics and the contribution to the sciences of astronomy, mathematics and metallurgy. The four Vedas, i.e, the Rigveda, Yajurveda, Samaveda and the Atharvaveda were configured through ideals, practices and conduct. The doctrine of action (Karma) occupies a very significant place in the Indian system of education. Two methods of teaching were being practiced during the Vedic period. The first, the verbal/oral method and the second based on thinking (Chintan). Current higher education has shown trends of multidisciplinary approach in similar lines. NEP 2020 also suggests a multidisciplinary approach. Bloom's Taxonomy defines three domains of learning, cognitive, affective and psychomotor. The ancient education system is also based on the three domains, to develop higher order learning by building up the lower -level cognitive skills. With this background, the exploratory study based on secondary published research articles seeks to interpret extant academic research on relevance of ancient education system in modern multidisciplinary education.

Keywords: Ancient Education, Vedic Knowledge, Multidisciplinary, Bloom's Taxonomy, Modern Education.

Paper No. 2.14: Ancient Indian Management and their Relevance

THE RELEVANCE OF CHANAKAYS NEETHI IN THE SAFE BANKING MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT:

There is no shortcut for success, there is no substitute for hard work. The good director care for each other's knowledge, the close director understand each others talent, but true committed director beyond time, beyond words, beyond distance, protect the interest of customer, public money and bank. The main object of this empirical study is to boost the EFFECTIVENESS and EFFICIENCY of Board agenda and ruling, in the Bank with self and collective empowerment of wisdom and talent, to protect the interest of the PROFIT and LOSS ACCOUNT powered by STABLE/STRONG BALANCE SHEET of the Bank, to win the confidence of the shareholders, stock holders and customers in all respects. The case study bank and incident is a public sector Bank owned by Union Government, State Government and commercial Bank. With Bank Board consists of directors representing RBI, NABARD, State Government and Union Government respectfully. It is disclosed in the BANK ANNUAL REPORT IN THE YEAR 2000 the bank transferred specific reserve fund to, revenue account, in profit loss account, accordingly the profit is overstated to that extent of amount, in which the official clearance is pending at RBI/NABARD to do so. Further, it is learnt from reports the said fund is contributed by each loan account holder, for the benefit for the loan account holders only. In terms of Law, it is the, Act,, lie,, beyond the authority of the Bank to perform/execute. Accordingly, besides illegal transaction, profit declared by Bank is also a questionable matter and debit subject matter. Accordingly the role of the Central Bank director is nothing but the CHANUKYA NEETHI in kings times. If necessary by amending the powers of RBI director, if the agenda is not satisfied by the RBI director, no rulings taken by and decision, pending till clearance is given by related competitive authority. Further the CHANUKYA NEETHI has given good information about, how to handle the, Internal enemy/ external enemy. Similarly, the internal enemy are, the integrity suspected officials, the external enemy are the WILL-FUL NPA ACCOUNT HOLDERS, SUPPORTED BY THE DELIQUENT OFFICIALS. This is attributed by observing the fraud in the Bank, high growth of NPA in the Bank, exposed in the print media and social media, is almost news every day. The key solution to every Banking aspect, is the vigilance department must be controlled by the Central Bank nominee director with this, it is concluded that, KNOW--KNOWLEDGE – NO PAIN, NO KNOWLEDGE – KNOW PAIN. The RBI has to protect the public money in Banks. The RBI as to protect the public money in Banks.

KEYWORDS: Ethical Profit, Central Bank, Setubandha, Whistle Blower, Castigate, Act of Omission, Knowledge Nutrition.

Paper No 3.01: Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

ಗೃಹವಾಸ್ತು ಮತ್ತು ದೇವವಾಸ್ತು

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ABSTRACT

ಅಕವಾಟಮನಾಚ್ಛನ್ನಮದತ್ತಬಲಿಭೋಜನಮ್|

ಗೃಹಂ ನ ಪ್ರವಿಶೇದ್ಧೇಮಾನ್ನಾಪದಾಮಾರೋ ಹಿ ತತ್||

ಶಿಲ್ಪಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕನುಸಾರವಾಗಿ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಗೃಹವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಾಣಮಾಡಿ ದಾರುಕನಿಂದ ಪೂಜೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಸಿ ಮನೆಯನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಬೇಕು. ಸಚ್ಛಾಸ್ತ್ರಸಂಪನ್ನರಿಂದ ಶಾಂತಿಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಸಿ ವಾಸ್ತುಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಸಬೇಕು. ತದನಂತರ ಸಕುಟುಂಬನಾಗಿ ಮನೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸಿದರೆ ಆ ಮನೆ ಭಗವಂತನ ಅನುಗ್ರಹದಿಂದ ಸುಖಶಾಂತಿಗೆ ನೆಲೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಧನಧಾನ್ಯಾದಿಸಂಪತ್ತು ಸಮೃದ್ಧಗೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಅರೆಬರೆ ಕೆಲಸಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ಗೃಹಪ್ರವೇಶವು ನಿಶಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿದೆ. ಮಾಡಬೇಕಾದ ಬಲಿ, ಸತ್ಯಾತ್ರರಿಗೆ ಅನ್ನದಾನ ಮೊದಲಾದವುಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡದಿದ್ದರೆ ಆ ಮನೆಯು ಆಪತ್ತುಗಳಿಗೆ ಆಶ್ರಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಹಿರಿಯರು ಆದೇಶಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ವಾಸಕ್ಕೆ ಅಥವಾ ದೇವತಾಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠೆಗಾಗಿ ಇರುವ ಯಾವುದೇ ಮಂದಿರ ಕಟ್ಟಡಗಳನ್ನು ಶುಚಿಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಭಗವತ್ಸನ್ನಿಧಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಯೋಗ್ಯಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಪ್ರವೇಶಿಸುವುದೇ ವಾಸ್ತುವಿನ ತಾತ್ಪರ್ಯ.

ವಾಸ್ತು ಎನ್ನುವುದು ಒಂದು ದೇವತೆಯ ಹೆಸರು. ಶ್ರೀಮಧ್ವಾಚಾರ್ಯರು ತಮ್ಮ ತಂತ್ರಸಾರಸಂಗ್ರಹದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸ್ತುವಿನ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹೀಗೆ ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ.

.... ವಾಸ್ತುವರ್ತುಹಸ್ಯ ಹರೇಃ ಸುತಃ|

ಶ್ರೀಮನ್ನಾರಾಯಣ ದಶಾವತಾರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮೂರನೆಯದಾದ ವರಾಹರೂಪಿ ಪರಮಾತ್ಮನ ಮಗನೇ ವಾಸ್ತು. ಕಾರಣಾಂತರಗಳಿಂದ ಭೂಮಿಗೆ ಬಿದ್ದ ಅವನ ಅವಯವಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ದೇವತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಆರಾಧಿಸಬೇಕು. ಅವನ ತಲೆಯು ಈಶಾನ್ಯದಿಕ್ಕಿಗೆ ಇರುವ ಕಾರಣ ಆ ದಿಕ್ಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ದೇವತಾರಾಧನೆಗೆ ಒತ್ತು ಕೊಡಬೇಕು. ಹೀಗೆ ಐಹಿಕ – ಪಾರತ್ರಿಕ ಸುಖಸಮೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಕಾರಣವಾದ ಗೃಹನಿರ್ಮಾಣದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಹಾಗೂ ಅನುಭವದಿಂದ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಚಿಂತನೆ ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ಇದೆ.

Keywords: Vaastu, tantrasara, Girha

Paper No 3.02: Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

ಈಗಿನ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ವಾಸ್ತುವಿನ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆ

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ABSTRACT

ವಸತಿಶಿಲೆ ವಸ್ತು, ವಾಸ್ತುರೇವ ವಾಸ್ತು ಎಂಬ ನಿರ್ವಚನದಂತೆ ಒಂದು ವಸ್ತು ಹೇಗೆ ಇರಬೇಕೋ ಅದೇ ರೀತಿ ಇದ್ದರೆ ಅದು ವಾಸ್ತು ಎಂದೆನಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಮನೆ, ದೇವಸ್ಥಾನ, ಮಂದಿರ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸ್ತು ಎಂದು ಜನಜನಿತವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪರಗೃಹೇ ಕೃತಾಃ ಸರ್ವಾಃ ಶ್ರೌತಸ್ಮಾರ್ತಕ್ರಿಯಾಃ ಶುಭಾಃ|

ನಿಷ್ಫಲಾಃ ಸ್ಯುರ್ಯತಸ್ತೇಷಾಂ ಭೂಮಿಪಃ ಫಲಮಶ್ನುತೇ||

ಪರಗೃಹದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಡಿದ ಧರ್ಮಕರ್ಮಗಳ ಪಲ ಬಹಳ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಆ ಮನೆಯ ಯಜಮಾನನಿಗೂ ಅದು ಸಲ್ಲುತ್ತದೆ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ತನ್ನ ಮನೆ, ಹಾಗೂ ಆ ಮನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಿತ್ಯಾನುಷ್ಠಾನ, ದೇವಪ್ರೀತ್ಯರ್ಥ ಪೂಜೆ, ಅಗ್ನಿಪ್ರೀತ್ಯರ್ಥ ಯಾಗ, ಪಿತೃಪ್ರೀತ್ಯರ್ಥ ತರ್ಪಣ, ಅತಿಥಿಸತ್ಕಾರ , ತುಳಸಿಪೂಜೆ, ಗೋಸೇವೆ, ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಪೋಷಣೆ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದರೆ ಇಹದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಖ ಹಾಗೂ ಪರಶ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮೋಕ್ಷವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬಹುದು.

ಮನೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಾಣಮಾಡುವ ಮೊದಲು ಸಪ್ತಸುಂದಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಮಣ್ಣನ್ನು ಅಗೆಯುವಾಗ, ಮರವನ್ನು ಕಡಿಯುವಾಗ, ಕಲ್ಲು ಕೆತ್ತುವಾಗ ಸಂಭವಿಸುವ ದೋಷನಿವಾರಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಅವಶ್ಯವಾಗಿ ವಾಸ್ತುಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾವಿಧಿಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬೇಕು.

Keywords: vastu, vastupurusha, nityaanushtaana

Paper No 3.03. Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

The Shaivism Tradition in Assam: With a special reference to Nag Shankar Temple

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ABSTRACT

Everyone in this world wants to live happily without any fear from devils, natural calamities and any other unwanted pandemic situation. To get rid of all these unwanted situations, that may bring threatening for anyone life, people have been believing in worship in Gods by the way of various religious rituals in temples. In Assam, the three streams of religious rituals of Hinduism – Shaivism, Shaktism and Vaishnavism – have been in harmony.

In Shaivism, Shiva, also known as Mahadeva is the supreme being and also, the most influential deities in Hinduism. The worship of Lord Shiva dates back to the Mahabharata. There are many Shiva temples and Shiva Lingo scatters in various parts of Assam.

The Nag Shankar Temple is one of the Shiva Temple of Assam which is located in the border of Sonitpur and Biswanath district. In this paper, we are going to highlight the Shiva tradition and Worship in Assam with a special reference Nag Shankar temple. To prepare this paper we will use various reference books and data collected data from different people related to Nag Shankar Temple.

Keywords- Hindusim, Shiva, Nag Shankar

Paper No 3.04. Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

ಮತ್ಸ್ಯಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸ್ತುಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ

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ABSTRACT

ಭಾರತದ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಎತ್ತರದ ಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿಲ್ಲುತ್ತವೆ. ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿತವಾಗಿರುವ ಜ್ಞಾನರಾಶಿಯನ್ನು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯಜನರಿಗೂ ತಲುಪಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬ ದಿವ್ಯ ಸಂಕಲ್ಪದಿಂದ ಭಗವಾನ್ ವೇದವ್ಯಾಸರು ಸರಳವಾದ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಥೆಗಳ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರಾಣಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿದರು. ಪುರಾಣ ಎಂಬ ಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಪುರಾತನವಾದುದು ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಗೋಚರವಾದರೂ ಆ ಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಹಳೆಯದಾದರೂ ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಅದು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಎಂಬುದು ಅತಿಶಯೋಕ್ತಿಯಲ್ಲ.

ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ಹದಿನೆಂಟು ಮಹಾಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಇವೆ. ಮತ್ಸ್ಯ, ಮಾರ್ಕಂಡೇಯ, ಭಾಗವತ, ಭವಿಷ್ಯ, ಬ್ರಹ್ಮ, ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಾಂಡ, ಬ್ರಹ್ಮವೈವರ್ತ, ವಾಯು, ವಾಮನ, ವಿಷ್ಣು, ವರಾಹ, ಅಗ್ನಿ, ನಾರದ, ಪದ್ಮ, ಲಿಂಗ, ಗರುಡ, ಕೂರ್ಮ, ಹಾಗೂ ಸ್ಯಾಂದ ಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಜನಜನಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಹದಿನೆಂಟು ಉಪಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿವೆ. ಪುರಾಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜ್ಞಾನ, ಕರ್ಮ, ಭಕ್ತಿ, ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ, ಉಪಾಸನೆ, ಯೋಗ, ಧರ್ಮ, ಮಾನವೀಯ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳು ಹೀಗೆಯೇ ಹತ್ತು ಹಲವು ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖವಾಗಿವೆ. ವ್ರತಗಳ ಮಹತ್ವ, ದಾನದ ಮಹತ್ವ, ತೀರ್ಥಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದ ಮಹತ್ವ, ಅನೇಕ ಮಹನೀಯರ, ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳ, ದಾರ್ಶನಿಕರ, ಜೀವನಚರಿತ್ರೆ ಪುರಾಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾಗಿ ಹರಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಕೇವಲ ಇಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲ, ನಿತ್ಯ ಜೀವನಕ್ಕೆ ಸಹಕಾರಿಯಾಗುವ ಕೃಷಿ, ಪಶುಸಂಗೋಪನೆ, ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ, ಭೂಪರಿಕ್ಷಾ, ಅಶ್ವಪರಿಕ್ಷಾ, ಗಜಪರಿಕ್ಷಾ, ವೃಕ್ಷಾರೋಪಣ, ವಾಸ್ತುವಿದ್ಯೆ ಹೀಗೆ ಹತ್ತು ಹಲವು ವಿಷಯಗಳೂ ವಿವರಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿವೆ.

ಇಂತಹ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠವಾದ ಪುರಾಣಪ್ರಪಂಚದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ಸ್ಯಪುರಾಣವೂ ಸಹ ಒಂದು. ಸಾಕ್ಷಾತ್ ಭಗವಂತನೇ ಮತ್ಸ್ಯರೂಪಿಯಾಗಿ ಧರ್ಮಾಚರಣೆಯ ಕ್ರಮವನ್ನು ಉಪದೇಶ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದರಿಂದ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಮತ್ಸ್ಯಪುರಾಣವೆಂಬ ಹೆಸರು ಬಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಸುಮಾರು 291 ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಗಳೂ, ಸುಮಾರು 14000 ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳು ಇವೆ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 255 ನೇ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯದಿಂದ 270 ನೇ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯದ ವರೆಗೆ ಸುಮಾರು ಹದಿನೈದು ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸ್ತುಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ವಿವರಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಆ ಕುರಿತು ಒಂದು ಸ್ಥೂಲವಾದ ಪರಿಚಯವನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಈ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಯ ಮೂಲ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ.

Paper No 3.05. Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

The Indian Ancient Architecture and Town Planning

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The construction industry is an important component of the modern economy. Development in engineering, more specifically civil engineering guides the present-day construction plan and execution. However ancient Indian knowledge provides a root for sustainability in the field of the construction industry. Ancient knowledge of architecture and 'Vasthu' provides an invisible value system through which the people can be more comfortable and in welfare. Therefore, there is a need to trace the root of those values related to the construction sector in the Indian ancient knowledge system. Such an attempt is made in this paper.

Objectives: The main aim of this paper is to trace the guidelines that Indian ancient knowledge on architecture and town planning provides. The specific objectives are;

- To review different aspects and ethical values of the construction industry in ancient India.
- To understand the concept of 'Vasthu' and town planning in Ancient India.

Description: This paper is descriptive in nature and based on reviewing various literatures available on Indian ancient architecture, Vasthu, and town planning. Understanding the roots of the present-day construction industry and engineering in ancient literature would help us to go further in a sustainable manner. Various aspects involved in ancient architecture such as light, wind in general natural energy to sustain are analyzed.

Keywords: Ancient Architecture, town planning, Vasthu, civil engineering, construction industry.

Paper No 3.06. Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

The concept of vasthu, an architectural science in traditional guthu houses of south canara

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ABSTRACT

Vasthu plays a very important role in designing the building. Vasthu is a scientific discipline in architecture, not a fiction. This article examines the scientific justifications for the vasthu concepts used in traditional guthu houses of south canara. The Guthu houses are the typical landlord houses of bunts. If a building were in tune with its surroundings, people would be healthy and happy, according to Vasthu. This research focuses on the vasthu principles of guthu houses, as well as whether or not the structure is climate-responsive. For this purpose, a 200 year-old traditional settibettu Guthu house has been used as an example. The detailed case study of the house involves documenting floor plans, elevations, sections, site plan, material study, and information on the building's orientation. The study's final finding is that by implementing vasthu principles, houses will have excellent light and ventilation, reducing our need for artificial ventilation. It also helps in the orientation of the building, which is in harmony with the five elements of earth, water, air, fire, and space, which are an integral part of Guttu houses of south canara.

Keywords: Architectural science, Vasthu, Guthu House, Traditional.

Paper No 3.07. Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

ವಾಸ್ತು ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಮೂಲ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು (The origin of Vastu and its benefits)

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ABSTRACT

ವಾಸ್ತುಮೂರ್ತಿ: ಪರಂಜ್ಯೋತಿ: ವಾಸ್ತುದೇವೋ ಪರೈಶಿಶಿವ: |

ವಾಸ್ತುದೇವಸ್ಯ ಸರ್ವೇಷಾಂ ವಾಸ್ತುದೇವಂ ನಮಾಮ್ಯಹಮ್ ||

“ವಸತಿ ಇತಿ ವಾಸ್ತು:” = ವಾಸ ಮಾಡುವುದು ವಾಸ್ತು ಎಂದು ವಾಸ್ತು ಶಬ್ದವನ್ನು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಬಹುದು. ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತದಲ್ಲಿ, ವಾಸ್ತು ಅಂದರೆ ಸ್ಥಿರವಾದ ವಸ್ತು, ಪದಾರ್ಥ, ಭೌತಿಕ ವಸ್ತು, ಸಂಪತ್ತು, ಅಥವಾ ಆಸ್ತಿ.

“ವಾಸ್ತು” ಎಂಬ ಪದವು “ವಸ್” ಎಂಬ ಧಾತುವಿನಿಂದ ಉತ್ಪತ್ತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. “ವಸ” ಎಂದರೆ “ವಾಸವಿರುವಿಕೆ” ಎಂದರ್ಥ. “ವಾಸ್ತು” ಎಂದರೆ “ವಾಸವಿರಲು ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾದ ಭೂಮಿ” ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು. ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಅಂದರೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ, ವಿಶೇಷ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಅಥವಾ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ / ಪಾರಂಪರಿಕ ಬೋಧನೆ ಎನ್ನಬಹುದು.

ವಾಸ್ತುದೇವನು ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ನಿವೇಶನದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇರುವನು. ಮನೆ, ಮಠ, ಮಂದಿರ ವಗೈರೆ ಸಮಸ್ತ ಕಟ್ಟಡಗಳ ಭೂಭಾಗದೊಳಗೆ ನೆಲೆಸಿರುವನು. ಆ ಸ್ಥಳವು ಸಣ್ಣದಿರಲಿ, ದೊಡ್ಡದಿರಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲದರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ವಾಸ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ವಾಸ್ತುದೇವನಿಗೆ ನಿಶ್ಚಿತವಾದ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಲಕ್ಷಣಯುಕ್ತವಾದ ಶರೀರ ಇರುವುದು. ಆತನ ಮಸ್ತಕವು ಆ ಸ್ಥಳದ ಈಶಾನ್ಯ ದಿಕ್ಕಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಳಗಡೆ ಆಲೂಗಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದು. ಈ ವಾಸ್ತು ದೇವತೆಯು ಹೇಗೆ ಆವಿರ್ಭಾವ ಹೊಂದಿದನು ಎಂಬ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮತ್ಸ್ಯ ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ಕಥೆ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇವನು ದೇವತೆಗಳ ಆಕ್ರಮಣಕ್ಕೊಳಪಟ್ಟು ಬಿದ್ದುಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಕ್ರೂರ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದು “ವಾಸ್ತು ಪುರುಷ” ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವನು.

ವಾಸ್ತುಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಇಂದಿನದಲ್ಲ. ಹಿಂದಿನದು. ಅತಿ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನವಾದದ್ದು. ವಾಸ್ತು ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು ಸೂಕ್ಷ್ಮವಾಗಿ ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಿ, ದಿಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಮೂಲೆಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಅವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಕಟ್ಟಡ, ಬಾಗಿಲು, ಕಿಟಕಿ ಇಡುವುದರಲ್ಲಿನ ಅರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಹಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

Keywords: ವಾಸ್ತು, ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ವೇದಕಾಲ, ವಾಸ್ತುಪುರುಷ, ದೇವತೆಗಳು, ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ, ಪಂಚಭೂತ ಭೂಮಿ, ದಿಕ್ಪಾಲಕರು, ಭಗವಂತ

Paper No 3.08. Ancient Indian Architecture and Vasthu:

विष्णुधर्मोत्तर पुराण में नृत्त के द्वारा देवताओं की पूजा करने का कथन

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सारसंक्षेप (Abstract) –

विष्णुधर्मोत्तर पुराण ललित कलाओं पर आधारित एक महत्वपूर्ण ग्रन्थ प्रतीत होता है। द्वापर युग के अन्त में तथा कलियुग के प्रारम्भ में देवताओं ने जब पृथ्वी पर आना बन्द कर दिया था तब महर्षि मार्कण्डेय राजा वज्र को मन्दिर निर्माण करने के लिये कहते हैं। नृत्त को आधार स्तम्भ बनाकर कैसे मन्दिर बनाने से लेकर नृत्त के द्वारा ही कैसे देवताओं की पूजा करनी है इसका विस्तृत वर्णन पुराण के तीसरे खण्ड में प्राप्त होता है। नृत्त के ज्ञान के बिना चित्र, प्रतिमा, शिल्प तथा स्थापत्य कला को समझना असंभव है से शुरुवात करते हुये मन्दिर निर्माण के पश्चात किस तरह नृत्त के सहारे से देवताओं को प्रसन्न किया जा सकता है, तथा नृत्त कैसे पूजा का उच्च माध्यम है इसका वर्णन पुराण के तीसरे खण्ड के अनेकों अध्यायों में प्राप्त होता है। जो की पुराण कालीन नृत्त के महत्व को ही नहीं दर्शाता अपितु नृत्त को केवल मनोरंजन का साधन ही नहीं बल्कि देवराधना का माध्यम भी साबित करता है। नाट्यशास्त्र में जहाँ नृत्त को नाट्य का सौन्दर्य वर्धक माना है वही विष्णुधर्मोत्तर पुराण इसे देवताओं की पूजा का साधन कहता है। वर्तमान में भी नृत्त केवल मनोरंजन के ही साधन के रूप में प्रतीत होता है। नृत्त के आध्यात्मिक महत्व को अन्य किसीभी ग्रन्थ में इतने विस्तृतता से नहीं बताया गया है। पुराण के आधार पर कौन कौन से व्रतों तथा मौकों पर नृत्त से पूजा करनी चाहिये इसको उजागर करना इस शोध पत्र का उद्देश है। उपलब्ध साहित्य के आधार पर इस शोध पत्र को प्रस्तुत किया जायेगा।

Paper No. 4.01: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

वेदेविज्ञानम् –समीक्षात्मकसंपादनम्

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतं नाम ज्ञानस्य विज्ञानस्य च भाण्डागारम् । संस्कृतेन अस्पृष्टः विज्ञानस्य भागः प्रायः नास्ति । अस्य फलस्वरूपभूता विज्ञानपरम्परा अधुनापि अनुवर्तमाना वर्तते । एतस्य भारतीयविज्ञानस्य अध्ययनम् अस्माभिः अधुना अत्यावश्यकं ।

Sanskrit is a classical language and has its application almost in every subject that we study today. The rich history of this language is reflected in the Vedas and Upanishads. They are verses and concepts in Vedas and Upanishads that explain the modern scientific inventions and discoveries. The attempt is made here to understand the science that was known to us in Vedic period which the modern world accepts even today.

It is said in तैत्तरीयसंहिता –

“मित्रोदधारपृथिवीमुतद्यामामित्रकृष्टीः” ।

The above line explains that the sun is the center of the solar system and it is he who upholds the other celestial objects.

Johannes Kepler, a German scientist in the 16th century stated in his Laws of Planetary Motion that –

“**All planets move about the Sun in elliptical orbits, having the Sun as one of the foci”.**

The above law gives the same explanation as per the verse in the तैत्तरीयसंहिता. The Vedas and their hymns are just not to please the almighty but also speaks about the science that the modern world is witnessing from a few centuries before.

Hence, it becomes very important to understand the essence of the statements that are mentioned in our Vedas and Puranas. This also gives the insight to the knowledge of our ancestors.

Keywords: तैत्तरीयसंहिता, Johannes Kepler, Laws of Planetary Motion, Vedas,

Paper No. 4.02: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

Vedic Astrology and its relevance in today's modern Bharath

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ABSTRACT

Jaimini and Parasara are two important sages whose methods have been used in predictive astrology. Unfortunately, some people think today that Parasara and Jaimini taught two totally different approaches to astrology. When it is about arudha padas, argalas, chara karakas, chara dasa and other rasi dasas, people think of them as “Jaimini astrology”.

People even use terms like “Jaimini karakas” and “Jaimini dasas”. However, all these concepts were covered by Parasara also in “Brihat Parasara Hora Sastram”. The “Parasari vs Jaimini” distinction is based on unfortunate

Vimsottari dasa and Ashtottari dasa, as they are the most commonly used nakshatra dasas. Kalachakra dasa was termed the “most respectable dasa” by Parasara and a discussion on dasas cannot be complete without it. In the galaxy of dasas, rasi dasas taught by Parasara and Jaimini have their own place and two rasi dasas used for timing material success – Lagna Kendradi Rasi dasa

All the above great saints have given scientific and fairly reliable methods of predicting the future. However there is certain mistrust among the hindu community when the word astrology or astrologers are perceived today. They are discounted as orthodox, unreliable. As astrologers it is our duty to put back faith and trust of people in system of vedic astrology.

Keywords: Parasara, JaiminiPadathi, Bhavas Vimsottari, Dasa Rasi

Paper No. 4.03: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

The Concept of Vedic Agronomy

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India is a land of Agriculture. In India Agriculture is not only an occupation but it is the life of people. 70% of the population depends on Agriculture for livelihood. So Healthy Agriculture is essential to a country's well being. This is found in Vedic literature. This present paper discusses a few points of Vedic Agriculture and Agronomy. Vedic Agricultural system was enriched by numerous practices like Cultivation, Ploughing, Sowing, Harvesting, Threshing, Different types of farmers and granaries. Agronomy is regarded as the mother of agriculture. Agronomy means "Art of managing the field". It deals with the principles and practices of field crop production and management of soil for higher productivity. Vedic people were well versed in Science and art of managing the field. They knew how to increase the soil fertility and improve the productivity of the cultivated land. Strongly they followed by traditions and cultures.

Every Agricultural practice was associated with religious customs. Farmers cultivate the land on auspicious days with the advice of saints. So ancient agriculture was very rich. Hence present day generation should be aware about ancient and traditional agricultural systems and practices which may further help the farmers in improvement of cultivation.

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Paper No. 4.04: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

“ಜಾತಕ ಫಲ ನಿರೂಪಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗಗಳ ಪಾತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹತ್ವ”**B. Srikantha Upadhya ***
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“ज्योतिःकल्पोनिरुक्तचशिक्षाव्याकरणंतथा ।

छन्दोविरचितेतानिषडङ्गानिविदुः श्रुते॥”

ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ ಮಾರ್ಗದಲ್ಲತಿಳಿಸಿರುವಂತೆ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಕಲ್ಪ, ನಿರುಕ್ತ, ಶಿಕ್ಷಾ, ವ್ಯಾಕರಣ, ಭಂದಸ್ಸು ಇವುಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿವೆದದ ೬ ಅಂಗಗಳಾಗಿದೆ.ಭಂದಸ್ಸು ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ವೇದದ ಕಾಲುಗಳು, ಶಬ್ದಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವುಮುಖ್ಯ,ಕಲ್ಪವು ಕೈ, ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷವು ವೇದದಕಣ್ಣು, ಶಿಕ್ಷಾ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ಮೂಗು, ನಿರುಕ್ತವು ರಿಪಿ, ಹೀಗೆ ಇದನ್ನು ವೇದದ ಅಂಗಗಳೆಂದು ಮುನೀಂದ್ರರು ಹೇಳಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಛಂದೋವಿರಚಿತೋ ಛಂದೋ ಛಂದೋ ಛಂದೋ” ಎನ್ನುವಂತೆ ಕಣ್ಣೆಲ್ಲದವನು ಹೇಗೆ ಪೂರ್ಣ ಮಾನವನಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲವೋ, ಇತರ ಅಂಗಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಕಣ್ಣಿಗೆ ಹೇಗೆ ಪ್ರಾಧಾನ್ಯವೋ ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವೂ ಕೂಡಾ ವೇದದ ಕಣ್ಣಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಈ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಇತರ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಪ್ರಾಧಾನ್ಯತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು.

ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು “ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು” ಎನ್ನುವಂತೆ ಖಗೋಳದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಗ್ರಹ ನಕ್ಷತ್ರಗಳ ಪರಿಚಯ, ಅವುಗಳ ಚಲನ ವಲನ, ಭೂಮಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮ, ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಹಗಳ ಚಲನೆಯಿಂದ ಮಾನವನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯುವ ಘಟನೆಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುವಂತದ್ದೇ ಈ ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ. ಯಾವ ಯಾವ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ಯಾವ ಕರ್ಮಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ವಿಧಿಸಿ, ವಿವರಿಸುವ ಈ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ಬಹು ಉಪಯುಕ್ತ ಹಾಗೂ ಬಹಳ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾದ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವಾಗಿದೆ.

ವಿಷಯಸೂಚಿ: , ಯೋಗ, ಗಣಿತ, ಸಂಹಿತ, ಹೋರಾ, ವರಾಹಮಿಹಿರ, ಶ್ರೀಕೃಷ್ಣ

Paper No. 4.05: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

HOROSCOPE & SELF ESTEEM: - A COMPARITIVE STUDY BETWEEN THE ZODIAC SIGNS AND SELF ESTEEM IN INDIAN ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

Self-esteem is the belief in one's own abilities or value. Beliefs and emotions about oneself are included in self-esteem. How we see and regard ourselves is a measure of our self-esteem. It is founded on our perceptions of ourselves, which can be challenging to alter. This could also be referred to as confidence. Depending on your level of self-esteem, you might: Like and appreciate yourself as a person. Astrology holds that celestial events have a causal relationship with human behavior based on the axiom "as above, so below," and as a result, the zodiac signs are thought to symbolize certain ways of expressing ourselves. There are other, more logical explanations for the apparent relationship between self esteem and birth months, such as the impact of seasonal birth in humans. The study investigated how zodiac signs and self-esteem interact with one another and can support people in dealing with their overall experiences and validating their own self-perceptions. 360 Indian adults were surveyed, had their self-esteem evaluated, and their zodiac signs were reviewed. The obtained data is to be subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS to evaluate if there is a significant difference in self-esteem between the zodiac signs. It is predicted that, there is a significant difference in the level of self-esteem between zodiac signs. It could thus be inferred that zodiac signs have significant impact on self-esteem. As a result of psychological processes like self-attribution and selective self-observation, astrology may have a significant impact on how people perceive themselves.

Keywords: - Zodiac sign, Self esteem, Indian adults, Self attribution, Personality traits.

Paper No. 4.06: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

ज्योत्पत्तिषये सम्राट् जगन्नाथस्य योगदानम्

त्तगरीशभट्टः त्ति

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सारांशः – फसलिज्योत्तिषग्रन्थेषु तनरूत्तपिनां शुभाशुभफलानाम् आदेशाथथमेऽि गणकः ग्रहस्फुटाः भास्फुटाश्च साध्यन्ते। परस्फुटाः सासिऽानां ग्रहस्फुटानां भास्फुटानाञ्च आरेण कृिः फलादेशाः एते परस्फुटाः भिन्तन्तः। अस्फुटान् ग्रहस्फुटानां भास्फुटांश्च स्वीकृत्य कृताः फलादेशाः परस्फुटाः भिन्तन्तः। एते परस्फुटाः फलादेशान् कर्तुं ग्रहाणां, लग्नाददभावानाञ्च स्फुटीकरणम् अदनवाययतया करणीयां भवदत्तः। ज्यागणतां दवना ग्रहाणां भावानाञ्च स्फुटीकरणं कर्तुं कथञ्चदपि न शक्यते। अत्र एते सूयथससद्धान्तादारभ्य केऽिकीग्रहगणपयथन्तं सिष्वत्तप ससद्धान्त-िन्त रकरणग्रन्थेषु ज्योत्पत्तिषयकाः ससद्धान्ताः उपत्तनिद्धाः सन्तन्तः। एते ज्योत्पत्तिः ससद्धान्तज्योदतषस्य प्रमुखः आधारभूतः ससद्धान्तः इति उच्ये चेऽि अत्तिशयोन्तं िन्थ भित्तिः। ज्यानाम् उत्पत्तिः ज्योत्पत्तिः इति षष्ठीऽित्पुरुषसमासः।

“The Science of calculation for the construction of Sine” इति आङ्ग्लभाषायां ज्योत्पत्तिशब्दस्य व्याख्या। वृत्तपररधेः एकस्मात्दिन्दुतः अन्यदिन्दुं यावत्कृता सरलरेखा एव पूण्यज्या। सा पूण्यज्या एव सरलरेखागणते ज्याशब्देन व्यवहियते। परन्तु ग्रहः स्वसञ्चारिऽिस्य पररिऽ स्वसञ्चारिऽिमध्यसूराऽि अथज्यायाः अग्रे सञ्चरति, न िऽ पूण्यज्यायाः अग्रे इति कारणाऽि ग्रहगणने अस्याः पूण्यज्यायाः अथरूपा अथज्य ि ज्याशब्देन असभीयि। एते ग्रहगणने सिथर अथज्यायाः एते उपयोगः भित्तिः। न िऽ पूण्यज्यायाः। एते अस्याः अथज्यायाः उपरर एते ज्योत्पत्तिषयकाः ससद्धान्ताः गणकः प्रत्तिपात्तदाः। सम्राट् जगन्नाथेन ससद्धान्तसम्राट् इति कश्चन ससद्धान्तग्रन्थः त्तिरसचिः। अन्तिन ग्रन्थे िेन ज्योत्पत्तिः ससद्धान्तानां प्रत्तिपादनाथथम पञ्चत्तिंशत्तिश्लोकात्मकम् एकं प्रकरणमेऽि सलसिऽिमन्तस्तः।

Paper No. 4.07: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

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भारतीयज्योतिषशास्त्रन्तु अपौरुषेयवेदस्य शिक्षेत्यादि षडङ्गेषु नेत्रभूतं स्थानम् आवहति। तदुक्तं प्रश्नमार्गे यथा - “वेदस्य चक्षुः किल शास्त्रमेतत्प्रधानताङ्गेषु ततोऽस्य युक्ता” इति। एवं वेदाङ्गभूते ज्योतिषशास्त्रे त्रयः मुख्याः विभागाः विद्यन्ते। सिद्धान्त-संहिता-होरा इति स्कन्धत्रयं शास्त्रे सन्दृश्यते। वरहमिहिराचार्यस्य इदं वचनं पुष्टीकरोति यथा “ ज्योतिषशास्त्रमनेकभेदविषयं स्कन्धत्रयाधिष्ठितम्॥ ” इति। एवं च स्कन्धत्रयाधिष्ठिते शास्त्रेऽस्मिन् जातकं गोलः निमित्तं प्रश्नः मुहूर्तः गणितम् इति षडङ्गानि अपि अन्तर्भवन्ति। प्रस्तुते लेखने शास्त्रस्य विभागाः यथाशास्त्रानुसारं क्रियते। तथैव अङ्गषट्कस्य विवरणं यथाशास्त्रं प्रस्तूयते। अपि च गणित-फलित-संहितायां प्रकृतिः अंशाः प्रस्तूयन्ते। यथा सिद्धान्ते सिद्धान्तस्य स्वरूपं लक्षणं च। तथैव संहिता-होरायाः स्वरूपविमर्शनं निगद्यते। अपि च तत्स्कन्धेषु उपवर्णिताः विचाराः अन्तर्भवन्ति।

एवं स्कन्धत्रयाणां वर्णनम् अल्पकाले असाध्यमेव। तस्मात् अत्र शास्त्रे विद्यमानस्य संहितास्कन्धस्य विचारान् समुपस्थापयामि। भारतीयज्योतिषशास्त्रे संहितास्कन्धः वैषिष्ट्येण कथ्यते। वराहः वदति यथा “ तत्कात्स्न्योपनयस्य नाम मुनिभिः सङ्कीर्त्यते संहिता॥ ” इति। अस्मिन् स्कन्धे गणितफलितविचाराः प्रतिपाद्यन्ते। तस्मादेव अयञ्च स्कन्धः विशिष्टो वर्तते। त्रिस्कन्धान्तर्भूतं नैकप्रकारकविषयप्रपञ्चनं यत्र उपलभ्यते सैव संहिता । अर्थात् भूगर्भविज्ञानादारभ्य अन्तरिक्षव्यापिग्रहधिष्ण्योल्काप्रभृतीनां भुवः उपरि कीदृशं फलदानमस्ति इत्यादिकं विविच्य प्रतिपाद्यते अत्र ।

Paper No. 4.08: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

करणीगणिते भास्कराचार्यस्य रोगदानम्

अननलकु मारदेसानर्ः

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सारांशः – यस्य कस्यापि राशः मूलां (गिगमूलं िा घनमूलं िा चतुमूलं िा णिमनप गणितीर्मूलं) अपूिायङ्केन भिन्त चेत् तत् करीशब्देन व्यनिर्ते । सङ्क्षेपतिः, अवर्ात्मकराशः मूलम व करणी इत्युच्यते । उदाहरणार्थं $\sqrt{3}$, $\sqrt{94}$, $\sqrt{रा}$, $\sqrt{ना}$ इत्यादीनन करिनाम् उदाहरिनन भिन्तन्त । $\sqrt{का}$ या इपत करणाः स्वरुिां भवपत । अत्र 'या' नाम करणीक्रमः (order) । का नाम करणीयम् (radicand) । एतादृशियः करणः समरुिकरणः (Like Surds), असमरूपकरणियः (unlike surds) चेनत निनििानन भिन्तन्त । र्ेषां करिनां सरलरूपे समकरीक्रमािः समकरीर्ानन च भिन्तन्त ते समरूपकरणियः इत्युच्यन्ते । तथा र्ेषां करिनां सरलरूपे करीक्रमािः समकरीर्ानन च णभन्नणभन्नानन भिन्तन्त ते असमरूपकरणियः इत्युच्यन्ते । आङ्गलभाषायां करणीनां Surds इनत नाम । करीगणितं व्यक् तगणितेऽप्यन्तभयिनत, अव्यक् तगणितेऽप्यन्तभयिनत । यर्था सामान्यानाम् अङ्कानां सङ्कलनव्यवकलनर्ुणनभजनापदिररकमाणण वयां साक्षाद व कु माः । िरन्तुकरणीनां सङ्कलनापदिररकमाणण वयां साक्षात्कतुं न शक्नु मः । करणीनां सङ्कलनापदिररकमाणण कतुं णभन्नप्रक्रयाः अनुसरणीयाः भवन्तन्त । भास्कराचार्येण णसद्धान्तणशरोमणः इपत बृहद्ग्रन्थः रणचतः । णसद्धान्तज्यौपतष ग्रन्थस्यास्य महत्त्वां मूर्ान्यस्थान वतात । अस्य ग्रन्थस्य चत्वारः भार्ाः सन्तन्त । त क्रमशः, लीलावती, बीजर्णतां, ग्रहर्णतां, ालाध्यायश्च पत ।

कू टशब्ाः – करणी, महती, लघु, वर्ाः, वर्ामूलम

Paper No. 5.01: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

The Personification of Saturn in Hindu Scriptures and Belief

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ABSTRACT

One of the most interesting things in Jyotiṣa is that planets, which are physical astrological bodies, are very clearly personified into human qualities. Specifically, the planet Saturn is personified as long-term misery. Yet, this personification aspect of Jyotiṣa has not been researched much. Given that every human will go through some sort of hardship in life, Saturn was chosen as the first planet of this type of research investigating how it is personified in different Hindu Scriptures and cultural belief.

The research method included reviewing classical and modern Jyotiṣa texts to see the span of how Saturn is seen over time, reviewing Itihasa& Purana literature to understand Saturn as a mythological character, interviewing devotees visiting the a Saturn temple on a Saturday, and conducting deeper interviewing with a few people who come from traditional Hindu families. The devotees who came to the temple saw Saturn as a great god capable of solving all their problems. But deeper interviews with those Brahmin's who come from traditional families, found Saturn described as a "good god, but one who is a troublemaker!". The stories of Saturn from Itihasa& Purana literature show him as a calculating god who puts people in trouble in a very precise way to cut out their ego and ultimately bring out the best in them. It is possible that the personification of Saturn in Vedic Astrology and Hindu culture is used in a therapeutic way to help believers mentally get through hard times in life.

Keywords: Jyotish, Vedic Astrology, Saturn, Shani, Astrology, Hindu Culture

Paper No. 5.02: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

The 'Planet' Problem and its Logical Solution

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ABSTRACT

Astrologers are asked the questions like, “you call sun as a planet?, it is a star”, “you call moon as planet?” “you call rahu and ketu as planets? they do not have mere existence”, “you miss out three more; where did Uranus, Neptune and Pluto disappear?” These simple questions are something difficult to answer. This is the ‘planet’ problem.

As such it is not the problem of the planets, but it is the problem of Planetizing. It is the problem of Englishizing. Further it is the problem of basic thinking. So, what is this ‘planet’ problem? This paper explains the psychology of the problem, and provides a logical solution for the same; which lies in the shloka, “namah suryaya chandraaya mangalaaya bhudhaayacha guru shukra shanibhyascha raahave ketaavae namaha”, taught during our childhood; but not in schools; but only at homes. It also explains more on the attitudes of the west and that of the east.

Keywords: Planets, Navagrahas, Surya, Chandra, Uranus, Neptune, pluto.

Paper No. 5.03: Ancient Indian Astrology and Numerology

Proposed Identification of the Dhruva of Siddhāntic Astronomers

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ABSTRACT

Dhruva – the pole star – has attracted the attention of several authors, ancient and modern, as it appears relatively fixed in the night sky, being close to the north celestial pole. Due to the effect of the precession of the equinoxes, the star which appears close to the north pole changes over the course of centuries. Despite this change, several ancient and medieval Indian texts spanning multiple millennia describe a star at the north pole. Previous research links the star mentioned in the Vedas and Purāṇas to Thuban, which was close to the pole at c. 2800 BCE. The present paper investigates the pole star (dhruva) of Siddhāntic authors (during fifth – twelfth centuries CE).

Several candidate stars were selected such that they are capable of approaching within one degree of the pole and were visible to the unaided eye through astronomical software. Based on the persons who referred to a pole star and their epochs, the north polar distance for these stars was computed and the stars that each astronomer could have referred to have been identified. $\Sigma 1694$, a faint double star located in the constellation Camelopardalis, was identified as a likely candidate during the Classical Siddhāntic Period as it came closest to the pole in c. 806 CE. Chinese records also confirm the sighting of the same event. This paper is written and presented in Sanskrit.

Keywords: Dhruva, North Pole, Siddhānta, Pole star, Dhruvatārā

Paper No. 6.01: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

इतिहासपुराणयोः वेदोपबृंहकत्वम्

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ABSTRACT

उपोद्घातः - 'वेदोऽखिलो धर्ममूलम्'। नित्यवित्प्रत्वात् वेदः सर्वाधारः। भाषाणां संस्कृतीनां शास्त्राणां जीवनपद्धतीनां संरक्षणार्थं संस्करणार्थं परिष्करणार्थं च वेदः अध्येतव्यः। तथैव वेदार्थसम्पादनार्थं षडङ्गान्यपि। पुराणं भारतमपि। अपि च धर्मेण कामितार्थप्राप्त्यर्थं मुमुक्षुणा वेदोऽनुसन्धेयः। सन्ध्या, पूजा यज्ञादिषु उपयुज्यमानाः मन्त्राः यदि ज्ञाताः स्युः तदैव कर्माणि तारकाणि भवन्ति। तदधुना जगति केवलं वैदिककर्म अज्ञात्वापि कर्तुं शक्यते। नान्यत्र कुत्रापि। तदेतस्य दोषस्य परिहाराय व्यासेन प्रादर्शि पन्थाः। "इतिहासपुराणाभ्यां वेदं समुपबृंहयेत्।"

महाभारतपञ्चरात्रादिग्रन्थाः अष्टादशपुराणानि च वेदोपबृंहकानि। वेदे प्रतिपादिताः आख्यायिकाः पुराणेषु स्पष्टतया विवृताः। अपि च अनेके औपासनाविषयाः पञ्चरात्रान्तर्गताः भवन्ति। भारते पुराणे च देवता स्तुतयः विश्वादि सूक्तानां अनुवादाः इव भासन्ते। अत एव एतेषां पञ्चमवेदत्वमुच्यते।

भागवतस्य तृतीयस्कन्धस्य विराडुपवर्णनावसरे समग्रपुरुषसूक्तस्य व्याख्यानं दृश्यते। अत्र तु चतुर्षु श्लोकेषु चतुर्षु वेदेषु पठ्यमानोऽयं मन्त्रः विवृतः।

"ब्राह्मणोऽस्य मुखमासीद् बाहू राजन्यः कृतः" इत्यत्र यदुक्तं पुरुषसूक्ते तत्र केवलं भागवते किन्तु विष्णवग्निपद्मादिषु पुराणेष्वपि विवृतं दरीदृश्यते।

भारते च

"ऊर्ध्वमूलमधःशाखमश्वत्थं प्राहुरव्ययम्"

कठे च

ऊर्ध्वमूलोऽवाक् शिराः एषोऽश्वत्थः सनातनः" एवं पुराणभारतवाक्यानि लभ्यन्ते।

प्रपञ्चेऽस्मिन् संहितारण्यकब्राह्मणोपनिषदां वाक्यानां पुराणभारतसंवादः संगृह्यते। प्रमुखतया अस्य रचनार्थं श्रीमदानन्दतीर्थविरचितसर्वमूलग्रन्थाः अष्टादशपुराणानि, पञ्चरात्रादि आगमग्रन्थाः ऋगादयो वेदाः साहाय्यं

कुर्वन्ति इति विश्वसिमि।

प्रणवार्था व्याहृतयः व्याहृत्यर्था ऋगादयः।

इतिहासपुराणं च पञ्चरात्रं च सर्वशः ॥

Paper No. 6.02: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

वेदार्थनिर्णायकरूपेण ब्रह्मसूत्राणि

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ABSTRACT

पूष्णानन्दस्वरूपो भगवान् विष्णुः। जीवास्तु दुःखयुक्ता एव। एतादृशानां दुःखिनां जीवानां दुःखनाशायैव वेदास्तु सततं प्रवर्तिताः। द्वापरयुगे तु सर्वजाति ज्ञानं अज्ञानेन छन्नमासीत्। अज्ञानेन, विपरीतज्ञानेन च जनाः सर्वे व्यथामनुभूतवन्तः सन्मार्गदर्शनेन। वेदोदितपन्थानो न ज्ञाताः सर्वे। तदा वेदविभागार्थं, वेदार्थनिर्णायकग्रन्थरचनार्थञ्च भगवान् विष्णुर्नारायणः बादरायणरूपेण द्वैपायनापरनाम्ना आविर्भूतवान्। ऊर्ध्वलोकस्था देवा अपि तं नारायणं प्रार्थितवन्त इत्यपि पुराणवाक्यानि स्पष्टमवगम्यन्ते। नारायणाद्विनिष्पन्नं, ज्ञानं कृतयुगे स्थितम्।

किञ्चित्तदन्यथा जातं त्रेतायां द्वापरेऽखिलम्॥ (इति

स्कन्दपुराणोक्तिः)

गौतमस्य मुनेः शापात् सुज्ञानेऽज्ञानानां प्राप्ते, भगवन् कृष्णद्वैपायनो वेदान् उत्सन्नान् चतुर्धा व्यभजत्। कृष्णद्वैपायनस्तु सत्यवती-पराशरयोः सुतत्वेन गणयते। अपि तु भगवतो जन्मराहित्यमेव लक्षणम्। ततः व्यासत्वेन अवततार। न तु गर्भावासादिदुःखम् अनुभूय सञ्जातः।

वेदविभागसामर्थ्यं तु भगवदन्येषां तु नास्त्येव खलु।
तस्माद्देदान् विभज्य, तदर्थनिर्णयाय ब्रह्मसूत्राणि चकार॥

Paper No. 6.03: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

“ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ” ಎಂಬ ‘ವೈಶ್ವಿಕ’ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗೆ ವೇದದ ಕೊಡುಗೆ- “ಯಜ್ಞ”ದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ

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ABSTRACT(ಮುಖ್ಯಾಂಶ)

“ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ” ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಇಂದು ಅತಿಹೆಚ್ಚು ಚಿಂತನೆಗೆ ವೇದಿಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಟ್ಟು ‘ವೈಶ್ವಿಕ’ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ. ವಿಶ್ವಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಯಾವುದೇ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳು ನಡೆದರೂ ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಮುನ್ನೆಲೆಗೆ ಚರ್ಚಿಸಲ್ಪಡುವ ಅಂಶ ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ. ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಭಾರತ ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಚಿಂತನೆಯನ್ನು ತನ್ನ ಅಪೌರುಷೇಯ ಸಂವಿಧಾನ, ವೇದ ತತ್ವಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಸಾಧಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿತ್ತು. ಇದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಅದು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡ ನೀತಿ- ವಿಧಿ ಅದು “ಯಜ್ಞ”ದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ.

ಯಜ್ಞ ಎಂದರೆ ಅಗ್ನಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ದ್ರವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಗ ಎಂಬುದಷ್ಟೇ ಅರ್ಥವಲ್ಲ. ‘ದ್ರವ್ಯಯಜ್ಞ’- ಜ್ಞಾನ, ತಪ, ಸ್ವಾಧ್ಯಾಯ, ಪಂಚಯಜ್ಞ... ಹೀಗೆ ಹತ್ತು ಹಲವು ಕವಲಾಗಿ ಯಜ್ಞವು ತನ್ನ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಇದು ಬದುಕಿನ ಹಾಗೂ ಬದುಕಿನಾಚೆಗಿನ ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯನ್ನು ಕೇಂದ್ರೀಕರಿಸಿ ಹೊರಟಿರುವಂಥದ್ದು.

ಇದರ ವಿಸ್ತೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಂಡಲ್ಲಿ, ಅಂತಹುದೇ ಬದುಕನ್ನು ಬದುಕುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿದಲ್ಲಿ, ಅನೇನ ಪ್ರಸವಿಶ್ಯಧ್ವಂ ಇದರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಸವಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಿ ಎಂಬ ಮಾತಿಗೆ ಅರ್ಥ ದೊರಕುತ್ತದೆ. ಕಸವಿಲ್ಲದೇ ರಸವಷ್ಟೇ ಬೆಳೆಯುವ, ಉಳಿಯುವ, ಮುಂದಿನ ಪೀಳಿಗೆಗೂ ಉಳಿಸಿ ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ವೇದೋಕ್ತ ಯಜ್ಞದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಸಮತೋಲನದ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಎಡೆಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುವ ಬಗೆಯನ್ನು ಈ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಲೇಖನವು ಚರ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪದಗಳು- ಯಜ್ಞ, ಸುಸ್ಥಿರ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ, ದ್ರವ್ಯಯಜ್ಞ.

Paper No. 6.04: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

तमोवादे वैशेषिकमतमण्डनम्

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ABSTRACT

मोक्षसाधनत्वेन पदार्थविचारणावसरे तत्र षडेव पदार्था इति स्थापयित्वा, आद्यत्वेन द्रव्यनिरूपणावसरे पृथिव्यादीनि नवैवेति प्रतिज्ञायन्ते वैशेषिकैः । तदसहमाना मीमांसकाः, तमो नाम तत्परमाणुभिरारब्धस्य रूप-परिमाणादिवद्द्रव्यान्तरस्य सद्भावात् कथन्नवैवेति कथ्यतेति शङ्कन्ते । तान् वैशेषिकाः पृच्छन्ति- तत्र परमाणुषु स्पर्शः अस्ति, न वा ? स्पर्शकार्यानुपलम्भात् न तत्र स्पर्शः शक्यकल्पनः । एवमस्पर्शवत्त्वे कार्यद्रव्यानारम्भकत्वं प्रसज्यते, तस्य तद्द्रव्याप्तत्वात् । तर्हि कथन्तत्रोत्पत्तिप्रक्रियाकल्पनमिति ।

ननु कथम्भवता सर्वजनप्रत्यक्षीभूतस्य तमसः निराकरणं क्रियते ? इति चेन्न । न हि वयं अन्धकारविरोधञ्चिकीर्षामः । किन्तु भवदुक्कारम्भप्रक्रियाया अनुपपत्त्या नीलिमामात्र-प्रतीतेश्च द्रव्यमिदं न भवतीति ब्रूमः । तमोऽपि न तेजोऽभावः । तथात्वे नीलाकारेण भानानुपपत्तिः। अपि च अभावः खलु कस्मिंश्चिदधिकरणे प्रतियोगिनिषेधरूपेण प्रतीयते, न स्वतन्त्रः । न हि तमो ग्रहणावसरे अन्यस्य ग्रहणमस्ति ! तर्हि किं स्वरूपन्तमस इति चेत् अत्यन्तन्तेजोऽभावे सति या नीलिमा समन्तादारोप्यते तत्रैव तमश्शब्दप्रवृत्तिस्सर्वेषामिति ।

न केवलन्तावदेव । तमः खलु कदाचित् नियतदेशपरिच्छिन्नतया भासते, तमः यद्यभावः तर्हि नैवं दैर्घ्य-ह्रस्वत्वादिप्रत्ययः स्यात् ! अभावस्य तथाभानायोग्यत्वात् । तदुक्तं -

“न च भासामभावस्य तमस्त्वं वृद्धसम्मत्तम् । छायायाः काष्ण्यमित्येव पुराणे भूगुणश्रुतेः ।

दूरासन्नप्रदीपादेर्महदल्पचलाचला । देहानुवर्तिनी छाया न वस्तुत्वाद्धिना भवेत्” । इति ।

एवन्तमस अतिरिक्तद्रव्यत्वविषये प्रस्तुतानाम्प्रमाणानामनुपपत्तीन् प्रदर्श्य, निराकृत्य तमस विषये स्वाभिप्रायम्मण्डयन्ति वैशेषिकाः ॥

Paper No. 6.05: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

उत्तरमीमांसायांपूर्वमीमांसा

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ABSTRACT

व्यासोच्छिष्टं जगत्सर्वम् इत्याभणकप्रथानुसारेण भारतीयवाङ्मयेषु मूलस्रोतरूपेण सर्वत्र व्यापृतं वर्तते वेदव्याससाहित्यम् । तादृशव्याससाहित्यञ्च द्वैविध्येन दरीदृश्यते । तैः व्यासमुनिभिः निर्मितानि महाभारतादीनि, ऋगादयः चत्वारः वेदाः न रचिताः, उपदिष्टमात्रमिति । तादृशापौरुषेयवेदमनुसृत्यैव प्रवर्तितानि भारतीयदर्शनानि आस्तिकदर्शनानि इति भण्यन्ते ॥

तानि च षट् कपिलसांख्यदर्शनम्, पातञ्जलयोगदर्शनम्, गौतमन्यायदर्शनम्, काणादवैशेषिकदर्शनम्, व्यासशिष्यजैमिनिप्रणीतमीमांसादर्शनम्, वेदव्यासप्रणीतं वेदान्तदर्शनमिति । एषु षड्दर्शनेषु मीमांसायाः पूर्वमीमांसा इति, अन्तिमस्य वेदान्तस्य उत्तरमीमांसा इत्यपि नाम वर्तते । यतः वेदार्थनिर्णायकस्वरूपयोः मीमांसावेदान्तयोः पौर्वापरसम्बन्धसद्भावात् विद्यमानानुपूर्वीमनुसृत्य पूर्वमीमांसा – उत्तरमीमांसा इत्यपि नाम युज्यते । तादृशापौरुषेयवेदमनुसृत्य पूर्वमीमांसा – उत्तरमीमांसा इत्यपि नाम युज्यते । तादृशापौरुषेयवेदमनुसृत्य पूर्वमीमांसा – उत्तरमीमांसा इत्यपि नाम युज्यते ।

एवमेव एषु षड्दर्शनेषु विविधाः विप्रतिपत्तयः यथा वर्तन्ते तथा केषुचित्विषयेषु परस्परमुपजीव्योपजीवकभावश्च दरीदृश्यते । यथा ‘काणादं पाणिनीयञ्च सर्वशास्त्रोपकारकमिति वैशेषिकदर्शनस्य सर्वशास्त्रोपजीव्यत्वं वर्तते तथा मीमांसायाः अपि वेदान्तशास्त्रोपजीव्यत्वं अनुभूयते । वेदान्तदर्शने च मायावादः तत्त्ववादः इत्यादिप्रभेदः लोकसिद्धः । तत्र च ‘द्वैतसिद्धान्तः’ इति प्रथिते श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्याणां तत्त्ववादसिद्धान्ते न्यायव्याकरणशास्त्रयोः उपयोगः यथा वर्तते तथा मीमांसायाः अपि प्रवेशः, उपयोगः, सम्बन्धः वर्तते । एवं माध्वीयोत्तरमीमांसायां पूर्वमीमांसायाः उपजीव्योपजीवकभावसम्बन्धः विचिन्त्यते

Paper No. 6.06: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

Vedic Remedy for Maths Phobia !

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ABSTRACT

Vedas includes knowledge of spirituality, science, mathematics, philosophy, literature and logic. Mathematics is study of numbers, formulas, shapes, quantities and their changes. The way of solving mathematical problems according to Vedas is described in Vedic Mathematics. This ancient method of calculations was developed from the Artharva Veda also known as the "Veda of magical formulae". It was developed in the year 1957 and consists of sixteen sutras and thirteen sub-sutras that help solve problems of arithmetic, trigonometry, geometry, algebra, and many more mathematical areas very easily within seconds. The calculations done here are mentally and does require a much of paperwork. The technique or tricks used for solving a problem are much faster, organised, streamlined, and integrated than the contemporary system.

Vedic Mathematics helps to elucidate all arithmetical problem-solving concepts and algebraic concepts more efficiently than the modern system. In this era of technology students have developed maths phobia due to rote learning, lack of motivation, lack of understanding, lack of confidence, inappropriate methods of teaching and lengthy algorithms. Through applying Vedic Mathematics we can overcome all the above said problems. This paper discusses how Vedic Maths techniques can be used to tackle a mathematical problem and build the student's confidence. Introducing Vedic Mathematics in schools as an alternative to the conventional mathematic teaching makes mathematics fun for students.

Paper No. 6.07: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

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ABSTRACT

Vedic educational approach to human life is well known. The Puranic chronology, the timeline of events in ancient Indian history and mythology as narrated in Epics- the Mahabharata, the Ramayana, and the 18 Puranas. Precise education system on Vedic base is the only one path to understand the actual purpose and value of life. Vedic education is the solution to all problems which we presently find in this world.

The Epics exhibit us what the right way to live life is, and explains the actual meaning of life. Epical stories contain the principles and lesson of life. Vedas are treasury of real knowledge about the Lord/Bhagvan who is the hero of Epical stories. Purans show perfect and valid paths of Sadhana through Bhakti and Performance of Karmas laid down by the the Shastras to reach the Lord. The Vedic Education vitally play an important role in the construction of contemporary humanism for it is in these works that many of the stories and concepts central to life and Dharma are found. The present paper explores Modern Education based on Community approach to look the above said issue with Ancient/Vedic root.

Keywords: Vedic education. Community schooling. Karma, Sadhana, Shastra.

Paper No. 6.08: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

ರಾಮಾಯಣ – ಮಹಾಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳು

ಡಾ. ಕೆ.ಕೃಷ್ಣಮೂರ್ತಿ ಮಯ್ಯ

ವಿಭಾಗ ಮುಖ್ಯಸ್ಥರು,

ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ವಿಭಾಗ, ಶ್ರೀ ಅರಬಿಂದೋ ಮಹಾವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ,

ಮಹಾಲಕ್ಷ್ಮೀಪುರಂ, ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು 86, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ, ಭಾರತ

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“ಭಾರತಸ್ಯ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠೇ ದ್ವೇ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಂ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಶ್ಚ”. ನಮ್ಮ ಭವ್ಯ ರವ್ಯ, ನವ್ಯ, ಹೆಮ್ಮೆಯ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠೆ, ಗೌರವ ಎರಡು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಎಂಬ ಈ ವಾಕ್ಯವು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತದ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಜಗತ್ತಿಗೆ ತೋರಿಸಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಗಾಧವಾದ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಸಂಪತ್ತು ಅಡಗಿದೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ನಮ್ಮ ದೇಶದ ಎರಡು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾದ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಾದ ಶ್ರೀಮದ್ ರಾಮಾಯಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಾಭಾರತ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ಪ್ರತಿಬಿಂಬಕಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ರಾಮಾಯಣ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹಾಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳು ಅಪಾರವಾಗಿ ಚಿತ್ರಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇವುಗಳು ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಜೀವನವು ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಯುತವಾಗಿರಲು ಸಹಾಯಕವಾಗಿವೆ. ಈಗಿನ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆ ಬಹಳವಿದೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಎರಡು ಮಹಾಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಜೀವನ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಜೀವಜಗತ್ತಿಗೆ ತೆರೆದಿಡುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವಿದೆ.

ಶ್ರೀಮದ್ ರಾಮಾಯಣವು ಆದಿ ಕವಿ ವಾಲ್ಮೀಕಿಯಿಂದ ರಚಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸರ್ವವಿದಿತ. ಅಂತೆಯೇ ಮಹಾಭಾರತವು ಶ್ರೀ ವೇದವ್ಯಾಸರಿಂದ ರಚಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಈ ಎರಡು ಮಹಾಕಾವ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾನವನಿಗೆ ಅತ್ಯಮೂಲ್ಯವಾದ ಉಪದೇಶವೇ ಇದೆ. ಎರಡು ಮಹಾಕಾವ್ಯಗಳ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರಗಳಾದ ಶ್ರೀರಾಮ, ಶ್ರೀಕೃಷ್ಣ, ಯುಧಿಷ್ಠಿರ, ಸೀತೆ, ದ್ರೌಪದಿ, ವಿದುರ, ಸುಗ್ರೀವ, ಕರ್ಣ, ಸುಧಾಮ, ಅಂಜನೇಯ, ದ್ರೋಣ, ಭೀಷ್ಮ, ಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಣ, ಭರತ ರಲ್ಲಿ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಆದರ್ಶಗುಣಗಳು, ಸಹೋದರತ್ವ, ಪಿತೃಭಕ್ತಿ, ಪತಿವ್ರತಾಧರ್ಮ, ಮಿತ್ರತ್ವ, ಸೇವಾ ಮನೋಭಾವ, ಭಲ, ಭಕ್ತಿ, ದುಷ್ಟ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಶಿಷ್ಟ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಮುಂತಾದ ಅನರ್ಘ್ಯ ಜೀವನ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳು ಸಿಗುತ್ತವೆ. ಮೇಲೆ ಹೇಳಿದ ಪಾತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ , ಅವರು ಆದರ್ಶವಾಗಿ ತೋರುವ ಜೀವನ ಮೌಲ್ಯಗಳ ಚಿತ್ರಣ ಇಲ್ಲಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪದಗಳು : - ಆದರ್ಶಗುಣಗಳು, ಪಿತೃಭಕ್ತಿ, ಭ್ರಾತೃ ಪ್ರೇಮ.

ಜಯತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಮ್

ಜಯತು ಭಾರತಮ್

Paper No. 6.09: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

॥ श्रीः ॥

काव्य – पुराण - शास्त्रयोर्मध्ये को भेदः ? कथम् ।

डा.केशव किरण बि

प्राध्यापकः

श्रीराघवेन्द्रभारती सवेद संस्कृत महाविद्यालयः मुग्वा-सुब्रह्मण्य

होन्नावर उत्तरकन्नड

कर्नाटक -५८१३३४

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नमःसभायै ।

शब्दप्राधान्यमाश्रित्य तत्र शास्त्रं पृथग्विदुः ।

अर्थे तत्त्वेन युक्ते तु वदन्त्याख्यानमेतयोः ॥

द्वयोर्गुणत्वे व्यापारप्राधान्ये काव्यगीर्भवेत् ।¹

विवक्षितस्यार्थस्य प्रतिपादनाय यत् वाक्यं प्रयुज्यते तत्र प्रतिपादकं भवति वाक्यम्, प्रतिपाद्यो भवत्यर्थः, तयोरुभयोः प्रतिपादनमिति व्यापारश्चेति तिपुटी काचित् सम्भवति, यथा - देवदत्तो ग्रामं गच्छतीत्यत्र समग्रं वाक्यं प्रतिपादकम्, 'देवदत्ताभिन्नाश्रयवृत्तिः ग्रामाभिन्नाश्रयवृत्तिसंयोगानुकूलो व्यापारः' इति, 'देवदत्तो ग्रामकर्मकगमनानुकूलकृतिमान्' इति वा अर्थः प्रतिपाद्यः, तयोरुभयोः प्रतिपादनमिति व्यापारः यश्च आश्रयतासम्बन्धेन शब्दे वर्तते विषयतासम्बन्धेन त्वर्थे । अस्यां च त्रिपुट्यां यदि शब्दस्य प्राधान्यं भवति तर्हि वाक्यस्य शास्त्रमिति व्यपदेशः । यद्यर्थस्य तर्हि पुराणमिति व्यपदेशः । अथ प्रतिपादनरूपस्य व्यापारस्य तर्हि काव्यमिति विशेषः ।

आमयाविनं प्रति 'अनामयो भूयाः' इत्युक्ते क्षेत्रियरोगेण पीड्यमानोऽपि अचिरादुल्लाघः सम्पद्यते । अत एवोक्तं भवभूतिना -

लौकिकानां हि साधूनामर्थं वागनुवर्तते ।

ऋषीणां पुनराद्यानां वाचमर्थोऽनुधावति ॥

। तत्र हि विवक्षितार्थद्वयस्य प्रतिपादके शब्दान्तरे प्रयुक्तेऽपि न काव्यत्वस्य हानिः । एतेन शब्दानां परिवृत्यसहत्वं शास्त्र आत्यन्तिकं सार्वत्रिकं च, काव्ये तु तदैच्छिकं क्वाचित्कं चेति वैलक्षण्यं सिद्धं भवति ।

Paper No. 6.10: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

वेदेषु मानवीयमौल्यानां स्वरूपम्

डा. कृष्ण वे, जोशि

क.सं.वि. बेंगलूरु

विष्णुसाहित्ये वेदाः एव उपलब्धग्रन्थेषु प्रथमो ग्रन्थः । समग्रं भारतीयचिन्तनं वेदादारभ्य अद्ययावत् समस्त संस्कृत वाङ्मये प्रतिबिम्बितं वर्तते । समस्त मानवजातेः कल्याणोद्देशेन प्रेरितं वर्तते यत्र मानवीय मूल्यानि अन्तर्हितानि वर्तन्ते । अखिल जगदुद्दीर्घिषवः ऋषयः सकलशास्त्राणि रचितवन्तः । अनेकेषु ग्रन्थेषु – वसुधैव कुटुम्बकम्, यत्र, विष्णु भवत्येकनीडम्, त्रैलोक्यं मङ्गलं कुरु, सर्वे भवन्तु सुखिनः सर्वे सन्तु निरामयाः इत्यादिनि वचनानि समस्त मानवजातेः हितमभिलक्ष्यैव केन्द्रीकृतानि दृश्यन्ते । वर्तमाने संघर्षप्रधाने विज्ञानयुगे बहुत्र मनसः उद्विग्नता, क्षोभः, द्वेषः, अशान्तिः ताण्डवनृत्यं कुर्वन्त्यः वर्तन्ते । मानवीय मूल्यानां ह्रासः एव तत्र कारणम् । एतेषां मूल्यानामावश्यकता संप्रति अधिकतया वर्तते । नैतिक मूल्यानां विषये पाश्चात्य विद्वान् वदति, नाना सामाजिक पद्धतिषु, विविध सभ्यतासु, निरन्तरं परिवर्तमानेषु समाजेषु, नैतिकता अथवा नैतिक मूल्यानां संरक्षणमेव अविच्छिन्ना शृङ्खला वर्तते या प्राचीनं विष्णुमाधुनिक विष्णुन सह संबन्धाति ।

सनातनपरम्परानुसारं धर्म-काम-मोक्ष नाम्ना चत्वार पुरुषार्थाः जीवनमौल्यानि एव भवन्ति।

आधुनिक भारतीय साहित्येषु धार्मिक सामाजिक-आर्थिक-सांस्कृतिक मूल्यानीति तेषां वर्गीकरणं कृतं इति दृश्यते । सन्दर्भेऽस्मिन् निखिले संस्कृतसाहित्ये विस्तृतमानवीयमूल्यानां विचारः सर्वत्र कृतो वर्तते । “वेदोऽखिलो धर्ममूलम्” इति वचनानुगुणं पुरुषार्थ-चतुष्टये धर्मस्यैव सर्वत्र मूलरूपेण प्राधान्यं प्रतिपादितम् । अर्थकामौ सर्वथा न तिरस्कृतौ इति न । निर्दिष्टानां स्वीय-सामाजिक-आर्थिक मूल्यानां समावेशः संस्कृतसाहित्ये सर्वत्र कृतो वर्तते । चतुर्षु वेदेषु एतानि मूल्यानि सूक्तिरूपेण सङ्गृहितानि । कासाञ्चन सूक्तीनामुद्धरणपूर्वकं तत्रान्तर्हित मूल्यनिरूपणं स्पष्टीक्रियते ।

Paper No. 6.11: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

चतुर्विधपुरुषार्थः

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ABSTRACT

पुरुषार्थः नाम स्व-जीवनोद्धारस्य उद्देशः । अयं हिन्दूधर्मस्य एका प्रमुखा परिकल्पना । अयं मानवजीवनस्य अन्तिमध्येयस्य उल्लेखं करोति । ‘पुरुषार्थः’ इति शब्दः संस्कृतस्य पदद्वयेन उत्पन्नः । ‘पुरुषः’ नाम मनुष्यः , ‘अर्थः’ नाम उद्देशः। अतः पुरुषार्थः इत्युक्ते मानवानाम् उद्देशः इति वक्तुं शक्यते । ‘अहम् अध्यात्मिक-अभिवृद्धये किमपि करोमि वा ? आत्मनः स्तरे वस्तुतः अहं किम् इच्छामि?’ इति एकक्षणं विचिन्त्य पृच्छामः चेत् , तदा मनसि आगच्छेत् वेदे उक्ताः त्रयः पुरुषार्थाः – धर्मार्थकामाः । एते त्रयः अपि परस्परं सम्बन्धिताः । धर्मः तु अर्थसञ्चयविषये सामान्यावश्यकता । कामविषये अर्थः आवश्यकः । एतेषां त्रयाणां सम्यक् आचरणेन मोक्षसाधनं भवेत् ।

धर्मः इत्युक्ते सत्यम् । जीवनस्य उत्तमः मार्गः धर्ममार्गः । जीवनस्य उद्देशः एव धर्मः इति वक्तुं शक्यते । ‘स्वधर्मे निधनं श्रेयः’ इति उक्तिः प्रसिद्धा । परधर्माचरणस्य अपेक्षया स्वधर्माचरणम् एव श्रेष्ठः । यदा धर्ममार्गे भवामः तदा अस्माकं निर्धारः कार्याणि च सम्यक् एव भवति । वयं जीवने परिपूर्णताम् अनुभवामः धर्ममार्गे । इहलोकस्य सम्बन्धानां कृते न्यायदानम् एव धर्मः । इत्युक्ते अस्माकं कर्तव्यस्य परिपालनम् । धर्मपालनार्थं अर्थसम्पादनम् अत्यावश्यकम् अनिवार्यं च । स एव अर्थः। जीवनस्य प्रतिस्तरेषु अपि भिन्न-भिन्नाः वाञ्छाः भवन्ति । तदेव कामः । व्यक्तित्वविकासाय कामात् मुक्तिप्राप्तये तस्य अनुभवः एव कुञ्चिका । मोक्षः मानवजीवनस्य अन्तिमः ध्येयः । स्वयं साक्षात्कारः । पुनर्जन्मचक्रात् विमोचनम् ।

Paper No. 6.12: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

श्रीमद्भागवते वर्णित सूर्यस्य लौकिकक्रमः, नानाग्रहाणां स्थितिः

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ABSTRACT

कृष्णं नारायणं वन्दे कृष्णं वन्दे ब्रजप्रियम् ।

कृष्णं द्वैपायनं वन्दे कृष्णं वन्दे पृथासुतम् ॥

श्रीमद्भागवतं अष्टादश सहस्रग्रन्थैः युक्तं, द्वादशस्कन्धेषु विभक्तम् अस्ति । अयं ग्रन्थः शुक्रमहर्षिः-परीक्षीन्द्राजयोर्मध्ये संवादरूपेण अस्ति । इयं भागवतकथा मोक्षस्य मुख्यकारणम् अस्ति । सहस्रशः अश्वमेधयागानाम् तथा शतशः वाजपेयानाम् आयोजनेनपि अस्याः परिकथायाः कलासमम् न भवति । गङ्गा-काशी-पुष्कर-प्रयाग इत्यादीनां तीर्थानाम् भ्रमणेन अपि अस्य श्रीमद्भागवतस्य कथाश्रवणस्य फलसमानम् न भवति । वेदाः, पुरुषसूक्तः, द्वादशाक्षरमन्त्राः, महाविष्णुः अस्मात् सर्वस्मात् भागवतकथा न भिन्ना । यः मानवः अस्य कथायाः अर्थज्ञानपूर्वकम् पठनम् करोति तस्य कोटि जन्मकृतम् पापनिवृत्तिः भवति इत्यत्र न संशयः । अन्त्यकाले यः अस्य कथायाः श्रवणं करोति तं श्रीमन्नारायणः स्वयं एव मुक्तिमार्गाम् प्रति नयति । एषा कथा एकाग्रतापूर्वकं श्रोतव्या । अस्याः कथाश्रवणाय न दिवसनियमाः । किन्तु निरन्तरम् श्रोतव्यम्, अस्मिन् कलियुगे तादृशसमर्थवृत्ताचरणम् असम्भवम् इत्यतः सप्ताहं यावत् श्रवणं इति सुलभोपायः शुक्रमहर्षिणा आदेशात् व्यवस्थापितः अस्ति ।

विषयपरामर्शः

श्रीशुक उवाच

एतावानेव ब्रूलयस्य सन्निवेशः प्रमाणलक्षणतो

व्याख्यातः ॥

खगोलशास्त्रस्य भूगोलस्य च मध्ये विद्यमानम् अन्तरिक्षम् इति उच्यते । अन्तरिक्षस्य एकः अन्तः पृथिव्याः उपरिभागं, अपरः अन्तः स्वर्गतलम् संयोजयति ।

Paper No. 6.13: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

ऋषिकाणां समाजं प्रति योगदानम्

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ABSTRACT

प्रतियुगं यदि वयं दृष्टिं प्रसारयामः तर्हि उत्तमस्त्रीणाम् उपनयनं, वेदाध्ययनं शास्त्राध्ययनं वा आ बहोः कालादेव आसीदिति ज्ञायते । “देव्यो मुनि स्त्रियश्चैव नरादिकुलजा अपि उत्तमा इति विज्ञेया” इति आचार्यमध्वैः व्योमसंहिताभागे उदाहृतम् । तन्नाम सर्वासां कुलजास्त्रीणां वेदाध्ययनं विहितमिति अत्र उक्तम् । पूर्वं कदाचित् मैत्रेयी पतिम् अपृच्छत् यत् “त्वया दत्ताभिः सर्वसम्पद्धिः अहम् अमृतत्वं प्राप्नुवानि किम्? इति पृष्टे सति तेन मुनिना उक्तम् “नैव भद्रे ! एषा सम्पद् ऐहिकसुखलोभाय केवलम् । अमृतत्वं प्राप्तुं वेदशास्त्रज्ञानं कारणम्” इति अवदत् । तदा मैत्रेयी “य देव वेद तदेव ब्रूहि मे” इति पृष्टवती । तदा मुनिः अतीव सन्तुष्टः, वेदज्ञानं दातुं सम्मतः अभवत् इति कथा श्रूयते । तासां काथानामाधारेण स्त्रीणां वेदाध्ययनम् उपनयनसंस्कारः, इत्यायः आसन्निति ज्ञायते ।

बहूः स्मृतयः सन्ति, ताः वेदानां सारं प्रतिपादयन्ति । तासु स्मृतिषु यमस्मृतिः काचित् विद्यते तत्र कश्चन श्लोकः एवम् अस्ति –

पुरा कल्पे तु नारीणां मौञ्जीबन्धनमिष्यते ।

अध्यापनञ्च वेदानां सावित्री वाचनं यथा ॥ यमस्मृतिः (निर्णयसिन्धुः)

यथा मन्त्ररष्टारः ऋषयः आसन् तथैव ऋषिकाः अपि आसन् पूर्वकाले । काश्चन ब्रह्मवादिन्यः अपि आसन्, ताः घोषा, गोधा, विश्ववारा, अपाला, इन्द्राणी, रोमाशा, सरमा इत्याद्यः । तासां समाजं प्रति योगदानं किम् ? ताः वेदज्ञानं प्राप्य धर्मरक्षणाय किं कृतवत्यः इत्यादिकं विषयं प्रस्तौतुम् इच्छामि ।

Paper No. 6.14: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳು - ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಬಳಕೆ

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ABSTRACT

ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವು - ಸಮಸ್ತಪ್ರಾಣಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಜಗತ್ತನ್ನು ಕೂಡ ಸೇರಿಸಿ ಲೋಕವೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಲೋಕೋ ಭೂವನಂ ಜನಃ ಎಂದು ಅಮರಕೋಶ. ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅದು ಎರಡುಬಗೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

1. ಸುಸಂಸ್ಕೃತರಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಸುಶಿಕ್ಷಿತರಾದವರಿಂದ ರಚಿತವಾದದ್ದು.
2. ಅಸಂಸ್ಕೃತರಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಅಶಿಕ್ಷಿತರಾದವರಿಂದ ರಚಿತವಾದದ್ದು.

ಮೊದಲನೆಯದನ್ನು ಶಿಷ್ಟಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆಂದು, ಎರಡನೆಯದನ್ನು ಯಾರಿಂದಲೋ ಕೇಳಿ ಬಹುಕಾಲದಿಂದ ಪಾಲಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಸಮಾಜಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆಂದು ಕರೆಯಬಹುದು. ಈ ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನೇ ಆಂಗ್ಲದಲ್ಲಿ folk-literature ಎಂದು ವ್ಯವಹರಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಲೋಕದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಜನರ ಭಾವನಾತ್ಮಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಜನಾತ್ಮಕತೆಯೇ ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಮೂಲಕಾರಣವೆಂದು ತಿಳಿಯಬಹುದು. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಲೋಕಗೀತೆ, ಲೋಕಕಥೆ, ಲೋಕನಾಟ್ಯ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ನಮಗೆ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಅಡಗಿದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಭಾಗವೇ ಲೋಕೋಕ್ತಿಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವು. ಅಂದರೇ ಲೋಕದಲ್ಲಾಡುವ ಮಾತುಗಳೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಲೋಕೋಕ್ತಿಗಳಲ್ಲ ಕಿಂತು ಲೋಕಕಲ್ಯಾಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬಳಸುವ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಉಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಮಾತ್ರ ಲೋಕೋಕ್ತಿಗಳೆನಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳು - ನ್ಯಾಯಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಯುಕ್ತಿ, ಪದ್ಧತಿ, ನಿಯಮ, ಯೋಜನೆ, ಯೋಗ್ಯತೆ, ಔಚಿತ್ಯ, ತರ್ಕಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಶಾಸನ, ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯದ ಆದೇಶ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಅನೇಕಾರ್ಥಗಳಿವೆ. ಆದರೇ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಯುಕ್ತಿ ಅಥವಾ ನಿಯಮ ಎಂದರ್ಥ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಲೌಕಿಕಜನರ ವ್ಯವಹಾರ, ಅನುಭವ, ಕಥೆ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನನುಸರಿಸಿ ಮಹತ್ತರವಾದ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯಂತಸರಳವಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿಕೊಡುವ ಯುಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನೇ ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು - ಶಾಸನಾತ್ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಮುಚ್ಯತೇ ಅಥವಾ ಶಾಸ್ತಿ ಅನೇನ ಇತಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಂ ಎನ್ನುವ ವ್ಯುತ್ಪತ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಪದಕ್ಕೆ ನಿಯಮನೆಮಾಡುವದು ಎಂದು ಅರ್ಥ. ಅದು ಆಸ್ತಿಕ - ನಾಸ್ತಿಕವೆಂದು, ಪುನಃ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ, ನ್ಯಾಯ, ವ್ಯಾಕರಣ, ವೇದಾಂತಾದಿರೂಪೇಣ ವಿಂಗಡಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ.

ಕೂಟಶಬ್ದಗಳು - ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವು, ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳು, ಲೋಕಗೀತೆ, ಲೋಕಕಥೆ, ಲೋಕನಾಟ್ಯ, ಅರ್ಥವೈಶಸನ್ಯಾಯವು, ಪಂಗ್ವಂಧನ್ಯಾಯವು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ.

Paper No. 6.15: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

संस्कृतसंहिताशास्त्रेषु भूगर्भस्थजलविज्ञानम् ।

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ABSTRACT

जगति जलविषयक-चिन्ता आस्ति तर्हि तस्य निराकरणं प्राचीन संस्कृत ग्रन्थे दृश्यते । वराहमिहिरस्य) इ.स.५०० (बृहत्संहितासूत्रणाम् वैज्ञानिकदृष्ट्या यदि परीक्षणं भवति तदा समाजस्य परमकल्याणार्थं भवतीति स्पष्टीभूतः । भूमिगतजलप्राप्तिसम्बन्धे बृहत्संहिताशास्त्रेषु बहवः विषयाः दृष्टिपथमायान्ति । बृहत्संहितायां भूगर्भस्थजलस्थितिसंबन्धिः दकार्गलाख्यः) : उदक- water ,अर्गल= obstacle (महत्त्वपूर्णविषयः वर्णितमस्ति । अयं विषयः भूगर्भे संचितस्य जलस्य स्थितिः सम्यक् प्रकाशयति । उदक-दक्- उद् - शब्दानां दकार्गलशब्दस्यार्थः जलशृङ्खलेति कथितम् । तत्तु आधुनिकविज्ञानेन जलशिरा) Aquifer) इति कथ्यते । भारते न केवलं मरुभूम्यामपि तु यत्र जलस्य दुर्भिक्ष्य अस्ति तत्र वराहमिहिर महाभागेन उक्तमोपायस्य प्रयोगः करणीय इति मन्ये । आधुनिक काले तु विविधा उपायाः, संशोधनं जातं किंतु तत् पर्याप्तं नास्ति । प्राचीनसाहित्ये एतादृशं विज्ञानं भवति ;तस्य आधुनिक-विज्ञानेन सह कलानुरूपेण मेलनं कर्तव्यमिति मन्यते । अवर्षणप्रान्ते शुद्धजलप्राप्तार्थं संहितासु कथितमोपायानां प्रयोगः कृत्वा प्राचीन-आधुनिक विज्ञानस्य मेलनं करणीयम् । इति अनुसंधानस्य उद्देशः अस्ति । वराहमिहिरमहाभागेन भूगर्भस्थजलविषये उत्तमविवेचनं दत्तम् । जलशिरा नाम भूगर्भस्थ वहामानाः जलप्रवाहः विद्यते । वराहमिहिरमहाभागेन आकाशस्थजलस्य विषये कथितम्-

एकेन वर्णेन रसेन चाम्भश्च्युतं नभस्तो वसुधाविशेषात् ।

नानारसत्वं बहुवर्णतां च गतं परोक्षं क्षतितुल्यमेव ॥

पृथ्वीलक्षणानामनुसारेण जलोपलब्धिः कुत्र कथं नास्ति इति यदि अस्माभिः ज्ञायते तदा जनाः यदावश्यकं मधुरजलं प्रप्नुयुः। परिणामतः जलाभावस्थानेषु अनेने साक्षात् प्रयोगेण जानाः लाभान्विता भवेयुः। तेषु अस्मिन् संस्कृत जलविज्ञानसाहित्यस्य अनुसंधानं मानवकल्याणार्थं भवेत् इति मन्यते ।

Paper No. 6.16: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

सदाशिवधनुर्वेदे आयुधविज्ञानम् – एकम् परिशीलनम्

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ABSTRACT

सामान्यतया संस्कृतग्रन्थेषु जैववैविध्येन सह मनुजसम्बन्धः तथा मनुजानां तादृशविषयेषु ज्ञानं च सुष्ठु प्रतिपादितम् वर्तते। तादृशग्रन्थेषु मुख्यः सदाशिवधनुर्वेदः। सैनिकपरिशीलने मार्गदर्शक इव स्थितस्यास्य ग्रन्थस्य मुख्यप्रतिपाद्यविषयाः एवं विभक्ताः सन्ति,

- आयुधनिर्माणम्
- धातुनिर्मितानाम् आयुधानां तीक्ष्णीकरणम्
- धातुनिर्मितानाम् आयुधानां सज्जीकरणम्
- शत्रूणाम् आयुधानां विनाशनम्
- दुष्टशक्तिः तथा क्रूरमृगेभ्यश्च संरक्षणम्
- युद्धपर्वताः इत्यादयः।

सदाशिवधनुर्वेदे आयुधविज्ञानम् – एकम् परिशीलनम् इत्यस्मिन् शोधप्रबन्धे सदाशिवधनुर्वेदे उक्तेषु विषयेषु आयुधविषये प्रतिपादितानाम् अंशानां प्रपञ्चनं क्रियते। शोधप्रबन्धस्यास्य करणे मुख्यतया व्याख्यात्मकपद्धतिरेव मया स्वीक्रियते। इदानीन्तनकाले देशरक्षणार्थं, आत्मरक्षायै, प्रजापालनार्थम् इत्येवं बहुषु क्षेत्रेषु आयुधानाम् उपयोगः दृश्यते।

कूटशब्दाः - आयुधः, आयुधनिर्माणम्, आयुधसज्जीकरणम्, धनुर्वेदः, देशरक्षणम्, परिशीलनम् ।

Paper No. 6.17: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

Agricultural knowledge of ancient Indians

ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಭಾರತೀಯರ ಕೃಷಿಜ್ಞಾನ

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ABSTRACT

ಇಂದು ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ-ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನಗಳು ಎಷ್ಟೇ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ, ಏನೇ ಆವಿಷ್ಕಾರಗಳು ನಡೆದಿದ್ದರೂ, ದೇಹಪೋಷಣೆಗೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಆಹಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಪರ್ಯಾಯವಾಗಿ ಬೇರೆ ಮಾರ್ಗಗಳನ್ನು ಶಾಶ್ವತವಾಗಿ ಕಂಡುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಕೃಷಿಯು ಹಿಂದಿನಿಂದ ಇಂದಿನವರೆಗೂ, ಇನ್ನುಮುಂದೆಯೂ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಮನಗಂಡಂತಹ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಋಷಿಗಳು ಬಹು ಹಿಂದೆಯೇ ಹಲವು ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಿ ಲೋಕೋಪಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ವೇದಗಳ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಹಲವು ಶಾಖೆಗಳಾದ ಭೌತಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಖಗೋಳಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಲೋಹಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಸಸ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವಿಷಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯು ನಡೆದಿತ್ತು. ಅಂತೆಯೇ ಕೃಷಿ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಆವಿಷ್ಕಾರಗಳಾಗಿದ್ದವು. ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯಗಳಾದ ವೇದಾದಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಕೃಷಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಹಲವು ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳಿವೆ.

ಪರಾಶರ ಮಹರ್ಷಿಗಳು ಕೃಷಿಯಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾದ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ನಡೆಸಿ ಹಲವು ಮಹತ್ತರವಾದ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸಂಗ್ರಹಿಸಿಟ್ಟಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅದುವೇ 'ಕೃಷಿಪರಾಶರ' ಎಂಬ ಕೃಷಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಮಹತ್ತರವಾದ ಕೃತಿ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹರ್ಷಿ ಪರಾಶರರು -

अन्नन्तु धान्यसंभूता धान्यन्तु कृषिर्विना नजा ।

तस्मात् सर्वं परित्यज्य कृषिं यत्नेन कारयेत् ॥^೧ - ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಹೀಗೆ ಕೃಷಿ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಭಾರತೀಯರಿಗಿದ್ದ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಅವರು ಕೃಷಿಯ ಕುರಿತು ನಡೆಸಿದ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಬೆಳಕು ಚೆಲ್ಲುವಂತಹ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಡಲಾಗುವುದು.

^೧ "ಅನ್ನಂತು ಧಾನ್ಯಸಂಭೂತಂ ಧಾನ್ಯಂತು ಕೃಷಿವಿನಾ ನಜಾ ।

ತಸ್ಮಾತ್ ಸರ್ವಂ ಪರಿತ್ಯಜ್ಯ ಕೃಷಿಂ ಯತ್ನೇನ ಕಾರಯೇತ್ ॥"- ಕೃಷಿಪರಾಶರ

Paper No. 6.18: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

“ಮಾರ್ಕಂಡೇಯಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗಸಿದ್ಧಿವಿಚಾರ”

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ABSTRACT

ಸನಾತನ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮಹತ್ವಪೂರ್ಣವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನವಿದೆ. “ಯುಜಿರ್ ಯೋಗೇ” ಧಾತುವಿನಿಂದ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನವಾದ ಯೋಗ ಶಬ್ದವು ಸಂಯೋಗ ಅಥವಾ ಸೇರುವಿಕೆ ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಉಪಾಯ, ಸಂಗತಿ, ಯುಕ್ತಿ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನೂ ನೀಡುವ ಈ ಪದವನ್ನು ಪತಂಜಲಿ ಮಹರ್ಷಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಯೋಗಸೂತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ “ಯೋಗಃ ಚಿತ್ತವೃತ್ತಿನಿರೋಧಃ” ಎಂದು ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಚಿತ್ತದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನವಾಗುವ ಎಲ್ಲ ಚಿತ್ತವಿಕಾರಗಳನ್ನೂ ಗೆಲ್ಲುವುದೇ ಯೋಗ ಎಂದು ಈ ಸೂತ್ರಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಕೇವಲ ಪತಂಜಲಿ ಮಹರ್ಷಿಗಳಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಅನೇಕ ಋಷಿಗಳು ಯೋಗಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಅನುಭವವನ್ನು ಪುಸ್ತಕರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಡಿದಿಟ್ಟಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಮಹಾಪುರಾಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾದ ಮಾರ್ಕಂಡೇಯ ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ವಿಷಯವನ್ನು ಬಹಳ ಸುಂದರವಾಗಿ ನಿರೂಪಿತವಾಗಿದೆ. ತ್ರಿಮೂರ್ತಿಗಳ ಅವತಾರವೆಂದು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧರಾದ ದತ್ತಾತ್ರೇಯ ಮುನಿಗಳ ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ವಿವರಣೆ ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಲೋಕೋತ್ತರ ಕೀರ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಅಲರ್ಕರಾಜನು ದತ್ತಾತ್ರೇಯ ಮುನಿಗಳಿಂದ ಅನೇಕ ದಿವ್ಯ ವಿದ್ಯೆಗಳ ಉಪದೇಶವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಯೋಗವಿದ್ಯೆಯೂ ಒಂದು. ಈ ಯೋಗವಿದ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಬಹಳ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾಗಿ ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳ ಸಹಿತವಾಗಿ ದತ್ತಾತ್ರೇಯ ಮುನಿಗಳು ಅಲರ್ಕನಿಗೆ ಉಪದೇಶಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಸುಮಾರು ಒಂಭತ್ತು ಸಾವಿರ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡ ಮಾರ್ಕಂಡೇಯ ಪುರಾಣವು ಸುಮಾರು 134 ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ.

Paper No. 6.19: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

“ನಾರದೀಯಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೇದಾಂಗಗಳ ನಿರೂಪಣೆ”

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ABSTRACT

ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪರಂಪರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರಾಣಗಳಿಗೆ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನವಿದೆ. ಮಾನವನ ಆತ್ಮೋನ್ನತಿಗೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಎಲ್ಲ ಅಂಶಗಳೂ ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಎಲ್ಲ ಜನರಿಗೂ ಸುಲಭಸ್ವರ್ಭಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಪುರಾಣದ ಕಥೆಗಳು, ಸುಭಾಷಿತಗಳು, ಸೂಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಜನರ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಅಚ್ಚೊತ್ತಿ ದೃಢವಾಗಿ ನೆಲೆಸಿದೆಯಾದರೂ ಕೆಲವು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಜನರ ಸಮೀಪಕ್ಕೆ ಇನ್ನೂ ತಲುಪಲಿಲ್ಲವೆಂಬುದೂ ಸಹ ಸತ್ಯವಾದ ವಿಚಾರ. ಅಂತಹ ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯ ಪೂರ್ಣವಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಪುರಾಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವು ಇವೆ. ಅಂತಹವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ವೇದಾಂಗಗಳ ವಿವರಣೆ.

ಭಾರತದ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ನಿಂತಿರುವುದೇ ವೇದಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ. ವೇದಗಳಿಲ್ಲದೇ ಯಾವುದೂ ಇಲ್ಲ. ಈ ವೇದಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಕ್ಕೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನರು ಒಂದು ಸುಂದರವಾದ ಕ್ರಮವನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಸಹ ಅದೇ ಕ್ರಮದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ವೇದಾಧ್ಯಯನಗಳು ನಡೆದುಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿವೆ. ಆ ಕ್ರಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದ ಭಾಗ ವೇದಾಂಗಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ. ಹೆಸರೇ ಸೂಚಿಸುವಂತೆ ವೇದಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭ್ಯಾಸಮಾಡಲು ಸಹಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿರುವ ಅಂಗಗಳನ್ನು ವೇದಾಂಗಗಳು ಎಂದು ಕರೆದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆರು ವೇದಾಂಗಗಳು; ಶಿಕ್ಷಾ, ವ್ಯಾಕರಣ, ಛಂದಸ್ಸು, ನಿರುಕ್ತ, ಜ್ಯೋತಿಷ, ಕಲ್ಪ ಎಂಬುದು ಅವುಗಳ ಹೆಸರುಗಳು.

ಹದಿನೆಂಟು ಪುರಾಣಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾರದೀಯ ಪುರಾಣವೂ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದುದು. 24 ಸಾವಿರ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳಿರುವ ಈ ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಪೂರ್ವಾರ್ಧ ಹಾಗೂ ಉತ್ತರಾರ್ಧವೆಂಬ ಎರಡು ಭಾಗಗಳಿವೆ. ಪೂರ್ವಾರ್ಧದಲ್ಲಿ 125 ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಗಳೂ ಹಾಗೂ ಉತ್ತರಾರ್ಧದಲ್ಲಿ 82 ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಗಳಿವೆ. ಅನೇಕ ರಾಜರುಗಳ ವರ್ಣನೆ, ಅನೇಕ ದೇವತಾಪೂಜಾವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಅನೇಕ ವ್ರತ-ತಂತ್ರಗಳು ಈ ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿವೆ.

Paper No. 6.20: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

Satyavati: The Unconquered Matriarch in Kavita Kane's The Fisher Queen's Dynasty

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ABSTRACT

Since the beginning of time, faith and mankind have had a close bond. As a result, mythology and religion are fundamentally associated with and connected to the history of civilizations. The epic Mahabharata had been written thousands of years ago. But even today, the astounding tales are still engulfing and overwhelming us throughout every form of art. It is a never-ending source of study rather than just a morality tale to be transmitted from generation to generation. Over the years the timeless epic has been retold, revisited, reviewed, and revised by many scholars across the globe. These writers selected contemporary issues and applied those aspects while retelling the epic. This paper deals with one such Mahabharata-based novel, which is an autobiography of Satyavati. This article explores the presentation of the epic character Satyavati in Kavita Kane's *The Fisher Queen's Dynasty* (2017). It highlights the dominant theme of the quest for identity.

The paper intends to explore the significant role played by Satyavati in shaping the plot and sequence of events in the novel. It also focuses on the journey of the protagonist from being a mere fisher girl to the matriarch of the Kuru dynasty. Thus it tries to bring forth how female observation of the epic varies from the male perception. Satyavati was the Queen-mother of the Hastinapur dynasty and actively participated in protecting the kingdom throughout her life. But she was not given prominence in the epic. However, the hardships she faced on her journey to womanhood and matriarch are justified in *Fisher Queen's Dynasty*. Thus this paper analysis her journey from a humble boat-rower and how she overcame adversities to become a powerful King-maker.

Paper No. 6.21: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

अमृतस्य पुत्राः

डा. सावित्री दिनवहि

ABSTRACT

महाभारतान्तर्गता सावित्रीसत्यवतोः कथा

सावित्री निजशुद्धभावेन शक्तिसामर्थ्याभ्यां यमपाशात् सत्यवन्तं विमोच्य प्रत्यानीतवती। तत्र मृत्युदेवेन सह सावित्र्याः संवादः अपि आसीत्। तेन मुग्धः यमः तस्यै वरान् दत्तवानिति व्यासविरचितमहाभारतकथा। तावान् एव कथायाः आशयः वा? तस्याः कथायाः अपेक्षितं सर्वं वयम् अवगतवन्तः वा? इति प्रश्नं कुर्मः चेत् नैव इत्येव उत्तरं भवति।

अस्यां पृथिव्यां वसद्भिः अस्माभिः मानवैः मरणं जित्वा अमृतत्वं साधनीयमेव। तदा एव " अमृतस्य पुत्राः " इति वेदशब्दस्य सार्थकता इति सुदृढम् उल्लिखितवान् श्रीमदरविन्दः स्वस्य " सावित्री " इति २४००० पादात्मके उद्ग्रन्थे।

अत्र सावित्रीसत्यवतोः कथायाः पात्राणां विषये अपि अवलोकनं कथं भवेदिति स्पष्टमुक्तवान् श्रीमदरविन्दः। इदं न केवलं रूपकम्। अत्र पात्राणि न कल्पितानि। तानि जीवन्ति चैतन्यशक्तियुक्तानि। मानवजन्म न पराकाष्ठम्, न वा अन्तिमम्। एतस्य पश्चात् दिव्यमानवः इत्यपि काचित् जातिः अस्ति भविष्यतीति ज्ञातव्यम्।

महोन्नतानाम् आध्यात्मिकशिखराणाम् अधिरोहणाय सावित्री ग्रन्थः पर्याप्तः। योगाभ्यासाय अपेक्षिताः सर्वे विषयाः अत्र वर्तन्ते इति तथ्यम्। भगवतः साक्षात्काराय अपेक्षितं सर्वम् अस्मिन् लभ्यते। इतरयोगेषु विद्यमाननिगूढविषयाः सर्वे अस्मिन् विवृताः। सत्यान्वेषणाय चैतन्यमभिज्ञातुं, अस्मिन् विश्वे विद्यमानानां समस्यानां परिष्करणाय अपेक्षितसाधनांशान् सर्वान् अस्मिन् श्रीमदरविन्दः उल्लेखितवान्।

सैव श्रीमाता वदति स्म, सत्यम् इति शब्दस्य अर्थः केवलं वाङ्मन्त्रं न। काचित् विशिष्टा अनुभूतिं ज्ञापयति सत्यम्। तदनुभवेनैव ज्ञातव्यम् इति। अस्मिन् ग्रन्थे द्वादशपर्वाणि, तेषु उपपर्वाणि अपि सन्ति मानवानां सामान्यसंशयाः अपि कुतः भवन्ति? कथं परिहर्तव्याः? कथं चिन्तनीयमित्यादि अनेकांशाः अपि नारदमुनेः सावित्र्याः मातुः संवादे अत्यन्तं रोचकम् अभिवर्णितम्

Paper No. 6.22: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

ವಿದುಷೀ. ಲತಾ ಪಾಟೀಲ್
ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕಿ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಕಲಾ ಮಹಾವಿದ್ಯಾಲಯ
ಧಾರವಾಡ, ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ.

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ವೇದ ಕಾಲದಿಂದ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕಾಲದವರೆಗಿನ ಕೃಷಿ - ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

"ಭಾರತಸ್ಯ ದ್ವೇ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಮ್ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಸ್ತಥಾ" ಎಂಬ ಉಕ್ತಿಯಂತೆ ಭಾರತವು ಜಾಗತಿಕವಾಗಿ ಚಿರಪರಿಚಿತವಾಗಲು ಮತ್ತು ಮಹತ್ವಪೂರ್ಣವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ನಮ್ಮ ವೇದಕಾಲದಿಂದ ಆರಂಭವಾದ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಮೂಲ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಕಾಪಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿರುವುದೇ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತದ ಮೂಲಭಾಷೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಂಪರೆ ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಬಂದಿರುವುದೇ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೃಷಿ ಪರಂಪರೆಯು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ ಪಡೆದ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ.

"ವೇದೋನಾಮ ಜ್ಞಾನಂ" ಚರಕ ಸಂಹಿತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿದ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ಕೃಷಿ ವಿಚಾರಗಳು, ಪರಾಶರ ಮಹರ್ಷಿಗಳ ಕೃಷಿ ಪರಾಶರ ಗ್ರಂಥದ ಕೆಲವು ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು, ಋಗ್ವೇದದಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಲಾದ ಕೃಷಿ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು, ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಪಿತಾಮಹ ಮಹಾನ್ ರಾಜನೀತಿಜ್ಞನಾದ (ಚಾಣಕ್ಯ) ಕೌಟಿಲ್ಯನ ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾದ ದೂರದೃಷ್ಟಿವುಳ್ಳ ಕೃಷಿ ಕುರಿತ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು, ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಇತ್ತೀಚೆಗೆ ಸಿರಿಧಾನ್ಯಗಳ ಪಾರಂಪರಿಕ ಕೃಷಿ ಕುರಿತು ಅವುಗಳ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಜಾಗತಿಕ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾಗೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಮೂಡಿಸಿದ ಡಾ|| ಖಾದರ್ ಇವರು ಬರೆದ "ಸಿರಿಧಾನ್ಯಗಳೇ ಆಹಾರ" ಎಂಬ ಕೈಪಿಡಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿದ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಸಂಕ್ಷಿಪ್ತ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ.

"ಅನ್ನಂ ತು ಧಾನ್ಯ ಸಂಭೂತಂ....."

.....ಕೃಷೀಂ ಯತ್ನೇನ ಕಾರಯೇತ್ ||

ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗುವುದು.....

ರುದ್ರಾಧ್ಯಾಯ ಚಮಕದಲ್ಲಿ :

"ವ್ರೀಹಯಶ್ಚಮೇ, ಯವಾಶ್ಚಮೇ, ಮಾಶಾಶ್ಚಮೇ, ತಿಲಾಶ್ಚಮೇ, ನೀವಾರಾಶ್ಚಮೇ" ಈ ರೀತಿ ಪ್ರಾರ್ಥಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ ಭತ್ತ, ಜವೆ, ಉದ್ದು, ಎಳ್ಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಹೀಗೆ ಬಹುತೇಕ ಎಲ್ಲ ಧಾನ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಜೊತೆಗೆ 'ನೀವಾರ'ವೆಂದರೆ ಅರಣ್ಯಧಾನ್ಯಗಳೆಂದರ್ಥ. ಇವೆಲ್ಲವೂ ತಮಗೆ ಲಭಿಸುವಂತಾಗಲಿ ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಧಾನ್ಯಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖವಿದೆ.

"ಕೃಷಿ ಪರಾಶರ" ಎಂಬ ಗ್ರಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ

"ಏಕಯಾಚ ಪುನಃ ಕೃಷ್ಯಾ"

.....ಭೂಯಾದೇಕಶ್ಚ ಭೂಪತಿಃ || ಎಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ಅಂದರೆ ಕೃಷಿಯನ್ನು ಯಾವಾತನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುತ್ತಾನೋ ಅವನು ತನ್ನ ಜೀವನ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆಗೆ ಎಂದಿಗೂ ಯಾರನ್ನೂ ಯಾಚಿಸುವ, ಆಶ್ರಯಿಸುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭವೇ ಬರುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಕೃಷಿಕನೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಭೂಪತಿ.

೧) ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೃಷಿಯ ಸ್ಥಾನ

೨) ಕೃಷಿ ಅಧಿಕಾರಿಯ ಪಾತ್ರ ಅಂದು-ಇಂದು.

೩) ಭೂಮಿ, ಬೆಳೆ ಬೆಳೆಯುವ ಕ್ರಮ

೪) ಆಧುನಿಕ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಬಳಕೆ

೫) ಕೃಷಿ ವಿಚಾರದಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ಕಾರದ ಪಾತ್ರ

"ಹೊಸ ಚಿಗುರಿಗೆ ಬೇಕು ಹಳೆಯ ಬೇರು" ಎಂಬಂತೆ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದ ಕೃಷಿ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಆಧುನಿಕ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನ ಬಳಸಿ ಹೊಸ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳ ಲಾಭದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಕೃಷಿ ಮಾಡುವುದು. ಕವಿತಾ ಮಿಶ್ರಾರಂಥ ಪ್ರತಿಭಾನ್ವಿತ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕೃಷಿ ಸಾಧಕಿಯರ ಕುರಿತು, ಮುಂತಾದ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಮುಂದೆ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

Paper No. 6.23: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

Relevance of Social Practices Derived from Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas

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ABSTRACT

Peace and prosperity – kshema- is something that every individual is ultimately searching for. In ordinary way of life, it becomes unattainable even after acquiring material surplus. There are plenty of social practices available in the Vedas, epics and puranas which are proven methods to bring welfare to the whole society. लोकाः समस्ताः सुखिनो भवन्तु used to be the wish and prayer of Ancient Bharatam, from time immemorial. In this paper, fifteen social practices are identified and presented with their relevance for sustainable development of modern society.

What is the purpose of life? To many, fulfil their desires would be the objective of life. In order to fulfil the desires, wealth needs to be acquired and so acquiring wealth also become an important objective of life. Our ancient sages, the visionaries must have foreseen the possibility of chaos in the society if those two aspects become the objectives of life. Sages put forward dharma as the first and foremost objective of a civilized society and how significant it is to offer awareness of dharma to each individual during the formative years. Thus the ideation and practice of 'purusharthas gives lot of scope to explore further. In this research, many such practices are identified and their social significance is explored. After a vast literature survey and a comparative analysis, practical applications are suggested.

Key words: social practices, purushartha, welfare, vyakti dharma, samaja kshema, panchayajna, एकात्मदर्शनम्

Paper No. 6.24: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणे मानवकल्याणाय वर्णितं योगत्रयी

डॉ मञ्जुश्री श्रीपाद नेहल

(तासिका तत्त्वेन) संस्कृत प्राध्यापिका

बाबाजी दाते कला आणि वाणिज्य महाविद्यालय, यवतमाळ, महाराष्ट्र

भ्रमणध्वनी क्र.९४०५७०९३६७ / ७०२०७२९१७५

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प्रस्तावना :-

भारतीयज्ञानपरम्परायां पुराणग्रन्थाः गौरवान्विताः मन्यन्ते | यथा वेदाः ईश्वरस्थाने विद्यन्ते तथैव पुराणग्रन्थानीश्वरस्य निःश्वास प्रचक्षते | न्यायादर्शनुमते – “इतिहासं पुराणं पञ्चमं वेदानां वेदम् |”^१ भारतीयप्राचीनपरम्परायाः विचारान् संमुखी कर्तुम् पुराणशास्त्रम् विद्यमानमस्ति | ‘यस्मात् पुरा भवति तत्पुराणम् |’ इति पुराणस्य परिभाषा | स्कन्दपुराणे उक्तमस्ति - “श्रुतिस्मृती तुनेत्रेद्रेपुराणं हृदयं स्मृतम् |”^२ श्रुतीस्मृत्योः एकस्याज्ञानी काणा, द्वयोः अज्ञानी अन्ध तु यं पुराणस्य ज्ञानं नास्ति स तु हृदयहीनः कथ्यते | पुराणस्य आद्याक्षरेण पुराणस्य सङ्ख्या देवीभागवते कथितमस्ति |

मद्वयं भद्रयं चैव ब्रत्रयं वचतुष्टयम् | अनापलिङ्गकूस्कानि पुराणानि प्रचक्षते ||^३

मद्वय – (१) मत्स्यपुराणम्, (२) मार्कण्डेयपुराणम्

भद्रयं – (३) भागवतपुराणम्, (४) भविष्यपुराणम्

ब्रत्रयं – (५) ब्रह्मपुराणम्, (६) ब्रह्माण्डपुराणम्, (७) ब्रह्मवैवर्तपुराणम्

वचतुष्टयं – (८) विष्णुपुराणम्, (९) वराहपुराणम्, (१०) वायूपुराणम्, (११) वामनपुराणम्

अनापलिङ्गकूस्कानि – (१२) अग्निपुराणम्, (१३) नारदपुराणम्, (१४) पद्मपुराणम्, (१५) लिङ्गपुराणम्,

(१६) गरुडपुराणम्, (१७) कूर्मपुराणम्, (१८) स्कन्दपुराणम्

मर्यादा एवं च व्याप्ति :-

मुख्यपुराणानां सङ्ख्याष्टादश सन्ति एवञ्च वर्णविषयाः अपि बहवः | तथैव योगः अपि बहुविधोऽस्ति | अस्मिन् शोधनिबन्धे श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणे उक्तं भक्तियोगकर्मयोगज्ञानयोगानामभ्यासात्मकं विचारः विद्यते |

उद्दिष्ट्यम् :-

- कर्मयोगभक्तियोगज्ञानयोगानां मानविकाल्याणाय भागवतपुराणाधारे अभ्यासः
- जीवने भक्तिकर्मज्ञानेभ्यः महत्वपूर्णः एवं च श्रेयस्करयोगस्य शोधः

संशोधनपद्धति :-

प्रस्तुतशोधनिबन्धाय विश्लेषणपद्धतेः उपयोगः क्रियते |

भागवतपुराणस्य महत्त्वम् :-

श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणम् संस्कृतसाहित्यस्यानमोलनिधीः अस्ति | एतद् निर्मलकल्पतरोः अमृतमयफलं वर्तते | वल्भाचार्येण भागवतं तु महर्षिव्यासस्य सामाधीभाषेत्युक्तम् | भागवतस्य गुढार्थभक्तुं वैष्णवसंप्रदायेन स्वमतानुकुल व्याख्या कृता तासु प्रमुखतया सुदर्शनसूरी, पदरत्नावली, सिद्धान्तप्रदीप सुबोधिनी, श्रीधर, हरीभक्तसायन एतेषामाचार्याणां भाष्यग्रन्थाः प्रसिद्धाः सन्ति | सर्ग, प्रतिसर्ग, वंश, वंशानुचरितम् एवं मन्वन्तरमेते पुराणस्य पञ्च लक्षणानि सन्ति | भागवतपुराणस्य द्वे स्कन्दे अल्पशः शब्दभेदेन पुराणस्य दश लक्षणानि कथितानि |

अत्र सर्गो विसर्गश्च स्थानं पोषणमूतयः | मन्वन्तरेऽणुकथा निरोधो मुक्तिराश्रयः ||^४

एवञ्च

सर्गोऽस्याथ विसर्गश्च वृत्तौ रक्षान्तराणि च | वंशो वंशानुचरितं संस्था हेतुरपाश्रयः ||^५

द्वितीयस्कन्दे एवं द्वादशस्कन्दे वर्णितानि लक्षणानि नामभेदेन भिन्नाः सन्ति किन्तु वर्णविषये समानता पुराणविमार्शे आचार्यबलदेवउपाध्यायेन स्पष्टीकृतास्ति |

श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणे द्वादशस्कन्दाः तेष्वष्टादशसहस्रश्लोकसङ्ख्या सन्ति | अष्टादशपुराणेषु एतद् एकमेवपुराणमस्ति यत्र महात्म्यं स्वतन्त्रतया षड् अध्यायेषु भागवतपुराणस्य प्रथमस्कन्दात् पूर्वम् एवञ्च द्वादशस्कन्दातन्तरं चतुर्षु अध्यायेषु वर्णयति | भागवदपुराणस्य भगवद्कथा कलियुगे भवरोगविनाशकारिणी भविष्यतीति वर्णनं महात्म्ये अस्ति | “कलौ भागवती वार्ता भवरोगविनाशिनी |”^६ तु पद्मपुराणे भागवतपुराणविषये कथ्यते – स्वकीयं यद्भवेत्तेजस्तच्च भागवतेऽदधात् | तिरोधाय प्रविष्टोऽयं श्रीमद्भागवतार्णवम् || अतो भागवतपुराणग्रन्थाभ्यासस्यावश्यकतास्ति |

Paper No. 6.25: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

The Concept of Vedic Agronomy

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ABSTRACT

India is a land of Agriculture. In India Agriculture is not only an occupation but it is the life of people. 70% of the population depends on Agriculture for livelihood. So Healthy Agriculture is essential to a country's well being. This is found in Vedic literature. This present paper discusses a few points of Vedic Agriculture and Agronomy. Vedic Agricultural system was enriched by numerous practices like Cultivation, Ploughing, Sowing, Harvesting, Threshing, Different types of farmers and granaries. Agronomy is regarded as the mother of agriculture. Agronomy means "Art of managing the field". It deals with the principles and practices of field crop production and management of soil for higher productivity. Vedic people were well versed in Science and art of managing the field. They knew how to increase the soil fertility and improve the productivity of the cultivated land. Strongly they followed by traditions and cultures.

Every Agricultural practice was associated with religious customs. Farmers cultivate the land on auspicious days with the advice of saints. So ancient agriculture was very rich. Hence present day generation should be aware about ancient and traditional agricultural systems and practices which may further help the farmers in improvement of cultivation.

Paper No. 6.26: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

Description of Hayayurveda Niroopana in Garuda MahaPurana and it's zoological aspects : An Analytical study

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ABSTRACT

Garuda narrated to Kasyapa Prajapati what Lord Vishnu had told Garuda. The Purana in question came to be known as Garuda Purana because it was narrated by Garuda. It describes the appearance of Brahma and the creation of the universe. In Garuda Purana stories of Krishna incarnations are also important. Scientific matters such as grammar, Ayurveda, astronomy, the evolution of life after death and the concept of fatherhood are all discussed here. The Puranas are the cumulative form of our cultural heritage, philosophies and many branches of knowledge like Ayurveda, Astrology, Vastu etc. Garuda Purana has two kandas Purva and Uttara. It is also called Acharakanda as the main part is the Purvakanda with 240 chapters describing the karmas. There are two parts in Uttarkanda, Pretam Brahman. There are 49 chapters in Pretha Kandham and 29 chapters in Brahmakanda. Thus Garuda Purana has 318 chapters and a total of 18000 verses. 54 chapters from 146 to 200 are devoted to Ayurveda and the narrative is structured in such a way that Dhanyanthari advises Sushruta. Various types of fevers, blood pressure, asthma, tuberculosis, diabetes, leprosy etc. are described and remedies are prescribed. Eye diseases etc. are specifically described and Studies like Vrikshayurveda and Hayayurveda are also part of the wider narrative. In this paper an attempt to made about the horses treatment described in the Garudamahapurana and explains about the zoological aspects by mrigapakshisastra.

Key words: Hayayurveda, Garuda, Garudamahapurana, Mrigapakshisastra, sushrutha

Paper No. 6.28: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

प्राणस्य महिमा वर्णनम्

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प्राणस्य महिमावर्णनम्

ABSTRACT

परमात्मनः सकाशात् ब्रह्मादिदेवाः सृज्यन्ते । ते महदादितत्त्वाभिमानिदेवताः । तेषु इन्द्रादिदेवताः अस्मत्पूर्वसृष्ट्वनियमनं केन क्रियते इति विचारवन्तः अभवन् । विवादः प्रारभत? पुरुषदेहप्रवेशनिर्गमनेन तन्निर्णयः भवेदिति मत्वा तथाऽकुर्वन् । यस्य प्रवेशेन देहः उत्तिष्ठति, यस्य निर्गमनेन देहः पततीति निश्चयं कृत्वा, स एव सर्वश्रेष्ठ इति निर्णयमकुर्वन् । तत्र प्राणप्रवेशेन देहस्थितिः प्राणनिर्गमनेन देहपतनमभवत् । तेन तमेव जीवोत्तमः सर्वे अमनुत । प्राण एव सर्वप्राणिषु स्थित्वा सर्वचेष्टप्रदः । स एव सर्वधारकः, सर्वजीव देहेषु सदा जागृतः इति अजानन्त । प्राणः एव जीवनां कर्मानुसारिण तत्तद्देहेषु नेता । देहात् देहान्तरनेता च । स एव प्रणयेऽपि प्रतिभतपरावरः । परमात्मा तेन सहैव जगतः सृष्ट्याद्यष्टकर्तव्यं करोति । प्राणः देहसम्बद्धसर्वजीवेषु ऽउउउउअउउहइउउउउउउन्नजापकः । प्राणापानव्यानोदानसमानरूपैः शरीरे सर्वव्यापारान् कृत्वा जीवनकर्म कारयति । बलज्ञानधैर्यबुद्धिशक्तिश्रद्धादिगुणाः एतेनैव जीवे उत्पाद्यन्ते । प्राणस्य महिमाऽपारा । गुणानां गणनमशक्यम् । एतादृशमहिमावतः प्राणस्य चेष्टकः विष्णुः सः स्वातन्त्र्याद्यनन्तगुणवान् ।

Paper No. 6.29: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

The role of Pro-social behavior in the Mahābhārata: exploring the value of altruism and serving others

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ABSTRACT

Pro-social behavior is one that is intended to benefit another person. Altruism is a form of pro-social behavior that is selfless and driven only by a desire to aid others, with no anticipation of compensation or acknowledgment. Several factors can influence pro-social behavior and altruism, including personal values, social norms, and the presence of role models who exhibit these behaviors. Mahābhārata the ancient Indian epic points out many examples of pro-social behavior and selflessness and presents it as a desirable trait for characters. the emphasis on pro-social behavior serves as a model for readers and encourages them to strive for similar qualities in their own lives.

This paper explores the value of altruism and service to others as forms of prosocial behavior in the Mahābhārata. Through the examination of various characters and their actions, this paper demonstrates how the Mahābhārata promotes the idea that altruism and service to others are morally praiseworthy and ultimately rewarding for both the person helping and the recipient of the help. This paper also discusses the enduring message of prosocial behavior in the Mahābhārata and its relevance in modern society.

Paper No. 6.30: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಗರ್ಭದೀಕ್ಷೆ ಆಧುನಿಕ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ

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ABSTRACT

ಶ್ರವಣಂ ಕೀರ್ತನಂ ವಿಷ್ಣೋಃ ಸ್ಮರಣಂ ಪಾದಸೇವನಮ್ |

ಅರ್ಚನಂ ವಂದನಂ ದಾಸ್ಯಂ ಸಖ್ಯಮಾತ್ಮನಿವೇದನಮ್ ||

ಎಂಬ ನವವಿಧ ಭಕ್ತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮೂರನೆ ಪ್ರಭೇದವಾದ ಸದಾ ವಿಷ್ಣುವಿನ ಸ್ಮರಣೆ ಎಂಬುದಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರಹ್ಲಾದಃ ಸ್ಮರಣೆ ನ ಚ ಎಂಬಂತೆ ಪ್ರಹ್ಲಾದನೆ ನಿದರ್ಶನವಾಗಿ ಎದ್ದು ಕಾಣುತ್ತಾನೆ . ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣ ಅವನಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಗಾಡವಾದ “ಹರಿಭಕ್ತಿ” . ತಂದೆ ಮಗನ ಸಂವಾದ ಪ್ರಸಂಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಲ್ಲಲ್ಲಿ ಭಕ್ತಿ ಅವನಲ್ಲಿ ಎದ್ದು ಕಾಣುತ್ತದೆ . ಉಳಿದಂತೆ ಪ್ರಹ್ಲಾದನಿಗೆ ನಾರದರ ಉಪದೇಶವು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ರೋಚಕವೇ ಆಗುವ ಮೂಲಕ ಇಂದಿನ “ವಿಜ್ಞಾನಗಳನ್ನು” , “ವೈದ್ಯರನ್ನೂ” ಆಶ್ಚರ್ಯಗೊಳಿಸಿ ಮೂಕವಿಸ್ಮಿತರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಅವರಿಂದಲೂ ತಲೆದೂಗುವ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ಒಪ್ಪುವ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆಗೆ ನೂಕುತ್ತದೆ . ಅದರಂತೆ ಅವರನ್ನು ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗೆ ಎಡೆ ಮಾಡಿಸಿ ಒಮ್ಮತದ ಅಂಗೀಕಾರವು ದೊರೆತಂತೆಯೇ ಆಗಿದೆ . ಅದರಿಂದಲೇ ಇಂದಿನ ಈ

ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಬ್ಬ ಹೆಣ್ಣು ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಹೆಂಡತಿಯಾಗದಿದ್ದರೂ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ತಾಯಿಯಾದರೂ ಆಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಗರ್ಭಿಣಿಯಾದಾಗ ಒಳ್ಳೆಯ ಹವ್ಯಾಸಗಳನ್ನು ಮೈಗೂಡಿಸಿಗೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕೆಂದು ವೈದ್ಯರು ಸಲಹೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಇನ್ನೂ ಹಲವಾರು ಪ್ರಹ್ಲಾದರ ಉದಯವಾಗಿ ತನ್ನೂಲಕ ಇಂದಿನ ಯುವಸಮಾಜದ ಏಳೈಯೂ ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುವುದು ನಿಶ್ಚಿತ .

Paper No. 6.31: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

वेदे ववज्ञानम् – समीक्षात्मकं संपादनम्

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतं नाम ज्ञानस्य ववज्ञानस्य च भाण्डागारम् । संस्कृतेन अस्पृष्टः ववज्ञानस्य भागः प्रायः नावस्त । अस्य फलस्वरूपभूता ववज्ञानपरम्परा अधुनावप अनुवततमाना वततते । एतस्य भारतीयववज्ञानस्य अध्ययनम् अस्मावभः अधुना अत्यावश्यकं ।

Sanskrit is a classical language and has its application almost in every subject that we study today. The rich history of this language is reflected in the Vedas and Upanishads. They are verses and concepts in Vedas and Upanishads that explain the modern scientific inventions and discoveries. The attempt is made here to understand the science that was known to us in Vedic period which the modern world accepts even today.

It is said in तैत्तरीयसंविता –

“वमत्रो दधार पृथिवीमुतद्याम् । वमत्र कृष्टीः” ।

The above line explains that the sun is the center of the solar system and it is he who upholds the other celestial objects.

Johannes Kepler, a German scientist in the 16th century stated in his Laws of Planetary Motion that –

“All planets move about the Sun in elliptical orbits, having the Sun as one of the foci”.

The above law gives the same explanation as per the verse in the तैत्तरीयसंविता. The Vedas and their hymns are just not to please the almighty but also speaks about the science that the modern world is witnessing from a few centuries before.

Hence, it becomes very important to understand the essence of the statements that are mentioned in our Vedas and Puranas. This also gives the insight to the knowledge of our ancestors.

Keywords: तैत्तरीयसंविता, Johannes Kepler, Laws of Planetary Motion, Vedas,

Reference: Science in Sanskrit - Samskrita Bharati

Paper No. 6.32: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

Putrakameshti Yagam

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Putrakameshti Yagnam is a unique yagna that has its own special place in Hinduism. This yagna is performed for the sake of having a child. This Yagna is also famous by the name, **Santhana Gopala Pooja**. Lord Vishnu is the deity of this yagna, nevertheless it forms a part of the Kaamya-karma.

Origin of Putrakameshti Yagnam are found in Suta Samhita which states that Lord Vishnu himself is the giver of this special knowledge of this homam. It was the great sage Sanat Kumar who first came to know about it from Lord Vishnu.

It was King Dasharatha of Ayodhya who first undertook the yagna that Sage Vashishta recommended him.

Who should perform Putrakameshti Yagna

- This Holy Yagna should be undertaken by a couple whose facing unwanted delay in parenthood. Nevertheless, an experienced priest must supervise the whole process.
- Putrakameshti is a special yagna that is fruitful only when performed according to proper guidelines.

How it works

- The positivity that arises from the changings results in the activation of the fourth chakra that is Anahatha.
- Anahatha is the chakra of love where Vishnu resides. Its activation ensures a strong bond between couples.
- This activation also releases the couple's stress and restores their peace of mind which stimulates the process of childbirth.
- Moreover, it also instils good qualities and success in the child to be born.

Paper No. 6.33: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

भक्तिवैविध्यम्

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ABSTRACT

अयि भोः...सुहृदः...! स्मृतिः"मनुष्यजन्मसाफल्यं केवलं धर्मसाधनात्" इति कथनादस्मज्जीवनस्य साफल्यं वक्ति। "मुक्तिसाधनसामग्र्यां भक्तिरेवगरीयसी" इति कथनाद्धर्मान्मुक्तिः भक्तिं विना नैव सिध्यति। अतः प्रथमं भक्तिस्वरूपम् अवगच्छावा। आचार्यमध्वः वक्ति "महात्म्यज्ञानपूर्वस्तु सुहृदः सर्वतोऽधिकः। स्नेहो भक्तिरिति प्रोक्तः तथा मुक्तिर्नचान्यथा" ॥ इति एषा भक्तिः नवधा सातु 'श्रवणं कीर्तनं विष्णोःस्मरणं पादसेवनम्। अर्चनं वन्दनं दास्यं सख्यमात्मनिवेदनम्।' इति एतस्याः ज्ञानेनानुष्ठानेन "भक्त्या मुक्तिर्नचान्यथा" इति कथनान्मुक्तिर्लभ्यते।

"अभिमन्युसुतो मुक्तिं गतश्श्रवणतो हरेः शुकस्तु कीर्तनादेव प्रह्लादस्मरणेन च।

पादसेवनतो लक्ष्मीःपृथुःपूजनतो हरेःवन्दनेन गजेन्द्रोऽपिदास्येनाञ्जनिकासुतः॥

सख्येनैवार्जुनो वीरो बलिरात्मनिवेदनात्॥" इत्युक्तीत्या एते सर्वेऽपि नवधा भक्त्या मुक्तिङ्गताः।

एवमेवास्मज्जीवनेऽपि वयं 'श्रवणादिविना नैव क्षणं तिष्ठेदपि क्वचित्' इत्युक्तीत्या नवधा भक्त्या मुक्तिसाधनमार्गस्यावलम्बनेन 'मार्गस्थो नावसीदति।' एवमेव 'तत्त्वं ज्ञेयं येन भूयो न जन्मा' इति कथनानुसारेण मुक्तिं लभेमहि॥

Paper No. 6.34: Great Indian Epics, Vedas, and Puranas:

ವೇದಗಳ ಮಹತ್ವ

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ABSTRACT

ವೇದಗಳು ನಮ್ಮ ಸನಾತನ ಪರಂಪರೆಯ ಮೂಲ ಆಧಾರಸ್ಥಂಭವಾಗಿದೆ. ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜ್ಞಾನದ ರಾಶಿಗಳು ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಅಡಗಿವೆ. ಅದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸುವ ತಾಳ್ಮೆ ಇರಬೇಕು. ಸಮಗ್ರ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳು ಅದರಿಂದ ಕಂಡುಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ವೇದಕ್ಕೆ ಎರಡು ರೀತಿಯಾದ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನು ಹೇಳಬಹುದು. ಮುಖ್ಯಾರ್ಥ ಅಮುಖ್ಯಾರ್ಥಗಳಾಗಿ. ಮೆಲ್ಲೊಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾಣುವ ಅರ್ಥ ಅಮುಖ್ಯಾರ್ಥ. ಅದನ್ನು ಆಳವಾಗಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ ಗೊತ್ತಾಗುವುದು ಅಮುಖ್ಯಾರ್ಥ.

ವೇದಗಳು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ನಾಲ್ಕು, ಋಕ್, ಯಜು, ಸಾಮ, ಅಥರ್ವ. ವೇದಗಳಿಗೆ ಪುನಃ ನಾಲ್ಕು ಉಪವಿಭಾಗಗಳಿವೆ. ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ, ಆರಣ್ಯಕ, ಉಪನಿಷತ್, ಸಂಹಿತಾ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ. ವೇದದಲ್ಲಿ ಲೌಕಿಕ ಅಲೌಕಿಕ ಎರಡರ ಸಮ್ಮಿಶ್ರಣವು ಇದೆ. ವೇದವು ಒಂದು ಧರ್ಮಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟದ್ದಲ್ಲಾ. ಸಮಗ್ರ ಮನುಕುಲದ ಏಳಿಗೆಗೆ ಇರುವಂತಹದ್ದು. ಮ್ಯಾಕ್ಸ್ ಮುಲ್ಲರ್ ಎಂಬುವನು ಆ ವೇದದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ತನ್ನ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವನ್ನು ಮಂಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಒಪ್ಪುತ್ತಿರುವಂತಹ ಅನೇಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಬೆಳಕನ್ನು ಚೆಲ್ಲಲಾಗಿದೆ. ವೇದಗಳಿಗೆ ಎಷ್ಟು ಮಹತ್ವವಿದೆಯೋ ಅಷ್ಟೆ ಅದರ ಉಪವಿಭಾಗಗಳಿಗೂ ಇದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕೆ ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ನೋಡಬೇಕು.

Paper No. 7.01: Indian medical and medicinal practices.

The Concept and the Relevance of ‘Mana – Shareera Sambandha’ in Ayurveda

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ABSTRACT

As per Ayurveda, a living being is constituted of Satwa, Athma & Shareera all of which are in a mutual relationship. Shareera and Manas are said to be inter-related to each other and Shareerika Vyadhis may lead to Manasika Vyadhis and vice versa. The modern concept of Psycho-somatic disorders is quite evident in our ancient Ayurveda literature which is very much relevant even today. Understanding this mysterious bondage between the ‘Psyche’ & the ‘Soma’ as per the classics is very much important to understand the pathology and to have a right approach towards treatment.

Body is made up of Shareerika Doshas namely Vata, Pitta and Kapha. Rajas and Tamas are considered to be the Manasika Doshas and Satwa is considered to be the Manasika Guna. These Doshas are said to influence each other. Psychological factors also influence the digestive fire as per Ayurveda, which gives hint about the evolution of Gut-Brain theory. In this present scenario of increased stress induced diseases, treating stress is the need of the hour and we may have to adopt the Satwavajaya Chikitsa for the stress along with Yukti Vyapashraya Chikitsa for the physical illness. The unique concept of Achara Rasayana in Ayurveda to increase one’s life span is again framed on the basis of this concept. The patients are categorised as Laghu Vyadhita & Guruvyadhita based on this concept which is highly relevant for present day practice. In all, this concept is scientific & much applicable in clinical practice.

Keywords: Mana, Shareera, Psychosomatic diseases, Achara rasayana

Paper No. 7.02. Indian Medical & Medicinal Practices

AnumanaPramana as a tool for Arista Lakshana

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, the diagnosis and the treatment of a disease is based on NidanaPancaka (Tools of Diagnosis), AturaPariksha (Examination of Patient) and these in turn depend upon Pramanas (proof or means of knowledge). In Ayurveda, four types of Pramana accomplish to ascertain known and unknown phenomena in both humans and the universe. Of them, methodology of inference viz. Anumana - Pramana is fundamental to diagnosis and research owing to its comprehensive design involving observations, analysis, rationale and consideration of facts. so, this study is planned to understand the concept of AnumanaPramana and also the contribution to diagnosis, treatment and prognostic symptoms. Charaka Samhita is the base of Chikitsa, so before starting the treatment portion Acharya Charaka has explained the symptoms and signs by which a vaidya can examine the diseases properly and in Indriyasthana it is indicated that after seeing some signs and symptoms a Vaidya can deny for treatment. Such signs and symptoms which indicate mortality are called Arista Lakshanas.

As science has grown it is necessary to know and correlate these Arista Laksanas with modern clinical parameters also. Here the AnumanaPramana plays an important role. Hence the study is carried out to know the importance of AnumanaPramana, its applicability in the clinical and literary field, also the importance of Indriyasthana, the utility of AnumanaPramana in Indriyasthana in understanding various Arista Lakshanas and their comparison in modern medical science so that our Samhitas are accurate till today.

Key words: *Anumana, Pramana, Indriyasthana, Arista Laksanas, Inference.*

Paper No. 7.03: Indian medical and medicinal practices.

Relevance of PratimarshaNasya as a Daily regimen in present scenario.

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ABSTRACT:

Recently, the whole world struggled to minimize deaths due to the Pandemic (covid19) and its variations year by year. Now it is almost showing as an epidemic, moving down from its Pandemicity. Modes of transmission being droplet infection and air borne, utmost care has to be taken to stop or interrupt the chain of transmission by controlling source or reservoir, modes of transmission and protecting the 'susceptible host'. This presentation throws light on the protection of susceptible host through ancient and the most scientific method, known as Nasya karma.

Nasya karma (pratimarshanasya – 1st method), being a daily regimen, enhances health and immunity there by acting on the local and systemic levels. As mentioned in the ayurvedic classics Nasya karma (marshanasya – 2nd method) is also a therapeutic measure, which is done by installing medicines (Nasyadravya) in the form of liquid or powder, through nose. As it is rightly said 'nose is the doorway of our head' (नासा हि शिरसो द्वारम्) by acharya Sushruta, Vagbhata, the dravya enter through nose and encounter the ailments of head and neck in an efficient way. It is high time to create healthy environment by inculcating healthy regimens in day to day practices, offered thousands of years ago.

Keywords: Nasya, Nasa, Nasyadravya, Nasyakarma, Pratimarshanasya.

Paper No. 7.04: Indian medical and medicinal practices.

A Case Report on Ayurvedic Management of Psoriasis.

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Psoriasis is a common chronic, recurrent, autoimmune disease of the skin and joints. It can have a significant negative impact on the physical, emotional and psychosocial well-being of affected patients. The use of modern medicine has greatly improved psoriasis treatment by providing symptomatic relief. However, some individuals fail to respond to treatment or lose initial efficacy, and it may be difficult to find the optimal treatment for these patients. Also, modern medicines have their own side effects in long course.

Ayurvedic diagnosis is considered as Kitibhakuṣṭha, which is a Vata-kapha predominant Kushta. Here, an effort was made to treat a Twenty eight years old male diagnosed with long standing moderate to severe erythrodermic psoriasis who had received systemic therapies in modern medicine without sufficient response previously, by classical Ayurvedic regimen. As the principle of treatment of all types of Kushta is Samshodhana along with Samshamana drugs, in this study, Virechana was given followed by which Samshamana drugs were given for 30 days. Assessment of skin lesions were done at the end of treatment.

Keywords: Psoriasis, Virechana, Kushta

Paper No. 7.05: Indian medical and medicinal practices.

Indian Medical and Medicinal practices

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ABSTRACT

Science refers to laws of nature of man and Universe. It originally means revealing the cause-mechanism effect of some natural phenomenon which is already existing. When an infective fever sets in, understanding why and how and reversing the same are explained by a true Science Ayurveda. Destroying Virus or bacteria is the job of Innate Immunity. All that is required to be done is to enable the immune system, clear the pathogens from the body as quick as possible and make subject healthy. SBEB protocol is not against any Virus or pathogen; rather it is the set of corrective measures directed against the pathological environment favouring the growth and multiplication of the pathogen. Infection is resultant of interaction between external factors and body's immune system. Impaired metabolism is the main reason which affects the normal drainage of metabolic wastes thus affecting the immune functions and various enzymatic activities. Protocol is designed to enhance the patient's metabolism and to activate, enhance and strengthen the immune response of the host towards the pathogen.

'Hastalamba' is a unique Viral Fever First Aid service where in patients can avail the online service of First Aid for their Viral Fever based on Science Based Evidence Based Ayurveda principles. First aid consists of dietary & lifestyle changes with medicated water. Data of over 300 patients are available to establish the fact that, infection can be effectively reversed with first aid strategy of Ayurveda without any suppressive medicines.

Keywords: Infective fevers, Cause-mechanism effect, Hastalamba, Science Based Evidence Based Ayurveda.

Paper No. 7.06: Indian medical and medicinal

॥ आयुर्वेदे अपस्मारः एवम् आधुनिकजीवनशैली ॥

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ABSTRACT

प्रचलित-

तन्त्रयुगे प्रायः वैद्यकीयशास्त्रस्य शब्दश्रवणमात्रेण पाश्चात्यवैद्यकीयशास्त्रस्य पद्धत्यानुसारेण पथ्यं विना औषधसेवनम् अथवा चिकित्सालये प्रवेशः इति प्रायः सर्वेषामतिः। एवमेव अन्यवैद्यकीयशास्त्रेऽपि इति प्रायः सर्वेषां भ्रमः। परन्तु, आयुर्वेदशास्त्रे एव नास्ति। आयुर्वेद-चिकित्साशास्त्रं केवलं औषधसेवनम् अथवा अभ्यङ्गादिपर्यन्तं सीमितं न वर्तते। तत्र सम्पूर्णजीवनपद्धतिः व्याख्यातम्। प्रायः यदि एवं सर्वैः ज्ञाते सति प्रचलितः व्याधिः, महाव्याधि इति नाम्ना सुश्रुतसंहितायामुल्लिखितः “अपस्मारः” जनानादारभ्यः अवरोधुं शक्यते। बालादारभ्य प्रायः सर्वेषां विभिन्नस्थरेषु अस्य महाव्याधेः समास्याः वर्तन्ते। आयुर्वेदचिकित्सां विना अन्यचिकित्सायाम् अस्य शाश्वतपरिहारः न वर्तते। प्रस्तुतसमाजे विद्यमानानि मानसिकव्याधयः (Psychological Disorder) इत्यस्यापि प्रायः परोक्षसम्बन्धः वर्तते। अतः अस्य अनुसन्धानस्य आवश्यकता वर्तते। ‘...तथा कामभयोद्वेगक्रोधशोकादिभिर्भृशम्...’ ॥ एतेके चनांशाः अपस्मारस्य कारणानि इति चरकाचार्याः तेषां ग्रन्थस्य उत्तरतन्त्रे ६१-०६ कथयन्ति। प्रस्तुतसमये प्रायः सर्वेषां कार्यक्षेत्रे एवं दैनन्दिनजीवने आचार्यैः उक्तरीत्या कामभयोद्वेगक्रोधशोकादिविपरीतं दृश्यते। अतः महाव्यधेः उपस्थितिः वर्तते। ‘संज्ञावहेषु स्रोतः सुदोषव्याप्तेषु मानवः। रजस्तमः परीतेषु मूढो भ्रान्तेन चेतसा ॥ सु० उ० ६१-०८ ॥’ इत्यादिविधलक्षणानि उक्त्वा यदि अस्य चिकित्सा न क्रीयते चेत् ‘अल्कालान्तरं चापि पुनः संज्ञालभेत सः ... ॥ ६१-१० ॥’ इति अग्रे कथयन्ति। अतः प्रस्तुतकाले अस्य समस्यायाः व्याप्तिः दृष्ट्वा, जनानां क्लेशः तथा ते कथं तस्य परिहारं कुर्वन्तः सन्ति इत्यस्य अनुसन्धानं अपेक्ष्यते। तदनन्तरं आयुर्वेदे अपस्मारः तथा तस्य चिकित्सायाः मार्गदर्शनस्य सर्वत्र प्रचारद्वारा सर्वेषां श्रेयोऽभिवृद्धिः अपेक्ष्यते इति मेमतिः।

Keywords: आयुर्वेदचिकित्सा, अपस्मारः, व्याधिः, महावायधिः, मानसिकव्याधिः, आयुर्वेदसंहिता

Paper No. 7.07: Indian medical and medicinal

IMPORTANCE OF ALCHEMY IN AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT:

Ayurveda is the science of life originating from the Indian subcontinent which has been existing from thousands of years. Foundation of ayurveda stands not only on healing of the disease but also preventing the disease . Ayurvedic science believes in treating the body as a whole by using elements available in the nature. It considers body and mind as one and not as a separate entity.

Rasa shastra or the science of alchemy is an important science in ayurveda which forms the base of the treatment . it mainly deals with usage of metals and non metals in the treatment of various diseases. It also deals with conversion of metals from its crude form to a medicinal form , to be able to administer it into human body. In older scriptures of rasa shastra, there has been mentioning of the practice of conversion of lower metals into higher metals called 'lohavada'. This paper is a sincere effort to putforth the ancient knowledge of Indian alchemy into the mainstream.

Keywords: rasa shastra, alchemy, ayurveda.

Paper No. 7.08: Indian medical and medicinal

AROGYAVARDINI RASA- A BOON TO SKIN DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Skin is the largest organ of human body. It's size and external location makes it susceptible to wide variety of disorders. In recent years skin diseases have gained more importance and attention by the medical science as well as public. There is definite increase in its incidence especially in the tropical countries like India. Skin diseases affect the individual in 4 ways .i.e. Discomfort, Disfigurement, Disability and Death.

Rasashastra is an exclusive branch of *Ayurveda*. The word *Rasashastra* literally mean the "science of *Rasa*(mercury)", generally refers to the science of making minerals assimilable for the body so they can be used as medicines. *Arogyavardini rasa* is an ayurvedic herbomineral formulation used for treatment of different types of *kushta*, *jwara*, *medhoro*ga and *yakritvikaras*. It has been described in the text by *Rasa Vagbhata* under *kushtachikitsa* and many other classical texts, including *AFI*. It is a *kharaliyarasayana* containing *Rasavarga Dravyas* such as *Parada*, *Gandhaka*, *Abraka Bhasma*, *Loha Bhasma* along with *Shilajathu*, *Guggulu*, *Triphala*, *Chitrakamula* and *Katuki* being the main ingredients. *Arogyavardini rasa* is an excellent remedy for skin conditions such as acne, eczema and psoriasis. Considering all these factors an effort is made to substantiate the role of *Arogyavardini rasa* and its probable mode of action in skin diseases .

Keywords: *Arogyavardini rasa*, skin diseases, *Rasashastra*, *Ayurveda*

Paper No. 7.09: Indian medical and medicinal

७.१५. संस्कृतवाङ्मये आयुर्विज्ञानम्

डारमेशःटिएस्

सहप्राध्यापकःसंस्कृतविभागाध्यक्षश्च, पूर्णप्रज्ञमहाविद्यालयः, उडुपि, कर्नाटक
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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतज्ञानस्यविज्ञानस्यचभाण्डागारंवर्तते।संस्कृतभाषयाअस्पृष्टःविज्ञानस्यभागःप्रायोनास्ति।संस्कृतवाङ्मयेयत्नानि
हितंतत्विज्ञानसमन्वितमेववर्तते।समुद्रवद्विशालेगभीरेचसंस्कृतवाङ्मयेवैज्ञानिकविषयादुर्लभाः,
संस्कृतग्रन्थाश्चरद्वाजाज्यस्यसंवर्धकाइतिकेचनकथयन्ति।अस्यआक्षेपस्यपरिमार्जनायकियान्प्रयत्नःकृतःसंशोधकैः?
श्रीदयानन्दसरस्वतीमहाभागेनएतदाक्षेपस्यउन्मूलनायकिञ्चिदिवप्रयत्नम्,
निर्मूलनेचवर्त्मप्रदर्शितम्।अत्रश्रीवेङ्कटरमण्यमहोदयेनरचितः‘सनातनविज्ञानसमुदयः’इतिग्रन्थोविलोकनीयः।तत्रचभौतविज्ञानम्,
, रसायनविज्ञानम्, सस्यविज्ञानम्, भूविज्ञानम्, प्राणिविज्ञानम्,
शरीरविज्ञानञ्चेतिविज्ञानस्यषट्सुप्रकारेषुभारतवर्षेयैःप्राचीनैःअवलीढोविषयःसमवायेनसङ्गृहीतोवर्तते, यश्चसर्वोऽपिवेदादेः,
महाभारतात्, वेदान्तदर्शनात्, आयुर्वेदात्, ज्यौतिषादेश्चग्रन्थात्परिगृहीतः।

इदानीकिञ्चित्आयुर्वेदविषयंनिरूपयामः-

आयुर्वेदस्तावत्अथर्ववेदस्यउपवेदत्वेनपरिगणितःवर्तते।तत्रआयुर्वेदेआधुनिकस्यवैद्यशास्त्रस्यसर्वमुख्यविभागाअन्तर्गताःसन्ति।
चरकसंहितायांकायचिकित्सा, सुश्रुतसंहितायांशल्यक्रिया(शस्त्रचिकित्सा), माधवनिदानेरोगनिदानम्,
नागार्जुनयोगशतकेशतौषधयोगः, वाग्भटस्यचअष्टाङ्गहृदयेशास्त्रस्यास्यअष्टौअङ्गानि वर्णितानि सन्ति।

अहम्इदानीहृद्रोगविज्ञानविषयंभवतःपुरस्तात्उपस्थापयितुमुच्छामि-

अधुनासर्वत्रदेशेहृद्रोगेणपीडिताजनाबहवोदरीदृश्यन्ते।तद्रोगस्यनिवारणंकरणीयंवर्तते।वेदकालिकेरत्नाकरवृन्दनामकग्रन्थेत्त्रि
वारणोपायःइत्थंप्रतिपादितःअस्ति, यथा-

*अस्थिभङ्गास्थिसंहारेहितःकफविनाशनः।**पित्तश्रमत्तृषादाहमेहवातविनाशकः॥**हृद्रोगंपाण्डुरोगंचविषबाधक्षतक्षयम्॥*

अर्जुनवृक्षःभग्नमस्थिसंयोजयति, कफंहरति, पित्तविनाशयति, श्रमंपरिहरति, तृषांनिवारयति,
मधुमेहंवातदोषंचअपनयति, हृद्रोगंपाण्डुरोगञ्च(Jaundice) दूरीकरोति, विषात्विमोचयति, व्रणंचनिष्कासयति।

तदौषधं कथंस्वीकरणीयमित्यपित्तत्रैवउक्तंवर्तते, यथा-

*घृतेनदुग्धेनगुडाम्भसावापिबन्तिचूर्णककुभत्वचोये।**हृद्रोगजीर्णज्वरपित्तकर्तृहत्वाभवेयुश्चिरजीविनस्ते॥*

अर्जुनवृक्षस्यत्वचःचूर्णयेघृतेनक्षीरेणगुडजलेनसहपिबन्तितावत्हृद्रोगाल्ज्वरात्रक्तपित्ताच्चमुक्ताभवन्ति।

येहृद्रोगेणपीडिताःसन्तितावत्त्रिमामर्जुनत्वचंप्रतिदिनंरिक्तोदरेक्षीरेणसहस्वीकुर्वन्तिचेहृद्रोगरहिताभवन्तिइत्यत्रना
स्तिसंदेहः।अर्जुनत्वक्हृद्रोगप्रसङ्गेयोरक्तसञ्चारनिरोधःतन्निवारयति।रक्तंशलक्षणीकरोति,
मेदसश्चनिवारयति।अनेनहृदयशस्त्रचिकित्सां(Open heart surgery) निवारयितुंशक्यते।हृदयेयत्नालं(Stunt)
संयोज्यतेतदपिनिवारयितुंशक्यते।

Keywords:Keyword one, Keyword two, Keyword three, Keyword four, Keyword five, Keyword six

Paper No. 7.10: Indian medical and medicinal

A Comprehensive Study Of Garbhini Paricharya (Ante-Natal Care) In Relationship To Monthwise Development Of Foetus And Its Scientific Interpretation.

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda being 'The Science of Life' greatly emphasizes on the maintenance of health and prevention of the disease. Prasooti tantra being a part of ashtanga ayurveda, mainly deals with lifestyle of a pregnant lady which includes ahara, vihara and vichara which is considered to be most important during the ante-natal period. The term 'Garbhini paricharya' consists of two words 'garbhini' means a 'lady in whom a garbha is present' and 'paricharya' means 'care in all aspects'. Pregnancy is the most important event in every woman's life and proper garbhini paricharya will result in the proper development of the foetus and its delivery to the outer world and also has a positive impact on the health of the mother, her ability to withstand the strain and stress during labour and also have a safe post-natal period. Present study consists of comprehensive references about dietary, medicinal and behavioral regimens in different Ayurvedic classics, its medical importance, scientific interpretation, discussion and conclusion.

Keywords: Garbhini paricharya, diet-regimen, ante-natal care, pregnancy, pathya, ahara-vihara, development of foetus.

Paper No. 7.11: Indian medical and medicinal

THE CONCEPT OF BALAGRAHA IN AYURVEDA AND ITS CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Balaroga, branch of Ashtanga of Ayurveda that deals with the care and diseases of children, it also defines a unique concept graharoga, a group of diseases that are caused by unknown vectors. Graha's are the invisible entities that cause diseases in children; they produce both physical and psychological manifestations. **Objective:** To study the concept of balagraha and its management mentioned in the classics scientifically.

Materials and methodology: Materials used for this article review are obtained from original Ayurveda classics and relevant textbooks and research articles from Google scholar and PubMed. The literature reviewed was scientifically analyzed in the study. **Results:** Graha's are definitely living organisms with microscopic nature, which causes both physical and psychological disturbances suggesting their generalized nature of the affliction, can be grouped under microbes causing infectious diseases. **Analysis:** By the study, graha's can be understood as micro-organisms. **Discussion:** There should be a cause for manifestations of disease, many times it may be invisible, and invisible entities are termed as graharoga by the Acharya's. These graharoga's are invisible due to their microscopic nature hence the disease caused by micro-organisms can be considered to understand the graharoga's.

Keywords: Balaroga, balagraha, micro-organisms.

Paper No. 7.12: Indian medical and medicinal

***Description of Hayayurveda Niroopana in Garuda
MahaPurana and it's zoological aspects : An Analytical
study***

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ABSTRACT

Garuda narrated to Kasyapa Prajapati what Lord Vishnu had told Garuda. The Purana in question came to be known as Garuda Purana because it was narrated by Garuda. It describes the appearance of Brahma and the creation of the universe. In Garuda Purana stories of Krishna incarnations are also important. Scientific matters such as grammar, Ayurveda, astronomy, the evolution of life after death and the concept of fatherhood are all discussed here. The Puranas are the cumulative form of our cultural heritage, philosophies and many branches of knowledge like Ayurveda, Astrology, Vastu etc. Garuda Purana has two kandas Purva and Uttara. It is also called Acharakanda as the main part is the Purvakanda with 240 chapters describing the karmas. There are two parts in Uttarkanda, Pretam Brahman. There are 49 chapters in Pretha Kandham and 29 chapters in Brahmakanda. Thus Garuda Purana has 318 chapters and a total of 18000 verses. 54 chapters from 146 to 200 are devoted to Ayurveda and the narrative is structured in such a way that Dhanyanthari advises Sushruta. Various types of fevers, blood pressure, asthma, tuberculosis, diabetes, leprosy etc. are described and remedies are prescribed. Eye diseases etc. are specifically described and Studies like Vrikshayurveda and Hayayurveda are also part of the wider narrative. In this paper an attempt to made about the horses treatment described in the Garudamahapurana and explains about the zoological aspects by mrigapakshisastra.

Key words:Hayayurveda, Garuda, Garudamahapurana, Mrigapakshisastra, sushruta

Paper No. 7.13: Indian medical and medicinal

Vedic Therapeutics for children with special needs- A review of our lived experiences & challenges faced in implementing the Vedic Chants Intervention Program (VCIP)

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ABSTRACT

As per census 2011, India is home to 26.8 million people with disabilities and the Government of India has identified that disabled children are the most vulnerable group needing special attention. Access to special education is not possible in many parts of India, especially in the rural areas due to problems in human resources, accessibility and awareness issues. Even in urban areas, where there is access to special educators and institutes for special children, there is need for newer and effective therapies that can offer support to the children by inducing positive behavioural modifications. Among the various therapies, Music Therapy is well recognized by therapists and researchers across the world. While several researches have been conducted to demonstrate the benefits of listening to Beethoven and Mozart, which has a great cultural significance in European countries, there is sparse research on the topic of use of Vedic Chants as a therapeutic intervention for children with special needs.

However, since 2012, we have, in collaboration with special schools and research institutions been investigating the therapeutic potential of Vedic Chants in children with special needs. In 2014, our organization published an article in the reputed medical journal "Molecular Cytogenetics" stating that the auditory stimulus of Vedic Chants has the potential to provoke the cognitive abilities in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). In this paper, we are sharing our lived experience of over 10 years, in implementing Vedic Chants Intervention Program (VCIP) and highlighting the benefits, challenges and also scope for future research.

Keywords: Vedic Chants, Vedic Therapeutics, Special Children, Vedic Chants Intervention Program, Sanskrit Chants,

Paper No. 7.14: Indian medical and medicinal

Life-span expansion using Ayurveda

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ABSTRACT

The word life-span means Ayushya or Ayu of a person. Ayushah vedah Ayurvedah- knowledge about one's life is Ayurveda. Ayu- represents a combination of the body, the sense organs, the mind, and the soul. All these combined with the virtue of the invisible past actions are designated as life. As soon as this combination is lost, the Ayu-life ceases to exist. That Shastra is designated as Ayurveda where, advantageous and disadvantageous as well as happy and unhappy states of life along with what is good and bad for life, its measurements are described. Ayurveda strongly opines that no gift can surpass the gift of life, because unless there is life, the four objects of human life i.e. Dharma, Artha, Kama and Moksha cannot be accomplished.

The very first Adhyaya narrated in one of the oldest treatise on Ayurveda i.e Charaka samhita is 'The Deerghajeevitiya Adhyaya' the quest for longevity. Maintaining the health of the healthy and to get rid of diseases of the diseased is the very aim of this CHIKITSA shastra. This is very well established while narrating principles, causes and treatments of diseases, rejuvenation therapies ect. Thus the ways of Ayu vriddhi is explained in each and every aspects of this Vaidya shastra. Ayurveda-the most sacred and honored by those proficient in the Vedas, as it is beneficial to mankind in respect of both the worlds (i.e. this world –IHA loka and the world beyond-PARA loka).So one desirous of long, happy, fruitful life should be aware of and practice the principles and methods proposed by Ayurveda.

Keywords : Ayuvriddhi, Deergha jeevitiya Adhyaya, Lifespan expansion, Rasayana therapy, Ayurveda

Paper No. 7.15: Indian medical and medicinal

INDIAN MEDICAL & MEDICINAL PRACTICES: SHALYA CHIKITHSA (SURGERY)

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ABSTRACT

Pilonidal derives its name from Latin- *pilus* meaning “hair,” and *nidus* meaning “nest.” The term pilonidal sinus describes a condition found in the natal cleft overlying the coccyx, consisting of one or more, usually non-infected, midline openings, which communicate with a fibrous track lined by granulation tissue and containing hair lying loosely within the lumen. The disease mostly affects men, in particular hairy men than women. Recurrence is common, even though adequate excision of the track is carried out. The multitude of surgical procedures advocated to eradicate pilonidal disease, combined with the lack of prospective trials, attests to the lack of overall superiority of one method over the others. Time spent off work and perceived recurrence rates, but more usually surgeon preference, influence the choice of method, which includes the laying open, marsupialisation, excision, Limberg procedure, Z-plasty etc. In Ayurveda, *Acharya Sushruta* has described this as *Shalyajanadivrana* and a multi-modular approach has been prescribed including *Ashtavidha shastra karma* (~8 Principal surgical techniques), *Kshara* (~herbal alkali), *Agni* (~thermal cautery) & *Shashti upakrama* (~60 condition specific wound management).

This is a case of a 15 years old girl with no significant medical history, reported with the chief complaint of recurrent pain, swelling and discharge from the natal cleft for 2 years. She had undergone surgical excision couple of times, but the condition recurred. With informed consent, under local anaesthesia, *Chedana* (~wide excision) of all the tracks followed by *Kshara karma* (~application of *Kshara*) was done. Post operative wound was treated with *Utsadhana karma* with an herbal combination mentioned in *Sushruta Samhita*. Wound granulated and healed progressively with minimal healthy scar in 40 days. A follow up of 6 months shows no recurrence till date. Ayurveda offers better and wide range of time-tested surgical managements for such challenging ailments which needs to be acknowledged globally.

Keywords: Pilonidal sinus, Ayurveda, Surgery, Wound, Kshara

Paper No. 7.16: Indian medical and medicinal

Rasayana- ARejuvenatingTherapy as mentioned in Ayurveda

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ABSTRACT

“*Swasthasyaswaasthyarakshanam, aturasyavikaraprashamanam cha*” is the ultimate aim of Ayurveda. Right from the *Vedic* Period, our *Acharyas* felt that the human life is too short to attain progress in every aspect. Hence, they proposed the concept of longevity by use of drugs like *Soma* in the *Vedic* rituals. This concept was further developed during the *Samhita* Period as ‘*Rasayana Chikitsa*’. *Charaka Samhita* right from the first chapter- ‘*Deerghanjeevitiyaadhyaya*’ which mentions different methods to preserve the good health as well as to treat the disease condition. Despite these methodologies, ageing is unstoppable and inevitable. This phenomenon was observed by the ancient physicians and hence the concept of *Rasayana* was evolved to slow down ageing. Many scientific researches have proven that *Rasayanas* not only act on physical but also act on mental health of the individual. They also exhibit nutritive, immuno-modulatory, cyto-protective, nootropic and adaptogenic activities. This paper attempts to compile proven researches on life-extending techniques.

Keywords: *Rasayana chikitsa, Deerghanjivitiya, geriatrics, immune-modulators, cyto-protective, nootropic*

Paper No. 7.17: Indian medical and medicinal

Indian Medical and Medicinal Practices Impact of Shalya Chikitsa in Clinical Practice

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ABSTRACT

Shalya Tantra one among the eight branches of Ayurveda focus on various surgical ailments and their suitable management. Sushruta Samhita of Acharya Sushruta, illuminates details of surgical techniques and diseases. Even though Sushruta samhita a unique document in surgical field, it also explains Method of dissection, Toxicology, obstructive labour, role of diet in surgical disease and ethical considerations. Shalya Tantra apart from offering the fastest cure has been considered for its versatile and successful approaches in the field of healing.

Shalya Tantra registers exemplar treatment options for the surgical diseases. 60 treatment options are explained in wound healing management, one of the surgical challenge faced across the globe. Anorectal ailments like Haemorrhoids, Fistula-in Ano and Fissure-in -Ano are addressed in a very methodic way so that it has been widely accepted across the world by its high cure rate. The novel method of Drug delivery, Kshara Sutra is an effective treatment for Fistula-In-Ano. Disorders like Tumours, BPH and urinary disorders like Bladder stone, stricture urethra have been systemically explained. Orthopedic ailments like Fractures, dislocations, sprains are explained in a very unique way. Internal and external injuries with due considerations of Marma points are discussed very vividly. Surgical and Parasurgical techniques are described in their minutest details and these techniques are followed even today. Sushrutacharya documents and developed the art of plastic surgery for the first time.

Keywords: Shalya Chikitsa, Sushruta, Ksharasutra.

Paper No. 7.18: Indian medical and medicinal

Contribution of Maharshi Sushruta in the purification of water w.s.r to Sphatika (Potash alum).

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ABSTRACT:

Water borne diseases are serious problem globally which cause about 1.5 million deaths annually. Therefore, reliable access to clean drinking water is most important step to prevent them. Presently purification techniques like water filters, purifiers and chemical agents are being adopted. These measures are not cost effective and consume more time and energy. To overcome this limitation, contribution of Ayurveda in water purification needs to be explored. The objective of the study is to throw light on contributions of Sushruta in the field of water purification. Also aims to understand the mode of action of Sphatika.

Acharya Sushruta has mentioned seven materials for jalaprasadana (purification of contaminated water) which are simple, easy to adopt and economical. They are Kataka (Strychnos potatorum), Gomeda (Hessonite stone), Visagranthi (Lotus root), Shaivalamula (Blue green algae), Vastra (Cloth), Mukta (Pearl) and Mani. In Dalhana's commentary Mani is clarified to be Sphatika. It can either be equated to potash alum or Quartz. Among these two, potash alum is used as an effective material since ages for the purification of water. There are 5 stages for water treatment – Coagulation, Flocculation, Sedimentation, Filtration and Disinfection. They need to be adopted based on intensity of contamination of water. Potash alum purifies water by the process of Coagulation and Flocculation.

Keywords: Sphatika, Water purification, Jalaprasadana, Sushruta, Water borne diseases, contaminated water

Paper No. 7.19: Indian medical and medicinal

CONTRIBUTIONS OF MAHARSHI CHARAKA, SUSHRUTA, VAGBHATA IN THE FIELD OF INDIAN ALCHEMY

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ABSTRACT:

Ayurveda is science of life. Ayurveda not only focuses on curing of diseased individual but also gives importance to maintenance of health of healthy person. Ayurveda is basically divided into eight branches based on specific field of expertise. Among these Rasashastra is not counted as a main branch as it was initially considered as an independent pharmaceutical science. It is study of use of metallic and mineral compounds for preparation of mineral and herbomineral formulations. The origin of Rasashastra has its roots in the “Indian Alchemy”. Alchemy was a form of chemistry studied in medieval period where in people tried to discover different ways to convert lower metals to higher metals. Historical development of rasashastra can be traced to vaidika(veda) period, Samhita period, Sangraha kala and Adhunik(Present) period. In Samhita period many treatise give references regarding rasashastra, rasadravya and their preparations. Charaka Samhita, sushruthasamitha and vagbhataSamhita(Astangasangraha / astangahrudaya) are the main treatise of samitha period.

In this Review article, an attempt was made regarding unveiling the references of rasashastra (Indian alchemy) from bruhatrayis. The references from each samhitas related to the field of Indian alchemy is gathered and listed in this review article

Keywords: rasa shastra, alchemy, ayurveda, Samhita.

Paper No. 7.20: Indian medical and medicinal

Noteworthiness of Charaka Samhita in obtaining Shreyasi Praja- a desired excellent progeny-A literary review

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that the world is looking forward to genetically made-up offspring i.e., designer babies. Epigenesis is also the subject of extensive research, as everyone are aspiring to produce a perfect offspring. Whereas, in India, thousands of years ago our scriptures have defined various methods of obtaining desired progeny with the highest qualities, which is referred to as *Shreyasi Praja* in *Charaka Samhita* and has a far broader sense than the designer baby definition. In Ayurveda, the measures told to obtain “*Shreyasi Praja*” not only to prevent genetically transmitted diseases, but also to aid in improving the physical, psychological as well as spiritual well-being of both mother and child. Also, decreases the risk of complications during pregnancy and childbirth.

Majority of the studies published based on research field are limited to the field of antenatal and postnatal treatment. There have also been a few studies on the principle of Garbhasamskara and how to have a good-looking, intelligent progeny. Hence, it is need of the time to analyse, understand, and interpret “*Shreyasi Praja*” concept in depth, so that it can be applied practically in obtaining an auspicious progeny, which will also aid in achieving the goal of Ayurveda. Through this literary research an effort has been made to illuminate all the unexplored dimensions of the concept and guidelines to obtain “*Shreyasi Praja*” explained in *Sharirasthana* of *Charaka Samhita*.

Keywords: Shreyasi praja, Garbhadhana Samskara, Bija, Desired progeny, Pregnancy.

Paper No. 7.21: Indian medical and medicinal

बिल्ववृक्षः - SCIENTIFIC AND RELIGIOUS SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

Bilva plant is found to be known to Indians since vedic period. It is grown in all parts of India and mainly planted near Shiva temples. It is identified scientifically as *Aegle marmelos* having common name bael tree. It is symbol of prosperity and its leaves are offered to lord Shiva. The bilva tree contains [furocoumarins](#), including [xanthotoxol](#) and the methyl ester of alloimperatorin, as well as [flavonoids](#), [rutin](#) and [marmesin](#); a number of essential oils. The botanical, ethnotherapeutical and pharmacological informations mention its benefit to human being. Having lot of benefits, Indians consider it one of the important and sacred plant. It is useful in treating many diseases such as diarrhea, piles, udararoga, grahañiroga, boils, obesity etc., as singly or mixed with other drugs.

Aegeline a constituent of the bilva leaf and consumed as a [dietary supplement](#) with the intent to produce weight loss. Being rich in [vitamin C](#), the fruits can be eaten either fresh from trees or after being [dried](#) and produced into candy, [toffee](#), pulp powder or [nectar](#). The trifoliate leaf is said to symbolize various factors like brahma Vishnu and Shiva, the three eyes of lord shiva, the three shaktis namely the power of decision, action and knowledge, the three lingas and three syllables of Omkara.

Keywords: Bilva vriksha, udararoga, thrimurthy

Paper No. 7.22: Indian medical and medicinal

Importance and Uses of Medicinal Plant-MoringaOleifera (Shigru)

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MoringaOleifera which has very important medicinal properties, is famous seasonal vegetable. It is used in various dishes such as Sabji, Sambar, Amati. Medicinal plants have curative properties due to the presence of various complex chemical substances of different composition. These are found as secondary plant metabolites in one or more parts of these plants. Medicinal plants have been used from vedic era in Ayurveda. Importance of these medicinal plant is explained in vedas and sanhitas. Atharva-Veda and Nighantoo are famous Sanskrit books related to medicinal plant from ancient era. Medicinal plants are connected with our lives directly or indirectly. Many people have no idea or knowledge about uses of medicinal plant. So the purpose of this study is to create public awareness about medicinal use and to develop scientific approach among people towards its medico-religious belief.

MoringaOleifera ‘The Miracle Tree’ provides a variety of nutrition in the form of various vitamins, minerals and proteins, aminoacids with significantly less fat, less carbohydrate and fewer calories. In traditional medicine it is used as anthelmintic (Krumighna) also for treatment of diabetes (Madhume), Cardiovascular Disease (Hrudrog), Ulcers and Gastrointestinal problems. It is hoped that study will inform general public about medicinal use of this plant to solve minor-major health problems in day-to-day life.

Keywords – MoringaOleifera, Nighantoo, Anthelmintic, Cardiovascular, Gastrointestinal.

Paper No. 7.23: Indian medical and medicinal

भारतेआयुर्वेदपारम्परिकःऔषधोपचारः

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ABSTRACT

“शरीरमाद्यंखलुधर्मसाधनम्” इतिकविकुलगुरुमहाकविकालिदासोऽक्तिःअत्यन्तंप्रसिद्धावर्तते। तथैवअस्यमानवशरीरस्यसंरक्षणाम्अस्माभिःकरणीयम्एव । अतैवअस्माकंनित्यजीवनेहितभुक्, मितभुक्, ऋतुभुक्, रोगनिवारणम्,आहारसामाग्रीणांप्रकृतिः,आहारणांरक्षणमएतादृशीआयुर्वेदीयाजीवनप्रद्वृत्तिःअनुसरणीया । केवलरोगकालेआयुर्वेदस्यऔषधस्यसेवनं न ।।तादृशंजीवनमेवअस्माभिःआत्मसाक्षात्कारंकरणीयम्इतिपारम्परिकऔषधोपचारैःक्रियतेइतिआयुर्वेदेउक्तम्अस्त।

मासैर्द्विसंख्यैर्माघाद्यैःक्रमात्षड्दशतवःस्मृताः ।

शिशिरोऽथवसन्तश्चग्रीष्मोवर्षाशरद्धिमाः ॥१॥

शिशिराद्यास्त्रिभिस्तैस्तुविद्याद्यनमुत्तरम् ।

आदानं च, तदादत्तेनृणांप्रतिदिनंबलम् ॥२॥

अतःआयुर्वेदेमानसिकशौचः, कर्मशौचः सांस्कृतिकः शौचः,शारीरिकशौचः, वाक्शौचः इतिपञ्चप्रकारःशौचाः सन्ति। एतेषुसर्वेषुव्यसमर्षयःवदन्तियतहृदयशुद्ध्यामनुष्यःसहजतयास्वर्गप्राप्नुयात् । अस्माभिःनित्यंसूर्यनमस्कारःक्रीयतेएवअथैवमत्स्यपुराणे “आरोग्यंभास्करादिच्छेत्”इतिसन्दर्भसुर्योयआत्मसमर्पणंकृत्वाआरोग्यंप्राप्तव्यम्इतिअस्ति । स्वास्थ्यस्यनिर्वाहणार्थंपरीश्रमःमिताहारस्वीकरणस्यअभ्यासः च कर्तव्यःइतिआयुर्वेदेउक्तम्अस्ति ।अस्यआयुर्वेदस्यअध्ययनेनस्वास्थ्यरक्षणक्रमंकिञ्चित्उल्लेखितुम्इच्छामि ।

Keywords: पञ्चशोचाः, आरोग्यम्, आत्मसाक्षात्कारः, आहरस्वीकरणक्रमःइत्यदयः....

Paper No. 7.24: Indian medical and medicinal

A Machine Learning Models for Categorization of Breast Cancer Data Set Using Feature Selection Method

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ABSTRACT

One of the top causes of death for women is breast cancer. The most serious problem for women is breast cancer. Although many people who develop breast cancer have no family history, women who have blood relatives who have the same disease are more likely to develop the disease themselves. Breast cancer is the second-worst type of cancer that has been identified so far.

The technique of trying to anticipate a result from data using machine learning models is known as predictive modelling. The quality of the input data that is given to the model has a significant impact on the output quality. Feature engineering is the process of deciding which input to choose for a machine learning model based on a range of factors. The effort is done to categories breast cancer patients into the categories of recurrence and non-recurrence. The optimal set of features is chosen from a categorical breast cancer dataset in this study in order to produce precise predictions. The Chi squared technique and the Mutual Information technique have both been utilized in feature selection. The final prediction was then made by the Logistic Regression model using the chosen features. It was determined that the Mutual Information approach achieved higher prediction accuracy and was more effective. The proposed model is expected to improve diagnostic decision-support systems by predicting breast cancer disease accurately.

Keywords: Predictive modeling, Machine Learning, Feature Selection, Breast Cancer.

Paper No. 7.25: Indian medical and medicinal

“ĀyurvedaŚāstraVsAyurvedic Science”

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ABSTRACT:

The way the East, the oriental civilizations approached knowledge and the way the West, the occidental greeko-roman civilizations, approached knowledge are totally different and in many ways diametrically oppose each other. In the East, the approach is holistic, taking all aspects of life including the God and the spirit into the realm of knowledge. On the other hand, in the West the approach to knowledge is increasingly reductionistic keeping out not only god and the spirit but all the subjective notions of knowledge which cannot be measured or proved to be existing in material parameters. For example; the Indian *Tarkaśāstra* defines *Dravya* to include *ātmā*, *manas*, *dik*, *kāla* etc., (तत्रद्रव्यानिपृथ्व्यप्तेजोवायुराकाशकालदिगात्मामनांसिनवैव) as *dravyas* but the Western Science (WS), when it defines matter or substance, include only physical matter, that can be touched, seen, felt, tasted, smelt, measured and weighed. For example, time, mind, individuation cannot be even conceived as matter by the western mind. They would rather laugh at such a proposal.

Therefore, the Indian śāstras, the storehouse, the embodiments of the knowledge of our country and our civilisations, cannot be even compared either in its approach or in its content with any seemingly corresponding science in the domain of western knowledge. For example, वस्तुगुण, द्रव्यगुण, cannot even be compared with Physics. The term भौतिकशास्त्र invented, coined by some irresponsible scholars to be made to mean the science of Physics never existed in Indian knowledge as a śāstra. The word śāstra is not only a misnomer but also misleading and mischievous. Same is the case with the term coined for Chemistry viz., *Rasāyanaśāstra*. There never was a śāstra like that. The list of ill-named bodies of knowledge being flaunted as the most respectable śāstras is endless: *khagolaśāstra*, *śarīranirmānaśāstra*, *śarīraracanāśāstra*, *gaṇitaśāstra*, *jīvaśāstra*, *jantuśāstra*, *vrkṣaśāstra*, etc. Now we have each WS clothed in Indian language and masquerading as a śāstra.

But the term śāstra had been in India having a very specific sacred, haloed meaning and significance. Śāstra is and had always been an unquestionable, an undeniable *pramāna* for us. Indian śāstras are given by highly revered authentic Seers. Every single śāstra is in agreement with the ultimate *Vedapramāṇa* in every aspect. There applicability is universal. There validity is eternal, *nitya*, *sanātana*.

Unfortunately somewhere after the WS has entered into the larger modern Indian mind we had learnt to compromise on many counts perhaps out of a false sense of threat. We started asserting that we have the equivalents of some of the WS in India already in existence for a long time.

Paper No. 7.26: Indian medical and medicinal

प्रश्नोपनिषदि वर्णितं पञ्चप्राणस्य आयुर्वेदानुसारं महत्त्वम्*

डा. दर्शना वरगंटीवारः सहायकप्राध्यापिका, संस्कृत संहिता सिद्धान्तविभागः, डा.मा.म.आयुर्वेदः महाविद्यालयः यवतमालः
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सारांशः

वेदानाम् अन्तिमभागः उपनिषद्। उपनिषदि ज्ञानकाण्डस्य विवेचनं प्राप्नोति। तथाच आयुर्वेदशास्त्रे स्वास्थ्यविषयकं ज्ञानं प्रतिपादितमस्ति। द्वयोः शास्त्रयोः मानवकल्याणाय, मोक्षार्थाय च रचना जाता। उपनिषदानां सङ्ख्या 108 तत्रापि 10 महत्त्वपूर्णाः उपनिषदाः सन्ति। आयुर्वेदशास्त्रे चरकसंहिता, सुश्रुत संहिता, वाग्भट संहिता (बृहत्संहिता) महत्त्वपूर्णाः संहिताः। संहिताग्रन्थेषु पञ्चप्राणसंदर्भं सर्वत्रमेव विवेचनम् उपलभ्यते।

प्रश्नोपनिषदि तृतीयप्रश्ने पञ्चप्राणविषये उल्लेखः आगतः। अस्मिन् शोधनिबन्धे प्रश्नोपनिषदि वर्णितं पञ्चप्राणस्य आयुर्वेददृष्ट्या स्वास्थ्यार्थं महत्त्वं कथितमस्ति। प्राणैव शरीरस्याधारः स एकः एव किन्तु शरीरान्तर्गतं तेषां स्थानानुसारं कार्यं तु भिन्नं भिन्नं वर्तते।

प्राणस्येदं वशे सर्वं त्रिदिवे यत्प्रतिष्ठितम्।

मातेव पुत्रान् रक्षस्व श्रीश्च प्रजां च विधेहि न इति।। (प्रश्नो.2/13)

प्राणस्यैवास्मिंल्लोके सर्वमिदं वशे। तथैव अस्मिन् देहे यावद् वायुः स्थितः तावदेव जीवनं वक्तुं शक्यते। तस्य निष्क्रान्तिः मरणं उच्यते। प्राणः एवास्माकं जीवनं अतः तस्य रक्षणार्थं प्रयत्नमावश्यकम्।

प्राणापानव्यानोदानसमानाः पञ्च वायवः। पञ्चप्राणानां स्थितिः एतस्मिन् विषये प्रश्नोपनिषदि तृतीयप्रश्ने कथितमस्ति। अपानः उपस्थे, व्यानः संपूर्णशरीरे, नेत्रादिमध्ये प्राणः, समानः जठरे। वायुः एव शरीरयन्त्रतन्त्रधरः अनेन वायुनैव शरीराणां समस्त कार्यकलाकलापाः प्रवर्तन्ते तित्यायुर्वेदशास्त्रे प्रोक्तमस्ति। वायोः अधीनैव संपूर्णं शरीरं विना तेन न गतिः। वायुः नाम प्राणवायुः इति मन्तव्यः। स्वस्थस्य स्वास्थ्य रक्षणम् आयुर्वेदस्य प्रथमं प्रयोजनम्।

द्वितीयम् आतुरस्य विकार प्रशमनम्। स्वस्थः सदैवं स्वस्थं भवेत् तदर्थं आयुर्वेदः प्रयतते। प्राणस्य रक्षणार्थं आयुर्वेदग्रन्थे ज्ञानं समाहितमस्ति।

प्रश्नोपनिषदि उल्लेखितं पञ्चप्राणाः तथाच आयुर्वेदशास्त्रे कथितं तेषां स्वास्थ्यविषयकं महत्त्वकथनमेव अस्य शोधनिबन्धस्य प्रयोजनम्।

बीजशब्दाः

उपनिषद्,

प्रश्नोपनिषद्, वेदः, आयुर्वेदः, पञ्चप्राणाः, वायुः।

संशोधनपद्धतिः

अस्य शोधनिबन्धस्य संशोधनपद्धतिः विवेचनात्मकं भविष्यति।

संदर्भग्रन्थाः

1) ईशादि नौ उपनिषद्

गीताप्रेस गोरखपुर

2) चरकसंहिता

चौखम्बा प्रतिष्ठानम्

3) अष्टांगहृदय

चौखम्बा प्रतिष्ठानम्

Paper No. 7.27: Indian medical and medicinal

संस्कृत वाग्‌मयमें आयुर्वेद संदर्भ – स्त्री सौंदर्य प्रसाधनों का महत्त्व

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संस्कृतसाहित्यमें आयुर्वेद का वही स्थान है जो शरीर में शिरोभाग का है। सहस्रोंवर्षोंसेकवियोने अनेक शास्त्रोंकामंथन करके, विचित्र कल्पलोक का निर्माण कियाहै। आयुर्वेद का महताशरीरमाद्यंखलुधर्मसाधनम्` इसकालिदासीयोक्तिसे चरितार्थ होती है।

रूप यहविकाररहित होता है। अच्छे

रूप को निश्चितही प्रधान्यदिया जाता है।

रूप कारक्षण करने के लिए विविध सौंदर्य प्रसाधनों का इस्तेमालकिया जाता है।

विविधप्रकारकेअगराग, लेप, अलंकार, वस्त्र इ. साधनोंद्वाराआकर्षित प्राप्त

करनाइसका संदर्भ वैदिककालसेमिलताहै। आर्षसाहित्यसेतत्कालिक

सौंदर्य विषयक संकल्पना सौंदर्य साधन इनका यथोचित दर्शन होता है।

- 1) केशोंको धूप देना।
- 2) पौरों पर तेल लगाना।
- 3) कानोंमें तेल डालना।
- 4) ओठोंपर राग-लाल रंग लगाना।
- 5) शरीर के विविध अंगोपर लेप लगाना।
- 6) कपड़ोको रंग देना।

केशोंको धूप देना : प्राचिन काल मेंकेशों की रक्षा के लिएइनसे उत्पन्न हुए कृति - जुँ आदि कोमारने के लिएकेशोंको सुखाने के लिए अगरू चन्दन आदि सुगन्धितवस्तुओंसे धुवा दिया जाता था। इसका उल्लेख कालिदासने ऋतुसंहार कुमारसंभवमेंकियाहै। उसी प्रकार माघनेभीइसकाउलेखकियाहै।

इस प्रकार के अनेक विषयों पर संस्कृत साहित्य मेंआयुर्वेदकी झलक व्यापक रूप मेंमिलतीहै। यह प्रस्तुत करने का प्रयास मैंकर रहीहूँ।

Keywords-1 सौंदर्य, 2धुवा, 3 लेप.

Paper No. 7.28: Indian medical and medicinal practices.

‘Servejanaaha Sukhinobhavanthu’ Ensuring Wellness by Deciphering Traditional Food Practices Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

There is a Sanskrit Sloka: Amantram aksharam naasti, Naasti muulam anoushadham, Ayoogyaha purushoo naasti, Yoojaka thathrai dhurlabha (No letter in alphabet that cannot be pronounceable, no herb is there without medicinal properties, there is no person noted as useless; however, there is a shortage of planners who foresee the right use of alphabets, herbs and persons for the best). On the lines of above sloka, people have less-knowledge of rationale behind food preparation and eating practices. May it be sitting on flour for dinning, showering water surrounding plankton leaf, putting a few droplets of rice outside the leaf and others - e.g., serving a bit of salt and sweet early stage of meal, have not been understood in its right spirit and often, were poohpooed as Brahminical. Unless and until, the traditional food preparation, serving and conservation practices are understood in right spirit, all-round wellness of generation next is not possible. Given this background, main objective of this paper is to throw light on Conventional Knowledge in Food Practices passed on for generations specifically coastal Karnataka that ensures Physical Wellness. The paper begins with the concept of wellness as stated by Gallup. Wellbeing encompasses the broader holistic dimensions of a well-lived life.

Although there are other definitions, Gallup’s global research has found five elements of wellbeing that add up to a thriving life: • Physical wellbeing: A person has energy to get things done. • Career wellbeing: One likes what that person does every day. • Social wellbeing: One has meaningful friendships in one’s life. • Financial wellbeing: One manages that person’s money well. • Community wellbeing: A person like where that person lives. Furthermore, it tries to adapt the ‘Effectuation and Causation Logic’ propounded by Saras D Saraswati (2001) used in food preparation and serving by the elders.

Keywords: Physical Wellness, Food Practices, Effectuation.

Paper No. 7.29: Indian medical and medicinal practices.

“Changing Scenario of International Business in Medical Tourism with India as a preferred destination with specific reference to Ayurveda”

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ABSTRACT

Medical tourism, with patients going abroad for surgeries, has grown exponentially over the past decade, particularly for Ayurvedic treatments. High costs and long waiting lists in the country, new technologies and know-how in the destination countries as well as low transport costs and internet marketing have played a role. Several Asian countries, especially India, dominate medical tourism. Conventional tourism has been a by-product of this growth, despite its tourism conditioning, and the overall benefits to the tourism industry have been significant. The growth of medical tourism underscores the privatization of healthcare, growing reliance on technology, unequal access to healthcare resources, and accelerating economic globalization of healthcare and tourism in India.

Keywords: Globalization of Health Care Tourism, Conventional Tourism, Health Resources, Economic Globalization, Traditional Indian Medicine System

Paper No. 8.01: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

YOGA IN PAST-PRESENT-FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

Patanjali Maharshi systematised the subject yoga and contributed in the form of a *Shashtra* for study and practice. Before Patanjali in all practice's yoga was a part of lifestyle for the capacity building and to develop the quality of a human being up to optimum level. It was in the form of sadhana. Even though various philosophies are there, practically systematized method of sadhana techniques is explained in yoga. When we have developed externally, internal development started to slowdown. Then sadhana methods developed in a systematic manner which is very accurate in yoga. Speciality of yoga is to learn and practice. No need of pre-qualification but only interest is required. Result of the practice depend upon the intensity of the practice. All practices are concentrated to reduce citta vikshepa.

Presently, unknowingly yoga practices are classified into physical, mental, spiritual practices etc. according to the understanding capacity of a person. Aim of the subject and practising techniques are left out and only temporary result-oriented level practising are used at present. This is not solution for life hurdles and skill development in the duty and life. But speciality of the subject is proper practice of yoga which gives complete development of a human being from the time immemorial. This helps mainly in the development of health and wealth of a person and Nation which are the key points. Presently its application is possible only in a systematic manner when it is implemented in the education system. Then each and everybody will get awareness and effect of yoga. This is basic foundation for the development of humanity, quality of life, health, wealth, skill and overall development with the sense of time.

Paper No.8.02: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

YOGA AS THERAPY- NECESSITY AND IMPORTANCE

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The spiritual and scientific discipline of Yoga is the most precious gem of our cultural heritage and is being practiced in India since time immemorial. Recently, there has been an increased awareness in health through natural methods like yoga in all parts of the world. ‘Yoga Shastra’, the science of Yoga has to be studied systematically to realize the hidden truth in this great ancient science. We can develop these concepts for the curative, preventive and promotive aspects in relation to health. Healing the health problems using the techniques of yoga is called as ‘Yoga Therapy’. Yoga is an effective and time-tested method for improving our health as well as to cure and prevent the diseases. We can systematically adopt these therapeutical values in the cure, prevention and management of the diseases.

The origin of the most of the diseases is in the mind according to yogic thought. The mind influences the body in every possible way. Distractions of the mind effect the physical body and which in turn imbalances the normal body functions and leads to diseases. Day by day; such psychosomatic diseases are increasing by the influence of the modern lifestyle. Yoga is the unique solution, which can directly control the mind and helps to maintain healthy body and mind by destroying the impurities. ‘yogāngānustānādaśuddhikṣaye jñānadīptirāvivekakhyāteh’ says Maharshi Patanjali. Holistic approach of yoga has the potentiality to heal the patients to the grass roots of their ailments. Researches undertaken in various aspects of yoga in relation to health, disease, physiological and psychological benefits of yoga proved it.

Keywords: Yoga, Therapy, Yoga Shastra, Health, Psychosomatic diseases

Paper No.8.03: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

योगशास्त्रे विज्ञानम्

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ABSTRACT

भगवता महर्षिणा पतञ्जलिना विनिर्मिते योगशास्त्रे 'यम-नियम-आसन-प्राणायाम-प्रत्याहार-धारण-ध्यान-समाधयोऽङ्गानि (२/२९) इति सूत्रम्।

योगशास्त्रमिति यदुच्यते तत् विज्ञानशास्त्रमित्येवावगन्तव्यम्। शास्त्रेऽस्मि यावन्ति विज्ञानानि विद्यन्ते तानि तावत् शास्त्रान्तरे नैव सन्तीति निश्चयः। विज्ञानेन सह धर्मार्थकाममोक्षाणां चतुर्णामपि पुरुषार्थानां सम्पादने योगविज्ञानानि समुपयोक्तुं पर्यन्ते इति विशेषः।

इदानीं विद्यमानचिकित्सालयेषु आरोग्यभाग्यस्य यावन्ति साधनानि सन्ति तानि विहायापि आरोग्यमाप्नुम इति योगविज्ञानस्य लोकविज्ञानादप्युत्तमत्वं वक्तुं शक्नुमः।

तथाहि – अष्टाङ्गहृदये हठप्रकरणे श्लोकमेकं पश्यामः –

वपुःकृशत्वं वदने प्रसन्नता नादस्फुरत्वं नयने सुनिर्मले।

अरोगता बिन्दुजयोऽग्निदीपनं नाडीविशुद्धिर्हठसिद्धिलक्षणम्॥ इति॥ (१-७८)

अत्र प्रत्येकस्मिन्नप्यंशे योगविज्ञानस्य वैशिष्ट्यं पश्यामः।

“ब्रह्माण्डे यानि तत्त्वानि तानि सन्ति कलेवरे” इत्युक्तरीत्या सर्वाण्यपि जगतस्तत्त्वानि देहे कथं वर्तन्ते इति तु योगाभ्यासेनावगन्तुं शक्यते। अणिमादिशक्तयस्तावत् योगविज्ञानादेव प्रभवन्तीत्येतत् विदितचरमेव। प्राचीनाः मुनयः योगविज्ञानेन स्वात्मनि निरुद्धं कामादिशङ्कनां मूलमुत्पाट्य अन्यस्यापि द्वेषादोषहरणे समर्था बभूवुरित्यपि विदितचर एवायं विचारः। एतदेव भगवता श्रीकृष्णेनाप्युक्तं - “समत्वं योग उच्यते” “योगः कर्मसु कौशलम्” इत्यादि। अनितरसाधारणस्य योगविज्ञानस्य विषये किञ्चित्पश्यामः॥

Keywords: Yoga Vijnana, Astanga yoga, aadhunika vijnaana

Paper No 8.04: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Yoga-Narration and Practice of Sree Narayana Guru

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ABSTRACT

Sree Narayana Gurus (1855-1928) profound and multifaceted impact on the socio cultural, educational, philosophical and religious realms are well accepted and appreciated by scholars all over the world. Sree Narayana Guru, the prophet of new world, as an Advaiti and a Yogi extracted his doctrine from Vedic and Agamic system of knowledge that he used to transform the individual and the society. Guru was an embodiment of the ideal of service to God in the poor. This service he has rendered as part of his yogic practices and advice others to follow this spiritual Yoga tradition. According to the Indian tradition the inherent spirituality of a person can experience or realize the truth purification of mind. To achieve this one need a strict discipline. A set of practices like Fivefold purities (sudhipanchaka -Kaya, vak, Manas, indriya griha), Five great sacrifices (dharmapanchaka- that is responsibility to the absolute, to our ancestors, natural phenomena, to the living beings, to the fellow humans) and eight noblepath etc.. Prescribed by Sree Narayana Guru. There are more than sixty works composed by See Narayana Guru in Malayalam Tamil and Sanskrit languages. All these works are classified as Stotra, Philosophy, translation, prose etc , Through these works Guru has narrated different aspects of Yoga like karma, jnana, bhakti, raja , sabda , sivarajayoga and so on. While closely study these works in the light of of ashtangayoga as narrated by Patanjali and ashtangamarga of Buddha it's easy to trace number of works of Guru that contributed for the explanation of yama niyama I e ahimsa,satya, astheya, brahmacharya, aparigraha, saoucha santhosh, tapa, swadhyay eswarapranidhana etc. The followings are some important works composed in this direction. They are Geevakarunya panchajam, Anukampadasakam, Nirvruttipanchakan, Sadacharam, Municharya panchakam, Janani navaratna manjari, Pindanandi Swanubhavageeti etc. This paper is an attempt to present Yoga-Narration and Practice of Sree Narayana Guru with special reference to the work Darsanamala.

Key words: Sree Narayana Guru, Darsanamala Bhakti,Karma,Jnana, Raja, Yoga

Paper No 8.05: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Yoga and Meditation - A Catalyst of Work-Life Balance

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ABSTRACT

Both yoga and meditation act as two eyes for successfully leading our life in today's competitive world. They play a remarkable role in managing present human being's busiest life. Implementation of yoga and meditation practices helps a human being in overcoming several problems and could be able to attain goals in our life. Due to severe growth in competition, human beings are losing their patience, tolerance, life values, etc. Due to present competition in the world, today we are finding more increase in clashes in families, unrest, divorce, deaths, suicides, etc rates were taking place due to not having proper skills to manage both personal and professional life and becoming stressful, anxiety, nervous, panic, etc. From the literature review, we can understand there is a significant relationship between the present competitive world and the life mode of employees' work life. We found there are many reasons and measures for the work-life balance. The main objective is to know yoga and meditation evolution, their practices, and how yoga and meditation help in balancing work and life.

Data concerning statistics about yoga & meditation and work-life balance was collected from authentic secondary sources, published articles, books, websites, magazines, and scriptures, etc. From the simple method of comparing valuable statistical data, we have found that different types of yoga & meditation practices play an important role in solving the work-life balance problems of employees. It is evident that yoga and meditation act as a catalyst to balance work and life.

Keywords: Yoga and Meditation, Work-life Balance, Holistic Work-life Balance, Catalyst.

Paper No. 8.06: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Yoga for Sexual Health

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ABSTRACT

Purushartha means “for the objective of self.” The original Kama Sutra texts suggested three pillars, Dharma, Artha, Kama, and they are interlinked. Kama denotes longing and desire for pleasures that drives human behaviour. A life without pleasure and enjoyment is without significance and sexuality is one of them.

When one is free from sexual disorders, one obtains the right kind of pleasure during sexual intercourse that provides satisfactory intimacy. However, not all experiences are smooth sailing. Good kama cannot be fulfilled when one is facing sexual defects. This is when right remedy should be sought. Yoga techniques are one remedy to obtain satisfactory sexual results from a yogic perspective. Asanas strengthens one’s pelvic muscles, other parts of body, improves blood circulation, stimulates reproductive organs, and builds endurance and stamina. Pranayama and meditation in controlled breathing helps to relax the body and motivate one to be aware of the sensations in their body in the present moment. Asanas, pranayama and meditation are parts of 8 limbs of Yoga which purify our Koshas (5 sheaths of soul). Regular practice of yoga and meditation help in balancing and maintaining dhatu. The seven dhatus are made up of rasa, rakta, mamsa, meda, asthi, majja and shukra. Out of these seven dhatus, shukra is essential and active during sexual intercourse. This is the reproductive fluid that provides profound strength to one body and is mainly involved in the creation of new life.

Keywords: Kama, sexual disorders, yoga, asanas, pranayama, meditation, mined.

Paper No. 8.07: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Nadi Pareeksha – Tool for diagnosis

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ABSTRACT

The Ayurveda system of medicine emphasizes more on diagnosis before initiating treatment. There are different types of examination mentioned in Ayurveda like trividha pareeksha, chaturvidha pareeksha, ashtavidha pareeksha dashavidha pareeksha and so on. Nadi pareeksha is one of the ancient methods of examination mentioned under the heading of Ashtavidha Pareeksha. The word nadi imparts so many other meanings other than the pulse in ancient samhitas. Nadi as a means of diagnosis was brought into practice by Acharya Sharangadhara during the 13th century. Concepts of Nadi are also found in other ancient books like Yogarathnakara, Bhavaprakasha, Nadi Pariksha by Ravan samhita, Nadivigyan by Kanad.

From ancient times pulse or Nadi was recognized as the most fundamental sign of life. The early physician paid the greatest attention to the character of the pulse to ascertain the health and the disease condition. Nadi pareeksha is the safest, fastest, and most effective diagnostic tool, which reflects the doshas (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) fluctuations in the body. The Doshas constantly change by the influence of thoughts, actions, foods, diseases, and also by diurnal variations. There is a precise description of dosha predominance in the texts which can be sensed from specific locations on the radial artery. The speed, stability, and gati of the pulse vary with the aggravated doshas, and assessing such variations with Nadi Pariksha is an art gained by the practice.

Nadi pareeksha vidhi and its role in diagnosis will be presented as a full paper in Seminar.

Keywords: Nadi Pareeksha, Dosha, Ashtavidha pareeksha, Ayurveda.

Paper No. 8.08: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Exploring Indigenous Practices with Western Consciousness

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ABSTRACT

Indigenous approach to understand human psyche is evident. Cross Cultural Approach studies cultural influence on cognitive aspects to human mind. Culture directs to the value system within the individual which intern helps in molding the personality of a person. The personality of an individual has two aspects to influence individual i.e., Orientation to the behaviour and Direction to the behaviour.

‘Individual’, ‘Interaction’, ‘Institution’ and ‘Ideology’ are the “4 I model” through which culture can be studied. Individual model deals with quest for Self, Self-Identity and understanding of the Self. It is in both surface and source levels. Interaction model refers to interaction with in, with society and with the environment. Institution model helps in analyzing influence of a specific establishment of law or system in order to keep the harmony between the individuals or group. Ideology refers to the philosophical aspects of a culture. This model is deeper in its nature.

To elucidate this model with some examples, Upanayana samskara and Vrata Chatustaya can be analyzed with individual model. Karma Meemasa will help in understanding more about interaction model. Varnashrama systems enlighten us with institution model and concept of Dhrama can be reviewed with the model of ideology. The present paper explores cultural model based on the theoretical and empirical approach to look the above said issue with indigenous root.

Keywords: Indigenous practices. Understanding human behaviour.

Paper No.8.09: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

सूतसंहितायाम् अष्टाङ्गयोगः

महेश्वरी एच्

शोधच्छात्रा, अद्वैतवेदान्तः राष्ट्रियसंस्कृतविश्वविद्यालयः

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धर्मार्थकाममोक्षाख्यानां चतुर्विधपुरुषार्थानां साधनाय नैके मार्गाः उपदिष्टाः दर्शनेषु । भक्त्या, कर्मणा, ज्ञानकर्मसमुच्चयेन, योगमार्गेण, केवलेन ज्ञानेन इत्यादयः मार्गाः । तत्र ज्ञानादेव हि कैवल्यम् इति श्रुत्या ज्ञानादेव मोक्ष इति वेदान्तिनां राद्धान्तः । योगमार्गेणापि शक्य इति केषाञ्चित् मतम् । पतञ्जलिप्रणीते पातञ्जलयोगदर्शने तल्लक्ष्यावाप्तये सोपानमार्गेण अष्टाङ्गयोगः प्रतिपादितः । स च सोपानक्रमः क्रमेण ज्ञानमार्गं प्रदर्श्य मोक्षावाप्तये कारणं भवति । अयमष्टाङ्गयोगः सूतसंहितायामपि उल्लिखितो वर्तते । सम्प्रपि जगति योग इत्यनेन आसन-प्राणायामौ एव झटिति बुद्ध्यावायान्ति । यतोहि तावुभावेव प्रत्यक्षं प्रतिभासतः । प्रत्यक्षयोः द्वयोः अङ्गयोरभ्यासेन मोक्षः असाध्यः दुष्करश्च ।

व्यासविरचितेषु अष्टादशपुराणेषु बृहत्तममिति प्रसिद्धं स्कन्दपुराणम् । इदं च खण्ड-संहिताभेदेन द्विधा विभक्तम् । सनत्कुमार-सूत-शङ्कर-वैष्णव-ब्रह्म-सौरसंहितासु षट्सु अन्यतमा, द्वितीया च सूतसंहिता । इयं संहिता षड् सहस्रश्लोकयुता (६०००), चतुर्भिः खण्डैः प्रविभक्ता, शैवधर्ममेव सर्वतोभावेन प्रतिपादयति । तत्र द्वितीये ज्ञानयोगखण्डे अष्टाङ्गयोगः त्रयोदशाध्यायतः - विंशत्यध्यायपर्यन्तम् अष्टस्वध्यायेषु प्रत्येकम् अङ्गः एकैकस्मिन्नध्याये निरूपितः । ईश्वर एव अमुमष्टाङ्गयोगम् उपदिशति ।

अथातः सम्प्रवक्ष्यामि तवाष्टाङ्गानि सुव्रत ।

यमश्च नियमश्चैव तथैवासनमेव च ॥

प्राणायामस्तथा विप्र प्रत्याहारस्तथा परः ।

धारणा च तथा ध्यानं समाधिश्चाष्टमो मुने ॥ इति ।

योगशास्त्रे प्रतिपादितेषु अष्टस्वङ्गेषु नामभेदो न वर्तते । परन्तु योगशास्त्रे यमनिमये पञ्च-पञ्चसंख्याभिः यथा विभक्ताः, तथात्र प्रत्येकं यम-नियमाङ्गौ दशधा विभक्ताः । यश्च सूतसंहितायां प्रतिपादितरीत्या अष्टानां योगाङ्गानाम् अभ्यासं करोति स च अवश्यं मोक्षं प्राप्नोतीत्यत्र नास्ति संशयः । यः इमं ज्ञानयोगखण्डम् अत्यन्तमासक्त्या शुभे दिने पारायणं कुरुते तस्य पुनर्जन्म नास्ति, साक्षात् मोक्ष एव इति । यदि पारायणकर्ता ज्ञानार्थी तर्हि ज्ञानमाप्नोति, सुखार्थी चेत् सुखं, जयार्थी चेत् जयं, वेदकमी चेत् वेदार्थं, राज्यकामी चेत् राज्यम् एवं यया कामनया पारायणं क्रियते सा कामना सम्पूर्यते इति खण्डस्यान्ते फलश्रुतिरपि प्रोक्ता ईश्वरेण ।

Key words – अष्टाङ्गयोगः, पुराणम्, सूतसंहिता

Paper No.8.10: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

MULTIPLE THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTIONS OF YOGA ON PARKINSONISM IN INDIA AND ACROSS THE GLOBE - A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

An age-old practice of India's treasured gift to the world is YOGA. Its harmonizing effects of science and spirituality are globally used in body-mind therapies. This study is an overview of multiple therapeutic yogic methods used for the well-being of Parkinson's Disease (PD) people across the world as well as in India. Adequate studies are carried out for improving the daily life of PD people to reduce dependency. Data is collected from various sources worked by different researchers according to their findings over the past 12 years.

The systematic review explains the general health improvement and quality of life including sound sleep and functioning of cerebral and somatic coordination through the intervention of yoga application. Special interest was taken in the majority of the study for the blood supply to the brain to stabilize the body-mind coordination. Statistical analysis and estimated results with the different sample groups are included. Multiple pieces of evidence suggest it is worth improving one's health, which is a priceless treasure. There is a lack of regular yoga practices, which can be modified, improved, and applied systematically in day today's life.

Keywords: Yoga, Therapy, and Parkinson's Disease.

Paper No.8.11: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Pulmonary Function and Immunological Assessment of Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) undergoing Yoga therapy

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a progressive lung disease characterized by airflow limitation and airway inflammation. Studies on the effect of yoga therapy in the management of COPD have demonstrated improved pulmonary function in COPD patients. However, there has been no study on the immunological effects of Yoga practice in COPD patients. The current study aims on the assessment of immunological and pulmonary function changes post yoga intervention in COPD patients as well as in healthy individuals. Yoga therapy has emerged as important complementary alternative therapies for many chronic diseases.

Methods: The study was conducted on 36 subjects who were divided into four groups as follows; healthy individuals without intervention, healthy individuals with intervention, COPD patients without intervention and COPD patients with intervention. Intervention groups followed yogic practices, such as 1 kriya, 12 yogasanas, 3 pranayama, 2 relaxations and 1 meditation for three months. Pulmonary function test were done before and after intervention. Blood samples were collected before and after intervention and subjected to immunological analysis by ELISA technique.

Results: Changes in the serum Immunoglobulin (IgG2) levels are seen in COPD patient upon yoga treatment when compared to control group and COPD patient without yoga intervention. Paired t-test Conform that difference in the mean level of pulmonary function forced vital capacity (FVC), forced expiratory volume (FEV₁) is found statistically significant, in COPD patient post yoga intervention.

Conclusion: The study demonstrated that changes in the levels of serum IgG2 in COPD patients associated of yoga intervention when compared to those without intervention. The study suggested that yoga training has a positive effect on improving lung function

Keywords: Yoga Therapy, COPD, immunology, pulmonary function, Lungs disease

Paper No.8.12: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Simple Home Solutions to the Complex Health issues – A review of Dr. BRC's approach.

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ABSTRACT

Health is Wealth. There are several traditional and natural ways of preventing, managing and curing of several diseases which have largely thrown to the backseat due to so called modern medicine; just like English language has virtually thrown hundreds of languages of the world. However modern medicine has failed to address several health related issues in effective and cost effective free from side effects. As such it only addresses the symptoms of the problem and do not attack the roots.

Over and above, the approach looks to be atrocious when compared to the natural and simple options available. In particular, the approach of Dr. Biswaroop Roy Chowdhury (Dr.BRC) is not only simple and practicable at home without getting hospitalized, but also effective, without any side effects. The solutions provided by Dr. BRC are nature based, with hardly any side effects. It includes solution for Diabetes Type I and II, heart problems, PCOD, thyroid, corona, thalassemia etc. This paper gives a brief overview of Dr. BRCs approach which largely is yoga and diet based.

Keywords: Corona, Diabetes, thalassemia, thyroid, PCOD, diet, yoga.

Paper No.8.13: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

पुराणसाहित्ये अष्टाङ्गयोगः

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ABSTRACT

भगवतसाक्षात्कार सम्पादनाय समाध्यवस्था सम्प्राप्तये जानिना कः उपायः अनुसरणीयः इति शङ्कायां यम - नियम - आसन - प्राणायाम - प्रत्याहार - धारण - ध्यान - समाधिलक्षण अष्टाङ्गयोगः कपिलेन निरूपितः। कः एषः अष्टाङ्गयोगः ? किं तत् स्वरूपं ? के के तस्य प्रभेदाः ? इति शङ्कायां विषये भगवान् कपिलः स्व मातुः देवहृत्याः सांख्यतत्वोपदेश अवसरे यम - नियमादि अष्टाङ्गयोगं परिचाययति ॥

विषयः :- भागवते तृतीयस्कन्दे :-

योगस्य लक्षणं वक्षे स बीजस्य नृपात्मजे।

मनोयेनैव विधिना प्रपन्नं याति सतत्पतं ॥

इत्यादि श्लोकेषु अध्यायसमाप्तिपर्यन्तं सविस्तरं निपुणतरं अष्टाङ्गयोगः निरूपितं वर्तते । यानि तावत् यम - नियमाद्यनुष्ठानद्वारा प्राणायाम प्रत्याहारद्याभ्या शोत्रादि बहिरिन्द्रियैः सह मानसः नियंत्रणं सम्पाद्य धारण ध्यानयोः क्रमेण भगवतः एकैकं अङ्गं समग्रं भगवद्रूपं च अवलोकयन् ततः तदनुग्रहेण समाधिं ततः तत्र भगवतः अप्राकृतं सच्चिदानन्द रूपं साक्षात् करोति इत्येवं भागवतादि ग्रन्थेषु अष्टाङ्गयोगः निरूपितः वर्तते ॥

उद्देशः :-

अनित्यत्वात् सुदुःखत्वात् न धर्माद्याः परं सुखम् ।

मोक्षमेव परानन्दः संसारे परिवर्ततां ॥

अस्य श्लोकस्य अयं भावः धर्म - अर्थ - कामा मोक्षाख्याः चतुर्विध पुरुषार्थाः लोके प्रसि तत्र प्राणवृतां धर्म अर्थ कामाः न परमपुरुषार्थाः कुतः ? असत्यत्वात् सुदुःखत्वात् धर्म धर्म अर्थ कामाः जन्यं सुखं तावत् न नित्यं । धर्माचरणेन स्वर्गं गताः अपि पुनरावर्तन्ते एव अर्थ काम जन्य सुखस्यापि अनित्यत्वं दुःख मिश्रितत्वं च सुप्रसिद्धमेव । तस्मात् संसारे परिवर्ततां जन्तूनां मोक्षं एव परमपुरुषार्थः इति।

प्रयोजनं एवं उपसंहारः :-

तथा च " सुखमेव मे स्यात् , दुःखं मनागपि मा भूत् " इति लोकानां सर्वापेक्षितां या मोक्षः सुख विषयिका या कामना तस्याः अवाप्तिः तावत् अष्टाङ्गयोगाभ्यासं विना अष्टाङ्गयोगस्वरूपस्य समीचीन ज्ञानं विना नैव संभवति

Paper No.8.14: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Science of Spirituality and the Vedic Varnashrama System

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ABSTRACT

It is normally said that where science ends, the spirituality (aadyatma) begins. Why is it said so? What are the limitations of science/technology when compared to spirituality? This paper scientifically narrates with the help of logic the application of well-known theories of modern science like the principle of mutual convertibility, thermodynamic laws etc., as to what is spirituality, what is the physiology involved in the process of aadyatma (spirituality)? The paper also explains as to what are the qualities of a person involved in spirituality and the benefits of the same.

Further, in spiritual terms, the paper tries to explain what is meant by ashrama, varnashrama, and how the vedic varnashrama system is related to the spiritual practices and not mere job one does to fill his/her stomach or profession.

Keywords: yoga, spirituality, varnashrama, science

Paper No.8.15: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

EFFECT OF INSPIRATORY MUSCLE TRAINING ON RESPIRATORY MUSCLE STRENGTH IN INSTITUTIONALIZED GERIATRIC PATIENTS – PRE AND POST INTERVENTIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Institutionalization factors like precarious social support, low income and the burden of increased spending for medical and health needs of geriatric patient have been seen observed on the greater extent in last three years. Aging may lead to ample number of physiological changes leading to deterioration of systemic functioning of the body, among which reduction in lung capacity can be highlighted here that can be due to reduced respiratory muscle strength over the period of time and is relevant to the clinical situation of elderly patients where age within 65 to 85 year is most likely to be affected. It is necessary to study the importance of inspiratory muscle training to improve the respiratory muscle strength which is less in institutionalized elderly people. Thus, the current study aimed to know the effect of inspiratory muscle training on respiratory muscle strength in institutionalized elderly people.

About 50 subjects (both male and female) between the age group of 40-70 years with BMI between 20-30 were included. An Inspiratory Muscle Training using Spirometer as well as Volumetric Inspiratory spirometer by SPIRO-BALL was carried out for 4 months. Results of the study showed the statistically significant improvement in the post mean values of respiratory rate (RR), SpO₂, Inspiratory Capacity (IC) and Peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) with $p < 0.05$. Hence the study concluded that the respiratory muscle training is beneficial for improving respiratory muscle strength in institutionalized geriatric patients.

Keywords: Institutionalized Geriatric Population, Inspiratory Muscle Training & Respiratory Muscle Strength.

Paper No.8.16: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

EFFECT OF FLEXIBILITY EXERCISES WITH MUSCLE ENERGY TECHNIQUES IN IMPROVEMENT OF GAIT IN PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON DISEASE - CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a common chronic neurodegenerative disease affecting 1% of the population over 60 years of age with incidence and prevalence 1.5 to 2.0 times higher in men than in women. PD affects physical, mental and psychosocial health with the mobility and gait dysfunction being the major issues limiting their daily life activities and participation in society. The aim of the study was to observe and analyse the effect of flexibility exercises with muscle energy techniques (MET) to improve the gait in Parkinson patients.

Four patients underwent flexibility exercise training with Muscle Energy Techniques for lower limbs including the antigravity muscles (quadriceps and gastrocnemius-soleus), 45 minutes per session, 5 days a week for 12 weeks. Gait parameters of cadence and average step length were measured for outcome at baseline and at the end of 12 weeks. The results showed statistically significant difference in the pre and post mean values of cadence ($p < 0.05$) but showed non-significant difference in the average step length mean values. Thus, the study concluded that Flexibility exercises with Muscle Energy Techniques may reduce the cadence while walking in patients with Parkinson disease and thereby improve mobility and gait.

Keywords: Flexibility Exercises, Muscle Energy Techniques, Step Length, Cadence, Parkinson Disease.

Paper No.8.17: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

EFFECT OF STRUCTURED CARDIO-RESPIRATORY FITNESS PROTOCOL VERSUS CONVENTIONAL EXERCISE PROGRAMME ON PHYSICAL FUNCTION AND PERFORMANCE IN GERIATRIC POPULATION – QUASI EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Cardio respiratory fitness is the ability of circulatory and respiratory system to provide oxygen to skeletal muscle to utilize the oxygen during prolonged moderate to vigorous physical activity. Aging is associated with decrease lung function and respiratory muscle strength during at a rate of 8 to 15% per decade of life after 50 years of age. The deficit in respiratory muscle strength affects physical performance leading to diminish in exercise tolerance, decorations of gait, and decrease of quality of life with advancing age. The reduction of respiratory muscle function in the elderly thus makes this population vulnerable to disease and disability. Effects of Cardio respiratory fitness protocol versus conventional physiotherapy programme has to be studied on physical function and performance in geriatric population.

A quasi experimental study was done. There was statistically significant improvement in the variables of pre and post mean values in both control and experimental group. The Post mean values of Heart Rate, Respiratory Rate, Peak Expiratory Flow Rate, Borg scale in geriatric patients with p values $p < 0.005$ in experimental group when compared to control group. Thus this study concluded that the Structured cardio respiratory fitness protocol training have statistically significant improvement on Physical function and performance in geriatric population and Structured cardio respiratory fitness protocol statistically improvement in Heart Rate (HR), Respiratory Rate (RR), Peak expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) and Borg-RPE scale which reflects in Physical function and performance in geriatric patients.

Key words: Geriatric Population, Structured Cardiorespiratory Fitness Protocol, Physical Function.

Paper No.8.18: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

EFFECT OF EXTRACORPOREAL SHOCK WAVE THERAPY IN CONJUNCTION WITH KINETIC CHAIN BASED EXERCISES ON PAIN AND KINESIOPHOBIA IN PARTICIPANTS OF SUBACROMIAL PAIN SYNDROME -A CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Sub acromial pain syndrome (SAPS) is defined as all non-traumatic, usually unilateral, shoulder problems that cause pain, localized around the acromion, SAPS can be treated non-operatively; Exercise therapy should be specific and should be of low intensity and high frequency with postural correction. Also the calcifications occurring in the adhesion area of the coraco acromial ligament influence the acromion morphology and may lead to Sub acromial impingement. As extra corporeal shockwave treatment (ESWT) method is influential on the resolution of the calcification and stimulating the tissue recovery and adding kinetic chain based exercises could help for early recovery and improvement in pain reduction and fear related with pain in the shoulder. In this scenario it is needed for us to develop a better treatment protocol with biomechanical consideration with various myokinetic chains acting in and around the shoulder. This study aims to investigate the effect of extracorporeal shock wave therapy on pain and kinesiophobia along with kinetic chain based exercises in participants of subacromial pain syndrome.

Key words: Extra corporeal shock wave therapy (ESWT), kinetic chain based exercises. N.P.RS (numeric pain rating scale), Tampa scale of kinesiophobia (TSK), sub acromial pain syndrome, (S.A.P.S), sub acromial impingement syndrome.

Paper No.8.19: Yoga and Naturopathy Practices

Meditation Intervention and Health Benefits

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays people feel flustered because of the pressures that they face and hence stress is an inevitable part of a busy modern life. Stress, that is unchecked, can contribute to many health problems and interfere with your work-life balance. One of the easiest and achievable stress relieving techniques is meditation. Meditation is a way to train your mind. It teaches you how to respond, rather than react to situations in your modern life. It is a practice in which you focus your attention inwards to reach a state of deep relaxation. It helps to improve physical and emotional health; raises the happiness quotient and sustains a positive state of mind and better management of day-to-day activities. The purpose of this study is to highlight the health benefits of real meditation intervention for the people. Although research studies have shown that long term guided meditation intervention have positive effects on the people, the research on effects of real meditation in transforming the life of the people is limited. The objective of the study include highlighting the health benefits if meditation intervention for the people, to create awareness on the process of meditation leading a better life in terms of Karma principle and to create awareness on the myths on meditation.

This is an exploratory study based on secondary data. Research studies examining the benefits of meditation on physical and emotional health indicate a decline in anxiety levels, depression, stress cortisol hormone levels and blood pressure. They revealed the positive relationship between meditation and increased performance in cognitive function such as awareness, attention, memory and working efficiency. The breath focus meditation, mindfulness meditation are panacea for health hazardous elements. The quality of your mind influences the quality of your life. So, the power of meditation is to know and master your mind and this affects everything in your life positively.

Keywords: Meditation, Intervention, Stress.

Paper No. 9.01- Shastra and Darshanas:

ಆಗಮಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ (ಯೋಗದೀಪಿಕಾನುಸಾರಿ)

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ABSTRACT

'ಪ್ರತಿಮಾಸ್ವಪ್ನಬುದ್ಧಾನಾಂ' ಎಂಬಂತೆ ಬಾಹ್ಯದೃಷ್ಟಿಗೆ ಅಗೋಚರವಾದ ಪರತತ್ವವನ್ನು ಆರಾಧಿಸಲು ಪ್ರತಿಮೆಯ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಮೆಯೇ ದೇವರಲ್ಲಿ, ಕಿಂತು ಪ್ರತಿಮೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ದೇವತಾಸನ್ನಿಧಾನ. ಒಂದೇ ಕಲ್ಲಿನ ಒಂದು ತುಂಡು ಎಲ್ಲರ ಕಾಲಿನ ಆಘಾತಕ್ಕೊಳಗಾಗುವ ಮೆಟ್ಟಿಲಾದರೆ ಅದೇ ಕಲ್ಲಿನ ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಭಾಗೆ ಎಲ್ಲರಿಂದ ಆರಾಧ್ಯವಾದ ಪ್ರತಿಮೆಯಾಗುವುದು. ಜಡವಾದ ಪ್ರತಿಮೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ದೇವತಾಶಕ್ತಿಯ ಸಾನ್ನಿಧ್ಯಸ್ವಾಪನೆಗೆ ಜ್ಞಾನಿಗಳು ವಿವಿಧ ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿರುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ವೈಷ್ಣವಮತಕ್ಕನುಸಾರವಾಗಿ ಸ್ನಾನ ಸಂಧ್ಯಾವಂದನೆ, ದೇವಾಲಯ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ, ದೇವತಾ ಅರ್ಚನೆ ಮೊದಲಾದವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಬೆಳಕುಚೆಲ್ಲುವ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರೀನಾರಾಯಣ ಪಂಡಿತಾಚಾರ್ಯರು ರಚಿಸಿದ ಯೋಗದೀಪಿಕಾ ಗ್ರಂಥವೂ ಒಂದು. ಇದರ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯು ಸಾಧಕರಿಗೆ ಬಹು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೊಡುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಶಯವಿಲ್ಲ.

ಈ ಗ್ರಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ೧೦ ಪಟಲಗಳಿವೆ. ಶ್ರೀಮಧ್ವಾಚಾರ್ಯರು ರಚಿಸಿದ ತಂತ್ರಸಾರಸಂಗ್ರಹ ಎಂಬ ಗ್ರಂಥವು ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಮೂಲವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳಿದ ಕೆಲವು ವಿಷಯಗಳ ವಿವರಣೆಗಳು ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಲಭ್ಯವಾಗಿವೆ.

ಈ ಗ್ರಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ೧ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಷ್ಯದೀಕ್ಷೆಯನ್ನೂ, ೨ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಲ್ಲಿ ದೇಹಶುದ್ಧಿ ನ್ಯಾಸ ಸಂಧ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ೩ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಶೌಚಾದಿಗಳನ್ನೂ ಪೂಜಾವಿಧಾನವನ್ನೂ ಹೇಳಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ೪ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಿಂದಿನ ಮೂರು ಪಟಲಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳಿದ ವಿಷಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಬೆಂಬಲವಿ ಸದಾಚಾರಸ್ತೃತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ೫ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾಗಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರಕವಾಗಿ ಅಗ್ನಿಮುಖದ ವಿವರಗಳು ಸಿಗುತ್ತವೆ. ೬ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಿಂದ ಆರಂಭಿಸಿ ೯ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದವರೆಗೆ ಮಂಟಪಸಂಸ್ಕಾರ, ಚಕ್ರಾಬ್ಜಮಂಡಲ ರಚನೆ, ಪೂಜಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ೧೦ನೆಯ ಪಟಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನುಸಂಧಾನ ಹಾಗೂ ಧ್ಯಾನದ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ವಿವೇಚಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿ ಯೋಗದೀಪಿಕಾವು ಆಗಮಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಕೊಡುಗೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿಯ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗಳು ಸರ್ವರಿಗೂ ಆದರಣೀಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

Keywords: agama shastra, ChakrabjamaNdala, Mantapa sanskaara

Paper No. 9.02- Shastra and Darshanas:

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ABSTRACT

ಸುಂದರ ಸುಭದ್ರ ಜೀವನದ ಕಟ್ಟಡದ ತಳಪಾಯ, ಹೊಸ ಚಿಗುರಿನ ಜೀವನದ ಸಸಿಗೆ ಸೂರ್ಯನ ಬೆಳಕು, ಅಂಧಕಾರದಿಂದ ತತ್ತರಿಸುವವರಿಗೆ ಬೆಳಕಿನ ಪ್ರಭೆ ಹೀಗೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವರ್ಗದವರಿಗೂ ಪ್ರೋಫಕವಾಗಿವೆ ಈ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಗಳು. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ಇದರ ಬಗೆಗಿನ ಅರಿವು ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಬೇಕೇ ಬೇಕು. ಗುರಿಯಿಲ್ಲದ ಜೀವನ, ಗುರು ಇಲ್ಲದ ವಿದ್ಯೆ ಹೇಗೆ ಅನರ್ಥಕಾರಿಯೋ ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥವನ್ನು ಅರಿಯದ ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಬದುಕು ಅನರ್ಥಕ.

ಹೀಗೆ ಎಲ್ಲರ ಜೀವನದ ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿ ನಿವೃತ್ತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರೇರಕವಾದ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥ ಎಂದರೆ ಏನು ಎಂಬ ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆಗೆ 'ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥ' ಎಂಬ ಪದವೇ ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಉತ್ತರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಪುರುಷಸ್ಯ ಅರ್ಥಃ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಃ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಎರಡು ಶಬ್ದಗಳು ಇವೆ. ಪುರುಷ ಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಪುರುಷ ಎಂದೂ, ಅರ್ಥ ಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನವೆಂದೂ ಅರ್ಥ. ಒಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥ ಎಂದರೆ ಪುರುಷನಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು ಎಂದು ಅರ್ಥ. ಅಥವಾ ಪುರುಷನ ಅಭ್ಯುದಯಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವಾದವುಗಳು ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಗಳು ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾದ ಅರ್ಥ.

ಇಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಪುರುಷಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಕೇವಲ ಮೇಲ್ (ಗಂಡಸು) ಎಂದಷ್ಟೇ ಅರ್ಥವಲ್ಲ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀಯರೂ ಇದರಿಂದ ವಾಚ್ಯರಾಗುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಶ್ರೀಕೃಷ್ಣನು ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪುರಿ ಶೇತೇ ಇತಿ ಪುರುಷ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಜೀವ ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿರುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ಮಹಿಳೆಯರು ಹಾಗೂ ಮಹನೀಯರು (ಗಂಡಸರು) ಎಲ್ಲರಿಗೂ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ್ದು ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದುಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಇಂತಹ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಲೌಕಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಅಲೌಕಿಕ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರಕಾರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಣ್ಣಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಂಡರೆ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರೇಯಸ್ಸನ್ನು ಸಂಪಾದಿಸಬಹುದು.

ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಸುಹೊಕ್ಕಾಗಿರುವ ಈ ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಚಿಂತನೆ ಹಾಗೂ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಅನುಭವಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಹಾಗೂ ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಗಳು ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಆ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವಿಧ ಆಯಾಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ನಡೆಸಿ ನಿರ್ಣಯಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

Keywords: Indian Classical literature, Purushartha, Darma, artha, kama, moksha,

Paper No. 9.03- Shastra and Darshanas:

ತಂತ್ರ-ಆಗಮ

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ABSTRACT

ನಮ್ಮಪ್ರಾಚೀನರು ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು ಆಗಮ ಶಬ್ದದಿಂದಲೇ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಿ ಬಳಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರು. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ 'ತಂತ್ರಂ ವೈ ವೇದಸಮಿತಂ' ಎಂದು ಘೋಷಿಸಿದರು.ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ತಂತ್ರ-ಆಗಮ ಒಂದೇ ಅರ್ಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಂದಿರತಕ್ಕ ಪದಗಳು.

ವೇದವು ಅನಂತ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಹಾಗೂ ನಾನಾ ಪ್ರಮೇಯಗಳ ಪುಂಜವಾದರೆ, ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕಪುಂಜವಾಗಿದೆ.

ತಂತ್ರಶಬ್ದದ ನಿರುಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಚೀನಗ್ರಂಥಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೊಗಸಾಗಿ ಈ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರೂಪಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ

'ತನೋತಿ ವಿಫುಲಾನ್ ಅರ್ಥಾನ್ ತತ್ತ್ವಮಂತ್ರಸಮನ್ವಿತಾನ್|

ತ್ರಾಣಂ ಚ ಕುರುತೇ ಯಸ್ಮಾತ್ ತಂತ್ರಮಿತ್ಯಭಿಧೀಯತೇ||

ಅಂದರೆ ತತ್ತ್ವಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಮಂತ್ರದ ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಕೊಟ್ಟು ಸಿದ್ಧಿಯ ದಾರಿಗೆ ನಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಕರೆದೊಯ್ಯುವ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವೇ ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ. ಆಪತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಂಗಾವಲಾಗಿ ಕಾಪಾಡುವ ಸಾಸ್ತ್ರ ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ. ಇಂಥಹ ದೊಡ್ಡ ಗೌರವದ ಮಾತನ್ನು ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನರು ಆಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ 'ವಸಂತೇ ವಸಂತೇ ಪುತ್ರಕಾಮೋ ಯಜೇತ|', ಎಂಬ ಪ್ರಮೇಯವು ನಿರ್ದೇಶಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಅದರ ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಜ್ಞಾನಕ್ಕೆ ನಾವು ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನೇ ಮೊರೆಹೊಕ್ಕಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ (ಭಾರತೀಯ ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ) ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಪಾಶ್ಚಾತ್ಯವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರಾದ ಸರ್ ಜಾನ್ ವುಡ್ ರೋಪ್ ಅವರ ಅನುಭವಾತ್ಮಕ ಮಾತು ಹೀಗಿದೆ. 'Tantra Shasta is a sadhana Shastra, the greatest part of which becomes intelligible only by sadhana.'

ತಂತ್ರಶಾಸ್ತ್ರವು ಒಂದು ಅದ್ಭುತ, ವಿಸ್ಮಯ. ಸಾಧಕರ ಬದುಕಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ದೊಡ್ಡ ವರವೂ ಹೌದು. ಸಾಧನಾ ಬದುಕಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ದಾರಿ-ದೀವಿಗೆ ಇದ್ದಂತೆ. ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹುತರಹದ ಶಾಖೆಗಳು ಇದ್ದ ಹಾಗೆ ತಂತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಬಹಳವಾದ ಶಾಖೆಗಳು, ಮಜಲುಗಳು, ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಭೇದಗಳು ಅಸಂಖ್ಯಾತವಾಗಿವೆ. ಇವುಗಳೆಲ್ಲದರ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾದ ವಿವರಣೆಯೇ ಈ ಲೇಖನ ಮುಖ್ಯವಿಷಯ.

Keywords: ತಂತ್ರ, ವೇದ, ತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಪ್ರಯೋಗ, ಸಾಧನೆ

Paper No. 9.04 – Shastra and Darshana (Uttara Meemamsa or Vedanta)

THE DOCTRINE OF SELF-VALIDITY – THE DVAITA VIEW AS DETAILED IN THE YUKTI MALLIKA

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ABSTRACT

It is strongly defended and stressed that a defect less and self-valid evidence is to be accepted to intuited the truth. As defect less perception is self-valid, so also the Sruti (*Veda*). It is self-valid by itself. Pertinent to this Vadiraja discusses the theory of self-validity of knowledge.

The discussion of the conception *Pramanya* or validity necessarily pre-supposes the explanation of so many aspects. It essentially requires the discussion of what is *Prama* (Know-ledge), *Pramana* (proof-evidence), *Prameya* (object of knowledge), *Pramata* (subject-knower) etc. The basic analysis of knowledge situation is incumbent to be known. *Prama* (knowledge), is something that takes place between a subject or knower that knows and object that is known. It is the cognitive experience that causes awareness of objects. The subject or knower and the process of knowing are purely subjective. Although related with subjective aspects as well as objective-world, they are the two aspects of one and the same spiritual entity. The knower, undoubtedly, needs something for the fruitfulness of his knowing process. And that which makes the knowing process fruitful, is called instrument (*Pramana*). The various systems of philosophy define and describe the nature, origin, scope and number of the concept *Pramana* in different ways.

Here *Pramanyaswatastava* is defined according to *Yuktimllika* of Shri Vadiraja.

Keywords: agama shastra, ChakrabjamaNdala, Mantapa sanskaara

Paper No. 9.05 – Shastra and Darshana

उत्तरमीमांसा - वेदान्तविचारः

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ABSTRACT

भारतीयज्ञानपरम्परायाः जगति अत्युन्नतस्थानं वर्तते। नैकविधाः दार्शनिकाः अस्मत्सुप्रतिथाः। नैकविधानि शास्त्राणि शुशुभिरे । तेषु दार्शनिकवर्येषु २२तमः दार्शनिकधुरंधरः चकास्ति आचार्यः श्रीमध्वाभिधः जगद्गुरुः । अतिमानुषकार्याणिचकार । तेषु अन्यतमावर्तते भारतीयज्ञानसरणेः नूतनदीपवत्प्रद्योतमानग्रन्थरचना । ३७ ग्रन्थान्वयरचयन् । तेषुशिखरप्रायंभवति अनुव्याख्यानम् । उत्तरमीमांसा इति प्रथितानि ब्रह्मसूत्राणि वेदार्थनिर्णायकानि । तादृशस्य वचोविन्यासकर्तृहृदयं प्राकटयन्स्वीये अनुव्याख्याने । एतस्य व्याख्यारत्नः द्वैतवेदान्तपारावारे उदितसुधा । 'सुधावापठनीयावसुधावापालनीया' इत्यस्ति आभाणकम् । एतस्य अस्ति २५ अधिकव्याख्यानानि । तेषु अन्यतमो अस्ति पञ्चिका इति । कुण्डलगिरिआचार्येण विरचिता । आदिमपञ्चा -धिकरणस्य प्रभातिव्याख्या एषा । व्याख्या एषा सरळा सुन्दरानूत्नाच । तत्र जिज्ञासाधिकरणस्य 'पञ्चिकाप्रपञ्चनं' विषयमिमम् अधिकृत्य प्रस्तौमि। अनेन सुधायाः विशेषज्ञानमावहति । सुधामाहात्म्यबोधकपञ्चिकायां तावत्बहत्र व्याकरणविषेशांशाः दृश्यन्ते । तथाहि श्रीमदाचार्यैः तावत् अविद्या ज्ञानेन निवर्तते इति प्रतिपादितम् । परन्तु शङ्कते अविद्या न निवर्तते ब्रह्मविदामपि अविद्यादर्शनादिति। अतःअविद्याबोधकवेदवाक्यानां तावत् अप्रामाण्यमिति । अतः ब्रह्मसाक्षात्कारःअविद्यानिवर्तकः नविवेकमात्रमिति चेन्न । तादृशब्रह्मज्ञानिनां च अवद्या दृश्यते । यदिसाक्षात्कृतब्रह्मणां सद्यः शरीरादिपाते वातपुत्रीयाः सर्वेऽपि आगमाः प्रसज्येरन् इति अवाचन् । अत्रव्याख्यातृणां कौशल्यं चकास्ति। तदभिप्रायस्तु वातागमनवेळायां पुत्रस्य पतनं भवति चेत्तत्किंवातनिदानमिति वदामो वा न तथा ,किन्तुयादृच्छिकम् इति वदन्ति। यद्वा वातपुत्रशब्दौ तद्व्यापारभूतगमनपतनलक्षकौ । नाम वातश्च पुत्रश्च वातपुत्रौ। वातस्यागमन पुत्रस्यपतनमिति भवति। ताविव वातपुत्रीय इति उक्त्वा कथंपाणिनीयं भवति इति समर्थयन्ति । तथाहि 'समासाच्चतद्विषयात्' सूत्रेण इव शब्दस्य प्रयोगेण समासे प्राप्ते ततः इव इत्यस्य प्रयोगेण निर्दिश्यमाने भिन्ने सन्दर्भे समस्तपदात्छप्रत्ययः विधी-यते। काकतालीय इतिवत्वातपुत्रीय इति रूपम्भवति इति बहुधा समर्थितवन्तः ।

Keywords: पञ्चिकायाः प्रपञ्चनम् , सुधायाः कुण्डलगिरिव्याख्यानम्, कुण्डलगिरिमहत्त्वम्

Paper No. 9.06 - Shastra and darshanas

शाब्दबोधे मुख्यविशेष्यविचारः

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ABSTRACT

दृश्यते अनेन इति दर्शनम् दृश्यते इति दर्शनम्। करणार्थे भावार्थे च दर्शनशब्दः प्रयुज्यते। तत्र आस्तिकदर्शनत्वेन पुरस्कृताः साङ्ख्ययोगन्यायवैशेषिक - पूर्वमीमांसा-उत्तरमीमांसाः। तत्र तावत् सर्वैः दार्शनिकैः अपि प्रमाणप्रमेय-प्रमिति चिन्तनम् कृतं विद्यते। जायमान - अनुभवोपपादनार्थं अनेके प्रकाराः कल्पिताः सन्ति।

तत्र प्रमाणचिन्तनावसरे प्रत्यक्षम् अनुमानम्। उपमानं, शब्दः इति प्रमाणचतुष्टयम् अङ्गीक्रियते। नैयायिकैः, मीमांसकैस्तावत् प्रत्यक्षानुमानोपमान - शब्द - अर्थापत्ति - अनुपलब्ध्याख्यानि षट् प्रमाणानि अङ्गीक्रियन्ते। तत्र उभयसम्मतः शब्दः - शब्दप्रमाणस्य प्रयोजनं तावत् शाब्दबोधः। शाब्दबोधश्च केन प्रकारेण जायते इति तैः दार्शनिकैः चिन्तितम्। तत्र पूर्वमीमांसकानां नैयायिकानां च मते विद्यमान शाब्दबोधे मुख्यविशेष्यत्वेन कस्य भानम् इति विचारः प्रस्तूयते।

शाब्दबोधक्रमः इत्थं विद्यते - पदश्रवणं पदार्थोपास्थितिः। ततः वाक्यार्थज्ञानम् इति। तत्र ज्ञाने, तावत् प्रकारता, विशेष्यता, संसर्गता च भासते। शाब्दबोधे मुख्यविशेष्यत्वेन किं भाति इत्यत्र विप्रतिपत्तिः विद्यते। प्रथमान्तोपस्थापितार्थः मुख्यविशेष्यत्वेन भाति इति नैयायिकाः। धात्वर्थः इति वैयाकरणाः। भावना इति मीमांसकाः।

प्रकृते शाब्दबोधे मुख्यविशेष्यत्वेन किं भवतीति नैयासिकमतखण्डनपुरस्सरं मीमांसमतोपपादनं भाट्टरहस्य ग्रन्थानुसारेण क्रियते।

Keywords – भाट्टरहस्यम्, भूषणसारः।

Paper No. 9.07 : Shastra and darshanas

प्राचीनवादप्रक्रिया

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ABSTRACT

सुखदुःखात्मकोऽयं संसारः । एवं द्वन्द्वात्मके अस्मिन् संसारे, सुखेन सहैव दुःखस्य अवस्थानात् सुखं सुष्ठु नानुभूयते । अतः द्वन्द्वात्मकात् अस्मात् संसारात् निवृत्तिर्वर्तते इति आत्यन्तिकी आशा एव भारतीयदर्शनानाम् अन्तरङ्गम् । सा च निवृत्तिः प्रमाणप्रमेयसंशयप्रयोजनादिषोडशपदार्थानां तत्त्वज्ञानादिति प्राचीननैयायिकाः । तेषु षोडशपदार्थेषु वादजल्पवितण्डहेत्वाभासच्छलजातिनिग्रहस्थानानि अन्यतमानि ।

जल्पवितण्डयोः वादिनियमः, प्रतिवादिनियमः, सभापतिनियमः, मध्यस्थनियमः, सदस्यानां नियमश्च एते अवश्यम् अनसर्तव्याः । किन्तु वादकथायां एतेषां आवश्यकता नास्ति । पर्णकुटीरे कस्मिंश्चित् वृक्षविशेषे वा गुरुशिष्यावुपविश्य चर्चा कर्तुं शक्यते । मुमुक्षुः तत्त्वनिर्णयाय, तस्मिन् दार्ढ्यसम्पादनाय च आन्विक्षिकीम् (तर्कशास्त्रं) अभ्यस्येत् । असूयारहितैः गुरुशिष्यसहपाठीभिः सह अन्यैर्शास्त्रज्ञैर्वा मिथो वादो भवतु । वादजल्पवितण्डादि तिसृषु कथासु वाद एव श्रेष्ठः । उक्तञ्च गीतायाम्—अध्यात्मविद्या विद्यानां वादः प्रवदतामहम् इति । यत्र वादः प्रचलति तत्र विशेषतया भगवतः विभूतिरस्ति इत्यर्थः ।

एवं नैयायिकनये प्रमाणवादजल्पादिषोडशपदार्थानां सुष्ठुज्ञानेन तत्तत्पदार्थेषु हेयताबुद्धिरुत्पद्यते । सा बुद्धिः परम्परया मोक्षं प्रति कारणं भवति ।

Keywords: Purushartha, Bhagavadgita, Karma

Paper No. 9.08 : Shastra and darshanas

वादिराजकृतिषु पुरुषार्थचिन्तम्

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ABSTRACT

द्वैतमतसंस्थापकः जगद्गुरुः श्रीमध्वाचार्यः स्वप्रतिपादितजगत्सत्यत्वादि तत्त्वज्ञानप्रसारणाय स्वीय साक्षात् शिष्यान् रजतपीठपुरे अष्टमठेषु नियुज्य पूजार्थं भैष्मीकरार्चितकृष्णप्रतिमां च प्रतिष्ठाप्य प्रस्थानत्रय, प्रकरणग्रन्थ, स्तुतिसुभाषितादिरूप सर्वमूलग्रन्थाञ्छ्रादात् । रूप्यपीठपुरे विद्यमानाष्टमठान्यतमः सोदेमठः । तन्मठप्रथमपरमहंसाः श्रीमद्विष्णुतीर्थाः । तत्परम्परायामेवागतः श्रीमद्वागीशतीर्थप्रियशिष्यः भावीसमीर श्रीमद्वादिराजगुरुसार्वभौमः । ते च “मायीभवैरिणः माध्वराद्धान्तवनचारिणः वचोनुखरिणः सर्वसज्जनवन्दितवादिराजकेसरिणः सर्वैःसज्जनैः प्रत्यहं प्रातः सर्वदा सर्वकार्यारम्भे च संस्मरणीयाः ।

तेन च कुम्भासीक्षेत्रसमीपस्थ हूविनकेरे इति ग्रामे श्रीरामाचार्यदम्पत्योः “गौरीगद्दे” इति केदारैः पुत्रत्वेन अजनि । तच्च केदारजातशिशुरूपपुष्पं श्रीवागीशतीर्थः श्रीकृष्णाङ्घ्रौ सन्यासदीक्षाप्रदानेन समर्पयामास । तेषाञ्च जीवितावधिस्तु विंशत्यधिकशतवर्षपर्यन्तं {मानवीयपूर्णमानायुः} । तादृशपुष्पस्य सुगन्धः आसेतुहिमाचलपर्यन्तम् व्याप्तो भूत्वा मध्वसिद्धान्तं च सर्वत्र विततार । अष्टमेवर्षे एव ते सन्यासदीक्षां स्वीकृतवन्तः । द्वादशाधिकशतवर्ष अस्खलितब्रह्मचर्यं, पादयात्रया एव पौनःपुन्येन देशपर्यटनम् रजतपीठपराधिवासिनः श्रीकृष्णस्य द्वैमासिकपूजा पद्धतिं विहाय द्वैवार्षिक पर्यायपूजाक्रमानुष्ठानं इत्यादि अनेक परिष्काराः, विस्मयाः, विशिष्टकार्याणि च ते कृताः ।

शताधिकग्रन्थप्रणेतृणाम् तेषां युक्तिमल्लिकाख्यः ग्रन्थराजः नवद्युमणिरिव प्रकाशते । पदार्थवबोधस्तु आलोकसहकृतेन प्रमाणते । प्रमाणान्यतम अनुमानरूप युक्त्यादिना दुर्वादिषु निरुत्तरता स्यात् । विश्व शुद्धि भेद गुण फल इति पञ्च सौरभाः, पञ्चसहस्राधिक श्लोकात्मक ग्रन्थः । अनुव्याख्यान, ब्रह्मसूत्रभाष्य, इत्यादिस्थ प्रमेयविचाराः एव अस्मिन् ग्रन्थे प्रबलयुक्त्या प्रतिपाद्यते । अयं च वादग्रन्थः समग्रवैष्णवशास्त्रप्रपञ्चे उन्नतस्थानं अप्राप्नोत् । शास्त्रन्यान् लोकन्यायानपि उपयुज्य वैष्णववेदान्ततत्त्वान् ज्ञातुमिच्छेतृणां अत्यन्त प्रभावकारी भवति अयं स्वतन्त्रग्रन्थः । एवं न्यायरत्नावली, श्रुतितत्त्वप्रकाशिका, हरिभक्तिलता, पाषण्डमतखण्डन, इत्यादि पद्यरूप शास्त्रग्रन्थः । न्यायसुधागुर्वर्धदीपिका, तत्त्वप्रकाशिकागुर्वर्धदीपिका, महाभारततात्पर्यनिर्णयभावप्रकाशिका, महाभारतलक्षालंकार इत्यादिप्रमुखव्याख्यानग्रन्थाः ।

विवरणव्रण , कल्पलता इति द्वौ खण्डनग्रन्थौ ।

रुग्मिणीशविजयः, सरसभारतीविलासः इत्यादि सुन्दर काव्यानि ।

Keywords: Vadiraja, Purushartha, Moksha

Paper No. 9.09 – Shastra and darshana – Tantragama

शब्दप्रमाणनिरूपणम्

मालिनी आर् *

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ABSTRACT

शाब्दाबोधो नाम शब्दज्जायमानो वाक्यार्थबोधः. शाब्दबोधोत्पत्तिक्रमः निरूप्यते- प्रथमतः पदाज्ञानम् अनन्तरं पदानां शक्तिस्मृतिः, अनन्तरं पदार्थोपस्थितिः, अनन्तरं शाब्दबोधः इति। अत्र पदार्थोपस्थितिः नाम वृत्त्या पदजन्यपदार्थोपस्थितिः। वाक्यरूपस्य शब्दस्यलक्षणम् "आप्तोपदेशशब्दः" इति। अथ वाक्यार्थः क इति, शब्दलक्षणविचारः क इति विविधदर्शनानुसरं प्रतिपाद्यते। स्फोटविचारः न्यायदर्शनकारः, मीमांसादर्शनकारः, वेदान्तदर्शनकारः निरकरणविचारः प्रतिपाद्यते। वाक्यार्थबोधे मुख्यविशेषः, आकाङ्क्षाविचारः, योग्यविचारः प्रतिपाद्यते।

न्यायसिद्धान्तमुक्तावल्यां आकाङ्क्षायोग्यतविचारः

न्यायमञ्जरीकाराः उक्तं "अर्थप्रतीतिकरणभुतंश्रोत्रगाह्यंस्तुशब्दप्रमाणामिति"। नीलकण्ठप्रकाशिकः उक्तं "प्रकृतवाक्यार्थगोचरयथार्थज्ञानजन्यवाक्यप्रमाणशब्द" इति। शब्दलक्षणमाणिकारस्तु शब्दखण्डारभ्ये "अथशब्दो निरूप्यते। प्रयोगहेतुभूतार्थतत्त्वज्ञानजन्यः शब्दःप्रमाणम्" इति। वेदान्तपरिभाषणं -"यस्य वाक्यस्य तात्पर्यविषयीभूतः संसर्गो मानान्तरेण न बाध्यते तद्वाक्यं प्रमाणम्" इत्युक्तम्। शब्दशक्तिप्रकाशिकायाम् "अनुभवहेतुः सकलेसाद्यः समुपासितामनुजे। साकङ्क्षासन्नाचस्वार्थयोग्यासरस्वतीदेवी" इत्युक्तम्। आकाङ्क्षाविचारे भट्टपादै "श्रुत्यामिक्षैवशेषोहि नैषांवाक्येनवाजितम्, तदुर्बलप्रमणत्वात्तयाश्रुत्यानिराकृतम्"। तर्कसंग्रहे पदस्य पदान्तरव्यतिरेकप्रयुक्तान्वयानुभावकत्वम् आकाङ्क्षा। योग्यतविचारे तत्त्वचिन्तामणौ उक्तम् "वस्तुतस्तु इतरपदार्थसंसर्गेऽपरपदार्थनिष्ठोत्पन्ताभावप्रतियोगितावच्छेदकधर्मशून्यत्वं योग्यता, लाघवात्शक्यज्ञानत्वच्च" इति। तत्र विद्यमान अंशान्ग्रहित्वा अस्मिन्प्रबन्धे अलिखम्।

Keywords - शब्दलक्षणविचारः, स्फोटविचारः, आकाङ्क्षाविचारः, योग्यतविचारः

Paper No. 9.10: Shastra and darshana/ Tantra

श्रीमदानन्दतीर्थभगवत्पादाचार्यविरचिते अनुव्याख्याने अनुव्याख्यानवृत्त्युक्तदिशा अज्ञानस्य निरूपणम्

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ABSTRACT

भूर्भुवस्वरादिचतुर्दशभुवनात्मकसंख्यातिगब्रह्माण्डकोटीः स्वरोमकूपे सन्निवेश्य सकललोकजनन्या श्रिया सह सर्पतल्पे शयानेन भगवता सृष्टेषु भूलोकखण्डेष्वन्यतमेऽस्मिन् भरतखण्डे जनिमतामस्माकं महद्भागधेयमिदं यदत्र भगवान् तत्तद्युगेष्ववतीर्य बलकार्यं ज्ञानकार्यं च सम्पाद्य स्वभक्तानन्वग्रहीत् । तत्रापि विरिञ्चिपित्रा चराचरकर्त्रा नारायणावतारिणा बादरायणेन सकलवेदार्थविनिर्णयाय प्राणिनां निःश्रेयसे च अध्यायचतुष्टयात्मकं ब्रह्ममीमांसाशास्त्रापरनामधेयं ब्रह्मसूत्रं व्यरचि । तस्यार्थवित्तये व्यासशिष्यः पावनः पवमानः स्वतृतीयावतारे मध्वनाम्ना ख्यातः सज्जनानुद्धिधीर्षुः सूत्रप्रस्थानस्य भाष्य - अणुभाष्य - अनुभाष्य (अनुव्याख्यान) - न्यायविवरणग्रन्थान् अरचयत् । सर्वेऽपि ते ग्रन्थराशयः अध्यात्मविद्यारसिकानां विचारविमर्शकानां जिज्ञासुपिपासूनां ज्ञानतृशं परिहरतीति निश्चप्रचं वक्तुं वयं प्रभवामः ।

तदस्मिन्ग्रन्थे मायावादिशास्त्रे अनुबन्धचतुष्टयेष्वन्यतमः अज्ञानरूपविषयः अनुपपन्नः । तस्मात्तदनुसारि शास्त्रप्रयोजनादिकं न सम्भवति “ अप्रकाशस्वरूपत्वाज्जडेऽज्ञानं न मन्यते ” इत्युदाहृतमूले प्रतिपाद्यते । अज्ञानं तु द्विधा वर्तते । भावरूपमभावरूपं चेति तेषां नयः । तत्र अभावरूपाज्ञानस्य वृत्त्यात्मकत्वात् ज्ञानाज्ञानयोः सहानवस्थानरूपविरोधसद्भावात् जीवे स्थितिः वक्तुं नैव शक्यते । अतः भावरूपाज्ञानमेव जीवावरकतया वक्तव्यं परन्तु तत्र सम्भवति । यतो हि मायावादिमतेन पारमार्थिकं सत् ब्रह्म एकमेव । तदतिरिक्तं सर्वं मिथ्येति राद्धान्तः । अत्र च अज्ञानस्य ब्रह्मातिरिक्तत्वे तस्य मिथ्यात्वेन शास्त्रप्रतिपादितं प्रयोजनादिकमपि मिथ्येति स्यात् । ब्रह्मस्वरूपत्वे तु मिथ्यायाः सस्वरूपत्वात् च ब्रह्मणः निस्स्वरूपत्वादक्यायोगः विरुद्धधर्माधिकरणत्वात् । इत्येवं रूपेण अतिविस्तृततया ग्रन्थे प्रतिपादितम् । तदत्र यथामति यथाशक्ति च निरूपयामि । तदर्थं विश्वविद्यालये प्रचाल्यमाने सम्मेलने अवकाशं कामये ॥

Keywords: Ajnaana. Bhavaroopta Ajnaana , Mithyaa

Paper No. 9.11: Shastra and darshana/ Tantra

तन्त्रज्ञानम्

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ABSTRACT

जगत्यस्मिन् विद्यमानेषु ज्ञानेषु अनन्यतमं ज्ञानं तन्त्रज्ञानं। आधुनिकैः तन्त्रज्ञैः पुरुषः तन्त्रज्ञानेन विना जीवनमेव नास्तीति जगति सिद्धान्तः स्थापितः वर्तते सत्यं तन्त्रज्ञानं जीवननिर्वाहाय अत्यन्त आवश्यकम् । विद्युत्-यानं चलदूरवाणि- गणकयन्त्रं इत्यादि सर्वमपि साधनानि देहस्य आहारमिवाभाति । एतादृश तन्त्रवैभवं पुराणकालेपि आसीत् । व्यासकृत पुराणेतिहासादिषु यावन्ति विज्ञानानि विद्यन्ते तानि तावत् प्रवृद्धमानेस्मिन् जगति एतावत्पर्यन्तं तादृशरीत्या नैवपरिष्कृतमस्तीत्येतत् निश्चयप्रचंचवः ।

विषयेस्मिन् किञ्चित् पश्यामः । कोटिसंख्यावर्षतः पूर्वं रामायणकाले त्रेतायुगे विमानं रमणीयं च तद्विमानं मनोजवम् विमानं पुष्पकं नाम सर्वरत्नविभूषितं ब्रह्मणोऽर्थे कृतं दिव्यं दिवि यद्विधकर्मणा । परेण तपसा लेभे यत्कुबेरः पितामहात् । कुबेरमोजसा जित्वा लेभे तद्राक्षसेश्वरः ॥ विमानं तस्य जग्राह पुष्पकं जयलक्षणम्

पुष्पकविमानमासीदिति श्रुणुमः पुष्पकं च कामगामित्यपि जानीमः । धनदस्य विमानमित्यपि जानीमः । रामायणे पुष्पकमधिकृत्य एवमस्ति

काञ्चनस्तम्भसंवीतं वैदूर्यमणितोरण महाभारते वनपर्वणि विमानस्यान्तः स्थलावकाशः कियदस्तीदिति वर्णनमस्ति

पद्मासनवरं श्रीमत्पुष्पकं विश्वकर्मणा

विहितं चित्रपर्यन्तमातिष्ठत धनाधिपः ॥

तमासीनं महाकायाः शंकुकर्णा महाजनाः

परिवार्योपतिष्ठन्ति यथा देवाः शतक्रतुम् ॥

इत्येव पुष्पकयानस्य कामगामित्वं सहस्राधिक जनानां आश्रयदायित्वं यथेष्ट भोगदातृत्वं रत्न काञ्चनैः विभूषितत्वं इत्यादि नैकगुणाः इतिहासपुराणेषु प्राचीनवज्ञान वैभव वा तन्त्रज्ञानवैदुष्यं वा अदिकृत्य अग्रे किञ्चित्पश्यामः ॥

Keywords: Tantrajnaana, Pushpakavimana, puranam

Paper No. 9.12 – Shastra and darshanas

Geometrical aspects of maṇḍalas in Hindu rituals

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ABSTRACT

Rituals in Āgamas consist of several constituents such as preparing ritual items (dravyas) required for rituals, drawing maṇḍalas, coloring maṇḍalas, invoking deities in maṇḍalas and then worshipping them. Among them drawing maṇḍalas with different geometric shapes are interesting part involved in rituals. Whether it is a Hindu ritual such as Sudarśana-homa, Gaṇapati-homa, etc., or the Buddhist tantric rituals, the constructions of maṇḍalas are as fundamental as the construction of the altars in Vedic sacrifices. Both the altars and maṇḍalas which are related to some or the other kind of rituals, basically comprise geometrical structures.

Geometry in ancient India dates back prior to 800th BCE when altars of different shapes and sizes needed to be constructed in order to perform yāgas. Some common geometrical figures such as triangles, squares, circles, hexagons, etc., were basic structures used in building altars. As a part of performing Vedic rituals, in almost all sacrifices, the tradition of drawing maṇḍalas or yantras is seen. These maṇḍalas being an essential part of the rituals also consist of a few basic geometrical shapes along with a few natural colors filled within. In my paper, I will discuss different geometrical patterns that appear in maṇḍalas, their significance, and their relevance in Āgamas.

Keywords: Āgama, altars, geometry, homa, maṇḍalas, yantra.

Paper No. 9.13 - Shastra and darshanas

ಪ್ರಾಚೀನಭಾರತದ ತೆರಿಗೆ ಕ್ರಮ ಮತ್ತು ಪದ್ಧತಿ.

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ABSTRACT

ರಾಜ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ತೆರಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಮುಖ್ಯ ಆಧಾಯದ ಮೂಲ, ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಜರುಗಳು ತೆರಿಗೆಯಿಂದ ಬಂದ ಹಣದಿಂದಲೇ ರಾಜ್ಯದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಕಾರ್ಯ, ಪ್ರಜಾಪಾಲನೆ, ಉಚಿತಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಅನ್ನಧಾನ, ಕೋಟೆಗಳ ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ, ಧರ್ಮಮಾರ್ಗದಲ್ಲಿ ನಡೆಯಲು, ಅರ್ಥಿಕ ಸುವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗೆ ಧನವೆ ಮೂಲ, ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ರಾಜನಾದವನು ಹಣಸಂಗ್ರಹಣೆಗೆ ಅಧಿಕಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದನು. ಅದರಿಂದ ರಾಜನಾದವನಿಗೆ ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಜ್ಞಾನಬೇಕಿತ್ತು. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ತೆರಿಗೆಯನ್ನು ಯಾರಿಗೆ ಯಾವ ಪ್ರಮಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇರಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಅದರಿಂದ ಯಾವೆಲ್ಲ ಕೆಲಸವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬೇಕೆಂದು ಸವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾಗಿ ಹೇಳಿದೆ. ಆದುದರಿಂದ ತೆರಿಗೆಗೆ ಅತಿಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ನಮ್ಮ ಪೂರ್ವಿಕರು ನೀಡಿರುವರು. ಆ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದ ತೆರಿಗೆ ಯಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ನೋಡಬಹುದು.

ಮುಖ್ಯಪದಗಳು:- ಆದಾಯ, ತೆರಿಗೆ, ಅರ್ಥಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ, ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ.

Paper No. 9.14 - Shastra and darshanas

श्रीमद् आद्य शंकराचार्य के स्तोत्र (नर्मदाष्टकम्) में गर्भित दर्शन-सिद्धांत³

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ABSTRACT

स्मृतिश्रुतिपुराणानामालयं करुणालयम् ।

नमामि भगवत्पादं शङ्करं लोक-शंकरम् ॥

भारतीय संस्कृति की नींव पुनःस्थापित करने का श्रेय आद्य शंकराचार्य को जाता है। प्रज्ञानं ब्रह्म, तत्त्वमसि, अहं ब्रह्मास्मि और अयमात्मा ब्रह्म – इन चार महामंत्र को ही आधारशीला बनाके पुरे भारतवर्ष में आसेतु हिमालय से कन्याकुमारी तक सनातन धर्म की पताका लहराकर सनातन धर्म की पुनःस्थापन करनेवाले जगद्गुरु शंकराचार्य भगवान शिव का अवतार माने जाते हैं।

तत्कालिन धर्म की दुर्दशा सुधारने हेतु पंचायतन पूजा समाज में स्थापित की और परमात्मा की सर्वव्यापकता का - अद्वैतवाद का – सिद्धांत प्रतिपादित किया। प्रकृति के जड़ और चेतन – प्रत्येक पदार्थ में परमात्मा व्याप्त है – इसी सिद्धांत को उनके हर एक वाङ्मय में प्रत्यक्ष या परोक्ष रूप में पाया जाता है।

उद्देश्य

- श्रीशंकराचार्य के अद्वैतवाद के सिद्धांत का नर्मदाष्टकम् के संदर्भ में अध्ययन

Keywords: नर्मदाष्टकम्, जगद्गुरु आद्य शंकराचार्य, अद्वैतवाद जड़, चेतन,

³ श्री निवास युनिवर्सिटी द्वारा आयोजित आंतर्राष्ट्रीय कॉन्फरन्स के लिए चूना हुआ विषय

Paper No. 9.15 - Shastra and darshanas

ತಂತ್ರಸಾರ ಆಗಮ ಹಾಗೂ ಇತರ ಆಗಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟತೆ

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ABSTRACT

ತಂತ್ರಸಾರ ಆಗಮ ಹಾಗೂ ಇತರ ಆಗಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಸಾಮ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟತೆ ತಂತ್ರಾಗಮಕ್ಕೂ ವೇದಾಂತಕ್ಕೂ ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಸಂಬಂಧವಿದೆ. ವೇದಾಂತವನ್ನು (ಸಚ್ಚಾಸ್ತ್ರವನ್ನು) ಚೆನ್ನಾಗಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ ತಂತ್ರಾಗಮ ರೀತ್ಯಾ ಸದಾಚಾರ, ಪಂಚಯಜ್ಞ, ಷಟ್ಕರ್ಮ, ದೇವರ ಪೂಜೆ, ಬಿಂಬ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠೆ, ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಕಲಶ (ಕುಂಭಾಭಿಶೇಕ), ಉತ್ಸವಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವುದರಿಂದ, ಹೇಗೆ ಬಿಂಬ ಸಾನಿಧ್ಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯಾಗುವುದು, ಗ್ರಾಮ, ರಾಜ್ಯ, ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರಕ್ಕೂ ಸುಭಿಕ್ಷೆಯಾಗುವುದು, ಇದು ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸವಾದರೆ ಹೇಗೆ ದುರ್ಭಿಕ್ಷೆಯಾಗುವುದು ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಚೆನ್ನಾಗಿ ಬಲ್ಲವನು. ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾದಿ ಕರ್ಮ ಮಾಡಲು ಅರ್ಹನಾಗುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಅಂತಹವನನ್ನು ಆಗಮಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳು ದೇಶಿಕ, ಆಚಾರ್ಯ, ತಂತ್ರ ಎಂಬ ಆತನನ್ನು ಕೊಂಡಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಆ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಆಚಾರ್ಯ ಮಧ್ವರಿಂದ ಪ್ರಣೀತವಾದ ಈ “ತಂತ್ರಸಾರಾಗಮ”ವು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ತರಹದ ಸುಖ, ಸೌಭಾಗ್ಯ, ಲೌಕಿಕ ಆನಂದ, ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಪಾರಲೌಕಿಕ ಪರಮಾನಂದವನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಸವಿಯಬಹುದು ಎಂಬ ವಿಚಾರವನ್ನು ಚೆನ್ನಾಗಿ ನಿರೂಪಿಸುವುದು. ತಂತ್ರ ಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ‘ತನ್’ ಎಂದರೆ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಬಯಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ತಂದುನೀಡುವಂತದ್ದು, ‘ತ್ರ’ ಎಂದರೆ ತ್ರಾಣ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ, ಬೇಡವಾದ ಅನಿಷ್ಟಗಳಿಂದ ರಕ್ಷಣೆ ಕೊಡುವುದು ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥ. ಹೀಗೆ ಇಷ್ಟ ಪ್ರಾಪ್ತಿ, ಅನಿಷ್ಟ ನಿವಾರಣೆಗಳಾಗುವುದರಿಂದ ‘ತಂತ್ರ’ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇಂತಹ ತಂತ್ರಗಳ ಸಾರವನ್ನು

ವೇದೋಪನಿಷತ್ತು, ಪುರಾಣ ಇತಿಹಾಸ, ಬ್ರಹ್ಮಸೂತ್ರ, ಧರ್ಮಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಷ್ಣು ಪಾರಮ್ಯದ ನೆಲಗಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ರಚಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ತಂತ್ರಸಾರ ಗ್ರಂಥಕ್ಕೆ ಸುಮಾರು ನಲವತ್ತಕ್ಕೂ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳಿವೆ. ಇದೇ ಈ ಆಗಮದ ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯ. ಮನುಷ್ಯ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲವು ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳನ್ನು ಓದಲೇಬೇಕು. ಅದರ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯಲೇಬೇಕೆಂದು ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹೇಗೆ ವಿಷ್ಣು ಸಹಸ್ರನಾಮ, ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ ಓದಲೇ ಬೇಕು, ಅದರ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯಲೇಬೇಕು, ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಆಗಮ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ತಂತ್ರಸಾರಾಗಮವನ್ನು “ಗ್ರಂಥೋತ್ಸಯಂ ಪಾಠ ಮಾತ್ರೇಣ ಸಕಲಾಭೀಷ್ಟ ಸಿದ್ಧಿಧಃ” ಎಂದು, ಇದನ್ನು ಓದುವುದರಿಂದ ತಿಳಿಯುವುದರಿಂದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಭೀಷ್ಟಗಳು ದೊರೆಯುವುದೆಂದು ಇದರ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಕೆಲವು ಮಂತ್ರಗಳ ಜಪಾನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಸಿದ್ಧಿಯಿಂದ ವಿದ್ಯೆ, ಐಶ್ವರ್ಯ, ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿತ್ವ, ಕೀರ್ತಿ, ವಾದಜಯ, ಶತ್ರು ಪರಾಜಯ, ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಪ್ರಾಪ್ತಿಯು ಹೇಗೆ ಪಡೆಯಬಹುದೆಂದು ತಿಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ.

Keywords: agama shastra, vatula agama, devataprathista

Paper No. 9.16 - Shastra and darshanas

वेदान्तदृष्ट्या जगतः सृष्टिः

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ABSTRACT

“ सृष्टिरक्षाहतिज्ञाननियत्यज्ञानबन्धनान् ।

मोक्षं च विष्णुतस्त्वेव ज्ञात्वा मुक्तिर्न चान्यथा ” ॥

इति आनन्दतीर्थभगवत्पादीयवचनानुरोधेन विष्णोः सृष्ट्याद्यष्टकर्तृत्वमवश्यमेव विज्ञेयम् । एतादृशमेव हि ज्ञानं मुक्तिसाधनम् । तदर्थं सृष्टिस्वरूपमिहावश्यं बोद्धव्यम् । यद्यप्यस्त्यत्र महती विप्रतिपत्तिः । केचनाद्भुतामिमां सृष्टिं अपारमार्थिकीं मन्यन्ते । अपरे पुनर्भगवानेव जगदात्मना परिणतवानित्यपि व्याचक्षते । सृष्टिरपि सर्वेषां जीवानां एकदैव भवति नवेत्यत्रापि विप्रतिपत्तिर्द्रुश्यते । तदत्र मतान्तरीयविचारधाराविमर्शपूर्वं शुद्धा काचन विचारपद्धतिर्विमर्शनार्थं इह प्रयतते ।

भगवती श्रुतिः “ यतो वा इमानि भूतानि जायन्ते ” यथोर्णनाभिः सृजते ” “यः सर्वज्ञः स सर्ववित्” इत्यादावनन्तकल्याणगुणपूर्णेन भगवता जीवजडात्मकस्य विश्वस्य सृष्टिमभिदधाति । बहुचित्रजगतः स्रष्टुर्भगवतोऽसाधारणं महत्त्वं सृष्टिस्वरूपविज्ञानेन भवतीत्यत्र न सन्देहगन्धः । तदुक्तं भगवत्पादाचार्यैः “ बहुचित्रजगद् बहुधा करणात्.....परमः इति । जगतः तन्नियामकानां देवानां च तारतम्यविज्ञानमपि सृष्टिस्वरूपनिरूपणस्यापरं प्रयोयोजनं शास्त्रेषूपवर्णितम् । यावदिदं न स्पष्टं विज्ञायते तावन्न मुक्तिर्भवतीति निष्कण्ठकः पन्थाः । अतोऽत्र श्रुतिस्मृतिपर्यालोचनया सृष्टिस्वरूपविमर्शार्थं पिपीलिका प्रवृत्तिः प्रवृत्ता ।

तथा “ यथोर्णनाभिः” इति श्रुतौ च भगवतो निमित्तकारणत्वं स्फुटमुपपादितम् । प्रतिषिद्धं चोपादानकारणत्वं विवर्तकारणत्वं वा ।

न हि ऊर्णनाभिजन्तुविशेष एव पदार्थात्मना परिणमते । न वा ऊर्णनाभिजन्तौ स्वोदरस्थं यस्त्वारोपितमनुभूयते । तदत्र ब्रह्मण उपादानकारणत्वविवर्तकारणत्वपराकरनपूर्वकं सर्वज्ञेन भगवता विश्वमिदं प्रणीतमिति श्रुतेराशयः सुजनानां प्रतीयते ।

एवं रूपेण तत्त्वनये तत्र तत्र निरूपितसृष्टिविषयं संकलय्य एकत्र संयोजनार्थं प्रयत्नः प्रवृत्तः माहान्तः अनुगृह्णन्तु इति संप्रार्थयते सुधिया अयं जनः ।

Keywords: जगत्सृष्टिः, ऊर्णनाभिः, नारायणः, निमित्तकारणम्, उपादानकारणम्

Paper No. 9.17- Shastra and darshanas

अलङ्कारशास्त्रम् अधिकृत्य एका समीक्षा

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ABSTRACT

शिक्षा व्याकरणं छन्दो निरुक्तं ज्योतिषं तथा।
कल्पश्चेति षडङ्गानि वेदस्याहुर्मनीषिणः।।

परन्तु तेन सह "उपकारकत्वादलङ्कारः सप्तममङ्गम्" इति यायावरीयस्य मतम्।
संस्कृते अलङ्कारस्य स्थानं अत्यन्तश्रेष्ठतमम्। अलङ्कारशास्त्रस्य अपरं नाम क्रियाकल्पसाहित्यम्,
अलङ्कारशास्त्रसाहित्यम्, काव्यलक्षणसाहित्यम्, काव्यशास्त्रसाहित्यम्, साहित्यशास्त्रं, सौन्दर्यशास्त्रं,
इत्यपि कथयन्ति।

ननु अलङ्कारः इत्युक्ते किम्? काव्यं नाम शोभादायकं, सत्यसंनिवेशं अत्यन्तमनोहररूपेण
अलङ्काररीति रसादीनां चमत्कारशब्दवाक्यप्रयोगत्वेन संपद्यते। तदा तत्काव्यम् उत्तमं काव्यं भवति।
अलङ्क्रियते अनेन इति अलङ्कारः। यथाशरीरं कटककुण्डलहारादयः भूषयन्ति शोभादायकत्वं कुर्वन्ति
तथैव अनुप्रासादयो अलङ्काराः काव्याङ्गं काव्यशरीरं शब्दार्थं भूषयन्ति। काव्यात्मानं रसाः भूषयन्ति। अतः
अलङ्कारः काव्यस्य प्रधानांशः।

अलङ्कारस्य महत्वप्रतिपादने एषः लघुप्रयत्नः मया क्रियते। जनाः महत्त्वं तस्य वैशिष्ट्यं भेदांश्च न
जानन्ति। अधुनापि प्रतिनित्यं अलङ्कारस्य प्रयोगं कुर्वन्ति। परन्तु तेषां महत्त्वं न जानन्ति।
उदाहरणम् – गृहसचिवः अमित्शाह्महोदयः आधुनिकयुगस्य चाणक्य इव वर्तते।
अत्र उपमालङ्कारस्य प्रयोगः कृतः।

अस्यां पत्रिकायां अलङ्कारस्य प्रमुखांशान्, अलङ्कारस्य संप्रदायांश्च (षट्प्रस्थानानि),
उद्दिश्य समीक्षात्मकं प्रबन्धं कर्तुम् इच्छामि।

Keywords: Alankara shastra, Upama, kavya

Paper No. 9.18- Shastra and darshanas

Bhagavadgita and Purushartha

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ABSTRACT

Bhagavad Gita is Lord Krishna's special gift to mankind. Out of 84 lakh species the human form is the most valuable. Therefore one must utilize it to the maximum. For example when we pay a huge amount of money for the latest smartphone we use all its features as per the manual to make the buy worth the money. So if this valuable human life should be used properly, Bhagavad Gita is the manual, and the source of the manual given is the creator of the universe Lord Krishna.

The Bhagavad Gita is filled with various interesting topics out of which Karma yoga is an important one. We all have heard the word 'karma'. 'Karma' means 'action'. A person performs karma according to the influence of the three modes of material nature i.e Satva Guna, Rajo Guna and Tamo Guna. This karma or action is the cause of our happiness and distress. It also decides our ultimate destination which can be either Moksha or Naraka. Just as a door can be locked and unlocked by a key, karma can be the reason for our entanglement in this world full of miseries and can also be the reason for our liberation.

This karma can be classified as good karma and bad karma. Good karma can be further classified as 'sakaama karma' (action with fruitive desires) and 'nishkaama karma' (action without desires for fruitive results). Karma becomes 'nishkaama' when offered to the Lord and done with a mindset that the lord is the doer as stated in the Gita '।कर्मजं बुद्धियुक्ता हि फलं त्यक्त्वा मनीषिणः जन्मबन्धविनिर्मुक्ताः पदं गच्छन्त्यनामयम्।।

This karma yoga is also the answer for the question which almost every person gets in their life 'Why do bad things happen to good people and why do good things happen to bad people' and the answer is karma.

Hence Lord Krishna out of mercy has shown us the path for happiness i.e performing karma as prescribed in the manual which is the Bhagavad Gita..' स्वे स्वे कर्मण्यभिरतः संसिद्धिं लभते नरः।

Keywords: Purushartha, Bhagavadgita, Karma

Paper No. 9.19- Shastra and darshanas

Mysticism elements in Kapilamuni Devahuti narrative in the BhāgāvataPurāṇa

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ABSTRACT

Mysticism has been generally understood as Union with God/ the Divine or the Absolute. As a personal spiritual experience, this union with the divine has its basis in mystical states of consciousness. Aspirants on this path have left behind detailed literature that explains these experiences and states, on the basis of which we can ascertain characteristics of mystical experiences.

In this paper, it is proposed to apply these characteristics of mystical experiences to a narrative in the BhāgāvataPurāṇa – The Kapilamuni Devahuti narrative. This narrative appears in Skanda VI of the BhāgāvataPurāṇa. The narrative details an exposition of Saṅkhya philosophy highlighting the intellectual aspect of mysticism, an explanation of practical meditation techniques signifying yogic mysticism, a discussion on the importance of devotion representing devotional mysticism and finally an aspect of Karmic/Action mysticism. This narrative is a classic as it displays the four major types of mysticism – Intellectual, Yogic, Devotional and Action in detail. It will prove how the narrative reflects Intellectual, Yogic, Devotional and Action Mysticism thus indicating Union with the Divine.

Keywords: Mysticism, Union with the Divine, Saṅkhya Philosophy, narrative analysis, meditation, mystical experiences.

Paper No. 9.20- Shastra and darshanas

सङ्हरामायणस्य पुरुषार्थ सङ्ग्राहकत्वम्

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ABSTRACT

उपोद्घातः -

मूलरामायणं शटकोटिग्रन्थविस्तीर्णम्। तच्च स्वयं हयग्रीवरूपि भगवता प्रणीतम्। तदेव चतुर्मुखः नारदाय उपदिदेश। नारदः वाल्मीकिमुनये प्रादात्। सम्प्रति ग्रन्थोयं नोपलब्धः। तस्य मूलरामायणस्य सारः अथवा सङ्ग्रहः मूलरामायणम्। मूलरामायणस्य सारः आचार्यमध्वैः श्रीमन्महभारततात्पर्य निर्णये प्रदत्तः। मूलरामायणस्य, मध्वरामायणस्य च सेतुबन्धः प्रस्तुतग्रन्थः 'संग्रह रामायणम्'।

इदमस्ति महाकाव्यम्, लिकुचकुलकविवरेण श्रीनारायण पण्डिताचार्येण रचितम्। महाभारत तात्पर्य निर्णयान् प्राप्तस्फूरतिः संग्रह रामायणं व्याचयत्। अस्य चतस्रः टीकाः उपलब्धाः।

- विद्याभूषण भिक्षुराचिता टीका - 1912- भावरत्नप्रदीपः
- श्री विश्वपतितिर्थीयटीका
- काशी श्रीनिवासाचार्यकृता टीका
- बन्नजे गोविन्दाचार्यविरचिता संग्रहचन्द्रिका

शास्त्रत्वेन, महाकाव्यत्वेन इतिहासत्वेन वैशिष्ट्यं भजते। संग्रहेण निरूपितं रामायणम् इति, सम्यगवबुध्यते रामायणमनेन इति च 'संग्रह रामायणम्'। एवं सर्षपे कूष्माण्डप्रवेशः।

Keywords: Ramayanam, moolaraamayanam, mahabharatatatparyanirnaya

Paper No. 9.21- Shastra and darshanas

ಯಾಜ್ಞವಲ್ಕ್ಯಸ್ಮೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಸರ ವಿಚಾರ

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ABSTRACT

ಅನೇಕ ಸ್ಮೃತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾದ ಯಾಜ್ಞವಲ್ಕ್ಯಸ್ಮೃತಿಯು ಧರ್ಮಾನುಬಂಧವಾದ ಲೋಕಜೀವನನಿರೂಪಣೆಯನ್ನೇ ಪ್ರಧಾನವಾಗಿ ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಿದೆ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಋಷಿಗಳ ತೀಕ್ಷ್ಣಸಮೂಹಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯು ಧ್ವನಿಪಡೆದಿದೆ. ಸಮಕಾಲೀನ ಸಮಾಜದ ಸಾಧಕ ಬಾಧಕಗಳ ವಿವೇಚನಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಚಾರಗಳಿವೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ನಾವು ಈಗ ಸಂಶೋಧಿಸಲು ಹೊರಟಿರುವುದು ಯಾಜ್ಞವಲ್ಕ್ಯ ಸ್ಮೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಪರಿಸರವಿಚಾರಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸಾವಿರಾರು ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಹಿಂದೆ ಋಷಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ತಪೋಸಿದ್ಧಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪಡೆದುಕೊಂಡ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಜೀವಸಂಕುಲದ ಅಭ್ಯುದಯಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವನದ ಸಧರ್ಮೀಕರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸಮಾಜವು ಆರೋಗ್ಯಕರವಾಗಿ, ಸುಸ್ಥಿರವಾಗಿ ಇರಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಸ್ವಚ್ಛ ಹಾಗೂ ಸುಂದರ ಪರಿಸರವು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಯಾಜ್ಞವಲ್ಕ್ಯಸ್ಮೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖವಾಗಿರುವ ಭೂಶುದ್ಧಿ, ಜಲಶುದ್ಧಿ, ಅರಣ್ಯಸಂರಕ್ಷಣೆ, ಸೇತು, ವಾಪಿ, ಕೂಪಗಳ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆ, ಯಜ್ಞದಮೂಲಕ ವೃಷ್ಟಿ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಉದಾಹರಿಸಿ, ಇಂದಿನ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟದ ಪರಿಸರದೊಂದಿಗೆ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕವಾದಿ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಮೂಲ ಮಾನವರಲ್ಲಿ ನಾವಿಂದು ಪರಿಸರಜಾಗೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಮೂಡಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

Keywords: ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಿಮುಹೂರ್ತ, ಭೂಶುದ್ಧಿ, ದ್ರವ್ಯಶುದ್ಧಿ, ರಾಜನಿವಾಸಸ್ಥಾನ, ವೃಕ್ಷರಕ್ಷಣೆ, ಜಲಶುದ್ಧಿ

Paper No. 9.22- Shastra and darshanas

ಸನಾತನ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ಜೀವಾಳ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರ

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ABSTRACT

ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರರಹಿತಾ ಯೇತು ತೇಷಾಂ ಜನ್ಮ ನಿರರ್ಥಕಮ್

ಪ್ರಾಚೀನರು ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಕೊಟ್ಟ ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಮಾತು ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರದ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಯಾವ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಿಂದ ವಸ್ತುವು ತನ್ನ ಮೊದಲಿದ್ದ ಸೌಂದರ್ಯವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದೋ ಆ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಗೆ 'ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರ'ವೆಂದು ಕರೆದರು. ಭೂಮಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಪದಾರ್ಥವೂ ಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಉಪಯೋಗಕ್ಕೆ ಬರುವುದು ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವಾದನಂತರವೇ. ಮಣ್ಣಲ್ಲಿದ್ದ ಚಿನ್ನಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವಾದ ನಂತರ ಅದು 'ಸುವರ್ಣ'ವಾಯಿತು. ಪಾತ್ರೆಗಳಿಗೆ 'ಪ್ರಕ್ಷಾಳನ'ವೆಂಬ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರದ ನಂತರ ಅಡುಗೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಅದು ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾಯಿತು. ನೀರಿಗೆ 'ಕುದಿಸುವಿಕೆ'ಯೆಂಬ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರದ ನಂತರ ಕುಡಿಯಲು ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾಯಿತು. ಬರಿಯ ಜಡಪದಾರ್ಥಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಿದ ನಂತರ ಇಷ್ಟೊಂದು ಸುಂದರ ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಗಳು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾದರೆ, ಒಬ್ಬ ಚೇತನನಿಗೆ ಮಂತ್ರ ಹಾಗೂ ದ್ರವ್ಯಗಳ ಮೇಳನದಿಂದ ಮಾಡಿದ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವು ಮತ್ತೆಷ್ಟು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗದಿರದು. ಈ ಹೆನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಚಾರ್ಯರು ಜಾತಜೀವಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವು ಅತ್ಯಗತ್ಯ ಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಾಗಿದೆಯೆಂದರು.

ಈ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಎರಡುವಿಧ. ಪೂರ್ವ ಹಾಗೂ ಅಪರ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ. ಇವೆರಡೂ ಹದಿನಾರು ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿವೆ. ಇಹಲೋಕದ ಸುಗಮಕ್ಕೆ ಪೂರ್ವ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದರೆ, ಪರಲೋಕದ ಸುಗಮಕ್ಕೆ ಅಪರ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿವೆ. ಇದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪೂರ್ವಷೋಡಶ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು 'ದೋಷಮಾರ್ಜಕ, ಅತಿಶಯಾಧಾಯಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಹೀನಾಂಗಪೂರಕ' ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಮೂರು ವಿಧ. ಜೀವಿಯು ಗರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿರುವಾಗ ತಾಯಿಯುಂಡ ಅನ್ನ-ಪಾನೀಯಗಳೇ ಮಗುವಿಗೂ ಆಹಾರವಾಗುವುದರಿಂದ ಸಹಜವಾಗಿ ತಾಯಿಯ ವಿಕೃತಿಯು ಮಗುವಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಫಲಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಹಾಗೂ ಗರ್ಭದ ಶಿಶುವಿನ ರಕ್ಷಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು 'ದೋಷಮಾರ್ಜಕ' ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳಾಗಿವೆ. ಗರ್ಭಾಧಾನ, ಪುಂಸವನಾದಿಗಳು ಈ ಹೆನ್ನೆಲೆಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಹತೆ, ವಿದ್ಯಾಗೃಹಣ, ಧಾರಣ, ವೇದಾಧ್ಯಯನ ಮುಂತಾದ ಅತಿಶಯವಾದ ಗುಣವನ್ನು ಕೊಡುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು 'ಅತಿಶಯಾಧಾಯಕ' ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಗಳು. ಚೂಡಾಕರ್ಮ, ಉಪನಯನಾದಿಗಳು ಈ ಸಾಲಿನವು. ಯಜನಾದಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅರ್ಹತೆ, ಗೃಹಸ್ಥಾಶ್ರಮ ಸ್ವೀಕಾರ, ಸಂತಾನಪ್ರಾಪ್ತಿ, ರಹಸ್ಯವಿದ್ಯೆಯ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಮುಂತಾದ ಮೊದಲು ಹೀನವಾಗಿದ್ದ ನಂತರ ಅಧಿಕಾರ ಕೊಡುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರ 'ಹೀನಾಂಗಪೂರಕ' ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರವಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿವಾಹವು ಈ ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೊಂದು ಉದಾಹರಣೆ.

Keywords - ಸಂಸ್ಕಾರ, ಅತಿಶಯಾಧಾಯಕ, ದೋಷಮಾರ್ಜಕ, ಹೀನಾಂಗಪೂರಕ, ಗರ್ಭಾಧಾನ.

Paper No. 9.23- Shastra and darshanas

वेदानां परमपुरुषार्थप्रदत्वम्

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ABSTRACT

धर्मार्थकाममोक्षमध्ये मोक्षः परमपुरुषार्थ बहुशः सर्वमतेषु। तादृशमोक्षस्वरूपं, तत्प्राप्तिमार्गः इत्येतत्स्वर्वं वेदेषु तत्र तत्र अनुवर्ण्यते। तज्ज्ञानं भयरहितलौकिकजीवनायापि सहायकं भवतीति धिया एतस्मिन् विषये संशोधनप्रबन्धः विधीयते।

वेदे तावत् चत्वारो विभागाः सन्ति। संहिता-ब्राह्मणं-आरण्यकं-उपनिषदश्चेति। तत्र चतुर्षु विभागेषु ओतप्रोतभावेन नैके विचाराः वर्तन्ते। तेषु अध्यात्मिकविचारः प्रधानः।

मातृभुक्तान्नेन गर्भाभिवृद्धिः अभिवृद्धस्य शिशोः मेधालाभः, क्षुत्पिपासोत्पत्तिः, तन्निवृत्तेरुपायः, संकरपरिदृशः, जीवनं, अभिवृद्धिः, पृकृतेर्महत्वं, वातावरणशुद्धिः इत्यादयो विचाराः बहवो जीवनोपायाः, अहितपरिहारः, हिताभिवृद्धिश्च निश्चप्रचं उल्लिखितमस्ति। तस्मादेव वेदानां सखितुल्यत्वमङ्गीकृत्य प्राचीनमहर्षिभिः वेदाध्ययनमेव जीवनमिति मत्वा कालो नीत इत्येतत् जानन्त्येव महान्तः। लोकविषयानविहायैव अध्यात्मवादः कथितः। ऊँकारवाच्यो भगवान् समस्तवेदाक्षरेषु प्रतिपादितो वर्तते। एतं भगवन्तं बाह्यज्ञानेन वा बाह्येन्द्रियेण वा ज्ञातुमशक्नुमः। वेदवचनमेव इत्थं वर्तते ॥

Keywords: Veda, Purushartha, Moksha, Upanishad, Aranyaka

Paper No. 9.24- Shastra and darshanas

इतिहासपुराणयोः वेदोपबृंहकत्वम्

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ABSTRACT

उपोद्घातः -

‘वेदोऽखिलो धर्ममूलम्’। नित्यविन्नत्वात् वेदः सर्वाधारः। भाषाणां संस्कृतीनां शास्त्राणां जीवनपद्धतीनां संरक्षणार्थं संस्करणार्थं परिष्करणार्थं च वेदः अध्येतव्यः। तथैव वेदार्थसम्पादनार्थं षडङ्गान्यपि। पुराणं भारतमपि। अपि च धर्मेण कामितार्थप्राप्त्यर्थं मुमुक्षुणा वेदोऽनुसन्धेयः। सन्ध्या, पूजा यज्ञादिषु उपयुज्यमानाः मन्त्राः यदि ज्ञाताः स्युः तदैव कर्माणि तारकाणि भवन्ति। तदधुना जगति केवलं वैदिककर्म अज्ञात्वापि कर्तुं शक्यते। नान्यत्र कुत्रापि। तदेतस्य दोषस्य परिहाराय व्यासेन प्रादर्शि पन्थाः।

“इतिहासपुराणाभ्यां वेदं समुपबृंहयेत्।”

महाभारतपञ्चरात्रादिग्रन्थाः अष्टादशपुराणानि च वेदोपबृंहकानि। वेदे प्रतिपादिताः आख्यायिकाः पुराणेषु स्पष्टतया विवृताः। अपि च अनेके औपासनाविषयाः पञ्चरात्रान्तर्गताः भवन्ति। भारते पुराणे च देवतास्तुतयः विश्वादि सूक्तानां अनुवादाः इव भासन्ते। अत एव एतेषां पञ्चमवेदत्वमुच्यते।

भागवतस्य तृतीयस्कन्धस्य विराडूपवर्णनावसरे समग्रपुरुषसूक्तस्य व्याख्यानं दृश्यते। अत्र तु चतुर्षु श्लोकेषु चतुर्षु वेदेषु पठ्यमानोऽयं मन्त्रः विवृतः।

“ब्राह्मणोऽस्य मुखमासीद् बाहू राजन्यः कृतः” इत्यत्र यदुक्तं पुरुषसूक्ते तत्र केवलं भागवते किन्तु विष्णुपद्मादिषु पुराणेष्वपि विवृतं दरीदृश्यते।

भारते च

“ऊर्ध्वमूलमधःशाखमश्वत्थं प्राहुरव्ययम्”

कठे च

ऊर्ध्वमूलोऽवाक् शिराः एषोऽश्वत्थः सनातनः” एवं पुराणभारतवाक्यानि लभ्यन्ते।

प्रपञ्चेऽस्मिन् संहितारण्यकब्राह्मणोपनिषदां वाक्यानां पुराणभारतसंवादः संगृह्यते। प्रमुखतया अस्य रचनार्थं श्रीमदानन्दतीर्थविरचितसर्वमूलग्रन्थाः अष्टादशपुराणानि, पञ्चरात्रादि आगमग्रन्थाः ऋगादयो वेदाः साहाय्यं कुर्वन्ति इति विश्वसिमि।

प्रणवार्थं व्याहृतयः व्याहृत्यर्था ऋगादयः।

इतिहासपुराणं च पञ्चरात्रं च सर्वशः ॥

Paper No. 10.01: Vedānta and Upanishad

जगत्स्वरूपस्यास्तित्वविषये उपनिषदामभिप्रायावलोकनम्**Dr. Shanmukha Hebbar**

Professor, Department Of Dwaita Vedanta, S.M.S.P. Samskrita College, Udupi.

Cell no. 9481748819, Email ID- shanmukha.hebbar@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

अस्ति तावत् प्रमेयानां प्रमाणाधीनत्वम् । प्रमेयसाधनेषु प्रमाणेषु प्रत्यक्षं प्रबलमपि, प्रत्यक्षेण जगतः सत्यत्वं सिद्धमपि जगतः वास्तवतायां विवादो वरीवर्ति । ऐहिकस्य सत्यतायाः सन्देहास्कन्दने सकलस्यापि ऐहिकामुष्मिककर्मजातस्य वैयर्थ्यशङ्काकलङ्कितान्तःकरणस्य न क्वापि सोत्साहम् प्रवृत्तिर्निष्पद्येत । अतः विचारस्यायमवसरः ।

उद्देश्यम्-

- * जीवोत्सहस्य वर्धनम् जामितानिवारणं च
- * जनानां जगतः स्वरूपविषये विवेकव्युत्पदनम्
- * जगतः सत्यत्वेन तत्सम्बद्धानां विषयाणां यथार्थत्वबुद्ध्युत्पादनम् ।
- * ब्रह्मणो जगत्कर्तृत्वस्य यथार्थताज्ञिसम्पादनेन भगवदुत्कर्षताजागरणम्

अतीन्द्रियपदार्थेषुविषयेषु आगम एव हि मुख्यं प्रमाणम् । अतः समस्यायाः अध्ययनार्थं वेदाः, तत्रापि उपनिषदः प्राधान्येन समाश्रयणीयाः । उपनिषदश्च दशैव स्वीक्रियन्ते प्रायः दार्शनिकैः आदृतत्वात् ।

प्रणाली-

आगमानाम् अर्थनिर्णये- उपक्रमोपसंहारोऽभ्यासोऽपूर्वता फलम् ।

अर्थवादोपपत्ती च लिङ्गं तात्पर्यनिर्णये ।

इति उपक्रमादीनि उपपत्तिलिङ्गानि श्रुतिप्रकरणादश्च गृहीताः इत्यतः तथैव प्रणाल्या उपनिषदाम् अभिप्रायः आविष्क्रियते ।

इह जगति वर्तमानाः पदार्थाः नित्यनित्यत्वेन विभक्ता अपि तेषां सत्यत्वमिथ्यात्वविचारः तावत् नित्यानित्यत्वाविचारात् विलक्षणम् । नित्यत्वादिकं प्रत्यक्षादिसिद्धमपि तत्र पुनः सत्यत्वादिविचारः दर्शनेषु प्रवर्तते । तत्र उपनिषत्सु परिशील्यमानेषु सत्यत्वमेव सिद्ध्यति न क्वापि मिथ्यात्वम् । तत्र कानिचन वाक्यानि अत्र उपस्थाप्यन्ते- ईशोपनिषदि अष्टमे मन्त्रे - **कविर्मनीषी परिभूः स्वयभूर्यथातथ्यतोर्थां व्यदधात्साश्चतीभ्यः समाभ्यः** इत्यत्र यथातथ्यतः अर्थान् इति भगवत्सृष्टपदार्थानाम् यथार्थत्वं साधितम् ।

आथर्वणोपनिषदि च पराविद्याविषयस्य अक्षरनामकस्य ब्रह्मणः स्वरूपजिज्ञासायां **तद्भूतयोनि परिपश्यन्तिधीराः** इति जगत्कारणतामेव ब्रह्मणो लक्षणमाह । जगत एव मिथ्यात्वे कथम् वा जगत्करणत्वं ब्रह्मणः सम्भवति । पुनरग्रे **यः सर्वज्ञः सर्ववित्** इति । सर्वस्याप्यभावे कथं तस्य सर्वज्ञत्वम् उपपद्येत ।

एवं पूर्वोक्तया अनया प्रणाल्या परीक्षणेन अयमंशः अवगम्यते यत्- विश्वं **मिथ्या भवितुं नार्हति । किन्तु सत्यमेव** । विश्वस्य मिथ्यात्वे ऐहिकामुष्मिकफलसाधनाय वैदिकाः विधयः व्यर्था आपद्येरन् ।

अतः सर्वैः आस्तिकैः जगतः सत्यत्वमभ्युपेत्यैव सर्वत्र प्रवर्तितव्यम् ।

Key words - Jagath, Mithyaa, Svarupam, Satyam

Paper No. 10.02: Vedānta and Upanishad

ವಿಶ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಶ್ರೀರಾಮತಾರಕಮಂತ್ರವನ್ನು ಕೊಟ್ಟ ರಾಮೋತ್ತರತಾಪಿನ್ಯುಪನಿಷತ್ತಿನ ಕಿರು ಪರಿಚಯ, ಮಂತ್ರದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನ ಫಲಗಳು.

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ಶ್ರುತಿ-ಸ್ತೋತಿ-ಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಸನಾತನ ಧರ್ಮದ ಅಡಿಪಾಯಗಳು. ಇವು ಅವಿನಾಶಿ. ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ತಾತ್ವಿಕ, ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಜೀವನಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳ ಮೂಲಸ್ರೋತ ಇವೇ. ಶ್ರುತಿಗಳೆಂದರೆ ವೇದಗಳು. ವೇದಗಳು ನಾಲ್ಕು. ಋಗ್ವೇದ, ಯಜುರ್ವೇದ, ಸಾಮವೇದ ಹಾಗೂ ಅಥರ್ವಣ ವೇದ. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ವೇದವು ಕರ್ಮ ಹಾಗೂ ಜ್ಞಾನಕಾಂಡಗಳೆಂದು ಎರಡಾಗಿ ಗುರುತಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ. ಕರ್ಮಕಾಂಡದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಹಿತೆ, ಬ್ರಾಹ್ಮಣ ಮತ್ತು ಆರಣ್ಯಕ ಎಂದು ಮೂರು ವಿಭಾಗ. ಜ್ಞಾನಕಾಂಡವೇ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತುಗಳು. ಪ್ರಸ್ಥಾನತ್ರಯಗಳಲ್ಲೊಂದು. ಇವು ವೇದಗಳ ಕೊನೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ವೇದಾಂತಗಳೆಂದೂ ಪ್ರಖ್ಯಾತವಾಗಿವೆ. ಹೀಗೆ ನಾಲ್ಕು ವೇದಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಟ್ಟು ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತುಗಳು ಒಂದುಸಾವಿರದ ನೂರವಂಭತ್ತು ಎಂದು ಒಂದು ಲೆಖ್ಯಾಚಾರ.

ಮಾನವನು ದೇವತ್ವಪ್ರಾಪ್ತಿಗಾಗಿ ಅನುಸರಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಸಾಧನಾಪಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಉದ್ಧಕ್ಕೂ ಜ್ಞಾನದೀವಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಬೆಳಕನ್ನು ತೋರಿಸುವ ಶ್ರುತಿಗಳ ಅಂತಿಮ ಘೋಷಣೆಗಳೇ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತುಗಳು. ಮಾನವನು ದಾನವನಾಗದೆ ಆದರ್ಶ ಪುರುಷೋತ್ತಮನಾಗಿ, ಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಪ್ರಾಪಂಚಿಕತೆಯ ಆಕರ್ಷಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಜಯಿಸಿ 'ಸತ್' 'ಚಿತ್' 'ಆನಂದ'ದ ಅನುಭೂತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುವಲ್ಲಿ ಕರಾವಲಂಬನೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುವುದೇ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತುಗಳು. ಮೋಕ್ಷದ ಗುರಿಯನ್ನಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಂಡು ಜೀವನ ಸಾಗಿಸುವ ಕಲೆ, ಪುರುಷಾರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುವ ನೆಲೆ, ಈ ದಿಶೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಪಾಲನೆಗೆ ತೆರಬೇಕಾದ ಬೆಲೆ, ಇವೆಲ್ಲವನ್ನು ನಿಖರವಾಗಿ, ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವ ಸೂತ್ರಗಳೇ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತುಗಳು.

ಉಪನಿಷತ್, ರಾಮೋತ್ತರತಾಪಿನ್ಯುಪನಿಷತ್, ಷಡಕ್ಷರಮಂತ್ರ, ರಾಮತಾರಕಮಂತ್ರ,
ಅವಿಮುಕ್ತತೀರ್ಥ, ಅವಿಮುಕ್ತಕ್ಷೇತ್ರ,

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॥ उपनिषदुक्ताख्यायिकासु धर्मसंस्कृतिजागृतिः ॥

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ABSTRACT

आर्षप्रपञ्चे वेदान्तशास्त्रमत्यन्तम् प्रसिद्धम् । मानवाभ्युदये अस्य शास्त्रस्य योगदानं महत्तरं वर्तते । आध्यात्मिकस्तरस्य जनानां साधनाय इदम् अत्यन्तं सहकारि । जीवस्य आत्यन्तिकसुखप्राप्त्यर्थं शास्त्रमिदम् आदौ तिष्ठति । आध्यात्मशास्त्रं नाम उपनिषदित्येव । आध्यात्मस्य प्राप्तये प्रबला साधना आख्यायिका एव । उपनिषदः अध्ययनम् अनुसन्धानं च मानवस्य आध्यात्मस्तरं प्राप्तुं सेतुरिव तिष्ठति । उपनिषदः परमपुरुषार्थः मोक्षः एव तस्याः अवान्तरफलत्वेन धर्मः उच्यते । संस्कृतेः आचरणमेव धर्मः इत्यभिप्रायः । धर्मः – धारयति इति धर्मः । उपनिषत्सु आख्यायिकया धर्मसंस्कृतेः बोधकविषयान् उपस्थापयन् अध्यात्मं प्रतिपादितम् । आख्यायिकायां सारल्येन धर्मसंस्कृतेः बोधः भवति । यतोऽहि अख्यायिकायां स्वारस्य वर्तते अतः ज्ञानमपि सारल्येन प्राप्यते । यथा रामायणमहाभारतपुराणादिषु । अत्र उपनिषदुक्ताख्यायिकानाम् औचित्यं एवं विव्रीयते ।

आख्यायिकशब्दस्य निर्वचनम् - आख्यायिका नाम सत्यार्थविषयिणी आत्मनः यथार्थप्रतिपादनाय स्तुतिपूर्विका उपलब्धार्थकथा (अमरः/कल्पद्रुमः) ।

नचिकेतोपाख्यानम् - कठोपनिषदि नचिकेतोपाख्याने प्रदर्शितं नचिकेतसा पितुः " ईदृशानि गवां दानेन पितुर्मम को वा लाभः भवेत् ? न कश्चिदपि । प्रत्युत सुखहीनाः अनन्दानाम नरकलोका एव मे जनकस्य भवेयुः । पितरि अहितं मा भूत् इति नचिकेतः उपमृत्युं जगम् । एवं पुत्रस्य धर्मं नचिकेतसा पालितः । सर्ववेदप्रतिपाद्यं तपसा ब्रह्मचर्येण च साध्यम् ओमित्येकाक्षरं पदम् । अत्र तपः ब्रह्मचर्यमिति धर्मः उच्यते ।

श्वेतकेतुकथा – छान्दोग्योपनिषदि श्वेतकेतोः आख्यायिकायां यत्किञ्चित् कर्म ज्ञानपूर्वकं कुर्यात् इति प्रतिपाद्यते । परिक्षया एव कर्माचरणं अत्र धर्मः तेन च श्वेतकेतवे अध्यात्मदर्शनं सिध्यति । एवं धर्मः अध्यात्मं च अस्यामाख्यायिकायां प्रतिपाद्यते ।

एवं आख्यायिकया धर्मसंस्कृतेः प्रतिपादनपूर्वकं आध्यात्मविद्यां च निरूप्यते उपनिषदः इति अस्मिन् लेखने मया प्रतिपाद्यते ।

Key Words: उपनिषदाख्यायिकानाम् अध्यात्मपरत्वम् (पीटिका), आख्यायिकशब्दस्य निर्वचनम् ।, उपनिषद् शब्दस्य निर्वचनम् ।, धर्मसंस्कृतिपदयोः निर्वचनम् ।, उपनिषदाख्यायिकासु धर्मसंस्कृतेः उल्लेखः ।

Paper No. 10.04: Vedantha & Upanishad

छान्दोग्योपनिषदि भारतीयपरम्परानुसारं सुखस्वरूपम्

प्रो. डॉ. मयूरीबेन भाटिया

प्रोफेसर (संस्कृत), भाषासाहित्य भवन, गुजरात यूनिवर्सिटी, नवरंगपुरा, अहमदाबाद. ३८०००९ गुजरात

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ABSTRACT

‘अनुकूलवेदनीयं सुखम्’ इति जगति सर्वे मानवाः अनुकूलतां नाम सुखमेव वाञ्छन्ति, न केऽपि दुःखम् किन्तु किं नाम सुखमिति विषये विभिन्नेषु देशेषु विभिन्नाः कल्पनाः वर्तन्ते । सामान्यतया सर्वत्र भौतिकसुखमेव सुखम् इति मन्यन्ते । परं भारतीयपरम्परायां सुखस्वरूपं विलक्षणमेवास्ति । यथा छान्दोग्योपनिषदि निर्दिष्टम्-

यो वै भूमा तत्सुखं नाल्पे सुखमस्ति भूमैव सुखं भूमा त्वेव विजिज्ञासितव्य इति भूमानं भगवो विजिज्ञास इति ॥

एवं सुखस्वरूपं वर्णितम् । अस्मिन् मन्त्रे भूमा नाम अनन्तं यत्परब्रह्म तद्विषयकं ज्ञानम् एव सुखम् । वस्तुतः संस्कृतसाहित्ये सुखदुःखयोः विषये लिखितं यत् -

सुखस्यानन्तरं दुःखं दुःखस्यानन्तरं सुखम्।
चक्रवत् परिवर्तन्ते दुःखानि च सुखानि च॥

अर्थात् सुखम् अनित्यं सान्तं च ज्ञायते, किन्तु यद् अनित्यं सान्तं तत्कथं सुखं स्यात् । सुखं तु तदेव यद् अनन्तं नित्यं च । अन्यानि सुखानि नाममात्राणि क्षणभङ्गुराणि च । भारते धनं जनं सुन्दरी कीर्तिः पदं वैभवं भवनं इत्यादीनि न सुखस्वरूपाणि प्रत्युत परब्रह्मप्राप्तिरेव सुखम् । अत एव भारतवर्षं विश्वगुरुपदमलङ्कृतवान् । अतः प्राप्तेषु बहुविधसुखस्वरूपेषु भारतीयपरम्परानुसारं सुखस्वरूपमेव श्रेष्ठतममिति । एवम् अस्मिन् शोधपत्रे मया सुखस्य यत् वास्तविकं स्वरूपं तदेव वर्णयिष्यते ।

Keywords: सुखम्, भूमा, परब्रह्म, भारतीयपरम्परा, परब्रह्मप्राप्ति

Paper No. 10.05: Vedānta and Upanishad

श्रीमदानन्दतीर्थभगवत्पादाचार्यविरचिते अनुव्याख्याने अनुव्याख्यानवृत्त्युक्तदिशा अज्ञानस्य निरूपणम्

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ABSTRACT

भूर्भुवस्वरादिचतुर्दशभुवनात्मकसंख्यातिगब्रह्माण्डकोटीः स्वरोमकूपे सन्निवेश्य सकललोकजनन्या श्रिया सह सर्पतल्पे शयानेन भगवता सृष्टेषु भूलोकखण्डेष्वन्यतमेऽस्मिन् भरतखण्डे जनिमतामस्माकं महद्भागधेयमिदं यदत्र भगवान् तत्तद्युगेष्ववतीर्य बलकार्यं ज्ञानकार्यं च सम्पाद्य स्वभक्तानन्वग्रहीत् । तत्रापि विरिञ्चिपित्रा चराचरकर्त्रा नारायणावतारिणा बादरायणेन सकलवेदार्थविनिर्णयाय प्राणिनां निःश्रेयसे च अध्यायचतुष्टयात्मकं ब्रह्ममीमांसाशास्त्रापरनामधेयं ब्रह्मसूत्रं व्यरचि । तस्यार्थवित्तये व्यासशिष्यः पावनः पवमानः स्वतृतीयावतारे मध्वनाम्ना ख्यातः सज्जनानुद्धिधीर्षुः सूत्रप्रस्थानस्य भाष्यं - अणुभाष्यं - अनुभाष्यं (अनुव्याख्यानं) - न्यायविवरणग्रन्थान् अरचयत् । सर्वेऽपि ते ग्रन्थराशयः अध्यात्मविद्यारसिकानां विचारविमर्शकानां जिज्ञासुपिपासूनां ज्ञानतृशां परिहरतीति निश्चप्रचं वक्तुं वयं प्रभवाम ।

तदस्मिन्ग्रन्थे मायावादिशास्त्रे अनुबन्धचतुष्टयेष्वन्यतमः अज्ञानरूपविषयः अनुपपन्नः । तस्मात्तदनुसारि शास्त्रप्रयोजनादिकं न सम्भवति “ अप्रकाशस्वरूपत्वाज्जडेऽज्ञानं न मन्यते ” इत्युदाहृतमूले प्रतिपाद्यते । अज्ञानं तु द्विधा वर्तते । भारूपमभावरूपं चेति तेषां नयः । तत्र अभावरूपाज्ञानस्य वृत्त्यात्मकत्वात् ज्ञानाज्ञानयोः सहानवस्थानरूपविरोधसद्भावात् जीवे स्थितिः वक्तुं नैव शक्यते । अतः भावरूपाज्ञानमेव जीवावरकतया वक्तव्यं परं तत्र सम्भवति । यतो हि मायावादिमतरीत्या पारमार्थिकं सत् ब्रह्म एकमेव । तदतिरिक्तं सर्वं मिथ्येति राद्धान्तः ।

Keywords: Ajnaana. Bhavarooopa Ajnaana, Mithyaa

Paper No. 10.06: Vedānta and Upanishad

नित्यजीवने सदाचारवृत्तिः

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ABSTRACT

अस्मिन्भारतक्षेत्रे अनेके धर्माः वर्तन्ते । ते सर्वेऽपि अत्यन्तं विशिष्टाः । अनेकेषु धर्मेषु तत्तदुक्तानि अनिष्ठानान्यपि प्रचलिष्यन्ति । अस्मिन् देशे अनेके आचार्याः भुवमागत्य स्वस्वमतान् प्रसार्य तेषाममूल्यं ज्ञानधारामत्र प्रास्तुवन् । तेषु आचार्येषु स्वसिद्धान्तप्रतिपादकेषु श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्याः सदाचारस्मृतिरिति ग्रन्थं विरचय्य मनुकुलस्य भृशमुपकारं कृतवन्तः । अस्माकं सर्वेषामपि आचाराः शुद्धा भवेयुः इति सम्भाव्यैवास्मिन् ग्रन्थे प्रातःकालादारभ्य सायाहपर्यन्तं किं किं करणीयं तत्सर्वमपि सङ्कलय्य अत्र निरूपितवन्तः । अस्माकं सदाचारे किं नियमाः भवेयुः तेषामवश्यकता तथा तेषां वैज्ञानिकांशसंबन्धः तत्सर्वमपि अत्र अनुवर्णिताः । ब्रह्मचर्य-गृहस्थ-सन्यास-वानप्रस्थरूपचतुराश्रमिणां समग्रमाचारम् अत्र निरूपितः आचार्यैः । तथा अत्रोक्ताः आचाराः अस्मिन् जगति प्राप्तजन्मानमस्माकम् उपकारायैव भवेत् जीवननिर्वहणे । अत्र यदुक्तं तत्सकलं केवलमेकस्यैव वक्तुं न शक्यते । सर्वेषामपि मतिजीविनामपि इदमुपदिष्टम् शास्त्रोक्तमिति तु विषयेस्मिन्नास्ति संशितिलेशोऽपि ।

Paper No. 10.07: Vedānta and Upanishad

उपनिषत् चिन्तनदृष्टौ कनकदासः

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ABSTRACT

कीर्तनानि रचयन् तानि गायन् च कनकदासः जीवनं यापयति स्म । कदाचित् वैकुण्ठः कियद्दूरं वर्तेत इति भावः तस्मिन् उत्पन्नः । हरिदर्शने उत्कण्ठा प्रवृद्धा । केशवमन्दिरे अर्चकः नीराजनं करोति स्म । नीराजनस्य प्रकाशः केशवस्य नेत्रयोः प्रतिफलितः । अनुक्षणं प्रतिफलितं तेजः सर्वत्र प्रसृतम् । अर्चकः गर्भगृहम् इत्येतत्सर्वमपि अदृश्यतां गतम् । नेत्रस्फारे प्रज्वले प्रकाशे साक्षात् विष्णुः दृष्टः । कनकदासः भाववशः गीतम् आरब्धवान् ।

एतावत्कालं वैकुण्ठं, बहुदूरम् इति वदति स्म । निष्ठाकारणतः अद्य रङ्गनाथस्य दर्शनम् अभवत् ।

(ಇಷ್ಠ ದಿನವೇ ವೈಕುಂಠ ಎಷ್ಟು ದೂರ ಎನ್ನುತ್ತಲಿದ್ದೆ, ನಿಷ್ಠೆಯಿಂದಲಿ ನಾನು ಕಂಡೆ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಗೀಶನ ಶ್ರೀರಂಗಶಾಲಿ)

कथा इव भासन्ते चेदपि उपनिषदां मूलध्येयः मोक्षत्वम् । कनकदासेन प्रज्ञानं ब्रह्म इति वाक्यम् अनुसरता भक्तिज्ञानेन परमात्मा अवाप्तः । केशवः एव सर्वस्वम् इति वदन् अयमात्मा ब्रह्मा इति वाक्यं सार्थकम् अकरोत् । हे केशव । त्वमेव तत्त्वमसि इति वदन् आत्मनामककेशवः सर्वत्र अस्ति । अहं ब्रह्मास्मि इति च कथितवान् । इत्थम् उपनिषदः सर्वस्मिन् भारतीये अपि आत्मरूपेण प्रवहन्ति । तेषां जागरणं कार्यरूपे आनयनं च करणीयम् । तेन श्रेष्ठ-कनकदाससदृशाः अनेके महान्तः जायेरन् । ततः आत्मोन्नतिः स्वस्थसमाजनिर्माणं च भविष्यति ।

Paper No. 10.08: Vedānta and Upanishad

द्वैतवेदान्ते मानवतावादः

बदरीनाथ बळ्ळारि

अतिथि उपन्यासकः, शोधकर्ता च द्वैतवेदान्त विभागः

राष्ट्रीयसंस्कृतविश्वविद्यालयः, तिरुपति:

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ABSTRACT

“भारतस्य प्रतिष्ठे द्वे संस्कृतं संस्कृतिस्तथा” इति आभाणकं सर्वैरपि विदितमेव। तेनावगम्यते अस्माकं संस्कृतिः संस्कृते अन्तर्हिता इति। अस्मिन् संस्कृतशेवधौ महदिदं रत्नं विलसति श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता इति। तस्याः वैशिष्ट्यमस्ति इदं यत् तत्रोक्तविचारप्रणाली नास्तिकस्य नास्तिकतां, आस्तिकस्य आस्तिकतां, कर्मठस्य कर्मनिष्ठाम्, आधुनिकस्य प्रौढिवादम् इति यस्य यादृशी मनीषा यावती विस्तृता अथवा यावती संकुचिता तत्तत् प्रति तथैव बोधयति इति। तत्र आधुनिकविज्ञानसम्बद्धाः महान्तः प्रमेयांशाः अपि सरळभाषया निरूपिताः वर्तन्ते। उदाहरणार्थं :-आत्मैव ह्यात्मनो बन्धुरात्मैव रिपुरात्मनः इदं वाक्यं मनश्शास्त्रसम्बद्धं । न केवलं मनश्शास्त्रम्, अपि तु नानाशास्त्राणां उल्लेखः दरीदृश्यते। एवं सामाजिकाः अपि विषयाः प्रायशः न्यभासिषुः। अतः तद्विषये अनुसन्धानं अतीवावश्यकं वरीवर्ति। इमं ग्रन्थं आधृत्य नैके दार्शनिकाः व्याख्यानमालाः व्यरीरचन्। तेषु अन्यतमद् विराजते भगवता आनन्दतीर्थमुनिना विरचितं गीताभाष्यतात्पर्यं च । स्वकीयसारस्वतप्रपञ्चे गीतायाः महत्वस्थानं विद्यते। एवञ्च भगवत्पादैः गीतायाः सामाजिकता सम्यक् न्यरूपि। अतः इदानीं मया अत्र द्वैतवेदान्ते मानवतावादः इत्येनं विषयमधिकृत्य प्रस्तूयते॥

द्वैतवेदान्ते मानवतावादः इमं विषयं प्रस्तोतुं मया तुलनात्मकपद्धत्यनुसरणं क्रियते। मम शोधस्य सारः एवमस्ति आधुनिकाः अधुनातनकाले humanity इति यत्कथयन्ति तस्य मूलमस्ति गीता। शोधकार्ये मया गीताभाष्य-गीतातात्पर्य- महाभारततात्पर्यनिर्णयेत्यादिसर्वमूलग्रन्थानां उपयोगः कृतः। अस्यां शोधपत्रिकायां मया एते अंशा प्रतिपाद्यन्ते। ते अंशाः अधोनिर्दिष्टाः भवन्ति॥

1. समानताविषयः।
2. प्रतिव्यक्तेः कर्तव्यं तथा तस्य आवश्यकता।
3. कर्तव्या एव देवपूजा इति प्रथमतः गीतायां निरुक्तम्।
4. कर्माधिकारिजीवस्य इच्छाधिकारोऽपि अस्ति।
5. ज्ञानसहितकर्मणः आवश्यकता।
6. भक्तिस्वेच्छाऽचारयोः मध्ये भेदः।

Paper No. 10.09: Vedānta and Upanishad

Sri Vaishnavism and Acharyas in the North, East, and West of India

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ABSTRACT

Sri Vaishnavism is not only practised in the southern part of our country, but also considerably in other parts of India. Sri Vaishnava Acharyas who perform Sri Vaishnava Deeksha (Samashrayanam) do exist in the northern, eastern, and western parts of India, belonging to both Vadakalai and Thenkalai Paramaparas. There is a research gap where other scholars have failed to trace the spread of the Vishistadvaita Siddhanta from south India to other regions and this paper is intended to highlight the same. This research would serve as a bridge to connect Sri Vaishnavas all over the country.

We have started this research with the Acharyas belonging to the Vadakalai sect and have found that most of the matams in other parts of the country originate from Sri Ahobila Matam. We have travelled to temples, matams, and other places across states in order to gather information, and we have analysed old and authentic books/grantas like Sri Sampradhay Ithihas (by Jagadguru Swami Aniruddhacharyaji-15th Pontiff of Srivatsa Math), Srirangam Andavan Ashrama Varalaru (by Sri.U.Ve.Natteri Rajagopalachariar Swami), and websites like www.sriahobilamuttmysore.in, www.anudinam.org, www.shreevatsa.com, etc., and interviewed Matadhipathis, Vidwans, and other Kainkaryaparas, both in person and through phone calls. In fact, we have made a collection of pictures and videos that also authenticate our research, which is presented in our paper.

Keywords: Sri Vaishnavism Acharyas Matams Matadhipathis Vidwans

Paper No. 10.10: Vedānta and Upanishad

चार्वाकस्य न वाक् चार्वी (युक्तिमल्लिकायां चार्वाकमतनिरासः)

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ABSTRACT

लोके चार्वाक इति लोकायत इति नाम्ना प्रसिद्धानां नास्तिक्यवादिनां मतं सर्वैरपि आस्तिकदर्शनाचार्यैः निराक्रियते इति सुविदितः विषयः। आस्तिकदर्शनेषु अन्यतमस्य द्वैतदर्शनस्य सिद्धान्तप्रतिष्ठापनाचार्येषु सोदे अथवा सोन्दा इति क्षेत्रवासिनः श्रीमद्वादिराजतीर्थगुरुसार्वभौमाः तत्त्वस्थापने प्रत्येकं स्थानमलङ्कुर्वन्ति। श्रीमद्वादिराजतीर्थानां कृतिषु युक्तिमल्लिका इति ग्रन्थः सम्पूर्णस्यापि द्वैतसिद्धान्तस्य सौरभम् आग्रापयति (गिच)। तत्र श्रीमद्वादिराजतीर्थाः चार्वाकस्य न वाक् चार्वी इत्यादि श्लोकैः चार्वाकदर्शनं निराकरोति। केवलं प्रत्यक्षस्यैव प्रामाण्यमभ्युपगन्तारं चार्वाकं प्रति किं रक्षेदात्मप्रमाणताम् इति प्रश्नपूर्वकं वाग्रूपस्य शास्त्रस्य प्रामाण्यं तावन्न प्रत्यक्षसिद्धम्। शास्त्रस्य प्रामाण्यं विना शास्त्रोक्तस्य अक्षैकमानरूपतत्त्वस्य प्रामाण्यं न सम्भवति इति तं निराकरोति।

अस्मिन्पत्रे श्रीमद्वादिराजतीर्थैः विरचितायाः युक्तिमल्लिकायाः समीक्षणतात्मकमध्ययनं क्रियते। तथा च चार्वाकस्य न वाक् चार्वी इत्यनेन चार्वाकशास्त्रस्य कुसमयित्वं प्रतिपादयन्ति। तत्र कारणं सूचयन्ति - कुर्वीतात्मवधं यतः इति। अत्र वादिराजतीर्थाः कुर्वीत इति कृधातोः आत्मनेपदस्य प्रयोगं कृतवन्तः। परस्मैपदि आत्मनेपदि उभयपदि इति विभक्तेषु धातुषु उभयपदिधातूनां यदा परस्मैपदित्वं यदा आत्मनेपदित्वं इति सूचयितुं पाणिनीयसूत्रं प्रसज्यते यत् स्वरितजितः कर्त्रभिप्राये क्रियाफले (1-3-72) इति सूत्रानुसारेण ये धातवः स्वरितान्ताः उत जितान्ताः सन् तत्फलस्य यदि कर्तारमेवाधिगच्छन्ति तदा आत्मनेपदि प्रत्ययाः भवन्ति इति सूत्राभिप्रायः। तेन ज्ञायते यत् शास्त्रस्य प्रयोजनरूपं यत्फलं तत् कर्तारं चार्वाकमेवेति इति फलं च आत्मवधमित्यनेन सूचितम्। तथा च अक्षैकमानरूपं तत्त्वं धर्माद्यभावं वदता चार्वाक एव मृतिमेष्यति इति प्रतिपदयन्ति। अनेन श्रीमद्विष्णुतत्त्वनिर्णयोक्तं धर्माद्यभावज्ञानेन परस्परहिंसादिना अपकारस्यैव प्राप्तेः इति आचार्यवाक्यं सूचितं भवति। एवं रूपेण युक्तिमल्लिकायां व्याकरणांशाः तथा तत्त्वप्रतिपादने सूचिताः सर्वमूलग्रन्थांशाश्च समीक्षिताः।

प्रधानांशाः

न चार्वी कुसमय इति यावत्

युक्तिमल्लिका ग्रन्थविशेषः

अक्षैकमानं चार्वाकस्य तत्त्वम्

आत्मवधं चार्वाकशास्त्रस्य प्रयोजन

Paper No. 10.11: Vedānta and Upanishad

तैत्तिरीयोपनिषदि अद्वैत-द्वैतरीत्या ज्ञानकर्मसमुच्चयवादविमर्शः

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सुखप्राप्तये दुःखनिवृत्तये च सर्वेऽपि मानवाः विविधेषु उपायेषु प्रवर्तन्ते। लौकिकैः उपायैः पुरुषार्थमलभमानाः पुनः पुनः संसरन्ति। तदर्थं उपायान्वेषणे प्रवृत्ताः दृश्यन्ते। तेषाम् अनितरसाधारणः उपायः भवति वेदोपनिषदादिशास्त्रम्। तदेवोक्तं तेषां दुःखप्रहाणाय श्रुतिरेषा प्रवर्तते इति। श्रुतीनामुपनिषदाश्च अर्थनिर्णयाय तावत् प्रवृत्तं वेदान्तदर्शनम्। वेदान्तशब्देन मुख्यतया उपनिषद् प्रथिता। परा विद्या इति प्रसिद्धा इयम्। अस्याः अध्ययनेन अविद्यानाशः, मोक्षप्राप्तिः, दुःखक्षयश्च भवति। अनेकाः उपनिषदः सन्ति चेदपि ईशादि-दशोपनिषदः प्रसिद्धाः। तत्रान्यतमा तैत्तिरीयोपनिषद्। कृष्णयजुर्वेदान्तर्गततैत्तिरीयारण्यके वर्तत एषोपनिषद्। इयं शिक्षा-ब्रह्मानन्द-भृगुनामाङ्कितवल्लीत्रयोपेता। तयोः आधारेण अर्थात् अद्वैत-द्वैतरीत्या ज्ञानकर्मसमुच्चयवादविमर्शनं शोधप्रबन्धस्यास्य मुख्यं लक्ष्यम्।

कूटशब्दाः -ज्ञानेनैव कैवल्यमिति , ज्ञानेन भगवत्प्रसादः, स्वानन्दानुभवप्राप्तिः ,तैत्तिरीयोपनिषदि ,अद्वैत-द्वैतरीत्या ज्ञानकर्मसमुच्चयवादविमर्शः ।

Paper No. 10.12: Vedānta and Upanishad

व्याकरणवाङ्मयस्य वैशिष्ट्यम्

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ABSTRACT

मानवाः भावजीवनाः। तेषां भावनानां परस्परं वचननमयार्थं ननतरां भाषा अपेक्षते। अनया साधनभूतया एव प्राणिषु मानवाः सववश्रेष्ठाः इत्युच्यते। ववश्वस्स्िन् अनेकाः भाषाः सस्तत। तासु देववािी सांस्कृ तभाषा सवावसां भाषािाां जननी इत ननगद्यते। अस्याः भाषायाः साधुत्वसम्पादनार्थं ववद्यते व्याकरिवाङ्मयम्। इदां व्याकरिं वेदस्य अङ्गभूतम्। “एकाः शब्दाः सम्यग् ज्ञाताः शास्त्रास्तवताः सुप्रयुक्ताः स्वगेव लाेके कामधुग्भवनत” इत पातञ्जले महाभाष्येपतञ्जललना भणितम्। शब्दाः शास्त्रज्ञानपुरस्सरां साधु प्रयुक्ताः स्वगेव लाेके च माेक्षदायकाे भवनत इत तात्पयवम्। तस्िाद् अवश्यां व्याकरिम् अध्येयम्। व्यावियतते अनेन शब्दाः इत व्याकरिम्। एते शब्दाः साधवाः इत ननश्चयात्िकां ज्ञानां व्याकरिस्य अध्ययनेन एव जायते। तत्र इतराः, चतराः, अावपशली, शाकटायनाः, पाणिनाः इत्येवां नैके व्याकरिचायावाः ववद्यतते। सवेवऽवप व्याकरिसम्बद्धान् ग्रथान् रचयामासाः। तत्र व्याकरिध्ययनपरम्परायां द्विधा ववभागाः वतवते।

➤ एेतरां व्याकरिम्।

➤ माहेश्वरव्याकरिम्।

एेतरां व्याकरिम् अत्यततां प्राचीनम्, उपलब्धाै दुःशकां च। कालेऽस्स्िन् माहेश्वरव्याकरिं प्रससद्मम्। सवैवाः अस्यैव अध्ययनां वियते। अत्र प्राधातयेन पाणिननववरलचता सूत्रबद्धा अष्टाध्यायी, वररुलचववरलचतां वानतवकम्, पतञ्जललववरलचतां महाभाष्यम् एतेषां ग्रथानाम् अध्ययनां वियते। एतान् ग्रथानिधधक् त् अनेके व्याख्याग्रथार्थाः, प्रवियाग्रथार्थाः, टीकाः, ननबतधाः वतवतते। एतेषामवप ग्रथानाम् अध्ययनां कालेऽस्स्िन् भवनत। भगवान् पाणिनाः अल्पाक्षरैः असस्तदग्रूपेि अत्यततलाघवेन सरलरतया व्याकरिससद्भाततान् सूत्ररूपेि युयाेज। तस्िात् अयां लाेकाः पाणिनीयव्याकरिम् अध्ययनार्थवम् अाश्रयनत।

तत्र व्याकरिध्ययनस्य प्रयाेजनानन कानन ? पाणिनीयव्याकरिध्ययने साैलभ्यां वकम् ? कर्था पाणिनना लाघवेन

वैयाकरिससद्भातताः ननबद्धाः ? अष्टाध्यायीसूत्रप्रकाराणि कानन ?

Keywords – Panineeya Ashtadhyayi, Patanjali’s Mahabhashya.

Paper No. 10.13: Vedānta and Upanishad

Adwaita Darsana Through the view point of Sree Sankaracharya and Sree Narayana Gurudeva : An Analysis

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ABSTRACT

It is obvious from nowhere that Sree Shankaracharya and Sree Narayana Gurudeva are the Paramacharyas that Kerala has given to the world. There are many similarities and differences between the lives of both. It can be seen that the culture of the people and the characteristics of the period have had a great impact on the outlook and lifestyle of the two Mahatmas. Both are Advaitacharyas. Advaita - non-dual i.e. one. Therefore, the thought of Sree Shankar's advaita and Sree Narayanagurudev's advaita has no place. Advaita is empirical. For those who have died in that pure consciousness, Gurudev prescribes that 'All is Nijabodha only'. Some people wrongly assume that Sree Shankaracharya is the originator of Advaita. Sri Shankaracharya has nowhere said that Advaita Vedanta philosophy is a new philosophy that he discovered. Darshan is mainly expressed through the interest determination of Shruti. Advaita Darshan was irresistibly formulated on the basis of sruti and logic, and he did theorizing. In this paper an attempt to made about the different view points of Adwaita darsana by Sree Sankara and Sree Narayana Gurudeva

Paper No. 10.14: Vedānta and Upanishad

॥श्रीमद्-हनुमद्गीमध्वान्तर्गत-रामकृष्णवेदव्यासात्मकलक्ष्मीहयग्रीवाय नमः॥

वणागनां ननत्यत्वाननत्यत्वनवषये श्रीमन्मध्वाचायागणां योर्दानां

डा.श्रीहरर.रा.वाळवेक् अनीपानिकाध्यापकः.

द्वैतवेदान्तनवभास्य. रानियसांस्कृतनवश्वनवद्याननलयः.नतरुपनत

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नवददतचरमेव समेषां, यद्वैनिष्यां पदसमुदायात्मनां वाक्यानांसवगसम्पकगसांिनत्वरूपम्(it is a

communicaication) such as omni channel] अनप च न भवनत तत्वाक्यम्, नवना पदसमुदायात्

। दकञ्च न सम्भवत तत्पदम्, वणगसमुदयमन्तरेनत (word means a group of letters) । the letters

वणागस्तावत्न प्रारुच्चारणात्(before pronousation) उपलभ्यन्ते। नानप उच्चारणादान्तरम् their are

letters तेवणागः प्रायः तत्षण एव उत्पद्यन्तेनवनश्यन्त चेत भासते। दकञ्च वणोत्पत्तां प्रनत उच्चारणमेव

कारणनमनत भानत । परन्तुअनुभावानुरेण सम्यक्परिीलने, न वणागनां षणेनोत्पनतः नािो वा नवद्यत इनत

अवर्त्यते। यथा अकाि-काल-प्रकृत्यादयः ननत्याः(उत्पनतनवनािरनहताः), तथा वणागअनप तेष्वन्यतमा

ननत्या इनत (unborn and undead) । नभन्ननभन्नकालैः प्रनतव्यक्त्युच्चररताः वणागएक एवे”नत वणैक्यां

अनुभूयते। यथा;- देवदतेनोच्चररतः “क”कारः, यज्ञदतेनानप उच्चररत इत्यादद । तस्मात् षणोत्पनतनािो

वणागनां युज्येतेतराम्। अनप तुननत्यतैव तेषाम्युज्येतेतमानमनत । नवषयोऽयांश्रीमदान्दतीथगभर्वत्पादैः

प्रत्यनभज्ञाप्रमाणतः व्यस्तार । नवष्णुतत्वननणगये- “न चोच्चारणकाल एव वणागनामुत्पनतररनत वाच्यम्।

तदेवेदां इनत वचननमनत प्रत्यनभज्ञानवरोिात्” इनत । नवषयनममनिकृत्य पाश्चात्य-पौवागत्यदिगनसाहाय्यतः च

सांिोिनांनवीयते। वणागनांषणनकतामाहः माध्यनमकाः। केचन कत्वां’त्वां इनत सामान्यस्य (जातेः) ननत्यत्वां,

वणागनांचाननत्यत्वांनवजर्ुः । नवदिपीनडया – The same letterform may be used in different

alphabets but have different sounds. इनत । द्वैतवेदान्तेवणागनांननत्यत्वाननत्यत्वे

श्रीमन्मध्वाचायागणां योर्दानांनवनिष्यते। तौलननकरूपेण सांिोधयोऽयांनवषयः समाजोपयोर्ाय भवेत्।

तदुपयोर्तया इमेग्रन्थाः अनुसन्दिताः= नवष्णुतत्वननणगयः,

ब्रह्मसूत्रअनुव्याख्यानां,श्रीमन्न्यायसुिा,तत्वसांख्यानां, WIKIPEDIA [wikipedia.com] इत्यादयः ।

इमेसनञ्चन्त्यन्तेऽनस्मन्िोिपनत्रकायाम्---

1. वणागनांननत्यत्वम्।

2. वणोत्पनतनािसािक-बािके।

Paper No. 10.15: Vedānta and Upanishad

दशोपनिषत्

अर्चना चन्द्रशेखर भट्ट

ABSTRACT

वेदानां अन्तः यस्मिन् सह वेदान्तः। अन्त शब्दस्य निश्चयः इत्यर्थः। वेदानां सारभूतः अर्थः वेदान्तः इत्यभिप्रायः। तत्र मीमांसायाः प्रथमः भागः कर्ममीमांसा इत्युच्यते। उत्तरः भागः ब्रह्मीमांसा अथवा शारीरकमीमांसा इति शब्देन अभिधीयते। ज्ञानप्रधानभूतम् इदं वेदान्तदर्शनम्। उपनिषद्, भगवद्गीता, ब्रह्मसूत्राणि इति प्रस्थानत्रयं वेदान्तदर्शने आकारग्रन्थत्वेन स्वीक्रियते। भूमिमिदं सम्प्राप्य यथा एकैका सरित् बहुधा विभजते, तथैव एकमेव इदं वेदान्तदर्शनम् बहून् शुद्धान्तः कारणान् आचार्यान् सम्प्राप्य अनेकधा अभवत्। अयमेव विचारः अप्पय्यदीक्षितैः स्वग्रन्थे सिद्धान्तलेशसङ्ग्रहे उक्तः – “अधिगतभिदा पूर्वाचार्यानुपेत्य सहस्रधा, सरिदिव महीभेदान् सम्प्राप्य शौरिपदोद्गता” इत्येवं रूपेण। एवं विभक्तम् इदं वेदान्तदर्शनम् अद्वैत, द्वैत, विशिष्टाद्वैत इत्यादि नाम्ना प्रथितम्।

तत्र प्रस्थानत्रयेषु उपनिषद् अन्यतमा इत्युक्ता। दशोपनिषदः सन्ति। सामान्यतया सर्वासु उपनिषत्सु अनेकाः कथाः उपलभ्यन्ते, तस्मात् उपनिषदः कथाम् एव वर्णयन्ति इति कदाचित् भ्रमः स्यात्, तत्र आख्यायिकाः किं निमित्तीकृत्य प्रवृत्ताः इत्यंशः कदाचित् न गृहीतः स्यात् अतः उपनिषत्सु याः आख्यायिकाः उक्ताः ताः किं उद्देशेन प्रवृत्ताः इति मया विचाराः कृतः। तदत्र अद्वैतवेदान्त अनुसारेण मया अस्मिन् लेखे लिख्यते।

Paper No. 10.16: Vedānta and Upanishad

॥वैयाकरणसम्मतं वाक्यलक्षणम्॥

प्रमोद जि के

सहायक प्राध्यापकः

संस्कृत एवं संहितासिद्धान्त विभागः

श्रीराघवेन्द्र आयुर्वेद आयुर्वेद विद्यालयः

मल्लाडहल्लि, चित्रदुर्गा, कर्णाटकराज्यम्

सम्पर्कसंख्या – 9481019569

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सर्वोऽपकारकेऽस्मिन् व्याकरणशास्त्रे “वाक्यस्य टैः प्लुत उदात्तः”
इत्यनयोः सूत्रयोः
समानवाक्येनिघातयुष्मदस्मदादेशा वक्तव्याः इति वाक्यकारवचनेन च वाक्यशब्दप्रयोगो दृश्यते ।
वाक्यमुद्दिश्य कार्याण्यपि विहितानि । वाक्यस्फोटोऽतिनिष्कर्षे तिष्ठतीति मतस्थितिः इति
व्याकरणशास्त्रे वाक्यस्फोटस्यैवार्थप्रतिपादकतया निर्णीतत्वेन
लोकेऽर्थविषयकप्रथमिकार्थबोधजनकत्वञ्च वाक्य एवाभ्युपगमत्वेन वाक्यशब्दस्य निष्कृष्टार्थः कः
कीदृशी तस्य परिभाषा इत्यत्र प्रबन्धे यथा प्रतिभानं प्रस्ताव्यते ।

अधो निर्दिष्टानि वार्तिककारस्य भगवतो वररुचोराद्यान्यपूर्वाणि च वाक्यलक्षणानि
महाभाष्यकारैः महाभष्ये संद्गृहीतानि । तानि च -

- 1 आख्यातं साव्यकारकविशेषणं वाक्यम् ।
- 2 सक्रियाविशेषणं च ।
- 3 एकतिङ् वाक्यम् ।

प्रथमवाक्यलक्षणस्य अवान्तरवाक्यलक्षणानि त्रीणि संपद्यन्ते ।

- 1 आख्यातं साव्ययं वाक्यम् । उदा - उच्चैः पठति । नीचैः पठति ।
- 2 आख्यातं स्मारकं वाक्यम् । उदा - ओदनं पचति ।
- 3 आख्यातं सकारकविशेषणं वाक्यम् । उदा - ओदनं मृदु विशदं पचति ।
- 4 सक्रियाविशेषणं च वाक्यं भवति । उदा - सुष्ठु पचति । दुष्ठु पचति ।

अत्राव्ययकारकविशेषणानि प्रत्येकं समुदितानि चाश्रीयन्ते । समुदितस्य देवदत्तः
शोभनं तण्डुलं स्थाल्यां विशदं पचतीत्युदाहरणम् ।

⁴अष्टाध्यायी सूत्रपाठः ८-२-८२

⁵अष्टाध्यायी सूत्रपाठः ८-१-८

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प्रश्नोपनिषदि वर्णितं पञ्चप्राणस्य आयुर्वेदानुसारं महत्त्वम्

डॉ. दर्शना दि वरगंटीवार

सहायकप्राध्यापक संस्कृत संहिता सिद्धान्त विभागः,

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प्रस्तावना

उपनिषद् ब्रह्मविद्यायाः आदि स्रोतः । आत्मनः यथार्थ स्वरूपस्य बोधनमुपनिषदानां प्रमुखः उद्देशः। मानवकल्याणाय तथाच मोक्षार्थमुपनिषदानां रचना जाता। एतेषां सङ्ख्या 108 तत्रापि 10 उपनिषदः प्रमुखाः सन्ति ईश-केन-कठ-प्रश्न-मुण्ड-माण्डुक्यः- तित्तिरः ऐतरेयं च छान्दोग्यं बृहदारण्यकं तथा । अज्ञानतः प्रकाशं प्रति गमनस्य मार्गः नः उपनिषदः दर्शयति। वेदानामन्तिममं भागमुपनिषद् कथ्यते। कर्म, उपासना, ज्ञान त्रिषु काण्डेषु ज्ञानकाण्डस्य विवेचनं तत्रोपलभ्यते। साक्षात् कामधेनुः खलु उपनिषद्। आयुर्वेदः अथर्ववेदस्य उपवेदः इति मन्यते । तत्रापि मानवस्वास्थ्याय कल्याणाय च बोधनं कृतमस्ति। धर्मार्थकाममोक्षाणामारोग्यं साधनं वर्तते। उत्तमारोग्येनैव जीवने सर्वं साधयितुं शक्यते । प्रश्नोपनिषदि वर्णितं पञ्चप्राणः (प्राणः, उदान, समानः, व्यान, अपानः) आयुर्वेदस्यात्मास्ति । विना वायुना शरीरं न जीवति । यावद् वायुः स्थितो देहे तावदेव जीवनम् । तस्य निष्कान्तिः मरणमुच्यते। तदर्थं प्रश्नोपनिषदि एवमायुर्वेदशास्त्रे वायोः इत्युक्ते पञ्चप्राणस्य महत्त्वं कथितमस्ति । अस्मिन् शोध निबन्धेऽस्य बोधनस्य प्रयत्नं कृतमस्ति।

व्याप्तिः

प्राणादि (पञ्चप्राणसंदर्भे) ऐतरेय, माण्डुक्योपनिषद्यप्युक्तमस्ति तथापि विस्तारभयाद् केवलं प्रश्नोपनिषदि वर्णितं पञ्चप्राणविषयमधिकृत्यास्मिन् शोधपत्रे लिखितमस्ति । तथा च आयुर्वेदग्रन्थे त्रिदोषेषु वातदोषः एकः अतः तत्रापि वायुं विना नैव किमपि साधयितुं शक्यते। आयुर्वेद संहितायां यत्रतत्र पञ्चप्राणविषये ज्ञानमुलभ्यते। अत्र केवलं तस्य महत्त्वं एतद्विषये विचारं कृतमास्ति।

उद्देशः

उपनिषदि एवं आयुर्वेदशास्त्रे वर्णितं पञ्चप्राणविषयस्य बोधनं प्रमुखः उद्देशः ।

संशोधन पद्धतिः

अस्यशोधपत्रस्य संशोधनपद्धतिः विवेचनात्मकं भवति ।

बीजशब्दाः

उपनिषद्, पञ्चप्राणः, आयुर्वेदः, वेदः, पिप्पलादमुनिः, चरकसंहिता, अष्टाङ्गहृदयम्, प्राणः, उदानः, समानः, व्यानः, अपानः आदि ।

Paper No. 10.18: Vedānta and Upanishad

Śrī-Lakṣmī: Exploring the relationship between etymological and philosophical discourses in the Viśiṣṭādvaita school.

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ABSTRACT

Goddess Śrī occupies a vital position in the ontology and theology of the Viśiṣṭādvaita school. The *Paratattva* Viṣṇu-Nārāyaṇa being eternally and inseparably associated with Śrī-Lakṣmī is one of the most distinguishing doctrines of the Viśiṣṭādvaita philosophy. Śrī and Lakṣmī are two names synonymously used to refer to the Goddess. K.S.Narayanacharya (2000)⁶ notes that the etymological meanings for the term Lakṣmī given by Yāskācārya are reflected in a work by Parāśara Bhaṭṭar, a disciple of Rāmānujācārya, known as ‘*Śrīguṇaratnakośa*’. And that these meanings correspond to the etymological meanings of Śrī and Lakṣmī found in the *Lakṣmī Tantra*. This suggests a strong link between the etymological and philosophical discourses in the authoritative texts of the Viśiṣṭādvaita *Sampradāya* that is worth exploring.

Thus, this paper attempts to highlight the underlying relationship between the etymological and philosophical discourses in the Viśiṣṭādvaita school by exploring the etymologies of Śrī and Lakṣmī as given in Yāskācārya’s *Nirukta* and *Sampradāyika* texts like *Lakṣmī Tantra* and *Śrīguṇaratnakośa* in the light of the general tenets with regards to Goddess Śrī-Lakṣmī in the Viśiṣṭādvaita school. This also helps bring to fore the role of etymology in enunciating the nature and role of Śrī-Lakṣmī in the Viśiṣṭādvaita school. Moreover, the probable interdependency between etymological and philosophical discourse itself is an important topic of study.

Keywords: Śrī-Lakṣmī, Viśiṣṭādvaita, Etymology, Philosophy

⁶ K.S. Narayanacharya, *The Role of Sri in Srivaisnavism – A Critical View*, in Sri-Laksmi – Legends and Lores, Ananthacharya Indological Research Institute, Mumbai, 2000, p.50

Paper No. 10.19: Vedānta and Upanishad

लोक<सि>सं?यावाचकशब्दानां सं?यासंज्ञाविनयपणम्

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4ाकरणशाकेबन4ः संज्ञाः सूत्रकारेण आश्रययते। तेषुसं?या संज्ञास्यस्यतमा । सा च
“ब्रह्मणवतुडित सं?या”1 इत्यनेन ब्रह्मशब्दत्रय, गणशब्दत्रय, दित्तस्ययासतशब्दत्रय,
वतुषुस्ययासतशब्दत्रय च कथ्यते। यस्मिन् सूत्रेदित्त-वतुडित्तस्यस्ययोः त्रिनदशः अथापि के वलयोः
स्यस्ययोः <योग-अनहर्वात् स्ययासतत्रयैव संज्ञा । तत्रैवात्रैव “संज्ञाविधौ स्ययासतत्रयैव
तदसतिविधनापि”2 इति परंभाषायाः अनाहयणम्। “एकमः सं?यापरमाणे दित्त च”3 इत्यनेन दित्तः,
“यदेतेयः परमाणे वतुषु”4, “एकमदायां वो घः”5 इति त्रयांशाकायां वतुषुः विधानंभगवता
पाणिनिना अकारं । तत्र ब्रह्मशब्दः सं?यावचनः, वैश्वदेववचनः । गणशब्दोऽपि सं?यावचनः,
समूहवचनः । तस्मिन् सं?यावचनयोरेव ब्रह्म-गणशब्दयोः <कृतसूत्रेण सं?यासंज्ञाविधानिमित्त
ज्ञातव्यः

Paper No. 11.01: Science & Indian Philosophy

A cross sectional study to understand the effect of *Sandhyāvandanam* on emotional intelligence and mindfulness among adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Upanayana 'samskāra' followed by the practice of *Sandhyāvandanam* has been an integral part of *Hindu* philosophy, which is initiated during the crucial adolescent age of an individual's life. This *samskāra*, in the present scenario, has been reduced to a symbolic ceremony, practiced by only a few sections of the society. With problems of lowered concentration levels, diminished memory, deteriorating practical skills besides increased stress-anxiety-depression levels bothering students and increasing socio-economic crimes disturbing the society, this Observational Cross-sectional single center study was carried out at a Gurukula like residential school setting with a view to establish and endorse the positive influence of *Sandhyāvandanam* on Emotional Intelligence and Mindfulness of adolescents.

The study involved male students aged between 12-16 years residing in a Gurukula like residential school. The Gurukula had students who were practicing *Sandhyāvandanam* and also those who were not practicing *Sandhyāvandanam*. They were divided into two groups based on practitioners and non-practitioners of *Sandhyāvandanam*. They were assessed for their Emotional Intelligence and Mindfulness, using Emotional Intelligence Inventory and Child and adolescent mindfulness measure.

The results indicate a distinct possibility of enhancement of Emotional Intelligence and Mindfulness by proper practice of *Sandhyāvandanam* during the adolescent period of one's life, which is the crucial time of knowledge, skill and emotional advancement. These further throws light on the Indian classics which consider *Upanayana samskāra* followed by the practice of *Sandhyāvandanam* as the most important sacrament of the adolescent age.

Keywords: *Sandhyāvandanam*, Emotional Intelligence, Mindfulness, Adolescents

Paper No. 11.02: Science & Indian Philosophy

A Theoretical Study on the Role of Vedic Mathematics in Improving the Level of Mental Math

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ABSTRACT

Vedic Mathematics is an approach which exploits both halves of the brain by using the pattern recognition capabilities of one and the analytical capabilities of the other” (Ranade, 2001).

“Vedic Mathematics” is called so because of its origin in the Vedas. To be more specific, it originated from “Atharva Vedas” the fourth Veda. “Atharva Veda” deals with the branches like Engineering, Mathematics, sculpture, Medicine, and all other sciences of which we are today aware. The Sanskrit word Veda is derived from the root Vid, meaning to know without limit. The word Veda covers all Veda-Sakhas known to humanity. The Veda is a repository of all knowledge, fathomless, ever revealing as it is delved deeper. Vedic mathematics, which simplifies arithmetic and algebraic operations, has increasingly found acceptance the world over [1]. Pundits suggest that it could be a handy tool for those who need to solve mathematical problems faster by the day. Using regular mathematical steps, solving problems sometimes are complex and time consuming. But using Vedic Mathematics’ General Techniques (applicable to all sets of given data) and Specific Techniques (applicable to specific sets of given data), numerical calculations can be done very fast.

An Ancient technique, which simplifies multiplication, divisibility, complex numbers, squaring, cubing, square roots, and cube roots. Even recurring decimals and auxiliary fractions can be handled by Vedic mathematics. The basis of Vedic mathematics is the 16 sutras, which attribute a set of qualities to a number or a group of numbers. The ancient Hindu scientists (Rishis) of Bharat in 16 Sutras (Phrases) and 120 words laid down simple steps for solving all mathematical problems in easy-to- follow 2 or 3 steps. Mental sum or Vedic Mental methods can be used effectively for solving divisions, reciprocals, factorization, HCF, squares and square roots, cubes, and cube roots, algebraic equations, multiple simultaneous equations, quadratic equations, cubic equations, bi-quadratic equations, higher degree equations, differential calculus, Partial fractions, Integrations, Pythagoras Theorem, Apollonius Theorem, Analytical Conics and so on. Relating to Vedas, scholars did not use figures for big numbers in their numerical notation. There is a race against time in all the competitions. Only those people having mental sum ability will be able to win the race. Saved time can be used to solve more problems or used for difficult problems. Given the initial training in modern maths in today’s schools, students will be able to comprehend the logic of Vedic mathematics after they have reached the 8th standard. It is amazing how with the help of 16 Sutras and 13 sub-sutras, the Vedic seers were able to mentally calculate complex mathematical problems.

Paper No. 11.03: Science & Indian Philosophy

Some Aspects on Science in the Vedas

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ABSTRACT

1. The Earth is moving around the Sun. But some people (a section of the anti Bharat) like to establish that in earlier ages, in our Nation there was a mis-conception that the Sun is moving around the Earth. It is the glory of our Nation that the *Rgveda (RV)* mentions that the Earth is moving

2. The modern science says that the stars and planets are flourishing in the atmosphere due to their mental attractions. The *RV (10.64.14)* informs us this eternal truth thousands of years back.

3. The sources of energy have been classified into two as Renewable sources and Non-Renewable sources. Petroleum, Coal etc. are treated among the Renewable sources of energy, whereas solar energy, Tidal energy, wind energy etc. treated to be Renewable sources of energy. The *RV 1.163.2* informs us the concept of Solar energy :

suraa dasvam vasavo niratasta /

This may mean that the wise people may generate Solar energy. Now our Nation has been emphasizing on Solar energy. In this context it may be recalled that the Solar energy may be treated to be the best for the sacrificial purpose.

Paper No. 11.04: Science & Indian Philosophy

Contribution of Aryabhata to the Field of Mathematics

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ABSTRACT

Aryabhata is a well known astronomer and mathematician of our mother land. Since Vedic period to V CE Mathematics and Astronomy were developing hand in hand. Aryabhata has the credit of giving a separate status to Mathematics. His work आर्यभटीयम् (*Aryabhatiyam*) is a hand book of Mathematics to each and every learner. This paper tries to bring out the major contributions of Aryabhata and their present day relevance. His accuracy in calculation is appreciated. The main purpose is to motivate and to create awareness among the present generation to have an over view of the concepts that evolved in this land; rich heritage that they have; to feel proud about it and to progress in different domains of this field.

Some of the concepts dealt in this paper are – Value of π , the table of sine Values from $3^{\circ}45'$ to 90° , representation of large numbers through letters, solution of indeterminate equations, his dealing with plane figures, his method of solution of quadratic, simultaneous and other equations which are applicable even to this day.

Key word one : Contribution of Aryabhata

Key word two : Aryabhatiyam

Key word three : equations

Paper No. 11.05: Science & Indian Philosophy

संस्कृतसंहिताशास्त्रेषु भूगर्भस्थजलविज्ञानम् ।

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ABSTRACT

जगति जलविषयक-चिन्ता अस्ति तर्हि तस्य निराकरणं प्राचीन संस्कृत ग्रन्थे दृश्यते । वराहमिहिरस्य (इ.स.५००) बृहत्संहितासूत्राणाम् वैज्ञानिकदृष्ट्या यदि परीक्षणं भवति तदा समाजस्य परमकल्याणार्थं भवतीति स्पष्टीभूतः । भूमिगतजलप्राप्तिसम्बन्धे बृहत्संहिताशास्त्रेषु बहवः विषयाः दृष्टिपथमायान्ति । बृहत्संहितायां भूगर्भस्थजलस्थितिसंबन्धिः दकार्गलाख्यः (उदक –water, अर्गल = obstacle) महत्त्वपूर्णविषयः वर्णितमस्ति । अयं विषयः भूगर्भे संचितस्य जलस्य स्थिति सम्यक् प्रकाशयति । उदक-दक् -उद् - शब्दानां दकार्गलशब्दस्यार्थः जलशृङ्खलेति कथितम् । तत्तु आधुनिकविज्ञानेन जलशिरा (Aquifer) इति कथ्यते । भारते न केवलं मरुभूम्याम अपि तु यत्र जलस्य दुर्भिक्ष्य अस्ति तत्र वराहमिहिर महाभागेन उक्तमोपायस्य प्रयोगः करणीय इति मन्ये । आधुनिक काले तु विविधा उपायाः, संशोधनं जातं किंतु तत् पर्याप्तं नास्ति । प्राचीनसाहित्ये एतादृशं विज्ञानं भवति; तस्य आधुनिक-विज्ञानेन सह कलानुरूपेण मेलनं कर्तव्यमिति मन्यते । अवर्षणप्रान्ते शुद्धजलप्राप्तार्थं संहितासु कथितमोपायानां प्रयोगः कृत्वा पचीन-आधुनिक विज्ञानस्य मेलनं करणीयम् । इति अनुसंधानस्य उद्देशः अस्ति ।

वराहमिहिरमहाभागेन भूगर्भस्थजलविषये उत्तमविवेचनं दत्तम् । जलशिरा नाम भूगर्भस्थ वहामानाः जलप्रवाहःविद्यते । वराहमिहिरमहाभागेन आकाशस्थजलस्य विषये कथितम् –

पृथ्वीलक्षणानामनुसारेण जलोपलब्धिः कुत्र कथं नास्ति इति यदि अस्माभिः जायते तदा जनाः यदावश्यकं मधुरजलं प्रप्नुयुः। परिणामतः जलाभावस्थानेषु अनेने साक्षात् प्रयोगेण जानाः लाभान्विता भवेयुः। तेषु अस्मिन् संस्कृत जलविज्ञानसाहित्यस्य अनुसन्धानं मानवकल्याणार्थं भवेत् इति मन्यते । संशोधनस्य कृते 1.विश्लेषनात्मकपद्धतिः 3.तुलनात्मकपद्धत्याः उपयोजनं भवेत् ।

कूट शब्दाः, **Key Words** - जलविज्ञानम् - Groundwater , जलशिरा- Aquifer

Paper No. 11.06: Science & Indian Philosophy

भारतीय तत्वशास्त्रे पुनर्जन्म सिद्धान्तस्य तुलनात्मक अध्ययनम्।

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ABSTRACT

भारतीय तत्वशास्त्रेषु कर्मिणां मनुष्याणां कृते पुनर्जन्म व्यवस्था स्थापिता वर्तते. अपवाद रूपेण चार्वाकाः आत्मनः अस्तित्वं नैव अङ्गीकुर्वन्ति अतः परलोकस्य पुनर्जन्मनो वा न तत्र काचित् व्यवस्था चार्वाकाणां नास्ति कोऽपिसिद्धांतः, तैः लोकायतिकाः। अन्ये दर्शनिकाः आस्तिकाः दैवं स्वर्गलोकादि अस्तित्वं पुनर्जन्मानिच अङ्गीकुर्वन्ति। अतः सर्वेषाम् भारतीय दार्शनिकानां पूर्वपक्षत्वेन चार्वाक दर्शनं विचारं कृत्व अन्यदर्शनानां अन्तिमे विचार्यन्ते। पुनर्भवस्य विचारणियत्वे प्रथमाग्रासे चार्वाकमतं विचार्यते। एतेमरणमेव मुक्तिमिति अङ्गीकुर्वन्ति। बौद्धाः स्कंद पञ्चकेषु मिथ्या संघात भुतेषु आत्मत्वरूपेण पुनर्जन्म व्यवस्थापयन्ति। जैनाः तदेव विषयमङ्गीकुर्वन्ति। काणादाः गौतमीयाश्च नातिवाहिक शरीरं अङ्गीचक्रुः। इदं च आतिवाहिक शरीरं मरणानन्तरं जायते स्थूलदेहं दत्वाच निवर्तत इति वेदान्तिनां सम्मतिः। एवं रीत्या येयेदार्शनिकाः येनमार्गेण पुनर्जन्म आमनन्ति इति लेखनस्य मुखोवद्दश्यः।

Paper No. 11.07: Science & Indian Philosophy

शालिग्रामशिलायाः आध्यात्मिकमहत्त्वम् ।

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अऑदफढअडफ

ॐ नमो भगवते विष्णवे श्रीसालग्रामनिवासिने ।

सर्वाभीष्टबलप्रदायदुरितनिवारिणे सालग्रामाय स्वाहा ॥

सालग्राममूलमन्त्रः ।

आद्विसहस्रवर्षेभ्यः काचित् जीवाश्मशिला अस्माकं सनातनधर्मस्य किञ्चन उपासनासाधनमस्ति। तस्याः शिलायाः नाम अस्ति शालिग्रामशिला । भारतस्य विभिन्नस्थानेषु इयं शिला शालग्रामः, सालग्रामः, सालिग्रामः इत्यपि नामभिः अभिधीयन्ते । यथा शैवानां ज्योतिर्लिङ्गं तथा वैष्णवानां शालिग्रामः । शालिग्रामः भगवतः नारायणस्य अपरं नाम अपि वर्तते। नेपालदेशस्य लघुग्रामे महाविष्णुः “शालग्रामन्” इति नाम्ना अभिधीयते । एषा शिला जीवाश्मशिला (fossil) अस्ति, यस्य प्रयोगः भगवतः प्रतिनिधिरूपेण तस्य आह्वानार्थम् उपयुज्यते । यतोऽहि ammonite fossils विश्वेशु प्रसिद्धः तथापि कृष्णवर्णीया, काली-गण्डकी नद्याः उद्भूता एषा जीवाश्मशिला असामान्या । भारतीयसंस्कृतेः अनिवार्यसाधनेषु एका अस्ति ईश्वरस्य पूजा । तत्र एतस्याः जीवाश्मशिलायाः एकं महत्त्वपूर्णं स्थानं दृश्यते ।

एतस्याः शिलायाः विषये अधिकं ज्ञातुम् अपि च तस्य महत्त्वस्य विषये अवगमनार्थम् अस्य लेखस्य उपयोगः भवति । एतस्य लेखस्य हेतुः अस्ति कथं नेपालदेशे प्राप्यमाणा एषा शिला भारतस्य उपासनासाधनेषु अन्यतमम् अभवत् । शालिग्रामः काचित् शिला इति केषाञ्चन मतम् । केचन तु ammonite fossil इति वदन्ति। एषः एव शोधकार्यस्य मुख्यतत्त्वम् । शालग्रामशिलायाम् अङ्कितानि चिह्नानि महाविष्णोः सुदर्शनचक्रस्य प्रतिनिधिरूपेण पश्यन्ति वैष्णवाः । शालिग्रामशिलाः विविधवर्णेषु यथा रक्ताः, नीलाः, कृष्णाः, हरिताः उपलभ्यन्ते । विविधवर्णानां पूजनेन विविधफलानि इति मतं बहुत्र दृश्यते । एवमेव विविधचिह्नानि महाविष्णोः विविधावतारान् सूचयति । एतस्य लेखस्य शोधप्रविधिः तु विभिन्नग्रन्थकर्तृणां ग्रन्थाः, लेखाः च सन्ति । विविधपुराणेषु उल्लिखितानाम् अंशानाम् अध्ययनम् अपि क्रियते ।

ऑङ्खळः शालग्रामशिला, जीवाश्मशिला, आध्यात्मम्, गण्डकीनदी, गण्डकीनदी इत्येतत् ।

Paper No. 11.08: Science & Indian Philosophy

Exploring the Connections between Vaisheshika Philosophy and Modern Physics: A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

In the sixth century BCE, the Indian philosopher Kanada established the Vaisheshika School. This school pursues a methodical approach to metaphysics and the essence of reality. The scientific study of the basic characteristics of matter, space, time, and so on. Modern physics has a wide-ranging field. There are numerous eminent physicists who have made significant contributions to the physical universe. The main objective of this paper is to compare and point out the similarities of Vaisheshika philosophy and Modern Physics.

There are several ideas in the ancient Indian Vaisheshika philosophy that are analogous to those in contemporary Physics. Like Atomism, which is a key premise in Vaisheshika philosophy, is the notion that physical objects are made of eternal, unbreakable, point-like atoms. This notion is comparable to the atomic theory of current physics, Sir Isaac Newton was a physicist who formulated the laws of motion. Long before Newton, Kanada describes the laws of motion in Vaisheshika sutra. According to Vaisheshika philosophy, space and time are separate, self-sufficient beings. This is comparable to the contemporary physics idea of space-time..And in the case of Causality, Pluralism ,etc... We can see many such parallels. This paper aims to bring out such analogies by interpreting the Vaisheshika Sutras.

Keywords: Physics and Vaisheshika Philosophy, Modern physics and vaisheshika, Ancient Indian science, Atomism in vaisheshika, Laws of motion and vaisheshika philosophy

Paper No. 11.09: Science & Indian Philosophy

EMBRYOLOGY: Modern and Vedic viewpoint.

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ABSTRACT

Science and spirituality has always remained a burning issue for large community of thinkers and leaders. Modern scientific advancements have achieved success in making gross material tools for sense enjoyment but they have little knowledge about subtle factors like emotions, mind, intelligence, ego etc which have far more impact on us. Embryology is always a fascinating field and lot of advancement has happened in this field in terms of understanding development of embryo in womb. But there is very little which can be done to modify that. When we look our scriptures especially Srimad Bhagvatam, there is a comprehensive description of development of embryo which not only matches the modern day conclusions but also gives a more comprehensive understanding of life.

In the current article we compared the Embryological description from Scriptures and standard embryology books. There were lots of similarities noticed like description of fertilization, formation of Morula and blastocyst which was described as PLUM SHAPE in scriptures. Furthermore, description of universal flexion postures and kicking was comparable. Scriptures also were giving description of life entering the sperm which were not found in modern text books. We conclude that modern scientists should be open minded and understand that GOD is a reality and scriptures are very important in understanding this universe as well as the origin and purpose of life.

Keywords: Embryology, Medicine, Vedic Scriptures, similarities, God.

Paper No. 11.10: Science & Indian Philosophy

Understanding the Pattern of Existence

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ABSTRACT

We all have questions on how the whole cosmos come to existence including ourselves and entire human race were seeking answers since ages. Presently Big Bang Theory is being popularized for the origin of our Universe. But the assumption of the whole universe has started from a singularity, that is a point of infinite density and heat is not correct it is purely due to mathematical extrapolation. Singularity (hypothetically containing the entirety of space) is not a physical thing and it is really not the Big Bang theory says. Big Bang is not the starting point of Universe but is the event thereafter. The cosmic inflation occurred in just 10^{-32} secs from beginning and at the epoch of inflation gradual expansion takes over. Parallel to this description thousands of years ago, according to Sankhya Darshanas, Srushti Utpathi has being mentioned from Prakruthi dravyas i.e Avyaktha, Mahat and Ahankara.

It is quit intuitive that without the advent of modern sophisticated technologies like Hubble telescope or CMB telescopes, how our Rishis could possibly had conceptualized the origin of cosmos thousands of years before. Perhaps this must be from their known experiences of waking, dreaming and deep sleep; fundamental experiences that all experience every day might have driven them to derive an elaborate description about how this cosmos might have come to existence. These experiences are Avastha Traya explained in Mandukya Upanishad, in order to point out the fourth one who is the consciousness which is experiencing these experiences. Mandukya Upanishad is one of the 10 important Upanishad of which are considered as one among the 3 central books of Advaita Vedanta. Through this article a humble attempt is made to understand how our everyday experience of waking, dreaming and deep sleep may be extrapolated to understand the pattern of existence.

Keywords: Pattern of existence, Big Bang Theory, Cosmic Inflation, Avyaktha, Mahat, Ahankara, Mandukya Upanishad, Advaita Vedanta.

Paper No. 11.11: Science & Indian Philosophy

A Study on Ancient Indian Origin Vedic Mathematics for Fast Calculations

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ABSTRACT

India is well known for its cultural heritage, and Sanskrit knowledge and Mathematics nontraditional methods. Vedic Mathematics is ancient Indian origin knowledge rediscovered between 1911 and 1918 and exposed to the world in 1957 by Sri Bharathi Krishna Tirthaji Maharaj. Most of the students find difficulties or challenges in Quantitative Aptitude part in Competitive Examinations, which requires good foundations in Mathematics. Vedic Mathematics is well known for fast calculations, improves logical ability, and logical thinking in all levels of users. Vedic Mathematics contains 16 suthras or formulae and 13 Sub-suthra or Sub-formulae written initially in Sanskrit. Vedic Mathematics is shortest path to crack Competitive Examinations. The different Suthras are Ekadhikina Purvena, Nikhilam Navatashcaramam Dashatah, Urdhva-Tiryagbyham, Paraavartya Yojayet, Shunyam Saamyasamuccaye, Anurupyena-Sunyamanyat, Sankalana-Vyavakalanabhyam, Puranapuranyam, Chalana-Kalanabyham, Yaavadunam, Vyashtisamanstih, Shesanyankena Charamena, Sopaantyadvayamantyam, Ekanyunena Purvena, Gunitasamuchyah, and Gunakasamuchyah. In this paper 16 Suthra and 13 Sub-sutras compared with traditional method. A detailed literature review on Role of Vedic Mathematics in fast calculations are made and analyzed. Based on the study some recommendations also made.

Keywords: Vedic Mathematics, Sutras, Sub-sutras, Sanskrit, Quantitative Aptitude, Competitive Examination

Paper No. 11.12: Science & Indian Philosophy

Geometrical Aspects of Maṇḍalas in Hindu Rituals

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ABSTRACT

Rituals in *Āgamas* consist of several constituents such as preparing ritual items (*dravyas*) required for rituals, drawing *maṇḍalas*, coloring *maṇḍalas*, invoking deities in *maṇḍalas* and then worshipping them. Among them drawing *maṇḍalas* with different geometric shapes are interesting part involved in rituals. Whether it is a Hindu ritual such as *Sudarśana-homa*, *Gaṇapati-homa*, etc., or the Buddhist tantric rituals, the constructions of *maṇḍalas* are as fundamental as the construction of the altars in *Vedic* sacrifices. Both the altars and *maṇḍalas* which are related to some or the other kind of rituals, basically comprise geometrical structures. Geometry in ancient India dates back prior to 800th BCE when altars of different shapes and sizes needed to be constructed in order to perform *yāgas*. Some common geometrical figures such as triangles, squares, circles, hexagons, etc., were basic structures used in building altars. As a part of performing *Vedic* rituals, in almost all sacrifices, the tradition of drawing *maṇḍalas* or *yantras* is seen. These *maṇḍalas* being an essential part of the rituals also consists of a few basic geometrical shapes along with a few natural colors filled within. In my paper, I will discuss different geometrical patterns that appear in *maṇḍalas*, their significance, and their relevance in *Āgamas*.

Key words: *Āgama* , altars, geometry, *homa*, *maṇḍalas*, *yantra*.

Paper No. 11.13: Science & Indian Philosophy

The Grotesque as the Sublime: Transcendental and Ecosophy in the Poetry of Karaikkal Ammai

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ABSTRACT

Karaikkal Ammai, or the mother of "Karaikkal" is an unparalleled woman saint poet of India whose religious fervour and poetic compositions ushered epistemic and poetic revolutions, that shook the Tamil devotional and poetic landscapes. This powerful poet of the sixth century has created one hundred and forty three poems in three anthologies viz. *Thiruvirattai Manimalai*, *Thinivaalankaatu Mootha Thirupatigangal* and *Thiruvivettai Manimalai*, in praise of Siva. Apart from being a pioneering woman saint poet in Tamil, she is the precursor of the later formulated Saiva Siddhantha mode of worship. Her poems present an iconoclastic ecological terrain, where the grotesque mundane is transcreated into a sublime medium of devotion. Thus, the burning cremation ground, the ghouls, cobra, the garland of skulls, the sacred ash, the burning corpse, vultures, jackals etc. impart a sublime philosophy of the Isvara Tattva to Ammai. Emanating from the eco-poetic tradition of traditional Sangam Tamil poetry, her poems stand out singularly in their outpour of devotion that surges with an immediacy and power that transcends the conventional essentialised notions of "female" and "feminine".

This paper would analyze the ecosophy that emerges from her brilliant poetic compositions that transform the seemingly grotesque and mundane to an everlasting sublime philosophy that transcends boundaries.

Paper No. 11.14: Science & Indian Philosophy

वेदे विज्ञानम् – समीक्षात्मकं संपादनम्

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतं नाम ज्ञानस्य विज्ञानस्य च भाण्डागारम् । संस्कृतेन अस्पृष्टः विज्ञानस्य भागः प्रायः नास्ति । अस्य फलस्वरूपभूता विज्ञानपरम्परा अधुनापि अनुवर्तमाना वर्तते । एतस्य भारतीयविज्ञानस्य अध्ययनम् अस्माभिः अधुना अत्यावश्यकं ।

Sanskrit is a classical language and has its application almost in every subject that we study today. The rich history of this language is reflected in the Vedas and Upanishads. They are verses and concepts in Vedas and Upanishads that explain the modern scientific inventions and discoveries. The attempt is made here to understand the science that was known to us in Vedic period which the modern world accepts even today.

It is said in तैत्तरीयसंहिता –

“मित्रो दधार पृथिवीमुत्तद्याम् । मित्र कृष्टीः” ।

The above line explains that the sun is the center of the solar system and it is he who upholds the other celestial objects.

Johannes Kepler, a German scientist in the 16th century stated in his Laws of Planetary Motion that –

“All planets move about the Sun in elliptical orbits, having the Sun as one of the foci”.

The above law gives the same explanation as per the verse in the तैत्तरीयसंहिता. The Vedas and their hymns are just not to please the almighty but also speaks about the science that the modern world is witnessing from a few centuries before.

Hence, it becomes very important to understand the essence of the statements that are mentioned in our Vedas and Puranas. This also gives the insight to the knowledge of our ancestors.

Keywords: तैत्तरीयसंहिता, Johannes Kepler, Laws of Planetary Motion, Vedas,

Reference: Science in Sanskrit - Samskrita Bharati

Paper No 12.01: Manuscript Preparation, Edition, & Preservation

Native Samskruth key board for Indic manuscript digitization and e-publications

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ABSTRACT

Manuscript Digitization for Indic language –E publications needs a native Indic Language character input generator and text editor. Ka-Naada is first indigenous keyboard, providing foundational ‘Svara-Vyanjana organized layout’ of all Indic languages, without recourse to (a) Romanized spelling representation of Indic script characters (b) memory-training to use complex / proprietary key-stroke sequences to generate language visuals display by Font constraints in user devices (c) Overcome constraints of OS locks and applications for manuscript editing limiting portability and edit-ability (d) limitations of QWERTY-overlay challenges for indic scripts.

Ka-Naada is USB-hardware add-on, manufactured at India, carries patented unique layout, facilitating linguistically convenient text–character– voice –sequenced inputs in ‘Svara-Vyanjana / shikshaa shaastra derivative format from Panini Shiva sutras. Ka-Naada is one key board for all Indic language manuscript editing and digitization, respecting the primary rule: Write as spoken’- Sequentially Key in Voiced sounds as articulated. The keystrokes and combinations follow the articulate voice –pronunciation, without recourse to ‘spelling feature’, an alien intrusion for Indic languages.

Ka-Naada fills the research gap of providing one uniform layout keyboard for all indic languages manuscripts. Illustration below demonstrate use of Ka-Naada in Tulu-Ramayana – manuscript editing and (i) giving a new Digital Life to ‘Tulu’ script, which was locked in manuscripts, and pending Unicode clearance. (ii) Use of plurality of technologies : OCR, image processing, Text entry, editing, in finally delivering e-publication with a hard copy. The same can be globally repeated for all indic language manuscripts, for use in higher education, research and publications.

Keywords: Ka-Naada, Tulu –Ramayana, Samskruth-key-board, Indic-manuscript-digitization, e-publications.

Paper No 12.02: Manuscript Preparation, Edition, & Preservation

॥ माध्वसम्प्रदायस्य अज्ञातताळपत्राणां संरक्षणम् ॥

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ABSTRACT

॥ माध्वसम्प्रदायस्य अज्ञातताळपत्राणां संरक्षणम् ॥

तैलात् रक्षेत् जलात् रक्षेत् रक्षेत् शिथिलबन्धनात् ।

मूर्खहस्ते न दातव्यं एवं वदति पुस्तकम् ॥ इति संस्कृते सुप्रतिथं वचनम् । हस्तप्रतिग्रन्थानां संरक्षणक्रमं महत्वञ्च उपदिशति अयं श्लोकः । अस्मत्पूर्वजाः बहून् विषयान् ग्रन्थरूपेण संरक्षितवन्तः । बहुप्रयासेनैव ग्रन्थनिर्माणं भविष्यति । ताळवृक्षस्य पत्राणि संस्कृत्य तस्मिन् लिखन्ति स्म । एताः हस्तप्रतयः शत-शतमानपर्यन्तं जीवन्ति । अत एव एताः सर्वदा अस्माभिः संरक्षणीयाः । अस्मत्पूर्वजाः हस्तप्रतीनां महत्वं उपदिश्य “कष्टेन लिखितं ग्रन्थं यत्नेन परिपालयेत्” इति आदिदिशुः । पाठशुद्धिविषये हस्तप्रतयः बहु उपकुर्वन्ति । ग्रन्थशोधने द्विविधं कार्यम् वर्तते । पाठशुद्धिः अर्थशुद्धिश्चेति । तत्र तावत् पाठशुद्धिं विना अर्थशुद्धिः न सम्भवति । अत एव शुद्धपाठार्थहस्तप्रतीनां सम्पादनं संरक्षणं आद्यं कर्तव्यं भवति । कर्नाटकस्य समुद्रप्रदेशे अपरिमिताः हस्तप्रतयः सन्ति । अस्मिन् प्रदेशे प्रतिगृहं विद्वद्ब्रह्ममासीत् । तेन कारणेन गृहेषु शताधिकाः ग्रन्थाः आसन् । परन्तु इदानीं यान्त्रिकप्रभावेण पाश्चात्यशिक्षणप्रभावेण ताः ग्रन्थाः नष्टप्रायाः अभूवन् । आदरता पूज्यता च नास्ति । केचन मूढाः ताः ग्रन्थाः अनुपयुक्ताः इति मत्वा अग्नौ नद्यां वा क्षिप्त्वा आनन्दं अनुभूतवन्तः । तथापि केचन ग्रन्थाः विद्वज्जनानां प्रभावेण संरक्षिताः सन्ति । तौळवमण्डले जगद्गुरुवः श्रीमध्वाचार्याः ग्रन्थनिर्माणे महत्तरं योगदानं ददुः । स्वयं ग्रन्थनिर्माणं कृत्वा अन्यानपि स्वशिष्यान् प्रेरयामासुः । तेन श्रीहृषीकेशादयः यतयः ग्रन्थनिर्माणं चक्रुः । परम्परागतेन प्रभावेण मठेषु ग्रन्थसंरक्षणकार्यं इदानीमपि प्रचलति । मठेषु बहवः ग्रन्थाः अमुद्रिताः सन्ति । मुद्रिता अपि अपूर्णाः सन्ति । अतः तेषां संरक्षणेन पाठशुद्धिः अर्थशुद्धिश्च लभ्यते

Paper No 12.03: Manuscript Preparation, Edition, & Preservation

ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆ: ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳ ಸಂಪಾದನೆ: ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಆಯಾಮವಾಗಿ ಭಾಷೆ

ಡಾ. ಸತೀಶ್. ಎ.ಪಿ., ಡಾ. ರಾಜೇಶ್ ಬೆಜ್ಜಿಗಳ್.

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ABSTRACT

ವಿವಿಧ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಯಾಗಿರುವ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯ ಬರೆಹ ಭಾಷೆಯನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಕ್ಕೊಳಪಡಿಸ ಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಕನ್ನಡ ಭಾಷೆಯ ವಿಕಾಸ ಕ್ರಮವನ್ನು ಅರಿಯಲು ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳ ನೆರವನ್ನು ಪಡೆದು ಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು. ಒಂದು ಕಾಲದ ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರದೇಶದ ಭಾಷೆಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಯಲು ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳು ಆಕರಗಳಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತವೆಂಬುದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸಂಗತಿ. ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿ ಲಿಪಿಕಾರರು ಬರೆಹದ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಡುನುಡಿಯ ಜೊತೆ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಗ್ರಂಥಸಂಪಾದನೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರಕಟಿಸಿರುವ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕೃತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯ ಭಾಷೆಯು ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳ ಭಾಷೆಗಿಂತ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ ಭಿನ್ನವಾಗಿದೆ. ಗ್ರಂಥ ಸಂಪಾದನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರು ಅನೇಕ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯನ್ನು ನಕಲುಮಾಡುವಾಗ ಮೂಲಕೃತಿಗೆ ನಿಷ್ಠರಾಗಿರಲಿಲ್ಲ.

ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿ: ಪುರಾತನ ಕೃತಿಯ ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂಪಾದನೆಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪ, ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂಪಾದಕನ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕರ್ತವ್ಯಗಳು, ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಯನ್ನು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಸಂಪಾದಿಸುವಾಗ ಅವನ ಮುಂದೆ ಉದ್ಭವಿಸುವ ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂಪಾದನೆಯ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯನ್ನು ಲಿಪ್ಯಂತರಕಾರರು ಬಳಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ರೀತಿ ಮುಂತಾದ ಸಂಗತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಿಸುವ ಉದ್ದೇಶದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಈ ಲೇಖನ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಈಚಿಜಟಿರಿ ಚಿಟಿಜ ಓಟಿಫಿಚಿಣಚ್ಚಿ (ಫಲಿತಗಳು)

- ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡು ಬರುವ ಭಾಷಿಕ ಪ್ರಬೇಧಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯಾಕಾಲದ ಪ್ರತಿಕಾರರ ಕನ್ನಡಗಳ ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯವೆಂದು ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸಂಕಥನವೆಂದೂ, ಬರವಣಿಗೆಯ ಬಹುಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಗಳ ವಿಕಾಸವೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಿದರೆ ಕನ್ನಡ ಬರವಣಿಗೆ ಮತ್ತು ಉಚ್ಚಾರದ ಹಲವು ವೈವಿಧ್ಯಗಳು ದೊರೆತು ಬರವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ನೆಲೆಯು ಪ್ರಾಪ್ತವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
- ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವಿಧ ಕಾಲಘಟ್ಟಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಮಾಡಿದ ಪ್ರತಿಕಾರರು ಅವರ ಕಾಲದ ಆಡುಮಾತಿನ ರೂಪಗಳನ್ನು, ಅಕ್ಷರ ರೂಪಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವಿಧ ವಿನ್ಯಾಸಗಳಿಂದ ಮೂಡಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಆ ಅಕ್ಷರಗಳ ವಿನ್ಯಾಸ ಹಾಗೂ ಪದಗಳ ಸ್ವರೂಪಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಆ ಭಾಷೆಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿದರೆ ಆಯಾ ಕಾಲದ ಆಡುಭಾಷೆಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳ ಬರೆಹದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಮೂಲಕ ತಿಳಿಯಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸಮಾರೋಪ:

ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಯ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ನೋಟವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಲು, ಮೊದಲು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಯನ್ನು ಮನಸ್ಸಿನಲ್ಲಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಸಂದರ್ಭದ ಕುರಿತು ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಯನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿದ ಭಾಷಾ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಪ್ರಭಾವಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ನಾವು ಆಳವಾದ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಕಲಾಕೃತಿಯಾಗಿ ಅದರ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಏಜಿಫಿಠಿಠಿಠಿ: ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿ ಲಿಪಿಕಾರರು, ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸಂಕಥನಕಾರರು, ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿ ತಯಾರಿ, ಆವೃತ್ತಿ, ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪ, ಸಂಪದಕನ ಹಕ್ಕುಗಳು, ಭಾಷಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು, ಲಿಪ್ಯಂತರಕಾರರು, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನ

Paper No 12.04: Manuscript Preparation, Edition, & Preservation

Translation and preservation of ancient Indian Sanskrit texts with special reference to Sarvamula Grantha: a critical review of the contribution of Padmashree Dr. Bannanje Govindacharya

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to highlight the challenges of translating the hitherto ancient Sanskrit texts in terms of their terminologies and vocabulary with reference to their translations in Kannada and English.

Design/methodology/approach: A comprehensive review of the existing literature in the form of texts, audio is employed for the study. Also, interviews with the multi lingual scholars in the field conducted.

Finding/ research: The critical review of the available literature on the vocabulary/etymology/connotations of the words is presented for the general understanding of the translations. A table of the listed words and the corresponding spelling and pronunciation is proposed.

Originality/ value: The researcher has tried to bring together the various interpretations of the same word/phrase and sentences which could provide a ready reference to the researchers.

Paper type: Exploratory linguistic study of the audio files of Dr. Bannanje Govindachyara.

Keywords: Translating, Ancient Sanskrit texts, challenges, Sarvamula Grantha, Tulu manuscript.

Paper No 12.05: Manuscript Preparation, Edition, & Preservation

ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆ: ಕನ್ನಡ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಸಂರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳ ಪಾತ್ರ

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ABSTRACT (ಸಾರಲೇಖ)

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ಮಾನವನ ಹಲವು ಆವಿಷ್ಕಾರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಷೆ ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯವಾದದ್ದು. ಈ ಭಾಷೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಮನುಷ್ಯ ಇತರ ಪ್ರಾಣಿಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ಭಿನ್ನವಾದ: ಅಂತೆಯೇ ಭಾಷೆ ಮನುಷ್ಯನನ್ನು ಇತರ ಪ್ರಾಣಿಗಳಿಗಿಂತ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಕಂಗೊಳಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಿತು. ಭಾಷೆಯ ಅನಂತರ ಮನುಷ್ಯ ಬರಹವನ್ನು ಆವಿಷ್ಕರಿಸಿಗೊಂಡ. ಇದರಿಂದ ತನ್ನ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಇತರರಿಗೆ ವಾಹಕವಾಗಿ ಕೊಂಡೊಯ್ಯಲು ಬರಹ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಸಾಧನವಾಯಿತು. ಇದರಿಂದ ತನ್ನ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಇತರರಿಗೆ ವಾಹಕವಾಗಿ ಕೊಂಡೊಯ್ಯಲು ಬರಹ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಸಾಧನವಾಯಿತು. ತನ್ನ ಬರಹವನ್ನು ಬಹುಕಾಲ ಜತನವಾಗಿಟ್ಟುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಹಲವಾರು ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿದ. ಅವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಲೋಹ, ಇಟ್ಟಿಗೆ, ತೊಗಟೆ ಕಲ್ಲು ಬಟ್ಟೆ ತಾಳೆಗರಿ ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾದವುಗಳು. ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುದ್ರಣ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳಿಲ್ಲದ ಕಾರಣ ಇಂತಹ ವಸ್ತುಗಳನ್ನು ಅಂದಿನ ರಾಜರು ಕವಿಗಳು ಆಶಯಿಸಿದರು. ಇವುಗಳ ಆಕಾರಗಳಿಂದ ನಾವು ಇಂದು ಕವಿ-ಕಾವ್ಯ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ, ಚಾರಿತ್ರಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕಟ್ಟಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾದ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆ ಇದೆ. ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಇವುಗಳೇ ಆಯಾ ಕಾಲದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ ಭಂಡಾರಗಳು. ಇವುಗಳಿಂದಲೇ ಕೃತಿಯನ್ನು ಕವಿಯನ್ನು ನಂಬಲರ್ಹವಾಗಿ ಅಧಿಕೃತವಾಗಿ ಅವನ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಪುನರ್ಮಿಸಲು ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ಸತ್ವವನ್ನು ತನ್ನಲ್ಲಿ ಅಡಗಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಸಹಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿವೆ. ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಶೀಲ ಉತ್ಪನ್ನಗಳಾಗಿರುವ ಈ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳು ಆಯಾಕಾಲದ ಏಕ ಘನಾಕೃತಿಯ ಚರಪಠ್ಯಗಳು. ಇವುಗಳಿಂದಲೇ ನಾವಿಂದು ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯಿಕ, ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ, ಹಾಗೂ ಚಾರಿತ್ರಿಕ ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯನ್ನು ಅನಾವರಣಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದಾದ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆ ಎದುರಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ನಿಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಕ, ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶೇಷವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನಮಾನಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ನಾನು “೧೨.೧- ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿ ಸಂಪಾದನೆ ಅನುವಾದ ಮತ್ತು ನಿರ್ಣಾಯಕ ಆವೃತ್ತಿಗಳ ಪೂರ್ವಭಾವಿ” ಎಂಬ ಉಪ ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ “ಕನ್ನಡ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಸಂರಚನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಗಳ ಪಾತ್ರ” ಎಂಬ ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆಯ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಲೇಖನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸಲು ಇಚ್ಛಿಸಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

Paper No 13.01: Natyashastra

Blending of Viṣama Nr̥tta in Laghu Nr̥tya – question of meaning and propriety

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ABSTRACT

Viṣama Nr̥tta as a type of Nartana, the art of dancing is first mentioned in Mānasollāsa of Someṣvara dating back to 12th c. C.E.. It is one among the three types of Nr̥tta as defined in Saṅgītaratnākara and later texts. Laghu Nr̥tta and Vikāṭa Nr̥tta being the other two. Displaying acrobatic movements forms the characteristic of Viṣama Nr̥tta. Contemplating the evolution through 21st c. C.E. Nr̥tta, the beautiful rhythmic movements of the body and its types are an area of study which demands a correlation between theory and practice.

This paper tries to analyse the blending of Viṣama Nr̥tta movement in aesthetically choreographed and presented Laghu Nr̥tya, which is a salient feature of the desi Śāstra-aṅtargata dance form Bharatanatyā. Also here is an attempt to discuss its role in the process of meaning making and propriety. The method of textual analysis of a performance number namely 'Kṛṣṇa Kautvam' identifies a specific type of acrobatic manoeuvre and its relevance in the art of abhinaya. Nr̥tta, an aid to bring out charm to a Nāṭya performance was the point of departure at the time of Nāṭyaśāstra. Eventually it evolved over the last two millennia as independent dance numbers as well as complementing the interpretative dance Nr̥tya. Present paper claims that embracing certain acrobatic technique with propriety is a significant evolutionary factor in the process of aesthetically rich artistic propagation.

Keywords: Viṣama Nr̥tta, Laghu Nr̥tta, Experiments in Bharatanatyā, Adopting Viṣama Nr̥tta, Viṣama Nr̥tta and Classicism, Cartwheel in Bharatanatyā

Paper No 13.02: Natyashastra

ಭರತನ ನಾಟ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ: ಅಭಿನವಗುಪ್ತನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನ

ಡಾ. ನೂರಂದಪ್ಪ, ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಕರು, ಕನ್ನಡ ವಿಭಾಗ, ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ ಕಾಲೇಜು, ನೆಲ್ಯಾಡಿ, ತಾ.ಕಡಬ, ದ.ಕ
೫೭೪೨೨೬

ಮೊಬೈಲ್: ೭೩೪೬೧೦೨೫೬೬

ಈಮೇಲ್: ಟಿಪ್ಪಣಿಚಿಚ್ಚಿಜ್ಜಾಣಧಿರೇ೭೩೩೩.೩೫೩

ಸಾರಾಂಶ

ಭರತನ ನಾಟ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ 'ರಸಗಳು' ಎಂಬ ಅರನೆಯ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯವು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಕಾವ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಮತ್ತು ಸೌಂದರ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ತಳಹದಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಭರತನ ಎಂಬ ರಸಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದಕ್ಕೂ ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಿದೆ, ದಾರ್ಶನಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳಿವೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ದಾರ್ಶನಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಗಳಿಂದ, ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಗಳಿಂದ ರಸಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತದ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನ ಮಾಡುವ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನವು ಕಾವ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಶಿಸ್ತಿನ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಾರತೀಯ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಪರಂಪರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ದಾರ್ಶನಿಕ ಒಳನೋಟಗಳಿಂದ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸುವ ಪರಂಪರೆಯು ನಮ್ಮ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಅಕ್ಷರಲೋಕದ ಜ್ಞಾನಶಿಖರದ ಬೆಳೆದುಬಂದಿದೆ. ಈ ಪರಂಪರೆಯನ್ನು ಅನೇಕ ಋಷಿಮುನಿಗಳ, ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರ, ದಾರ್ಶನಿಕರ, ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕಾರರ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಣುತ್ತೇವೆ. ಭರತನ ನಾಟ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಕ್ಕೆ 'ಅಭಿನವ ಭಾರತಿ' ಎಂಬ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನ ಬರೆದ ಅಭಿನವ ಗುಪ್ತನ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆಯು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನ ಪರಂಪರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಗ್ರಗಣ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಕೇವಲ ಕಾವ್ಯದ ಸಾಲುಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿ ರಸಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿರುವ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರಸಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಕ್ಕಿರುವ ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಗಳಿಂದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಬೇಕಿದೆ. ಈ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇಂದ್ರಿಯದ ಹಂತದಿಂದ ಅತ್ಯಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಹಂತದವರೆಗೆ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಅಭಿನವಗುಪ್ತನ ರಸಸ್ವರೂಪದ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯು ಕುರಿತು ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ನಾಟ್ಯಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ರಸವನ್ನು ಕೇವಲ ನಾಟಕಕಾರನ, ನಟನ, ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರೇಕ್ಷಕನ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನದ ಮೂಲಕವಷ್ಟೇ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗದ ಅಭಿನವಗುಪ್ತನ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನವು, ಪರತತ್ವವು ಇಂದ್ರಿಯಗ್ರಾಹ್ಯವೇಷದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸುವ ಕಲಿಯಾಗಿ ಮಾಹಿತಿಮಾಡುವ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಲಾಕೃತಿಯೊಡನೆ ರಸಾತ್ಮಕ ಸಂಬಂಧವು ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ ಪರತತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಒಯ್ಯುವ ಅನುಭೂತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಉಂಟಾಗುವ ಸಂಯೋಜನೆಯನ್ನು ಸೂಕ್ಷ್ಮವಾಗಿ ಗ್ರಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ರಸವು ರಂಗದ ಮೇಲೆ ನಾಟಕವನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸುವ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಉಪದೇಶ ನೀಡಿದರೂ ಕೂಡ ಯೌಗಿಕ ಮನಸ್ಕೃತಿಯೊಂದನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿನಿಧಿಸುವ ಅಭಿನವಗುಪ್ತನ ವೀಕ್ಷಣೆಯು ಶಿವಾದ್ವೈತದ ಮೂಲಕ ಶಾರೀರಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾನಸಿಕ ನೆಲೆಗಳ ಔನ್ನತ್ಯದ ಮಟ್ಟವನ್ನು ತಲುಪುವ ತಾತ್ವಿಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವೊಂದನ್ನು ತೆರೆದಿಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ದೃಢ ಮತ್ತು ಮನೋವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಕಾರಣಕರ್ತೃತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿ ರಸಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತವನ್ನು ಅರಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಮುಖ್ಯವೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗಿದೆ.

Paper No 13.03: Natyashastra

ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಸಕಸಜ್ಜಿಕಾ ನಾಯಿಕಾ ಭಾವಾಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಅಮರು ಶತಕದ ಕೊಡುಗೆ

ವಿದುಷಿ ಯಶಾ ಕೆ ಎಸ್*, ಡಾ|| ರಾಮಕೃಷ್ಣ ಹೆಗ್ಡೆ**, ವಿದುಷಿ ದೀಕ್ಷಾ ಆರ್***

* ಉಪ ಪ್ರಾಂಶುಪಾಲರು, ಶಾರದಾ ಪಿ.ಯು. ಕಾಲೇಜ್, ಕುಂಜಿಬೆಟ್ಟು, ಉಡುಪಿ

** ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು(ಬಿ.ಬಿ), ಐ.ಎಮ್.ಜಿ. ಸಮೂಹ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳು, ಕುಂದಾಪುರ

*** ಕಾರ್ಯದರ್ಶಿ, ಹೆಜ್ಜೆ - ಗೆಜ್ಜೆ ಫೌಂಡೇಶನ್ (೦), ಉಡುಪಿ - ಮಣಿಪಾಲ

ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನ ಅಭಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಶಾಕುಂತಲಾ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾಳವಿಕಾಗ್ನಿಮಿತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ, ಬಾಣಭಟ್ಟನ ಕಾದಂಬರಿಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಅಮರು ಕವಿಯ ಅಮರು ಶತಕ ಹಾಗೂ ಹಾಲಕವಿಯ ಗಾಢಾಸಪ್ತಶತಿ ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಯಕ ನಾಯಿಕಾ ಭಾವಗಳುಳ್ಳ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವಿದ್ದು ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾಗಿವೆ. ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಆಧಾರಿತ ನೃತ್ಯಾಭಿನಯ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿದ್ದು ಅದನ್ನು ಆಳವಾಗಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ ವಿಸ್ತರಿಸುವ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದೆಯಲ್ಲದೇ ಇದರಿಂದ ನೃತ್ಯಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಕ್ಕೂ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನವಾಗಲಿದೆ.

ನೂರು ಪ್ರೇಮಗೀತೆಗಳನ್ನೊಳಗೊಂಡು “ಅಮರು ಶತಕ” ಎಂಬ ಹೆಸರಿನಿಂದ ಪ್ರಖ್ಯಾತಗೊಂಡು ಸಾವಿರಾರು ವರ್ಷಗಳಿಂದಲೂ ರಸಿಕರಿಗೊಂದು ಹಬ್ಬ ಎನಿಸಿರುವ ಈ ಕಿರುಕಾವ್ಯವನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿದ ಕವಿ ಅಮರು ಅಥವಾ ಅಮರುಕ. ಅಮರು ಕವಿಯ ಈ ಶತಕ ಪದ್ಯಗಳು ಮುಕ್ತಕ ಎಂಬ ಕಾವ್ಯ ಭೇದಕ್ಕೆ ಸೇರಿದವು. ಅಮರು ಕವಿಯ ಒಂದು ಶ್ಲೋಕ ನೂರು ಪ್ರಬಂಧಕ್ಕೆ ಸಮ ಎಂಬ ಅರ್ಥದ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಶಂಸೆಯ ಮಾತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತದಲ್ಲಿದೆ. ರಸಾನುಭವವನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡುವುದು ನಾಟ್ಯ ಕಲೆಯ ಗುರಿ. ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಅಭಿನಯವೇ ಜೀವಾಳ. ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ತನ್ನ ದೇಹದ ಅವಯವಗಳಿಂದ ಅಂಗಿಕಾಭಿನಯ, ಗೀತೆಗಳ ಮಾಧುರ್ಯದಿಂದ ವಾಚಿಕಾಭಿನಯ, ಉಡುಪು ಅಲಂಕಾರಗಳ ಸಹಾಯದಿಂದ ಅಹಾರ್ಯಾಭಿನಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನೊಳಗೆ ಆಗುವ ಭಾವನಾವಸ್ಥೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಸಾತ್ವಿಕ ಅಭಿನಯ ಒಳಗೊಂಡಂತಹ ಶೃಂಗಾರ ಪ್ರಧಾನವಾದ ಈ ಅಮರುಶತಕದ ಮುಕ್ತಕಗಳನ್ನು ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸಲು ಯೋಗ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಮರು ಶತಕದಲ್ಲಿ ನಾಯಕ ನಾಯಿಕಾ ಭಾವವನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದ್ದು ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಮರುಶತಕದಲ್ಲಿ ‘ವಾಸಕಸಜ್ಜಿಕಾ’ ನಾಯಿಕಾಭಾವ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಪಡಿಸುವ ಪರಿಯನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಅದನ್ನು ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯ ಅಭಿನಯಕ್ಕೆ ಅಳವಡಿಸುವ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಭ್ಯಸಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಮರು ಶತಕದ ಆಯ್ದ ಮುಕ್ತಕಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ಪ್ರಬಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆಯಲ್ಲದೇ ಇದು ನಾಯಿಕಾ ಅಭಿನಯವನ್ನು ಉನ್ನತಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಕರೆದೊಯ್ಯುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಶಬ್ದಗಳು: ಅಮರು ಶತಕ, ಭರತನಾಟ್ಯ, ಅಭಿನಯ, ನಾಯಿಕಾ ಭಾವ, ವಾಸಕಸಜ್ಜಿಕಾ.

Paper No 13.04: Natyashastra

Origin of Natyashastra – the source Sanskrit document of Bharatanatyam

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ABSTRACT

Natyashastra is the most ancient Sanskrit document attributed to sage Bharata Muni. Natyashastra consist of 36 chapters which includes details of performing arts. Natyashastra has influenced dance, music, theater, performing art. The word Natyashastra has been adopted from Sanskrit. Natya means performing art, dance, theater. Shastra means literature. Bharatanatyam is one of the major dance forms of southern part of India. Most of the aspects of Natyashastra have been adopted as basis for Bharatanatyam. Bharatanatyam gives detail characteristics of Nayaka and Nayaki, mudras, stage craft, abhinaya, costume, make up, communication. Bharatanatyam like other dance forms consist of three aspects, Nritya, Nrithya, and Natya. People are aware of Bharatanatyam but most of them are not aware of basis for Bharatanatyam. There are Sanskrit and Tamil documents which gives simpler version of Natyashastra. Current scenario the translated version of source document is taken as basis for Bharatanatyam. The objective of the study is to know the origin of Natyashastra, to know the origin of Bharatanatyam through Natyashastra, and aspects of Natyashastra as basis for Bharatanatyam.

This study is only on doing descriptive analysis. This study will be done with the help of secondary data through which trying to bring out the aspects of Natyashastra inculcated in Bharatanatyam. After the analysis, the result aims at to know the basic features, important characteristics of abhinaya through various parts of the body, stage setting, performance, performers, communication.

Key words: Natyashastra, Bharatanatyam, origin, Sanskrit, source document.

Paper No 13.05: Natyashastra

Mudrās in Indian Classical Dance Bharatanāṭyam: Comparison to Present Practice

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ABSTRACT

While expressing ourself we use various facial expressions and hand gestures along with speaking. When it comes to silent conversation, like dance, hand gestures are very important. India has got a rich tradition of classical dances from Kashmir to Kanyakumari. While going through the pages of history, Indian classical dance has gone through many phases. Still, it is alive and growing. So, it is quite interesting and necessary to study the journey of the Indian classical dances, here, Bharatanāṭyam. Dance is most silent conveyer of feelings. In the Indian classical dancers use many hand gestures called mudrās, using one hand and two hands. Textual references like Nāṭyaśāstra and Abhinaya Darpaṇa give descriptions of these mudrās. Being a Bharatanāṭyam dance student myself, it is interesting to compare its usage in today's dance. In this research paper, use of mudrās in Indian classical dance like Bharatanāṭyam for different expressions and emotions is studied. This research paper concentrates on single handed mudrās only. The study is done by interviewing and observations of the dancers, along with collecting answers from questionnaires, for observing its current status. For the convenience, scope of the paper is restricted to some prominent mudrās and texts mentioned above

Key words: Mudrās, Dance, Bharatanāṭyam, Classical.

Paper No. 14.01: Sanskrit Literature

नन्दिनीवरप्रदानम् - व्याससृष्टिः कालिदासीया अनुसृष्टिः

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ABSTRACT

कविकुलगुरुणा कालिदासेन विरचितं रघुवंशमहाकाव्यं जगत्प्रसिद्धम् । तत्रत्याः रघुवंशीयानां राज्ञां कथाः अपि विश्वविख्याताः एव । तस्य महाकाव्यस्य नन्दिनीवरप्रदाननामके द्वितीये सर्गे या कथा अस्ति, यश्च सिंहदिलीपसंवादः अस्ति तौ अनन्तरकाले बहूनां सहृदयानाम् आदरपात्रतां गतौ । परन्तु एषा कथा कालिदासस्य एव कल्पना न, तत्पूर्वम् अपि सा कथा आसीत् इति बहवः न जानन्ति ।

महाभारतस्य, अष्टादशपुराणानाम्, उपपुराणानां ब्रह्मसूत्राणां च कर्ता भगवान् बादरायणः पद्मपुराणे एतां कथां निबद्धवान् अस्ति । वस्तुतः सा एव कथा रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये कालिदासेन पुनः निबद्धा अस्ति ।

तावता कालिदासे कृतिचौर्यस्य आरोपणं नोचितम् । “पूर्वसूरिभिः वर्णितम् एव अहं पुनः वर्णयामि” इति सः रघुवंशस्य आरम्भे एव विनयपूर्वकं निवेदयति । अन्यच्च पूर्वसूरीणां कृतिभ्यः कथां स्वीकृत्य तस्य विस्तारणं तत्र नूतनानाम् अंशानां योजनं च कविसमवाये अनुमतं श्लाघनीयं च अस्ति एव । तथा कृत्वापि कविः स्वस्य प्रतिभाविशेषेण श्लाघनीयः जगद्वन्द्यश्च भवति । तादृशेषु कविवर्येषु अन्यतमः अस्ति कालिदासः ।

प्रकृतम्, कालिदासेन पद्मपुराणात् या कथा स्वीकृता अस्ति, तस्याः तेन कृतायाः पुनःसृष्टेः च साम्यानि कानि सन्ति ? वैषम्याणि च कानि सन्ति ? आनुपूर्व्यां कः भेदः अस्ति ? अलङ्काराणां प्रयोगे किं वैशिष्ट्यम् अस्ति ? – इत्यादयः अंशाः अस्मिन् शोधप्रबन्धे विचार्यन्ते ।

Keywords: रघुवंशमहाकाव्यम्, अष्टादशपुराणानाम्, नूतनानाम् अंशानां योजनं, कालिदासः

Paper No. 14.02: Sanskrit Literature

Modelizing the Hanūmān approach for the betterment of Indian polity at forefront

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ABSTRACT

Ramayana has been the source of inspiration in the spiritual, social, creative, and political realms of Bhārath for eons. Several works, both artistic and scholastic, have been done exploring various dimensions of Rāmāyaṇam to date. Nevertheless, there is a need to structurize the model of Hanumān's approach toward the assigned task, as narrated in the VR, for applying and improving the state of administrative aspects of current India. As seen and experienced in multiple avenues of public administration and implementation of state policies, executive forefronts of the Indian state are often short-sighted, less dedicated, and lacking the overall picture of the mission, which leads to partial or complete failure of the intended project.

This paper shall first undertake a literature survey of the domain in a suitable manner and length to set up the context for establishing the intended claim. The paper relies upon the original work of Rishi Vālmīki rather than merely depending upon translations and secondary works. The primary segment of focus is the Sundarakāṇḍa of the VR. Then, having established a pattern of thought and deeds of Hanūmān, the paper proposes a suitable model to apply to our modern context to revitalize the administration at the forefront. The lacuna in our current system and the reasons for the same will also be shed light upon. The overall intention of the paper is to suggest a model for the betterment of administration at the bottom level, abstracting the ideas from the character of Hanūmān.

Keywords: State, VR (Valmiki Ramayanam), Hanuman, Model, Administration and Polity.

Paper No. 14.03: Sanskrit Literature

चित्रनैषधे शब्दालङ्कारः शृङ्गारश्च ।

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ABSTRACT

चित्रनैषधकाव्यम् आधुनिकेन कविना बेङ्गलूरुनगरवासिना डा.शङ्करराजारामवर्येण विरचितम् । तच्च १०१६ तमे वर्षे निरामयप्रकाशनेन प्रकाशितम् । प्रथममुद्रणे कविनैव रचितः आङ्ग्लानुवादः, आङ्ग्लटिप्पण्यः, अङ्कुरनागपालवर्यस्य हिन्दी अनुवादश्च विद्यते । काव्येऽस्मिन् नलदमयन्त्योः कथा वर्णिता । मुख्यश्च रसः शृङ्गारः । शृङ्गाररसः यत्र अभिव्यज्यते तस्मिन् काव्ये शक्तौ सत्यामपि कविना शब्दालङ्काराः न प्रयोक्तव्याः इति आलङ्कारिकाणां मतम् । परन्तु चतुर्दशाधिकद्विशतेन श्लोकैः युतं चित्रनैषधकाव्यं पूर्णतया गोमूत्रिकाबन्धे रचितम् । काव्येऽस्मिन् शृङ्गाररसः स्फुटतया अभिव्यञ्जितः । ईदृशस्थले अलङ्कारसहकृतः रसास्वादः कथं भवतीति अस्मिन् पत्रे प्रस्तूयते । अस्मिन् ग्रन्थे ग्रन्थकृता एव क्वचित् अलङ्कारादिनिर्देशः कृतः । परन्तु अलङ्कारसहकृतः रसः कथमभिव्यज्यते इति शब्दैः न प्रतिपादितम् ।

अस्मिन् शोधप्रबन्धे गोमूत्रिकाबन्धेन सह विद्यमानाः शब्दालङ्काराः स्पष्टतया निरूपिताः । तथा च रसवन्ति स्थानानि प्रदर्शितानि । शृङ्गारकाव्येषु शब्दालङ्कारप्रयोगविषये प्राचीनालङ्कारिकाणां मतानि उल्लिखितानि, तेषां च विमर्शः कृतः । अस्मिन् विषये आधुनिकानां मतं कीदृशं वर्तते इत्यपि विचारः प्रवर्तितः । काव्यशास्त्रपरिधौ इदं काव्यं दुष्यति इति मतेः वारणाय अनेकाः युक्तयः सोदाहरणं प्रदर्शिताः । अद्यत्वे आधुनिकपरिप्रेक्षे अनेकानि काव्यानि अभिजातशैलीरहितानि दृश्यन्ते । तत्र कविभिः शैली एव परित्यज्यते इतिकारणतः दोषदर्शनं सरलतया भवति । परन्त्वत्र अभिजातशैल्याः अनुसरणे कृते अपि आपाततः दोषः इति भासने हेतुः विद्यते । स च दोषः कथमित्यपि सम्यक्तया पूर्वपक्षः उपस्थापितः । ततश्च सिद्धान्तरूपेण आलङ्कारिकाणां दृष्ट्या पश्यामः चेत् अयम् उत्कृष्टः प्रबन्धः (चित्रनैषधम्) कथं भवितुमर्हति इति निरूपणं कृतम् ।

प्रमुखपदानि- चित्रनैषधम्, चित्रकाव्यम्, शब्दालङ्काराः, शृङ्गाररसः, गोमूत्रिकाबन्धः, श्लेषालङ्कारः, विरोधाभासः, शक्तिः, विप्रलम्भः

Paper No. 14.04: Sanskrit Literature

भाषाशैलीशास्त्रम्

उमामहेश्वरः एन्.

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ABSTRACT

भाषाप्रयोगविज्ञानम् इति भाषायाः अभिनवशाखात्वेन संवर्धमानं क्षेत्रम्। वस्तुतः प्रक्रिया, प्रमेयः प्रयोगश्चेति तिस्रो धारा व्याकरणस्य । एकैकस्या अपि धारायाः सुगभीरमध्ययनम् आवश्यकमेव। धारात्रयस्य पार्थक्येन अध्ययनविभागाः साम्प्रतं दृश्यन्ते इत्यतः प्रतिक्षेत्रमपि विशिष्टचिन्तनानि अध्ययनानि संशोधनानि भविष्यन्त्येवेत्यतः संस्कृतलोकः स्यात् सुपुष्टतरः। भाषाप्रयोगविज्ञानत्वेन प्रयोगधारायाः अभिनवविद्याशाखात्वेन विश्वविद्यालयेषु दृश्यमानः विभागः अनन्तप्रकारकभाषाप्रयोगसम्पद्भूषितां संस्कृतवाचं प्रयुयुक्षणां मनसि मोदं तन्तनीति। भाषाप्रयोगविज्ञानम् इत्यस्य प्राधान्येन लेखनाभिव्यक्तौ वा मौखिकाभिव्यक्तौ वा परिशील्यमाने भाषाशुद्धिः, भाषाविकासः, भाषासौन्दर्यम् इत्येवं विभागाः गोचरीभवन्ति। ज्ञानपूर्वकप्रयोगे धर्मः, समानाभिप्राये नानाप्रकारैः प्रयोगनिर्वहणम्, शैलीशास्त्रम्, वाचोयुक्तीनां व्यवहारे गद्ये पद्ये व्यवहारे च स्थाने प्रयोगाः इत्येवं बहवः अंशाः मनोमण्डलम् अवृण्वन्ति। तत्र शैलीशास्त्रम् इति किञ्चन पदम् आकर्षति अस्मान् । शैलीशास्त्रं साम्प्रतं प्रतिविद्याशाखं प्रतिकलाशाखं दृश्यते एव। शैली प्रकारापरपर्यात्वेन प्रयुज्यमानः शब्दः कश्चन । देशतः कालतो वा विषयवस्तुवैशिष्ट्याद्वा वैविध्यतो वा अभिरुचिहेतुतो वा शैल्यः भिद्यन्ते। शिल्पशास्त्रे, नृत्यशास्त्रे, सङ्गीतके, चित्रकलायां वा यथा देशकालादिभेदेन शैलीभेदो लक्ष्यते तद्वदेव अनन्तकालतः नदीव प्रवृत्तायाः वेदवेदान्तादिकाव्यसम्पत्सङ्गतायाः अस्याः गैर्वाण्याः अपि शैल्यः भिद्यन्ते इति प्रत्यक्षत एव सिद्धम्। प्राधान्यतः परिशील्यमाने गद्यशैली पद्यशैली नाटकशैली व्यवहारशैली इत्येवं विभागः शक्यते। साम्प्रतमिह व्यवहारम् अभिनवसाहित्यसृष्टिं च मनसि निधाय शैल्यः विचार्यन्ते।

काश्चन प्रसिद्धाः शैल्यः व्यवहारे अभिनवसाहित्ये वा नियताः। वाक्यारम्भे, वाक्यान्ते, परिच्छेदारम्भे, परिच्छेदान्ते, अभिप्रायद्वयस्य द्वयोर्वाक्यखण्डयोः वा संयोजने, भाषणे प्रतिभाषणे वा परिभाषणे वा तदीयाः एव काश्चन शैल्यः सन्ति ताः एव तत्र प्रयोक्तव्याः। पञ्चतन्त्रादिपरिशीलने आसीद्गोदावरीतीरे इत्येवं काचन शैली दृश्यते तत्र च क्रियापदम् आदौ प्रयुक्तम्। अपि कुशलम् इत्येवं वाक्यादौ प्रयुक्तः अपिः काञ्चिद्विच्छित्तिमापादयति प्रश्नवाचकत्वं च आवहति। इयं रामयणतः परिलक्ष्यमाणा शैली। द्वयोर्वाक्ययोः अभिप्राययोर्वा संयोजिन्यः शैल्यः बहुधा लक्ष्यन्ते। न केवलं बुद्धिमान् अपि तु प्रतिभावान् अत्र न केवलम्... अपि तु इति काचन वाक्यसम्बद्धा शैली। एवमेव मा किम्, किं बहुना, न केवलं तावता, यत्तच्छब्दशैली, इत्येवं बहव्यः शैल्यः व्यवहारे अभिनवसाहित्ये च

एवं शैल्यः भाषाप्रयोगविज्ञाने महत्त्वपूर्णं स्थानम् आवहन्ति। तासां विशेषतः निरूपणं समुपस्थापनं वा इतोमुखं करिष्यते । अत्र शैलीनां संशोधनाय भूयान् व्यवहारः परिशीलनीयः। नाटकादिवाङ्मयं विलोकनीयम् । कथालेखने उपन्याससृष्टौ वा सम्भाषणनिर्माणे वा अपेक्षिताः अनुकूलाः शैल्यः इह प्रदर्श्यन्ते । एकैव शैली प्रयोगानुसारं कथं रूपान्तरम् आप्नोति। शैलीषु व्याकरणशास्त्रीयभूमिका च का इत्यादिकं संशोध्य समुपस्थाप्यते।

कूटशब्दाः – शैलीशास्त्रम्, भाषाप्रयोगविज्ञानम्, व्यवहारशैली।

Paper No. 14.05: Sanskrit Literature

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ABSTRACT

भारतीयविचाराणां जीवनदृष्टेः च मूलाधाररूपेण विद्यमानं संस्कृतं ज्ञानविज्ञानयोः खनिः भवति। ज्ञानं तु विविधेषु विषयेषु अपि भवति । भौतिकविषयाः अपि संस्कृते बहुधा चर्चिताः सन्ति नानाशास्त्रेषु। आयुर्वेदः धनुर्वेदः गान्धर्ववेदः नाट्यशास्त्रम् एवं यानि १४ अथवा १८ विद्यास्थानानि सन्ति तानि सर्वाणि अपराविद्या इत्येव उच्यते । एषा अपराविद्या एकया दृष्ट्या भौतिकविज्ञानं भवति । एतेषु लौकिकालौकिकविषये चर्चा अस्ति एव । परन्तु तत् सर्वं नश्वरम् । एतानि तत्त्वविवरणं कुर्वन्ति । न तत्त्वम् इति कश्चित् विचारः । तर्हि पुनः कः अनश्वरः ?

(अङ्गानि वेदाश्चत्वारो मीमांसान्यायविस्तरः । पुराणं धर्मशास्त्रं च विद्याह्यताश्चतुर्दश॥आयुर्वेदो धनुर्वेदो गान्धर्वश्चेत्यनुक्रमात् । अर्थशास्त्रं परं तस्मात् विद्या ह्यष्टादश स्मृताः ॥ विष्णुपुराणम् ३-६-२९)

सा परा विद्या ब्रह्मविद्या । द्वे विद्ये वेदितव्ये परा च अपरा च इति उपनिषद् । (द्वे विद्ये वेदितव्ये इति ह स्म यद् ब्रह्मविदो वदन्ति परा चैवापरा च । - मुण्डकोपनिषत् १-१-४) एषा पराविद्या एव अज्ञाननाशिनी परमार्थप्रदायिनी । यस्य ज्ञानेन किमपि अन्यत् ज्ञातव्यं भवति । एतत् वस्तुतया विज्ञानम् (ज्ञानं विज्ञानसहितं यज्ञात्वा मोक्षसेऽशुभात् - भगवद्गीता ९-१)। एवं विद्यायाः विभागः कल्पितः वर्तते संस्कृतवाङ्मये । द्वयोः अपि अध्ययनं करणीयम् । येन विवेकः उदयते। अस्य अवगमनाय संस्कृताध्ययनम् अवश्यं करणीयम् । अन्यासु कासु अपि भाषासु एवं विवरणं नैव लभते । अतः एव ज्ञानं विज्ञानेन सह अनुभवः ज्ञानेन सह प्राप्तव्यम् इति वदन्ति पण्डिताः । इन्द्रियैः सम्पाद्यमानं सर्वं ज्ञानमेव परन्तु स्वानुभवज्ञानमेव विज्ञानम् इति अवगन्तव्यम्। अन्यत् सर्वं भौतिकलाभाय भवति न आत्मज्ञानाय ।

Keywords: ज्ञानविज्ञानयोः खनिः, परा विद्या ब्रह्मविद्या, संस्कृतवाङ्मयम्, धर्मशास्त्रम्

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किरातार्जुनीयस्य वैशिष्ट्यम्

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ABSTRACT

भारविः किरातार्जुनीयस्य महाकाव्यस्य कर्ता । तेन महाभारतस्य स्वारस्यमयं कथासूत्रं आधृत्य रचितं “किरातार्जुनीयं” महाकाव्यम् अनेकेषां काव्यरसिकानां विदुषाञ्च प्रशंसतां प्राप्नोत् । तपःप्रभावेण साक्षात् भगवतः शिवस्य प्रत्यक्षीकरणं अतीव सुन्दरशैल्या वर्णयित्वा योगसिद्धेः महिमानं सर्ववेद्यं च कृतवान् भारविः । भारविः स्वकाव्ये सौन्दर्यदृष्टिः तत्त्वदर्शनेन सह समन्विता भवतीति इत्येतत् वर्णनेन दर्शयति ।

पदानां वैशद्यं, अर्थप्रौढिमा, अर्थवैविध्यं, साकांक्षत्वम् इत्यादीनि उत्तमानि भाषाशैलीलक्षणानि भारवेः कृतौ संयुक्तानि इत्यतः “भारवेः अर्थगौरवम्” इति भारवेः विषयिका प्रशंसा सार्थिका विद्यते । अत्र पद्ये 'अहो ! दुरन्ता बलवद्विरोधिता' एष पद्यांशः नीतिगर्भः, अयमेव अत्र अर्थगौरवस्य बीजरूपेणावस्थितः। काव्येऽस्मिन् प्रतिपाद्यविषयः अर्थशास्त्रप्रक्रिया च भारवेः विशिष्टं लक्षणम् इत्येव दृश्यते । अत्र कवेः राजनीतिपाण्डित्यं बहुधा दृश्यते यतः व्यासस्य मूलकृतौ गुप्तचरोऽपि नास्ति, आदर्शराजः दुर्योधनः अपि न । व्यासः भीमः धर्मराजः द्रौपदी वा यः कोऽपि राजकारणपटुः इव न भाषते । परन्तु किरातार्जुनीये काव्ये सर्वेऽपि राजनीतिविशारदाः एव । काव्यस्यास्य शैली गम्भीरा प्रौढा च चित्ताकर्षिका विद्यते । कवेः असाधारणवर्णनाशक्तिः, सौन्दर्यप्रज्ञा, कल्पनाविलासः, रसाभिव्यक्तिः सामर्थ्यं च अत्यन्तं प्रशंसार्हम् अस्ति।

भारविणा लिखितं किरातार्जुनीयं महाकाव्यं राजनीतिशास्त्रदृष्ट्या सुसमृद्धं विराजते । अत्र दुर्योधनस्य कूटनीतिचर्चा सामान्यनीतिचर्चा च कृता सचेतसां चेतः चमत्करोति । क्वचिदत्र द्रौपदी भीमं प्रति नीतिमयानि वचनानि विनियुङ्क्ते तस्य उत्तेजनाय शत्रुवधाय च सावधानः स्यादिति । अपरत्र वनेचरस्य वचनैः नीतिस्रोतस्विनी प्रवहति । अन्यत्र युधिष्ठिरस्य गर्वोक्तिभिः छद्मप्रवृत्तिभिश्च राजनीतिः मुखरीभवति। एताः सर्वा एव उक्तयः काव्यवस्तुसम्भृता अपि विशिष्टां राजनीतिं व्यक्तीकुर्वन्त्यः नूनं ताः अर्थगौरवाय कल्पन्ते । अत एव 'भारवैर्गौरवम्' इत्येषा उक्तिः सुप्रसिद्धा वर्तते । विषयस्याऽस्य सौन्दर्यं नैतिकता च तदीयकाव्योद्धृतैः कैश्चित् पद्यैरत्र विव्रीयते ।

Keywords: किरातार्जुनीयम्, भारवेः पाण्डित्यम्, भाषाशैली, दुर्योधनस्य कूटराजनीतिः, भीमस्य सान्त्ववचनानि इत्यादयः

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कान्तासम्मितोक्तः प्रभुधर्मः

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ABSTRACT

धर्मशब्दस्य धारकः इत्यर्थः । योऽस्मान् धरति उद्धरति सः धर्मः । स च वर्णधर्मः आश्रमधर्मः वर्णाश्रमधर्मः नैमित्तिकधर्मः गौणधर्मः साधारणधर्मश्चेति षड्विधः। धर्मनिर्णये श्रुतिः स्मृतिः साधूनामाचारः आत्मनः तृप्तिश्चेति चत्वारि प्रमाणानि । वेदादिप्रमाणनिर्णीतो धर्मः कान्तासम्मितमिति प्रथिते काव्यवाङ्मये धर्ममर्मज्ञैः कविभिरुच्यते काव्यमपि धर्मे प्रमाणमित्यत्र न कस्यापि विप्रतिपत्तिः । अत एव कुन्तकेन उच्यते "धर्मादिसाधनोपायः सुकुमारक्रमोदितः काव्यबन्धः" इति । रञ्जनार्थकात् रन्ज्धातोः निष्पन्नस्य राजन् इति शब्दस्य रञ्जनकर्त्तरि शक्तिः, स एव प्रभुः । प्रजारञ्जनं तत्कर्तव्यम् । तदुक्तं कालिदासेन रघुवंशे राजा प्रकृतिरञ्जनात् इति । रामायणादिषु काव्येषु परिशीलितेषु द्विविधो राजधर्मोपदेशः दृश्यते । तत्र प्रथमः राज्ञः आत्मोद्धाराय द्वितीयश्च प्रजानां सुखाय ।

राजधर्मस्यास्य विचारः अद्य कथं प्रस्तुतत्वमेति? गणराज्यं प्रजाराज्यमिति व्यवहियमाणे आधुनिकक्रमे तदभावात् इति सन्देहः स्यात् । प्रजाभिरेव चितस्य मन्त्रिपदवाच्यस्य कर्तव्यं राजधर्मान्नातिरिच्यते । प्रजारक्षणं तत्पालनं देशरक्षणं च तस्याप्यवश्यं कर्म । तथापि इदमस्माकं दौर्भाग्यं यदनुपादेयं कणिकनीत्यादौ निर्दिष्टं तदेव अधुनातनैः राजकीयपुरुषैरनुष्ठीयते । येन केन प्रकारेण प्रभुत्वं धनं च हस्तापचेयं कार्यमित्येकमेव लक्ष्यं हृदि निधाय व्यवहरन्तस्ते स्वयमधर्मे उठन्तः अन्यानपि पातयन्तः धर्मकुठाराः संवृत्ताः । अपराधिनः रक्षन्तः साधून् कारागारे वासयन्तः सनातनीं संस्कृतिं च नाशयन्तः विजृम्भन्ते । तादृशेऽस्मिन् अवसरे प्राचीनैरनुष्ठितानां राजधर्माणां विमर्शः नूनम् औचित्यमावहति ।

मुख्याः शब्दाः दृ कान्तासम्मितम्, धर्मः, राजा, राजधर्मः प्रजारञ्जनम्, प्रजारक्षणम्

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श्री श्री सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां काव्यस्तोत्रादीनां सविमर्शावलोकनम्

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ABSTRACT

उपलब्ध अभिलेखानुसारं पञ्चगौडब्राह्मणेषु अन्यतमत्वेन गौडब्राह्मणाः सरस्वतीनद्याः तटे निवसन्ति स्म इति कारणात् तेषां गौडसरस्वतब्राह्मणाः इति नाम प्राप्तम् । कुम्बकोण मठस्य श्रीश्रीसुरेन्द्रतीर्थस्वामिनः शिष्याः श्री विजयेन्द्रतीर्थाः कोचिन् प्रान्तस्य गौडसरस्वतब्राह्मणानां प्रार्थनया क्रि.श.१६ शताब्द्यां श्रीहनुमन्तभट्टः इति नाम वटुं वाराणस्यां भिक्षुत्वेन चयनं कृत्वा श्री यादवेन्द्रतीर्थः इति नामकरणं चक्रुः तथा श्रीकाशीमठसंस्थानम् इति नूतनमठं प्रारभत । काशीमठः गुरुशिष्यपरम्परायाः अनुसरणं कुर्वन् मठः अध्यात्मिकः संस्था च अस्ति, यत्र श्रीमठस्य गुरोः समाधिपश्चात् शिष्याः मठाधिपतिनः भवन्ति । प्रस्तुत लेखने श्री यादवेन्द्र तीर्थतः विंशतितम यतिवर्याः श्री श्री सुधीन्द्र तीर्थैः विरचितानां स्तोत्रेषु उपलब्धानां स्तोत्रानां सविमर्शावलोकनं कृतमस्ति ।

१९२६ तमे वर्षे एर्नाकुलम्-नगरे जन्म प्राप्य श्री सदाशिव शोणै नाम बालकः १९४४ तमे वर्षे मुल्की नगरस्य शाम्भवीतटे श्री श्री सुकृतीन्द्र तीर्थात् सन्यासदीक्षां प्राप्य श्रीसुधीन्द्र तीर्थ इति नामाङ्कनं प्राप्तवान् । स्वगुरोः इच्छानुसारं ते वेद-वेदाङ्गादीनाम् अध्ययनं कृत्वा समग्रे भारते परिभ्रमन्तः अनेकानि मन्दिराणि पुनर्निर्माणं चक्रुः । हरिद्वारस्य व्यासाश्रमं तथा कल्यां (यत्र वेदव्यासस्य जन्म अभवत् तत्र) बालवेदव्यासमन्दिरनिर्माणं अकुर्वन् । सुधाग्रन्थाध्ययनमपि अकुर्वन् । श्री श्री सुधीन्द्र तीर्थाः विंशतितम शतमानस्य श्रेष्ठ संस्कृत कविषु अन्यतमाः । श्रीपादैः विरचितेषु स्तोत्रेषु गुरुभक्तेः पराकाष्ठा विद्यते । तेषाम् असाधारणबुद्धिः, विशेषतः विज्ञान-कला-सङ्गीतादि विषये सर्जनात्मक प्रतिभा दरीदृश्यते । भक्तिप्रधानानि त्रिंशत्यधिक स्तोत्राणि उपलभ्यन्ते । श्रीपादैः विरचितेषु स्तोत्रेषु, बादरायणसम्बद्धानि स्तोत्राणि, स्वीकृत्य यथामति सविमर्शावलोकनं प्रयत्नः विदितः । वेदव्यासस्य रूपं, श्रेष्ठत्वं, गुणकर्मादिकं तथा काव्यगुणानि च विमर्शा कृता । छन्दः (अनुष्टुप्, त्रिष्टुप् ... इत्यादि), रसाः (भक्तिः, शान्तः ... इत्यादि), अलङ्काराः, दशावतारः, रामायणं, महाभारतं, पुराणानि, ब्रह्मसूत्रं, कविकल्पना इत्यादीनां विचारेऽपि सविमर्शात्मिकम् अवलोकनं कृतमस्ति । भक्तदेवयोः व्यवहारमाध्यममेव स्तोत्रम् । धर्ममतभक्तिसाहित्यानि स्तोत्रेषु भवन्ति । समग्रदृष्ट्या स्वामिपादानां स्तोत्रानां सविमर्शाध्ययनं प्रबन्धेऽस्मिन् कृतमस्ति । प्रबन्धस्यास्य सारः, अध्ययनक्रमः च अस्मिन् लघुप्रबन्धे सङ्ग्रहेण दत्तमस्ति । अस्य लेखस्य विस्तृतः रूपः एव प्रबन्धे अवलोकयितुं शक्यते । अत्र तस्य दीर्घ प्रबन्धस्य सारः संग्रहरूपेण प्रदर्शितः ।

Keywords: श्रीसुधीन्द्र तीर्थः, काव्यस्तोत्र, गौडसरस्वतब्राह्मणाः, श्रीकाशीमठसंस्थानम्, बादरायण, अलङ्काराः, काव्यगुणः ।

Paper No. 14.09: Sanskrit Literature

न्यायशास्त्रोक्तषोडशपदार्थाः तेषां मोक्षोपयोगिता च

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ABSTRACT

इह जगति तावत् प्रयोजनमुद्दिश्यैव सकलप्रेक्षावतां प्रवृत्तिः दृश्यते । तच्च प्रयोजनं व्यावहारिकं पारमार्थिकं चेति द्विविधम् । तत्र व्यावहारिकप्रयोजनं तावत् दुःखादिसम्भिन्नात्वात् विवेकिभिः सद्भिः नादर्तुं योग्यम् । पारमार्थिकं च प्रयोजनं दुःखासम्भिन्नं निःश्रेयसापरपर्यायं मोक्षपदवाच्यमेव । तादृशपरमपुरुषार्थभूतमोक्षप्राप्तिमेव उद्दिश्य सर्वाणि अपि दर्शनानि प्रवृत्तानि । तत्र षट्सु आस्तिकदर्शनेषु अन्यतमं भवति महर्षिणा गौतमेन प्रणीतं न्यायदर्शनम् । तत्र प्रथमसूत्रे एव न्यायशास्त्रे प्रतिपाद्यमानाः षोडशपदार्थाः प्रतिपाद्यन्ते यथा - प्रमाणं, प्रमेयं, संशयः, प्रयोजनं, दृष्टान्तः, सिद्धान्तः, अवयवः, तर्कः, निर्णयः, वादः, जल्पः, वितण्डा, हेत्वाभासः, छलं, जातिः, निग्रहस्थानं⁷ च इति । तत्र त्रिविधा च अस्य शास्त्रस्य प्रवृत्तिः⁸ इति भाष्यकारैः वात्स्यायानैः उक्तरीत्या सूत्रे भाष्ये च षोडशपदार्थाः अपि उद्देश-लक्षण-परीक्षाक्रमेण निरूप्यन्ते ।

तथा च एतेषां षोडशपदार्थानां शास्त्रस्य च प्रयोजनं किमिति आद्यसूत्रे एव सूत्रितं, तच्च निःश्रेयसप्राप्तिरेव । तच्च कथं षोडशपदार्थानां तत्त्वज्ञानं मोक्षप्राप्तौ सहकारि इति चेत् जिज्ञासायां द्वितीयसूत्रे आहुः सूत्रकाराः – दुःखजन्मप्रवृत्तिदोषमिथ्याज्ञानानामुत्तरोत्तरापाये तदनन्तरापायादपवर्गः इति । तत्रादौ षोडशपदार्थानां तत्त्वज्ञानात् मिथ्याज्ञाननाशः भवति, ततः दोषनाशः, ततः प्रवृत्तिनाशः इत्येवं क्रमेण दुःखनाशः दुःखानुत्पादः इति एवं उत्तरोत्तरस्य अपाये नाशे तदुत्तराणां नाशः अनुत्पत्तिरिति अन्ते दुःखस्य नाशः अनुत्पादः एव वा मोक्षः इत्युच्यते । इत्थं न्यायशास्त्रस्यापि परम्परया परमपुरुषार्थभूतनिःश्रेयससाधकत्वम् इति ।

इत्थं क्रमेण षोडशपदार्थाः, तेषां च मोक्षसाधकत्वं, तत्र क्रमः इत्येवं विषयाः प्रस्तूयन्ते ।

Keywords: Tarka shastra, Padartha, Purushartha

⁷ प्रमाणप्रमेयसंशयप्रयोजनदृष्टान्तसिद्धान्तावयवतर्कनिर्णयवादजल्पवितण्डाहेत्वाभासच्छलजातिनिग्रहस्थानानां तत्त्वज्ञानान्निःश्रेयसाधिगमः । न्यायसूत्रम् - 1

⁸ न्यायसूत्रवात्स्यायनभाष्यम् ।

Paper No. 14.10: Sanskrit Literature

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ABSTRACT

सुभाषितस्य रुचेः पुरतः द्राक्षा म्लाना अभूत् । शर्करा शिलाखण्डः अभूत् । भीत्या सुधा स्वर्गलोकं प्रति फलयितवती । एवं सुभाषितस्य विषये सुभाषितरत्नभाण्डागरस्य उक्तिः। लौकिकजीवनं सार्थकम् अर्थपूर्णं च कर्तुं विद्यमानविशिष्टोक्तयः, लोकोक्तयः, हितवाक्यानि एव सुभाषितानि इति तु सुप्रसिद्धम् । सुभाषितानि मूल्ययुक्तम् एवम् अर्थगर्भितपदपुञ्जैः संयुक्तं वर्तन्ते। एतानि सरलया मधुरया मनोहरसंस्कृतभाषया एवं सलिलमनोहरछन्दसि रचितानि विद्यन्ते। एतत् भारतस्य सनातनज्ञानपरम्परायाः विचारधारायाः गरिमां वैशिष्ट्यं च अभिव्यनक्ति। सार्वकालिकसत्यं जीवनमौल्यं च बोधयति सुभाषितम्। भारतीयानां नृणां सर्वाङ्गीनविकासाय सुभाषितं कारणीभूतम् इत्यत्र नास्ति लेशोऽपि संशीतिः। समेषां अर्थपूर्णाय सन्तोषपूर्णाय सुखमयजीवनाय साहाय्यम् अभूत् सुभाषितम् । विदितं सत्यमिदं यत् भरतखण्डस्य प्राचीनसंस्कृतेः ज्ञानपरम्परायाः नागरीकतायाः दर्पणायते सुभाषितम्। एवमेव सुभाषितं वैविध्यपूर्णविषयाणाम् आगरः, भारतीयानां धर्म-तत्त्वज्ञान-समाजशास्त्र-कला-कुशलकर्मणाम् आगरः भाण्डारः सम्पत् विद्यते ।

भाषितमाध्यमेन समाजाय मानवानां लोपदोषान् ज्ञात्वा सङ्कष्टे विद्यमानेभ्यः समयानुसारं तेभ्यः नीतिपरोपदेशान् दत्त्वा मार्गदर्शनं अकुर्वन् । प्रत्येकं सुभाषिते कालानुगुणं, सन्दर्भानुगुणं जनेभ्यः जीवनस्य दर्शनम् एवम् उत्तमस्य जीवनमार्गस्य प्रदर्शनम् अकुर्वन् । एच्.वि.नगराजवर्याणाम् अर्थान्तरन्यासशतके पदे पदे सुभाषितानामुल्लेखः दरीदृश्यते । साम्प्रतसमाजया विभिन्नान् समदर्भान् उद्दिश्य विभिन्नप्रकारेण विभिन्नैः सुभाषितैः मार्गदर्शनं जीवनदर्शनञ्च अकुर्वन् ।

रामपत्नीं चोरयित्वा रावणो मृत्युमाह्वयत् ।

। व्याकरशास्त्रस्य महत् ज्ञानमसीतस्मीन्।तेन किं प्रयोजनम् ? रावणः तु महिलासु अनुरक्तः आसीत् । रम्भाय शापग्रस्तः असीदेति कथा श्रूयते । तादृशः रावणः सीतादेवीं चोरयित्वा मरणं प्राप्तवान् ।

Keywords: #शतककाव्यम् #सरलप्रयोगः #शतकरचनाशैली #नैतिकता #जीवनमूल्यानि

Paper No. 14.11: Sanskrit Literature

Lessons Of Sustainability in Vedic Literature

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ABSTRACT

The most revered of all Vedic literature is replete with hymns that praise nature. Daily Sanskrit mantras that honour the earth, animals, trees, rivers, and mountains are chanted by many. The Vedic philosophy of India has always emphasised the human relationship with nature. Some of the earliest teachings on ecological harmony and the necessity for humanity to treat nature with ethics may be found in the Mahabharata, Ramayana, Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, Puranas, and Smriti. They place a strong emphasis on coexistence with environment and acknowledge that all components of nature are sacred. People are beginning to understand that the consumption of our natural resources should have been more closely managed in light of the disastrous effects of climate change and the clear gap in quality of life between industrialised and developing countries. The notion of sustainability is now relevant in this situation. In order to be sustainable, human progress must coexist with the preservation of the natural systems that support the world. Sustainability has gained researchers interest in the past three decades. Even the Vedic literatures have been surveyed to understand their implications in the modern world, but there lies a gap in the research about sustainability ideologies set by Vedas in the contemporary research.

This study in a quest to understand the lessons of sustainability, explores the Vedic literature using the literature survey and hermeneutics, a qualitative methodology. Majority of the Vedic literature have laid a strong foundation for sustainable development of the contemporary world. Through rigorous research, we can enhance the ecological balance and have a sustainable development by building the bridges between the ancient Vedic literatures and modern sustainable technologies and innovations.

Keywords: *Sanskrit, Vedic literature, Bhagwat Gita, Sustainable Development, Environment, Ecology.*

Paper No. 14.12: Sanskrit Literature

ಮಾಧ್ವ ಮತದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿ

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ABSTRACT

ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸದಾಚಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಮುಖ್ಯವೋ ಹಾಗೆ ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯೂ ಮುಖ್ಯ. ಮಾನವನಿಗೆ ಬದುಕಲು ಆಹಾರ ಮುಖ್ಯ . ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯು ಒಂದು ಪ್ರದೇಶದಿಂದ ಮತ್ತೊಂದು ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹಳಷ್ಟು ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೇ ಆಹಾರ ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸುವುದರಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಕೆಲವೊಂದು ಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಇವೆ. ಕ್ರಮಪ್ರಕಾರ ನಾವು ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿ ಕೊಂಡರೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಆರೋಗ್ಯ ಹೊಂದಬಹುದು. ಸನಾತನ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯಕ್ಕೆ ಅನುಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳು ರೂಢಿಗೊಂಡಿವೆ .

ಈ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾಧ್ವ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಇರುವ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಆಹಾರ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುವ ಚಿಕ್ಕ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ . ಮಾಧ್ವ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಗವಂತನಿಗೆ ಆಹಾರವನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಪಿಸಿ ನಂತರ ಭೋಜನ ಮಾಡುವ ಕ್ರಮವಿದೆ . ಭೋಜನ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕ್ರಮಗಳ ಅನುಸರಣೆ, ವಿವಿಧ ಆಹಾರ ಪ್ರಕಾರಗಳು ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ನಿಯಮಗಳು, ಇಂದಿನ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಅದರ ಪ್ರಾಸ್ತಾವಿಕತೆ , ಅದರ ಅನುಕರಣೆಯಿಂದ ಆಗುವ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನ, ಶುದ್ಧತೆ, ಪರಿವೇಷಣ , ಆಹಾರವನ್ನು ತಿನ್ನುವ ಕ್ರಮಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ ಈ ಲೇಖನ. ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಆಹಾರವನ್ನು ಸಿದ್ಧಪಡಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ಜನಾಂಗದ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ ಆಹಾರ ತಯಾರಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವಿಧತೆ, ಹಬ್ಬಹರಿದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ತರಕಾರಿಯ ಬಳಕೆ, ವಸ್ತುಗಳ ಉಪಯೋಗ ಹೀಗೆ ಅನೇಕ ಅಮೂಲ್ಯ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ.

Keywords: ಮಾಧ್ವ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯ, ವಿವಿಧ ಆಹಾರ ಪ್ರಕಾರಗಳು, ಇಂದಿನ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಅದರ ಪ್ರಾಸ್ತಾವಿಕತೆ

Paper No. 14.13: Sanskrit Literature

The Landscapes of Kalidasa

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ABSTRACT

Kalidasa's creations have descriptions of different locales, that offered the reader word pictures of various geographical regions, cultures and civilizations. The purpose or research agenda of this paper is to research into the literary representations of places as also the cultures of these places in the works of Kalidasa. While studies abound with regard to the literary merits of the plots and characters of his plays and poems, spatial analyses or studies into the settings of the works are fewer in number. The dearth of studies on the presentation of cities and locales in Kalidasa's works is the research gap that is sought to be filled. The main objective is to understand how the descriptions of the regions and in particular cities that are the setting, aid our appreciation of the works.

The proposed research will be a content analysis and exploratory study of articles in peer-reviewed journals, doctoral theses and online sources. Some of the cities mentioned are Taxila, Hastinapura, Ujjayini, Milthila and Vrindavana. It is these vivid descriptions of urban settlements that make Kalidasa's plays and poems take root in the imagination of the reader and their immortality is proof of place and space providing solid foundations to the appreciation of literary creations.

Keywords: Kalidasa, Sanskrit Literature, Cityscapes, Literary Landscapes, Ujjayini

Paper No. 14.14: Sanskrit Literature

भासविरचितानां महाभारतान्तर्गतनाटकानाम् अध्ययनम्

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतवाङ्मये प्रथितनाटककारेषु अन्यतमः भासः। भासस्य नाटकानि वैविध्यमयः कथावस्तुभिः, ललितया भाषया, सरलया शैल्या सर्वजनहृद्यं भूत्वा संस्कृतवाङ्मये भासाय प्रमुखं स्थानं कल्पयन्ति। रामायण-महाभारतानां कथावस्तु आबालवृद्धेभ्यः ज्ञातपूर्वः एव। अतः कथाकथनं नूनं भासस्य उद्देशः न। तेषु विद्यमानाः रसभरिताः भागान् एव स्वीकृत्य अभिनययोग्यं नाटकं रचयित्वा सहृदयानां मनस्सन्तोषः एव तस्य उद्देशः।

अस्मिन् लेखे भासेन प्रणितेषु महाभारतान्तर्गतेषु नाटकेषु कथावस्तूनां वैविध्यम्, मूलकथानां परिवर्तनम्, स्त्रीपात्राणां चित्रणम्, नायकपात्राणां वैचित्र्यम्, शैली, रसनिरूपणम् इत्यादिविषयान् अधिकृत्य वक्तुम् इच्छामि। मध्यमव्यायोगः, पञ्चरात्रम्, दूतवाक्यम्, दूतघटोत्कचम्, कर्णभारम्, ऊरुभङ्गम् च महाभारतकथाधारितानि नाटकानि। पात्राणां उदात्तीकरणं भासस्य नाटकेषु द्रष्टुं शक्यते। सामान्यतः दुष्टपात्राणि इति वयं यानि पात्राणि कथयामः, तेषु पात्रेषु उत्तमान् अंशान् चित्वा सहृदयानां पुरतः प्रदर्शनम् एव भासस्य वैशिष्ट्यम्। अस्य नाटकेषु सामान्यजनानां मुग्धतां, गुरुषु भक्तिं, ज्येष्ठेषु आदरभावं जनेषु विनम्रताप्रदर्शनम्, दीनानां साहाय्यकरणम् इत्यादिकं वयं द्रष्टुं शक्नुमः।

Keywords: संस्कृतवाङ्मयम्, कथावस्तूनां वैविध्यम्, स्त्रीपात्राणां चित्रणम्, मूलकथानां परिवर्तनम्,

Paper No. 14.15: Sanskrit Literature

माघस्य पाण्डित्यं व्यक्तित्वं च

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ABSTRACT

माघकविः “शिशुपालवधम्” इति माहाकाव्यं लिलेख । अत्र इदं कथावस्तु, जरासन्धस्य वधं कृत्वा श्रीकृष्णः अर्जुनभीमाभ्यां सह इन्द्रप्रस्थं प्रत्यागतः, धर्मराजं युधिष्ठिरं सर्वं वृत्तान्तम् अवदत् च । तत् श्रुत्वा सः नितरां सन्तुष्टः । तत्पश्चात् युधिष्ठिरद्वारा राजसूययागं कर्तुं सिद्धतां कारितवान्। एवम् अस्मिन् काव्ये बहूनां प्राचीनानां कवीनां समन्वितां रूपं परिलक्षितम् अस्ति। अस्य काव्यस्य मूलं तु महाभारतस्य सभापर्वणि वर्णितं दृश्यते। तथैव श्रीमद्भागवत-पुराणादिषु अस्य कथा परिदृश्यते । अयं माघः सर्वेषां कवीनां मुख्यः प्रेरणास्रोतः अस्ति । स च पर्वत-ऋतु-वन-विहार-जलक्रीडा-सूर्यास्त-एवं प्रभातादिवर्णनं शिशुपालवधस्य एकैकस्मिन् सर्गेऽपि विस्तरेण कृतवान् अस्ति ।

वीररसप्रधाने अस्मिन् ग्रन्थे शृङ्गार-रौद्र-अद्भुतरसाः गौणतया दृश्यन्ते । अस्य माहाकाव्यस्य नायकः श्रीकृष्णः, स तु न केवलं देवपुरुषः अपि तु कुशलः शासकः इत्यपि कविः वर्णयति । श्रीकृष्णस्य पुरुषोत्तमस्वरूपं काव्ये तत्र तत्र दृश्यते । शिशुपालवधग्रन्थे माघस्य राजनैतिकज्ञानं कीदृशमिति द्वितीयसर्गे वर्णितम् वर्तते । माघः विलक्षणबुद्धिमान् इत्यतः समग्रं जीवनं विशेषज्ञानप्राप्त्यै यापितवान् ।

कवेरस्य राजनैतिकदृष्टिः महती एव आसीत् । शिशुपालवधे कौटिल्यस्य अर्थशास्त्रानुसारं राजसूययागस्य व्याजं कृत्वा राजकार्यस्य सम्पादनम्, नारदस्य आगमनम्, उद्धवेन सह मन्त्रालोचनं, कार्यगौरवचिन्तनम्, शिशुपालस्य वधः - इत्यादीनां वर्णनं अनिततरां शोभते । इदं काव्यं समकालीनं समाजाय कथम् उपकृतं भवति इति किञ्चित् विवेच्यते ।

Keywords: शिशुपालवधम्, इन्द्रप्रस्थवर्णनम्, महाभारतस्य सभापर्व, राजनैतिकदृष्टिः च इत्यादयः

Paper No. 14.16: Sanskrit Literature

Conflict, Dissent and Accommodations: Religious imagery in Kṛṣṇa Miśra's *Prabodhacandrodaya*

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ABSTRACT

The text *Prabodhacandrodaya* written by Kṛṣṇa Miśra is an allegorical drama. The major religious theme of the play is *Advaita Vedānta* of Vaiṣṇava tradition. In Sanskrit literature, allegory was never recognized as a distinct genre by Sanskrit writers on literary criticism and poetics.⁹ It was not until recent times, after Western literary categories became known, that writers in the modern Indian languages coined the Sanskrit term *pratīnāṭaka* (symbolic drama) and *rūpanāṭaka* (metaphorical drama) in order to describe “The Rise of Wisdom Moon” and works resembling it.¹⁰ The play *Prabodhacandrodaya* can be dated back to the second half of the eleventh century. The references concerning the Candella¹¹ ruler Kīrtivarman helps us in the dating of the play. The text provides the context that led to the play’s performance at the court of the Candella ruler Kīrtivarman. One of the Candella inscriptions¹² of Kīrtivarman’s reign also indicate the same. The language of the play is particularly Sanskrit, but as was the case with many Sanskrit plays, the dialect of *Prākṛit* is also used in the play.

The play explicitly provides the context which ushered its performance at the Candella court. The context is the restoration of the Candella kingdom during the reign of Kīrtivarman--at whose court the play was performed on the occasion of his victory. The restoration plainly indicates that he may have lost his kingdom or was losing it initially and later recovered it. In the same manner, we find the story of the rivalry between two brothers at interplay in the play, in which one has taken possession of the kingdom without sharing it with the latter. That further paved the way for the deposed brother to try and reclaim his share of kingdom. As this is an allegorical play, two brothers represent two different sets of religious

This paper aims to critically evaluate the text considering the prevailing contemporary religious conditions of the early medieval period. Moreover, it will focus to understand the nature of these various religious sects existing in the Indian subcontinent and how they have shaped and reshaped themselves over time in different socio-economic and political context.

Keywords: Advaita Vedānta, Allegory, Religious sects/Philosophies, Early Medieval period, Candellas.

⁹Kṛṣṇa Miśra, *Prabodhacandrodaya*, Tr. Matthew T. Kapstein, CSL, New York, 2009, p.xxxii.

¹⁰Ibid, pp.xxxii-xxxiii.

¹¹The Candellas ruled the region of Jeṅkabhukti (which has been also identified by modern Bundelkhand region) during the early medieval period. Initially, they were feudatory of Pratihāra rulers and later they were able to establish a successful regional kingdom.

¹²Ajaygaḍh Rock Inscription of the Time of Vīravarma, V.S.1325, *CII*, Vol.vii (part-iii), p.503.

Paper No. 14.17: Sanskrit Literature

An Analytical Study of Anthropology in Research of Vedic Literature.

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ABSTRACT

There is a huge difference between Vedic research and Vedic criticism. Vedic research is the influence of western scholars on India. It is as much a gift as it is a scourge. It cannot be applied to Vedic research because the concepts used in the research methodology are unsuitable. Researchers made two major mistakes in the area of research:

1. They did not focus on Vedic grammar.
2. Used anthropology as a research methodology.

“Anthropology is the science of a group of men and their behavior and production.” contemporary research in Vedic literature Anthropology is very essential and helpful equipment. In western countries, the most cases methodology of the study in Vedic literature is based on anthropological loom only. In this article we can see, what anthropology is. uses in research of Vedic literature and its limitations in research areas of Vedic literature.

Keyword – *Vedic, Culture, Anthropology, Research.*

Paper No. 14.18: Sanskrit Literature

कौटिल्यस्य अर्थशास्त्रे आधुनिकी दृष्टिः

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ABSTRACT

कौटिल्येन लिखितम् अर्थशास्त्रम् इति ग्रन्थः संस्कृतसाहित्य क्षेत्रे सर्वोत्कृष्टग्रन्थः इति प्रथितः अस्ति । यतः अयं ग्रन्थः भरतीयाणां आध्यात्मिकजीवनस्य अपेक्षया तस्य व्यतिरिक्तं लौकिकजीवनमपि प्रतिपादयति । अन्यच्च धर्मशास्त्राणाम् विषये अयं ग्रन्थः अत्यन्तं समुचितं समग्रं च चित्रणं ददाति । भासः, कालिदास, माघः भारविः इत्यादयः महाकवयः स्वीयकाव्यनाटकादिषु कौटिल्यस्य अर्थशास्त्रस्य तत्वानि उल्लिखितवन्तः सन्ति । एतेन अर्थशास्त्रस्य तत्वानि उल्लेखयितुं प्रतिपादयितुं च जनेषु आसक्तिः स्पष्टतया दृश्यते । एतस्मिन् ग्रन्थे राजनीतिविषये अपि च राज्यकार्याणां विषये पूर्णतया विवृतं दृश्यते। “अलब्धस्य लाभार्थः, लब्धस्य परिरक्षणं, रक्षितस्य विवर्धनं, योग्यस्य कृते तस्य प्रदानम् ” इति यद् कौटिल्येन अर्थस्य विषये उक्तमस्ति तत् अधुना अपि प्रस्तुतमस्ति ।

कौटिलीयम् अर्थशास्त्रं राजनीतिविषयकं ज्ञातुम् राज्ञा अवश्यं अध्येतव्यमेव । ग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् “तन्त्र”इत्यस्मिन् भागे राज्यपरिपालनाय अपेक्षिताः सर्वे विषयाः प्रतिपादिताः सन्ति अनेन कविना । कौटिल्यः पूर्वजानाम् अर्थशास्त्रज्ञानाम् अभिप्रायान् संग्रह्य विमृश्य च स्वाभिप्रायम् अर्थशास्त्रं रचितवान् । अस्याः कृतेः उत्कृष्टतां कौटिल्यस्य निर्दुष्टचिन्तनानि च लेखेऽस्मिन् प्रतिपादयितुम् इच्छामि ।

Keywords: कौटिलीयम् अर्थशास्त्रं, राजनीतिविषयः, राज्यभराक्रमे अर्थनीतिः

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श्री सिद्धान्तशिखामणिः – सविमर्शावलोकनम्

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ABSTRACT

श्रीसिद्धान्तशिखामणिः शैवसिद्धान्तस्य श्रेष्ठः ग्रन्थः । ग्रन्थस्य नाम एवास्य महत्त्वं सूचयति । अनुष्टुप् छन्दसि ग्रन्थोऽयं विरचितः । सच्चिदानन्दस्वरूपः परशिव एव प्रधानः देवः । गणनायकः रेणुकभगवत्पादः तत्त्वापेक्षी, मुनिं, स्वशिष्यं प्रति उपदिष्टवान् । अतः विचारश्रोतु एव आत्रागस्त्यः ।

श्री शिवयोगीशिवाचार्यः सिद्धान्तागमाधारेण श्री सिद्धान्तशिखामणिं व्यरचयत् । यथा भवगद्गीता उपनिषदानां सारः तथैव श्रीसिद्धान्तशिखामणिः सिद्धान्तागमानां सारः वर्तते । प्रमथगणान् तथा देवीमुद्दिश्य शिवेन प्रबोधितं शिवाध्वैतोपदेश एव कामिकादि वातुलान्ताः अष्टविंशतिः (२८) शिवागमाः । सिद्धान्तागमाः इत्येव एते सुप्रसिद्धाः ।

शिवोपदेशश्रुतैः प्रमथगणैः रेणुकः, दारुकः घण्टाकर्णः, धेनुकर्णः तथा विश्वकर्णाः इति पञ्चगणाधीशाः प्रमुखाः । एषु प्रमथगणेषु रेणुकगणेश्वरः शिवानुग्रहेण कोल्लिपाके श्री सोमेश्वरलिङ्गात् आविर्भूतः सन् शिवप्रेरणया प्राप्तं शिवाध्वैतज्ञानं मुनिमगस्त्यं प्रति उपदिशत् । एवं शिवेन शिवगणाय, शिवगणेन मुनिभ्यः, मुनिभिः मानवसमाजाय प्राप्तः शिवप्रसाद एव श्री सिद्धान्तशिखामणिः इति अवलोकनेन ज्ञायते।

श्रीरेणुकागस्त्ययोः संवादस्वरूपं श्रीसिद्धान्तशिखामणिं श्रीशिवयोगी शिवाचार्यः रचयामास । ग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् वेदसम्मताः सांख्ययोगपाञ्चरात्रवेदपशुपतेति पञ्चमतानामुल्लेखः विद्यते । माता एव एते, वेदसम्मताः इत्यत्र नास्ति संसितिः ।

जीवने साधनामयजीवनं कथं सिध्यति, पुण्यविशेष संग्रहं कथं करणीयः, पापरशिवमुक्तिः कथं भवति, शुद्धान्तः करण सिद्धिः कथं ? इत्यादि विचाराः ग्रन्थे सम्यक् निरूपितं वर्तते । आत्मानात्मविवेकं सम्पाद्य, संसारासक्तिं न्यूनीकृत्य शिवभक्तो भूत्वा, सद्गुरुं शरणं गन्तव्यम् । सद्गुरोः कारुण्यम्बुद्धौ दीक्षां प्राप्य, गुरोः मार्गदर्शनेन साधना पथेऽनुगन्तव्यमिति निर्देशनं वर्तते ।

ग्रन्थे मोक्षप्राप्तिः कथं सिध्यतीति विचारोऽपि स्पष्टतया निरूपितं वर्तते । भक्त, माहेश्वर, प्रसादी, प्राणलिङ्गी, शरणं ऐक्यं चेति षट्स्थलानां परिचयं कृत्वा, अनेन द्वारा शिवयोगसाधनं, प्रदर्शितमस्ति । अनेन मार्गानुसरणेण लिङ्गाङ्ग, सामरस्यरूपं मुक्तिं प्राप्तुं सर्वेऽपि शक्नुवन्ति इति निर्देशनं लभ्यते । ग्रन्थोऽयं सूक्ष्मतया सुलभतया च वीरशैवसिद्धान्तं परिचाययति । अत्रत्य भाषा, शैली च सरला वर्तते । काव्यशैल्या सिद्धान्तनिरूपणमेव ग्रन्थस्यास्य विशेषः । दीर्घप्रबन्धे समग्रग्रन्थं परिचयं कृत्व ग्रन्थविशेषं प्रदर्शितम् ।

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काव्यालङ्कारेषु रसस्वरूपम्

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ABSTRACT

सुरभारती इयं संस्कृतभाषा हृद्या रमणीया च । देववाणी इति संस्तूयमाना असौ भाषा मधुरा च वर्तते । महदिदं संस्कृतवाङ्मयम् । तत्र काव्यानि सन्ति भूयांसि । तथैव काव्यैः चतुर्वर्गफलप्राप्तिरपि भविता । मानवः काव्यरसास्वादेन विना जीवितुं न शक्नोति । अतः काव्यं जीवनस्य जीवातुभूतमेव । अतः काव्यस्वरूपनिरूपकाः अलङ्कारशास्त्रग्रन्थाः प्रायशः आदौ काव्यप्रयोजनानि एव परिशीलयन्ति । काव्यस्य आत्मभूतस्य रसस्य विषयः विस्तरतया लक्षणग्रन्थेषु प्रतिपाद्यन्ते ।

नाट्यशास्त्रे दशरूपके च रूपकाणां रसानां च विचारः दृश्यन्ते । शृङ्गारतिलकं रसतरङ्गिणी इत्यादिग्रन्थाः रससिद्धान्तं प्रतिपादयन्ति । रसः एव काव्यास्वादनार्थः सहृदयानाकर्षयति । रसं विना काव्यं नीरसं भवति । अतः रसः अपि प्रमुखं काव्यतत्त्वं भवति । एवञ्च संस्कृतसाहित्यं द्विधा कथ्यते । लौकिकसाहित्यं वैदिकसाहित्यञ्चेति । वैदिकसाहित्यं नाम चत्वारः वेदाः भवन्ति लौकिकसाहित्ये दृश्यं श्रव्यं च इति भेदद्वयं वर्तते । दृश्यं नाम नाटकादीनि भवन्ति । श्रव्ये गद्यं पद्यं चम्पूरिति भेदत्रयं भवति । एवञ्च दृश्यश्रव्यात्मकानि काव्यानि आनन्दस्यन्दीनि इति । एवं काव्यानि सहृदयानन्दजनकानि वर्तन्ते । रसाः आस्वाद्यमानाः भवन्ति काव्ये । रसाः नवधा –

शृङ्गारहास्यकरुणारौद्रवीरभयानकाः ।

वीभत्साद्भुत संज्ञौ च इत्यष्टौ नाट्ये रसाः स्मृताः ॥

इत्युक्त्वा शान्तोऽपि नवमो रसः इत्यब्रवीत् ।

Keywords: rasa in Sanskrit kavya, Natyashastra, kavyalakshana

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ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳು – ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಬಳಕೆ

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ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವು - ಸಮಸ್ತಪ್ರಾಣಿಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಜಗತ್ತನ್ನು ಕೂಡ ಸೇರಿಸಿ ಲೋಕವೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. **ಲೋಕೋ ಭೂವನಂ ಜನಃ** ಎಂದು ಅಮರಕೋಶ. ಅವರಿಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಅದು ಎರಡುಬಗೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

1. ಸುಸಂಸ್ಕೃತರಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಸುಶಿಕ್ಷಿತರಾದವರಿಂದ ರಚಿತವಾದದ್ದು.
2. ಅಸಂಸ್ಕೃತರಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಅಶಿಕ್ಷಿತರಾದವರಿಂದ ರಚಿತವಾದದ್ದು.

ಮೊದಲನೆಯದನ್ನು ಶಿಷ್ಟಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆಂದು, ಎರಡನೆಯದನ್ನು ಯಾರಿಂದಲೋ ಕೇಳಿ ಬಹುಕಾಲದಿಂದ ಪಾಲಿಸುತ್ತಿರುವ ಸಮಾಜಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವೆಂದು ಕರೆಯಬಹುದು. ಈ ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನೇ ಆಂಗ್ಲದಲ್ಲಿ folk-literature ಎಂದು ವ್ಯವಹರಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಲೋಕದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಜನರ ಭಾವನಾತ್ಮಕತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸರ್ಜನಾತ್ಮಕತೆಯೇ ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಮೂಲಕಾರಣವೆಂದು ತಿಳಿಯಬಹುದು. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಲೋಕಗೀತೆ,ಲೋಕಕಥೆ,ಲೋಕನಾಟ್ಯ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿ ನಮಗೆ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಅಲ್ಲಿ ಅಡಗಿದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಭಾಗವೇ ಲೋಕೋಕ್ತಿಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವು. ಅಂದರೇ ಲೋಕದಲ್ಲಾಡುವ ಮಾತುಗಳೆಲ್ಲವೂ ಲೋಕೋಕ್ತಿಗಳಲ್ಲ ಕಿಂತು ಲೋಕಕಲ್ಯಾಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಬಳಸುವ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟವಾದ ಉಕ್ತಿಗಳು ಮಾತ್ರ ಲೋಕೋಕ್ತಿಗಳೆನಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳು - ನ್ಯಾಯಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಯುಕ್ತಿಪದ್ಧತಿ, ನಿಯಮ, ಯೋಜನೆ, ಯೋಗ್ಯತೆ, ಔಚಿತ್ಯ, ತರ್ಕಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ, ಶಾಸನ, ನ್ಯಾಯಾಲಯದ ಆದೇಶ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಅನೇಕಾರ್ಥಗಳಿವೆ.ಆದರೇ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಆ ಶಬ್ದಕ್ಕೆ ಯುಕ್ತಿ ಅಥವಾ ನಿಯಮ ಎಂದರ್ಥ. ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ಲೌಕಿಕಜನರ ವ್ಯವಹಾರ, ಅನುಭವ, ಕಥೆ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನನುಸರಿಸಿ ಮಹತ್ತರವಾದ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಅತ್ಯಂತಸರಳವಾದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿಕೊಡುವ ಯುಕ್ತಿಗಳನ್ನೇ ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳೆನ್ನುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಶೋಧಪದ್ಧತಿ - ಈ ಪತ್ರವು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣಾತ್ಮಕಪದ್ಧತಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿ ಬರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಕೂಟಶಬ್ದಗಳು - ಲೋಕಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವು, ಲೌಕಿಕನ್ಯಾಯಗಳು, ಲೋಕಗೀತೆ, ಲೋಕಕಥೆ, ಲೋಕನಾಟ್ಯ, ಅರ್ಥವೈಶಸನ್ಯಾಯವು, ಪಂಗ್ವಂಧನ್ಯಾಯವು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ.

Paper No. 14.22: Sanskrit Literature

भारतीयसंस्कृतिः

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ABSTRACT

वैरिञ्चेलस्मिन् प्रपञ्चे विद्यमानासु सर्वासु संस्कृतिषु भारतीय संस्कृतिः प्राचीना । संस्कृतिरेषा प्राचीनत्वेन न गौरवान्विता प्रत्युत स्वगुणैः महनीया विद्यते । अत्र विचारस्वातन्त्र्यं सदाचारपालनं धर्मप्राधान्यं, दुर्भावदमनं पापापाकरणं, दुःखदहनं ज्ञानज्योतिप्रदानं असत्यप्रशमनं, शान्तिप्रदानं विश्वबन्धुत्वस्थापनं मनोमलीकरणं इत्यादयः दुर्लभागुणाः विराजन्ते यैः गुणग्रामैः संस्कृतिरेषा सर्वस्मिन् जगति स्वप्रभावं विस्तारयन्ती जनान् आकर्षति ।

भारतीयया संस्कृतिना सर्वेभारतीयाः जना एकतायाः सूत्रे पुष्पाणीव प्रोता सन्ति । तेषाम् ऐक्यस्य मूलम् संस्कृतिरेव विद्यते । किं बहुना भारतीयानां संस्कृतौ सदाचारपालनम् अतिथिनां सेवासत्कारपूजा, पितुः सेवाज्ञापालनम् गुरुजनानां समादरम् इत्यादयः भावाः समाहिताः सन्ति । एवमत्र जनस्य परिवारस्य समाजस्य देशस्य निखिलविश्वस्य चाभ्युदयार्थं सर्वे भावाः विराजन्ते । अत एव भारतीयया संस्कृतिः सर्वैः प्रशस्यते ।

Keywords: संस्कृतिषु भारतीय संस्कृतिः, विश्वबन्धुत्वस्थापनं, असत्यप्रशमनं, शान्तिप्रदानम् च

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ಶ್ರೀ ರಾಘವೇಂದ್ರೋ ಸಕಲಪ್ರದಾತ....

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ಭಾರತ ಎಂದರೆ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ತವರೂರು. ಈ ಒಂದು ಪುಣ್ಯ ಭೂಮಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವಾರು ಮಹಾಪುರುಷರು ಅವತಾರವೆತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವಾರು ನದಿಗಳು ಹರಿದು ಮನುಷ್ಯನ ಜೀವನವನ್ನು ಪಾವನಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಲೆಕ್ಕವಿಲ್ಲದಷ್ಟು ಪುಣ್ಯ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳೂ ಇವೆ. ಸ್ಮಶಾನವೇದವೇದಾಂತಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅಷ್ಟು ದಶ ಪುರಾಣಗಳು ಜನಿಸಿದ ಪುಣ್ಯ ಭೂಮಿ ಈ ದೇಶ. ಈ ಒಂದು ವೈದಿಕ ಸಾಗರದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಿಂದೆದಾ ವರು ಬಹಳಷ್ಟು ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರು ಇದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರೀ ಗುರುರಾಯರ ಪೂವಾಶರ ಮದ ಗೋಷೀತರ ವಾದ ಗೌತಮ ಕುಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಜನಿಸಿದವರು ಶ್ರೀ ರಾಜಾ.ಎಸ್.ಗುರುರಾಜಾಚಾರ್ಯರು. ಇವರು ಶ್ರೀ ಗುರುರಾಯರು ಬರೆದಿರುವ ಅದ್ವೈತೀ ಗರಂಧಗಳಿಗೆ ಟಿಪ್ಪಣಿಯನ್ನು ಬರೆದಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಅಷ್ಟೇ ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಇವರು ಪ್ರಖಂಡ ಪಂಡಿತರು ಆಗಿರುವುದರಿಂದ ಹಲವಾರು ಗರಂಧಗಳನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ಕೃತಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಿ ಭಾರತ ಸ್ವಾರಸ್ಯದಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ಹಲವಾರು ಮಠಾಧಿಪತಿಗಳಿಂದ ಸ್ವಾನುಕುಲ ಪಾತ್ರ ರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅಂತಹ ಶ್ರೀಷರ ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರು ಬರೆದಿರುವಂತಹ ಕೃತಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ (ಯಥಾಶಕ್ತು) ಒಂದು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲು ಹೊರಟೆದೇನೆ. ಇದೇಗ ನಮ್ಮ ಶ್ರೀ ಗುರುರಾಯರು ಬರೆದಿರುವಂತಹ “ಶ್ರೀಭಗವತ್ಪ್ರಾಣನಪು ಕರಣಂ” ಎಂಬ ಒಂದು ಗರಂಧದ ವೈಶ್ವಯವನು ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ಮಾತ್ರವೇ ತಿಳಿಸುತ್ತಿ ಇಚ್ಛಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ. ಈ ಒಂದು ಗರಂಧದಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಯರು ಭಗವಂತನ ಧ್ಯಾನವನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಬಹಳ ಸೊಗಸಾಗಿ ತಿಳಿಸಿಕೊಟ್ಟಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹೃದಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಧ್ಯಾನ ನಿರ್ಮಲದ ಮೂರು ಭಗವದ್ರ ಪ್ಪಳು ಯಾವುದೆಂದರೆ - || “ ಹೃದಯೇ ಧ್ಯಾನೇ ಮೂರ್ಯ ಸ್ವಿ ಸ್ಯು: ಹೃದಯಾಖ್ಯಾ: ಪ್ರ ಕೀರ್ತಯಾ:” || ಅಥಾವತ್ ಹೃದಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಧ್ಯಾನ ನಿರ್ಮಲದ ಭಗವದ್ರ ಪ್ಪಳು ಇವು ಮೂರು - “ಹೃದಯದಲ್ಲಿ ವಾಯು ನೃದ ಸ್ವೇಶನೃದ ಪುರುಷೇತು ಮನು ಪಾರ ದೇಶ. ಅವನು ಜೀವರಿಗೆ ಆಶರ ಯ ಸಾ ನವನಿಸಿದಾನೆ. ಸ್ವಾದೇವಾಶರ ಯನೃಗಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಸ್ವತನೃಗಿದ್ದಾನೆ. ಹೃದಯಕ್ಕಲ ಕೀರ್ತಮೂಲದಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವಾಂಗುಷು ಪ್ರ ಮಾಣ್ಡಿಂದ ಇರುವನ

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चाणक्यनीते: प्रयोजनम्

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ABSTRACT

चाणक्यः मौर्यवंशप्रथमराज्ञः चन्द्रगुप्तस्य मन्त्री सहायकः च आसीत् । सः कौटिल्यः वा विष्णुगुप्तः इति नामभ्याम् अपि प्रसिद्धः आसीत् । सः प्राचीनभारतस्य प्रसिद्धतमः कूटनीतिज्ञोऽभवत् । तस्य साहाय्येन एव चन्द्रगुप्तेन नन्दराज्यम् अवस्थापितम् मौर्यवंशं स्थापितः च । चाणक्यः अर्थशास्त्रम् इति पुस्तकस्य लेखको आसीत् । राजनीत्यां तस्य नीतिः चाणक्यनीतिः इति नाम्ना प्रसिद्धा अस्ति । चाणक्यस्य पिता चणकः कश्चन ब्राह्मणः आसीत् । बाल्ये चाणक्यः सर्वान् वेदान् शास्त्राणि च अपठत् । परं सः नीतिशास्त्रम् एव इच्छति स्म । सः यौवने तक्षशिलायाम् अवसत् । एकदा सः मगधस्य राज्ञा धननन्देन लङ्घितः आसीत् । अतः चाणक्यः धननन्दं प्रति प्रतीकारम् ऐच्छत् । चाणक्यः धीरेण चन्द्रगुप्तमौर्येण मिलित्वा तं सिंहासने स्थापयितुम् अचिन्तयत् । एका माता स्वपुत्राय अक्रुध्यत् । सा उवाच " पुत्र ! त्वम् किमर्थम् एतद् उष्णम् अपूपम् मध्यभागात् अखादत् । अपूपम् तस्य कोणात् खाद" इति । तस्याः वचनानि श्रुत्वा चाणक्यः उपायम् अकरोत् । सः नन्दराज्यस्य सीमाप्रदेशान् प्रथमम् अजयत् । ततः सः चन्द्रगुप्तमौर्यं सिंहासने स्थापयित्वा तम् अरक्षत् । विशाखदत्तस्य नाटकम् मुद्राराक्षसं चाणक्यस्य चरितं कथयति ।

यः कोऽपि राजा क्रोधात्, लोभात्, भयात् च कस्यचित् पक्षस्य तर्कं सम्यक् न गृह्णाति निर्णयं सम्यक् न स्वीकरोति चेत् भविष्ये स्वयं नृपः एव प्रजान् कष्टकूपे पातितवान् भवति । तादृशः नृपः सिंहासनात् अवरोहणीयः नो चेत् सम्पूर्णराज्यस्य अधःपतनं भवति । ग्रन्थेऽस्मिन् राज्यपरिपालनं, कूटनीतयः, राज्यशासनं, प्रजाभिः सहवर्तनम् इत्यादयः अनेके गुणाः वर्णिताः सन्ति । तेषाम् अध्ययनेन वयमपि जीवनस्य नानाघट्टेषु विविधान् प्रसङ्गान् कथं सम्मुखीकर्तुं शक्नुमः इति मन्मतिः ।

Keywords: चाणक्यः, नीतिशास्त्रम्, चन्द्रगुप्तकथा, राजशासनविधिः इत्यादयः

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वर्तमान परिप्रेक्ष में प्राचीन भारतीय गोसंरक्षण परंपरा

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ABSTRACT

भारत में ज्ञान परंपरा प्राचीन है। अनेक शास्त्र, विज्ञान, कृषी, आयुर्वेद, अर्थशास्त्र, राजनिती, पशुशास्त्र, इत्यादी शास्त्र का निर्माण हुआ। प्राचीन भारतीयोंने अपने समीपस्थ निसर्ग से अपना जीवन सरल बनाने का तरीका सीख लिया था। और निरंतर ऐसे ज्ञान संपादन करते जा रहे थे जो मनुष्य जीवन को कष्ट से मुक्ति दिला सके। परंतु पर्यावरण का विनाश किये बीना समतोल बनाये रखना प्राथमिकता थी। अपनी जीज्ञासा शांत करने की कोशीश से अनेक शास्त्रों का निर्माण हुआ। वर्तमान युग को विज्ञान युग कहा जाता है। परंतु भारतीयोंने कई वैज्ञानिक शोध लगाये थे। खगोलशास्त्र, गणितशास्त्र, भौतिकशास्त्र, रसायणशास्त्र, इत्यादी विज्ञान विषयों में भी भारतीय आगे थे। इन सब ज्ञान में एक ज्ञान है - गोसंरक्षण।

गाय को भारतीय समाज में महत्वपूर्ण स्थान प्राप्त है। प्राचीन भारत में गौ भारतीय जीवन का हिस्सा था। भारत कृषीप्रधान देश था। इसलिए भारतीय कृषि के लिए गौ और बैल का महत्व अधिक था। उसी प्रकार घोडा, बकरी, म्हैस, इन सभी पालतु तानवरों का इस्तेमाल किया जाता था। पर इन सब में गौ का स्थान सर्वश्रेष्ठ था। क्योंकि काय का दूध, दही, घी, गौमुत्र, गोमय (गोबर) इत्यादी सभी घटक मनुष्यों के लिए फायदेमंद थे। इसलिए गाय के दूध को अथर्ववेद में अमृत कहा गया था।

इस प्रकार गौ मनुष्यों को उपयुक्त है। इसलिये गौ की रक्षा करना चाहिए। गौ अवध्य है और गौ संरक्षण करना ही चाहिए। 'अथर्ववेद' में गौ को शुद्ध जल देना चाहिए और घास उपलब्ध कराये और गौ का रक्षण इन्द्र के शस्त्रोद्वारा सब दिशाओं से हो, इस तरह की प्रार्थना कि है। और गौ रक्षण हेतू गोठा निर्माण करना चाहिए। इस गोशाला में गौ की खाने पिये की और उनकी उत्तम संतती निर्माण होने के लिए उत्तम व्यवस्था करनी चाहिए।

इस प्रकार मनुष्य जीवन में गौ का महत्व जानकर गौ संरक्षण हेतू संपूर्ण प्रयास करना है। यह ज्ञान परंपरा आज भी उपयुक्त है।

इस शोध निबंध में प्राचीन भारतीय गोसंरक्षण हेतू उपयुक्त ज्ञान वर्तमान परिप्रेक्ष में किस प्रकार उपयुक्त है। यह इस शोध निबंध का हेतू है।

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ABSTRACT

भारतस्य प्रतिष्ठे द्वे "संस्कृतं संस्कृतिश्च" इति सुप्रसिद्धं वाक्यमस्त । इत्युक्ते संस्कृतभाषायाः तथा भारतीयसंस्कृतयोः द्वयोः अविनाभावसम्बन्धः विद्यते । भारतीयपरम्परायां संस्कृतभाषासाहित्यस्य प्रभावः बहुधा दृश्यते । संस्कारयुक्तभाषया उत्तमसंस्कारप्रदानाय संस्कृतभाषा प्रशक्ता अस्ति । अत्र सत्यं, दानं, त्यागः, अहिंसा, प्रेम, परोपकारः, राष्ट्रभक्तिः, मानवीयमौल्यानां निधिरेव विद्यते ।

संस्कृतभाषासाहित्यस्य विषये यदि किञ्चित् चिन्तयामः चेत् जगति साहित्यक्षेत्रे संस्कृतस्य योगदानम् अनुपममस्ति । इयं चिरपुरातना चेदपि नित्यनुतना । अस्याः साहित्यगङ्गा वैदिककालात् निरन्तरं निर्गलतया प्रवहन्ती एव अस्ति । तादृश साहित्यगङ्गाप्रवाहे अनेके उपनद्यः उद्भूताः सन्ति । एषा संस्कृतभाषा भारतीय-बहुभाषानां जननी तथा सम्पोषिका अपि विद्यते । अतः तादृश्य अद्भुतस्य श्रीमन्तस्य संस्कृतसाहित्यपरम्परायाः सामान्य परिकल्पना भारतीयानां भवेत् । येन अस्माकं संस्कृतभाषायाः गरीमा तथा भारतीयसंस्कृत्याः स्वाभिमानः प्रत्येकस्य भारतीयस्य भवतु इति आशास्महे ।

Keywords : संस्कृतम्, साहित्यम्, संस्कृतिः, भारतीयपरम्परा, स्वाभिमानः

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एको रसः करुण एव.....

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ABSTRACT

यथा प्राचीन कवीनां देशकालादिपरिचयः प्रायो दुर्लभो भवति न सा स्थितिः अमुष्य विद्यते। भवभूतिना स्वकीयेषु नाटकेषु संक्षेपेण स्वकीयः परिचयः “ग्रामं गच्छन् तृणं स्पृशति” इति न्यायात् प्रदत्तः एव । तद्यथा वीरचरिते मालतीमाधवे च दृ तथैव उत्तररामचरिते सूत्रधारमुखेन वाचयति ।

नाटकेषु सुखपर्यवसायिता शास्त्रैः अनुमोदिताः, तदनु रूपं भवभूतिना उत्तररामचरितस्य सप्तमे अङ्के सीतारामयोः सङ्गमः प्रदर्शितः । ततः प्राक् घटनावैचित्र्याणां रचनया करुणरसस्य सम्यक् परिपाकसिद्ध्यर्थं कविना स्वकीयकाव्यकलायाः पाण्डित्यं प्रदर्शितम् । विशेषतः तृतीयेऽङ्के अदृश्यसीतायाः रामेण सह निवसन्त्याः अपि रामविरहः कवेः अनुपमां प्रतिभां व्यनक्ति। सीतया सह व्यतीतघटनाः स्मारं स्मारं रामस्य चित्तवृत्तौ व्याकुलताप्रादुर्भावः प्रसङ्गस्य उपक्रमः अस्ति ।

मूर्च्छितस्य रामस्य सीतायाः स्पर्शमात्रेण सचेतनतायाः वर्णनम् भवभूतेः कल्पनाकौशलमेव । इत्थं भवभूतेः करुणरसवर्णनसाफल्यं तं चिरस्थायिनं कर्तुं सर्वथा प्रभवत्येव, तस्मात् कवेः वर्णनकौशलशैलीनां परिवीक्षणेन संस्कृतज्ञाः वयं सदैव नवचैतन्यं नूतनदिशं च प्राप्नुवाम ।

Keywords: भवभूतिः, उत्तररामचरितस्य विन्यासक्रमः, करुणरसवर्णनक्रमः, नूतनकल्पना

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भगवता परशुरामेण निर्मितः तौळवप्रदेशः

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ABSTRACT

भगवान् परशुरामः एकविंशतिवारं भूमण्डलं प्रदक्षिणीकृत्य दुष्टक्षत्रियान् अहनत् । कश्यपमहामुनये भुवं दानरूपेण अदात् । दत्तभुवौ वासः न विधेयः इति निश्चित्य समद्रं आयुधेन दूरीचकार । तत्र नूतनप्रदेशं निर्मितवान् । भूमेः सृष्टिकार्ये भगवतः सङ्कल्पः विलक्षणः । तत्र असुरसंहारोऽपि उद्देशः ।

एनं विषयं कृष्णावधृतः –

“भार्गवः ततः पाथसां निधौ अक्षिपच्छरं सातविक्रमः ।

तेन तद्गताः राक्षसाः हताः सोऽपि वारिधिर्दूरतो ययौ” [मन्दारमरन्दचम्पू-१-३४] इति निरूपितवान् ।

पश्चिमसमुद्रतटे कासरगोडुप्रदेशतः गोकर्णपर्यन्तरप्रदेशः तौळवप्रदेशः । क्रि.श. १४-१५ शतके विराजमानः पूज्यः श्री श्रीराजराजेश्वरतीर्थः –

“तत्राऽसीनः शिरसि महति प्रस्खलन्मेघबिम्बे

पश्याथस्तात् विवृतनयनस्तौळवं देशभागम् ।

आगोकर्णं जलधिवलयेनाऽवृतं दक्षिणेन

ब्रह्मावासं नृपतिरिपुणा जामदग्न्येन सृष्टम्” [रामसन्देश-पू. ४२] इति अवर्णयत् ।

स एव प्रदेशः “परशुरामप्रदेशः” । प्राचीग्रन्थेषु “शूर्पाकारप्रदेशः” इति उक्तम् । तस्मिन् प्रदेशे सप्तमोक्षदायकक्षेत्राणि प्रसिद्धानि ।

तथा हि –

“शौष्यपीठं कुमारद्विः कुम्भासी च ध्वजेश्वरः ।

क्रोडगोकर्णमूकाम्बाः सप्तैताः मोक्षदायिकाः” इति सप्तक्षेत्राणि प्रसिद्धानि ।

तत्र तावत् गोकर्णक्षेत्रं उत्तरकन्नडमण्डले सुब्रह्मण्यक्षेत्रञ्च दक्षिणकन्नडमण्डले वर्तते । उडुपिमण्डले पञ्चक्षेत्राणि सन्ति । अस्मिन्नेव उडुपीक्षेत्रे मध्यगोहकुलजाः वसन्ति स्म । एते तपोधनाः ज्ञानधनाः कृतिनिपुणाः परोपकारिणश्च आसन् । एतेषां कुलस्वामी श्रीभगवान् अनन्तासनः ।

तौळवमण्डलस्य विद्वत्परम्परा

तौळवमण्डले अविच्छिन्नविद्वत्परंपरा वर्तते । तत्र ग्रन्थकाराः व्याख्यानकाराः संशोधकाः अद्यापकाः प्रवचनकाराश्च प्रसिद्धाः । तौळवपण्डिताः द्विविधाः । यतयः गृहस्थाश्च इति । तत्र अनेके यतयः संस्कृतवाङ्मये अपूर्व योगदानं ददुः । तत्र तावत् श्रीमध्वाचार्यः

“नानासुभाषितस्तोत्रगाथादिकृतिसत्कृतीः

त्वयि रत्नाकरे रत्नश्रेणीः वा गणयन्ति के” [मध्व.१५.८४] इति पण्डिताचार्यस्य

वचनानुसारं श्रीमध्वाचार्यः अपरिमितं ग्रन्थसमूहं रचयामास इति ज्ञायते । सर्वमूलग्रन्थाः इत्येव प्रसिद्धाः एते ग्रन्थाः परमादरणीयाः । सर्वमूलग्रन्थान् विरचय्य द्वैतदर्शनं सुविस्तृतं चकार । व्यासदेवहृदयातिवल्लभान् ज्ञानभक्तिदान् ग्रन्थान् कृत्वा संशयतिमितं छित्वा विज्ञानभानुं प्रादर्शयत् । श्रीमध्वाचार्यस्य ग्रन्थान् बहवः तौळवयतिपुङ्गवाः ग्रहस्थाश्च व्याचख्युः ।

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गुमानिकवेः-उपदेशशतकम्

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतवाङ्मयं महासागरवत् अत्यन्त विस्ताररूपेण व्याप्तं अस्ति । अनेकानि कविरत्नानि असङ्ख्यातकव्यानि रचयित्वा संस्कृतवाङ्मयस्य माहात्म्यं प्रकाशितवन्तः । ऋषीणां दर्शनस्वरूपा एव वेदाः, ते षां सहायिकाङ्गानि वेदाङ्गानि, अष्टादश पुराणानि च महाकाव्यानां रचनायां पूरकं प्रेरकं च सन्ति । कालिदास, भास, भारवि इत्यादयः महान् कविवरेण्याः तेषां अनन्यकृतिभिः लोकप्रियाः अभवन् । न केवलं एते महाकवयः अपितु अन्ये बहवः कवयः बाह्यलोके प्रकाशम् अनागत्य इदानीमपि अज्ञाता एव वर्तन्ते । एते अज्ञातकवयः साहित्यकृष्यां प्रवृत्ता भूत्वा बहुमूल्यं योगदानं दत्तवन्तः । उदासीनतया अज्ञानतया अवशिष्टः ग्रन्थेषु गुमानिकवेः 'उपदेशशतकम्' अपि अन्यतमः ।

व्यक्तिगतरूपेण सामाजिकरूपेण च मनुष्याणां आचरणं कथं भवेत् इति नीतिशास्त्रग्रन्थाः अस्मान् बोधयन्ति । कथायाः अङ्गत्वेन आगता एते ग्रन्थाः मधुरलेपित औषधमिव स्वादिष्टाः परिणामकारिणः च भवन्ति । सरलभाषा, प्रत्यक्षनिरूपणा, मृदुमधुरपदप्रयोगः, सुभगशैली – एते गुणाः नीतिकाव्यस्य रहस्यम् । अनेकेषु नीतिकाव्येषु 'उपदेशशतकस्य' तथा तस्य लेखक गुमानिकवेः विषये संक्षिप्त परिचयोऽत्र दीयते ।

गुमानिकवेः – काल-देश-जीवन तथा साहित्यम् ।

गुमानिकविः क्रि.श. १७९०, फरवरी मासस्य प्रथमे दिनाङ्के उत्तरप्रदेशस्य नैनीतालमण्डलस्य 'काशीपुर' इति प्रसिद्धनगरे अजायत । तस्य पिता 'देवनिधिः' इति, माता 'देवमञ्जरी' इति । अयं कविः संस्कृतभाषायां, काव्यकलायां च पण्डितः अभवन् । तेन विरचितेषु पञ्चादश ग्रन्थेषु 'उपदेशशतकम्' प्रसिद्धं जनप्रियं च अस्ति ।

'आर्या' छन्दसी विरचिता शतश्लोकानां नीतिबोधक कृतिरेव 'उपदेशशतकम्' । अत्र प्रत्येकश्लोकस्य पादत्रयं कथामेकां निरूप्य चतुर्थः पादः अस्याः कथायाः नीतिं बोधयति । अत्र श्लोकाः रामायण-महाभारत-भागवतपुराण कथाभिः प्रेरणां प्राप्य रचिताः सन्ति । अस्याः कृतेः रचनातन्त्रं अनन्यमस्ति । कथा तथा नीतिनिरूपणावसरे संयोजनसन्दर्भे च कविः नैपुण्यं प्रदर्शितवान् । नीतिशास्त्रस्य विधि-निषेध मार्गद्वयमपि चतुरतापूर्वकं कविः प्रस्तौति । 'धीरः समयं प्रतीक्षेत', 'साम्ना मूर्खं वशेकुर्यात्' इत्यादयः वाक्येषु विधि मार्गेण नीतिं बोधयति । 'नहि निजबन्धुर्विरोद्धव्यः', 'प्राप्तैश्वर्यान् न दृप्तः स्यात्' इत्यादयः वाक्येषु निषेधमार्गेण नीतिं बोधयति । अलङ्कारभारं विना, कठिणपदप्रयोगं विना, सरलसुन्दर निरूपणशैली जनानन्दकरी अस्ति ।

'अज्ञातकवि' गुमानिना रचितं 'उपदेशशतकम्' ग्रन्थविषये मया सज्जीकृतं निबन्धं 'विश्वमाङ्गल्यं' संस्कृतसम्मेलने सविस्तारेण प्रस्तौतुं इच्छामि ।

Paper No. 14.30: Sanskrit Literature

प्राचीनजीवनपद्धतिः

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ABSTRACT

जगतीतले विद्यमानानां मनुष्याणां समेषां मध्ये प्रत्येकोऽपि मानवः स्वसुखमेव अभिप्रैति। न दुःखं जातुचिदपि। तत्सुखमनुसन्धातुमेव एषः जिगमिषति नव नवीन मार्गेषु। अत्र केचन भोगनिरताः दरीदृश्यन्ते। तत्र केचन योगेच्छवः। अन्यत्र किङ्कर्तव्यमुढाः। परं तु भारतेस्मिन् देशे भूत्वाऽपि विविधमतानुसारिणः स्वजीवनपद्धतिं एकेनैव रीत्या यापयन्ति जनाः इत्यहो वैशिष्ट्यं प्राचीन भारतीयजीवनपद्धतेः।

सन्ध्यादिकर्मानुष्ठानं, प्राणायामादि श्वासोच्छ्वासः, आयुर्वेदादिचिकित्सापद्धतिः योगेन देह दण्डनं-सदाचार पालनं - अन्नाद्याहार क्रमः - उत्सवादि आचरणानि इति नैकेषु विषयेषु एकाभिप्रायाः भारतीयाः राष्ट्रैकसूत्रतां परिपालयन्नपि विभिन्नेषु क्षेत्रेषु कृतभूरिपरिश्रमाः। यदन्यत्र व्याख्यानमासीत् "सदृशजनसङ्गः" इति राष्ट्रस्य तन्निराकृतमपि किञ्चिदिव समन्वितम्।

कोरोनानन्तरकालीनाः जनाः विशिष्य अभ्यासं प्राचीनजीवनपद्धतेः, तदन्तर्भूतानां विषयाणां च अध्ययने प्रवृद्धोत्साहाः जाताः नेत्यत्र संशयः। प्राचीनानां जीवनं प्राचीनग्रन्थेषु निबद्धं मन्यमानाः बुद्धिमन्तः ग्रन्थान्वेषणे प्रयतमानाः अपि दृश्यन्ते।

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महाकवेः कालिदासस्य सनातनधर्मपद्धतिः

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतवाङ्मये बहवः कवयः, बहवः नाटककाराः, अनेके गीतकाराः राजन्ते तेषु कविकुलगुरुकालिदासः सर्वश्रेष्ठोऽस्ति उक्तं च

पुरा कवीनां गणना- प्रसङ्गे, कनिष्ठिकाधिष्ठित कालिदासः ।

अद्यापि तत्तुल्यकवेरभावा दनामिका सार्थवती बभूव ॥

महाकविना जयदेवेन कालिदासः संस्कृतसाहित्यकामिन्याविलासः उद्घोषितः । यथा

यस्याश्चोरश्चिकुरनिकरः कर्णपूरो मयूरो, भासो हासः कविकुलगुरुः कालिदासो विलासः ।

हर्षो- हर्षो हृदयवसतिः पञ्चवाणस्तु बाणः, केषां नैषा कथय कविता कामिनी कौतुकाय ॥

एवं विवेचनेन निश्चीयते यत् प्राचीनकाले कविकुलगुरुकालिदासस्य प्रतिष्ठा सर्वाधिका आसीत् ।

कालिदासस्य काव्येषु काव्यस्य सर्वे गुणाः पौनः पुन्येन नरीनृत्यन्ति भावानुकूला भाषा, रसानुकूला पदयोजना आदर्शचरित्रस्य उपस्थापना अलङ्काराणां समुचितगुम्फनं समुचितच्छन्दोयोजनेत्यादिकं महाकवेः वैशिष्ट्यं यत्र-तत्र सर्वत्र लोचनपथमायाति ।

उपमालङ्कारयोजनायां तस्य वैशिष्ट्यं विश्वविख्यातमस्ति उक्तं च -

'वाग्' शब्दमादृत्य अनेन महाकविना रघुवंशमहाकाव्यस्य रचना कृता । यथा- वागर्थाविव संपृक्तौ

वागर्थप्रतिपत्तये । जगतः पितरो बन्दे पार्वतीपरमेश्वरी ॥

अयं कविः सुरभारत्याः महान् विद्वान् आसीत् । सर्वेषां शास्त्राणां ज्ञानं कालिदासस्य आसीत् । तस्य काव्यस्य अध्ययनेन ज्ञायते यदयं शास्त्राणां महान् ज्ञाता आसीत् । महाभारतमाहत्य अभिज्ञानशाकुन्तलस्य रचना अनेन विहिता रामायणामाहत्य रघुवंशमहाकाव्यस्य रचना कविकुलगुरुणा विहिता । कविरयं शिवस्य परमः भक्तः आसीत् । सर्वेषां नाटकानां प्रारम्भः अपि शिवस्य प्रार्थनया कृतः ।

नाट्यशास्त्रस्य दृष्टिकोणेऽपि कवेरस्य नाटकानि समीचीनानि सन्ति । कवेरस्य काव्यस्य अध्ययनेन ज्ञायते यत् अनेन कविना सम्पूर्णभारतस्य यात्रा विहिता । सम्पूर्णभारतस्य ज्ञानं तस्य आसीत् । असौ महान् यात्री आसीत् । सम्पूर्णभारतस्य भौगोलिक, सामाजिक, सांस्कृतिक च वर्णनमनेन विहितम् ।

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काव्यस्वरूपं तथा काव्यप्रवेशः कथम् ?

डा.गौरी हेगडे

कर्कि-नाका, होन्नवर उत्तरकन्नड कर्नाटक -५८१३३४

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ABSTRACT

कवेः कर्म काव्यम् । स च काव्यशब्दः कविशब्दात् ब्राह्मणदित्वात् ष्यञि निष्पन्नः कविकर्मणि वर्तते । राजशेखरस्तु कवृ वर्णे इति धातोः कर्मणि ष्यत्प्रत्ययेऽयं शब्द इत्यभिप्रेति— तदसत्, पाणिनीयतन्त्रे तद्भातोरदर्शनात् । तन्त्रातरेणाभिधानम् इत्युक्तेऽपि कार्यादिशब्दवत् अस्यापि शब्दस्य विशोष्यानिघ्नत्वापत्तिः । नहि अस्मिन्नर्थेऽयं शब्दः पुंसि स्त्रियां वा आम्नातो वर्तते । काव्य इति शब्दः पुंसि यद्यपि वर्तते तथापि भागवार्थकत्वात् तेन प्रकृते न कोऽप्यर्थः । एतादृशस्य काव्यस्य आविर्भावः कथं भवतीति बहुभिः बहुधा विचार्यते ।

१. काव्यस्य कारणम्

इह जगति यावन्तः पदार्थाः सन्ति ते तावत् नित्याः कार्याश्चेति द्वेषा विभक्ता अवलोक्यन्ते । नित्यास्ते पदार्था भवन्ति ये सर्वथा न जायन्ते, यथा गगनादयः । कार्याः पुनस्ते भवन्ति ये जनिमन्तः । अस्ति किञ्चित् कारणं तेषां जनौ । प्रकृतं यदिदं काव्यं तत् कार्यम् । तस्मात् तस्य जनौ किञ्चित् कारणमवश्यं वर्तेत । तच्च कारणं किमिति पर्यनुयोगे नैकमिदमुत्तरं श्रूयते काव्यमीमांसकेषु । तत्र दण्डिमम्मटप्रभृतयः प्राचीनाः प्रतिभा व्युत्पत्तिः अभ्यासश्चेति त्रयाणामेतेषां समुदायस्य कारणत्वं उर्रीकुर्वन्ति, तदुक्तं मम्मटेन – शक्तिर्निपुणता लोकशास्त्रकाव्याद्यवेक्षणात् । काव्यज्ञशिक्षयाभ्यास इति हेतुस्तदुद्धवे ॥

२. काव्यस्यात्मा कः ?

काव्यं हि नानाविशेषात्मकम् । अत्र सन्त्यालङ्काराः, गुणाः, रीतयः, रसः, वक्रोक्तिः, औचित्यमेव च । तत्र सारभूतं वस्तु किम्? यच्च आत्मशब्देन व्यवहियते? – अत्र तावत् नानामुखः समयः दृश्यते विपश्चिताम् । तथा हि – भामहादयः प्राचीना आलङ्कारिका अलङ्कारं काव्यस्यत्मानमामनन्ति । वामनो रीतिम्, कुन्तको वक्रोक्तिम्, आनन्दवर्धनो ध्वनिम्, क्षेमेन्द्रः औचित्यम्, भरताभिनवगुप्तमम्मटादयस्तु रसम् । तन्मतानुसारेण तत्तस्यैव प्रामुख्यम् । अत एव काव्यवाक्यानां वेदपुराणगतेभ्यो लोकगतेभ्यश्च वाक्येभ्यो वैलक्षण्यमिति तेषां भावः ।

३. काव्यप्रयोजनम्

'प्रयोजनमनुद्धिश्य न मन्दोऽपि प्रवर्तते' इति वाक्यं सर्वेषामपि प्रसिद्धम् । ततश्च यदि कुत्रचित् प्रवृत्तिरिष्यते तर्हि तस्य किञ्चित् प्रयोजनं वर्तेत । कवयस्तु काव्यस्य रचनायां प्रवर्तन्ते सहृदयाः पुनः तस्य श्रवणे दर्शने च । तस्मात् तस्य किञ्चित् प्रयोजनम् अवश्यं वर्तते इति निश्चयः ।

४. काव्यलक्षणम्

इह तावत् वाङ्मये आज्ञाप्रधानम्, अनुनयप्रधानं, प्रार्थनाप्रधानञ्चेति त्रिविधम् । आज्ञाप्रधानं भवति शास्त्रम्, यत् प्रभुसम्मिन्तम् इत्युच्यते । अनुनयप्रधानं भवति पुराणम्, यत् मित्रसम्मिन्तम् इत्युच्यते । प्रार्थनाप्रधानं तु काव्यम्, यत् कान्तासम्मिन्तम् इत्युच्यते । शास्त्रे शब्दस्य प्राधान्यम्, परिवृत्तेरसहत्वात् । पुराणे अर्थस्य प्राधान्यम्, सयुक्तिकं निरूपणात् । काव्ये तु व्यापारस्य, चमत्कारजनकत्वात् इति स्थितिः । काव्ये तावत् दृश्यकाव्यं, श्रव्यकाव्यं, पद्यं, गद्यं, खण्डं, महाकाव्यं, चम्पू इत्यादि प्रभेदाः दरीदृश्यन्ते ।

Paper No. 14.33: Sanskrit Literature

"Exploring the Myths and Legends of Two Ancient Cultures: A Comparative Study of Sanskrit and Greek Mythology"

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ABSTRACT

Comparative literature is the study of literature from different languages and cultural contexts. It involves comparing works of literature from different languages and cultures in order to understand the similarities and differences between them and to explore the ways in which they are influenced by their respective cultural, historical, and social contexts.

Myth and folklore play a significant role in the literature of both Sanskrit and Greek. In Sanskrit literature, myths and folklore are often found in the form of Hindu epics such as the Ramayana and the Mahabharata, as well as in the Puranas, a collection of Hindu myths and legends. These works often feature gods, goddesses, demons, and other supernatural beings, and they explore themes of love, loss, conflict, and redemption.

In Greek literature, myths and folklore are also an important part of the literary tradition. Greek myths are often found in the form of epic poetry, such as the Iliad and the Odyssey, as well as in plays and other works of literature. Greek myths often feature gods, goddesses, and other supernatural beings, and they explore themes of love, jealousy, betrayal, and redemption. Greek myths and folklore are also closely tied to the cultural values and beliefs of ancient Greece, and they often serve as a means of explaining natural phenomena or as a way to convey moral lessons.

Keywords: Myth, Legend, Sanskrit, Greek, Themes.

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'ವಾಮನನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸಿದ ವೈದರ್ಭೀ ರೀತಿಯ ದಶಗುಣಗಳನ್ನು ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕ 'ಆಬ್ರಾಂವ್ಚೆಂ ಯಜ್ಞದಾನ್' ನೊಂದಿಗೆ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ'

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ABSTRACT

ಲುವಿಸ್ ಮಸ್ಕರೆನ್ನಿಸ್‌ರವರು ಬರೆದ 'ಆಬ್ರಾಂವ್ಚೆಂ ಯಜ್ಞದಾನ್' ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಭಾಶೆಯ ಆಧುನಿಕ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಬೈಬಲಿನ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಸಂಗವನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಂಡು ವಿಶೇಷ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ಣನೆ ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ನಾನು ವಾಮನನು ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಮೂಲದ ಕಾವ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈದರ್ಭೀ ರೀತಿಯ ದಶಗುಣಗಳನ್ನು ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕ ಆಬ್ರಾಂವ್ಚೆಂ ಯಜ್ಞದಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದೇನೆ. ವೈದರ್ಭೀ ರೀತಿಯ ದಶಗುಣಗಳು ಎಷ್ಟರ ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಳವಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಇದರ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಿಂದ ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಭಾಶೆಯ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಭಾಶೆಯ ನಿಯಮಾವಳಿಗೆ ಎಷ್ಟು ಹತ್ತಿರವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರಿಂದ ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಭಾಶೆಯ ಕವಿತೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಕೊರತೆ ಇದೆ? ಯಾವ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ನಡೆಸಬೇಕೆಂದು ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯ ಪಾಶ್ಚಾತ್ಯ ಶೈಲಿಗೆ ಒಲಿದು ಹೋಗಿದೆ. ಪುರಾತನ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ನಿಯಮಾವಳಿಗಳ ಅರಿವು ಇಲ್ಲದ ಕಾರಣ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಕವಿತೆ ತನ್ನದೇ ಶೈಲಿಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರತಿಪಾದಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಆಬ್ರಾಂವ್ಚೆಂ ಯಜ್ಞದಾನ್ 1920 ಇಸವಿಯ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕವಾಗಿದ್ದು ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಿಂದ ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಕವಿತೆಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿ ತಿಳಿದು ಬರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಆಬ್ರಾಂವ್ಚೆಂ ಯಜ್ಞದಾನ್ ಪ್ರಸಂಗದಲ್ಲಿ ದೇವರು ಆಬ್ರಾಹಾಮಿನ ಒಬ್ಬನೇ ಮಗನಾದ ಇಸಾಕನನ್ನು ಬಲಿ ಕೊಡಲು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ದೇವರ ಆಜ್ಞೆಯಂತೆ ಆಬ್ರಾಹಾಮನು ತನ್ನ ಮಗನ ಜೊತೆ ಮೊರಯಾ ಪರ್ವತಕ್ಕೆ ಹೋಗುತ್ತಾನೆ. ಈ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕದಲ್ಲಿ ಬೈಬಲಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳಲಾದ ಪ್ರಸಂಗ ಮತ್ತು ಲುವಿಸ್ ಮಸ್ಕರೆನ್ನಿಸ್‌ರ ಕವಿತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳಲಾದ ಪ್ರಸಂಗ ಒಂದೇ ಆದರೂ ಅದನ್ನು ವರ್ಣನೆ ಮಾಡಿದ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಭಿನ್ನತೆ ಇದೆ.

Key Words: ಕೊಂಕಣಿ ಕಾವ್ಯನಾಟಕ ಆಬ್ರಾಂವ್ಚೆಂ ಯಜ್ಞದಾನ್

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ದಾಸಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ತೀರ್ಥಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳ ವರ್ಣನೆ

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ನಿರ್ದೇಶಕರು. ಶ್ರೀ ವಾದಿರಾಜ ಸಂಶೋಧನ ಪ್ರತಿಷ್ಠಾನ.(೮) ಉಡುಪಿ.

ABSTRACT

ಭಾರತದ ಮಣ್ಣಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವೈ ಮನಗಳ ಕೊಳೆಯನ್ನು ತೊಳೆಯುವ ಅದ್ಭುತವಾದ ಶಕ್ತಿ ಇದೆ. ರಾಮ-ಕೃಷ್ಣಾದಿ ಭಗವದ್ರೂಪಗಳ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಿಂದ ಈ ದೇಶದ ಪಾವಿತ್ರತೆ ಇಮ್ಮಡಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಮನುಷ್ಯನಾಗಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದ ಮೇಲೆ ಒಮ್ಮೆಯಾದರೂ ಭರತಖಂಡವನ್ನು ಸಂಚರಿಸಬೇಕು. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಹರಿಯುವ ನದಿಗಳು, ಕಣ್ಣಿಗೆ ಅನಂದವನ್ನುಂಟುಮಾಡುವ ಗಿರಿಕಂದರಗಳು, ದೇವನ ನಿತ್ಯಸನ್ನಿಧಾನದ ಪುಷ್ಕರ-ಗಯಾ-ಕಾಶಿ-ಬದರಿ-ಶ್ರೀರಂಗ -ಉಡುಪಿ ಮೊದಲಾದ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳು ನಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಉದ್ಧರಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. “ಅಯೋಧ್ಯಾ-ಮಥುರಾ-ಮಾಯಾ-ಕಾಶೀ-ರಾಂಚೀ-ಅವಂತಿರಾ-ಪುರೀ-ದ್ವಾರಾವತಿ” ಎಂಬ ಭಾರತದ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪವಿತ್ರ ತೀರ್ಥ-ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಮುಂಜಾನೆ ಎದ್ದು ಸ್ಮರಿಸಿದರೆ ಅನಂತಪುಣ್ಯ ಲಭಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇವುಗಳ ಮುಕ್ತಿದಾಯಕ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳು. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ ನಮ್ಮ ಕರಾವಳಿಯ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿಯೂ “ರೌಪ್ಯಹಿಮ-ಕುಮಾರಾದ್ರಿಃ-ಕುಂಭಾಶೀ-ಧ್ವಜೇಶ್ವರಃ-ಕ್ರೋಡ-ಗೋಕರ್ಣ-ಮೂಕಾಂಬಾಃ” ಏಳು ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳು ಮುಕ್ತಿದಾಯಕ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಾಗಿವೆ.

ಯಾತ್ರೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ

ನಮ್ಮ ಪೂರ್ವಿಕರು ತೀರ್ಥಯಾತ್ರೆಗೆ ಬಹಳ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ತೀರ್ಥ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳು ಭಕ್ತರಿಗೆ ಸ್ಫೂರ್ತಿ ನೀಡುವ ತಾಣವಾಗಿವೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿಯ ಪಾವಿತ್ರತೆಯನ್ನು ವರ್ಣಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ. ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾತ್ವಿಕರು ಗಿಡ-ಮರ-ಬಳ್ಳಿಗಳ ರೂಪದಿಂದ ನೆಲೆಸಿ ಸಾಧನೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ದೇವತೆಗಳೂ ತರುಲತೆಗಳ ರೂಪವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿ ಭಗವಂತನನ್ನು ಸೇವಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.

ಇಂತಹ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೋದಾಗ ನಮ್ಮ ಮನಸ್ಸು ಸಾತ್ವಿಕವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ದೇವನ ನಿತ್ಯಸನ್ನಿಧಾನವಿರುವ ಸ್ಥಳದಲ್ಲಿ “ನೀನಿದ್ದ ಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸರ್ವತೀರ್ಥಗಳು, ನೀನಿದ್ದ ಸ್ಥಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಸ್ತ ಸಾತ್ವಿಕರು,” ಎಂದು ವಿಜಯದಾಸರು ಸನ್ನಿಧಾನದ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೋದಾಗ ಅನೇಕ ಭಕ್ತರ ದರ್ಶನಭಾಗ್ಯ ನಮಗಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವರ ಉಪದೇಶಾಮೃತದಿಂದ ತತ್ವಚಿಂತನೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

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श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्याणां जीवनचरित्रम्

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ABSTRACT

श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्यः विश्वरक्षकाणां मुख्यप्राणानां तृतीयः अवतारः । कलिकालवशात् दुर्भाष्यवशाच्च सुज्ञाने नष्टे सति भगवदाज्ञानुसारेण वायुदेवः आश्वयुजमासस्य शुद्धविजयदशम्यां मध्वरूपेण अवततार । तस्य पिता मध्यगेहभ-ः, माता च वेदवती । जन्मस्थलञ्च उडुपिमण्डलस्थं पाजकम् । अस्य कालः क्रिस्तोत्तरं १२३८-१३१७ । मध्यगेहभ-ः वासुदेवनामकं मध्वाचार्यं प्रति अक्षराभ्यासं कारयामास । तदा सः वासुदेवः 'लिपिकुलं ननु तात गते दिने लिखितमेव पुनर्लिखितं कुतः ?' इत्यवोचत् । पिता तु तच्छ्रुत्वा विस्मयमाप । बालावस्थायामेव तादृशी मेधाशक्तिः तस्यासीत् । पित्रा पुराणप्रवचनावसरे त्यक्तस्य लिखितपदस्यार्थम् अकथयत् । तदनन्तरं पिता वासुदेवम् उचिते काले उपनयनम् अकारयत् । उपनयनात् पश्चात् सः गुरुणा पूगवनवंशस्थेन अपाठितस्यापि वेदभागस्य स्पष्टोच्चारणं कृतवान् । एतेन न केवलं पितरि, देवतास्वपि आश्चर्यं जनयामास । सज्जनकारुण्यात् वेदानां शुद्धार्थप्रतिपादनार्थं सः विरक्तशिखामणिना अच्युतप्रेक्षेण संन्यासं स्वीकृतवान् । ते तस्य पूर्णप्रज्ञ इति नाम दत्तवन्तः । आश्रमानन्तरं चत्वारिंशति दिनेषु वैशेषिकस्य वासुदेवपण्डितस्य वाचं स्तम्भितवान् । तदनु गुरुणा इष्टसिद्धिग्रन्थपाठनावसरे तस्य मङ्गलश्लोके एव द्वात्रिंशतं दोषान् उद्धृतयामास । पश्चात् विद्वत्तापूर्णं शास्त्रपाठं च अकार्षीत् । एवं पूर्णप्रज्ञस्य सामर्थ्यं ज्ञातवन्तः अच्युतप्रेक्षाः तं वेदान्तसाम्राज्ये अभिषिच्य आनन्दतीर्थ इति नाम्ना अलङ्कृतवन्तः । तार्किककण्टकान् तर्ककण्टकेनैव निष्कास्य अनुमानतीर्थ इति सः प्रथितो बभूव । बुद्धिसागर-वादिसिंहपराजयः, ब्रह्मसूत्रभाष्यस्य उपदेशः, दक्षिणदिग्विजयः, ऐतरेयसूक्तार्थचिन्तनम्, बदरिकाश्रमगमनम्, तत्र सर्वोत्तमं नारायणं नत्वा स्वकृतगीताभाष्यसमर्पणम् इत्यादिभिः विविधैः कर्मभिः भगवन्तं तोषयामास । ततः परं भगवदाज्ञया तत्रैव ब्रह्मसूत्रभाष्यं रचयामास । ततः रजतपीठपुरे नन्दनन्दनम् अतीन्द्रियाकृतिं श्रीकृष्णं प्रतिष्ठाविधिविधानेन प्रतिमायां सन्निहितमकरोत् । श्रीवेदव्यासः तं महाभारतस्य तात्पर्यरचनायां योजयामास । मध्वाचार्यः सकलविद्वत्सभासु स्वस्य प्रखरैः उद्धोधकैश्च प्रवचनैः परवादिभिरपि अभिनन्दितः ।

एवं श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्यः अस्यां भूमौ एकोनाशीतिवर्षाणि सार्थकजीवनमतीत्य पश्चात् दृगगोचरतां बभूव । एतेन प्रतिपादितः सिद्धान्तः तत्त्ववाद इति नाम्ना प्रथितो बभूव ।

Keywords : 1: madhwa 2: aanandateertha 3: anumaanateertha 4: vasudeva

5: dwaita 6: tathwavaada

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काव्यशास्त्रसम्बन्धः

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ABSTRACT

‘द्वे वर्त्मनी गिरां देव्याः शास्त्रं च कविकर्म च ।

प्रज्ञोपज्ञं तयोराद्यं प्रतिभोद्धवमन्तिमम् ॥

भट्टतौतस्य वचनमिदम् । उपदेशेन शास्त्रज्ञानं प्राप्तुं शक्यम् । किन्तु काव्यनिर्माणे सरस्वत्याः वरप्रसादरूपा प्रतिभा अपेक्षिता भवति । कवेः कर्म काव्यम् । काव्यमिदं कान्तासम्मिततया उपदेशपरम् । अतः काव्यादीनां शास्त्रसम्बन्धः विद्यते । श्रीमद्रामायणं तावत् विश्वस्य आदिकाव्यत्वेन अङ्गीकृतं वर्तते । ‘परं कवीनामाधारम्’ इति आदिकवेः वाल्मीकेः उद्गारः । अत एव तमधिकृत्य संस्कृतसाहित्यक्षेत्रे बहूनि काव्यानि विरचितानि । संस्कृतभाषायां पञ्चमहाकाव्यानि प्रसिद्धानि सन्ति ।

पञ्चमहाकाव्येषु कालिदासस्य काव्यद्वयं स्वीकृतम् रघुवंशः कुमारसम्भवश्चेति । महाकविः कालिदासः कविकुगुरुः इति प्राप्तयशः । संस्कृतसाहित्ये अयमेव मूर्धन्यप्रायः इत्यत्र नास्ति विप्रतिपत्तिः । ‘पुरा कवीनां गणनाप्रसङ्गे कनिष्ठिकाधिष्ठितः कालिदासः । अद्यापि तत्तुल्यकवेरभावात् अनामिका सार्थवती बभूव ॥ इति अस्मै प्राचीनैः प्रदत्ताप्रशस्तिः । किन्तु कुतः इयं प्रशस्तिः इति जिज्ञासमानायां अस्य काव्यरचनाकौशलमस्माकं दृक्पथमायाति । न केवलम् उपमादिविषये अपि तु सर्वशास्त्रेषु अस्य पाण्डित्यमवगम्यते । तथा च एतस्य महाकवेः रघुवंशमहाकाव्यस्य कतिपयश्लोकान् आश्रित्य काव्यशास्त्रसम्बन्धः अत्र निरूप्यते ।

‘समाप्तिकामो मङ्गलमाचरेत्’ इति अविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयत्वात् काव्यादौ मङ्गलं निबध्नाति । तथा च तत्र प्रथमशब्दे एव महाकवेः शास्त्रवैदुष्यं नरीनृत्यते । ‘वागर्थाविव सम्पृक्तौ इति आरब्धम् इदं महाकाव्यम् । अस्मात् शब्दात् अयमर्थो बोद्धव्यः इति नैयायिकानां मतम् अस्ति । ‘नित्यः शब्दार्थसम्बन्धः । शब्दार्थयोः वाच्यवाचकभावसम्बन्धः नित्यः इति कर्ममीमांसकानां मतम् । शब्दार्थो इत्यत्रापि नित्यसमासः ।

Keywords: श्रीसुधीन्द्र तीर्थः, काव्यस्तोत्र, गौडसरस्वतब्राह्मणाः, श्रीकाशीमठसंस्थानम्, बादरायण, अलङ्काराः, काव्यगुणः।

Paper No. 14.38: Sanskrit Literature

Importance of Goddess in Indian Literature

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ABSTRACT

Mother Goddess is worshiped in India since Indus valley civilization dating back to 1000 BC. Importance of goddess in India can be estimated from the saying “Shiva without Shakti is Shava”. Without Shakti, Shiva is dead body. Without ‘i’ in Shiva becomes Shva means dead body in Sanskrit so without Shakti shiva is powerless. Goddess in India is worshipped because of motherly care, fertility, procreation, nourishment, love, compassion, knowledge, wealth, savior in the times of difficulties. In Hinduism the tridevi are personified as Devi Saraswati, Devi Lakshmi and Devi Parvati. The tridevi goddess in Hinduism have given the role of creator (Maha Saraswati), preserver (Maha Lakshmi) and destroyer (Maha Kali). In this paper Maha Saraswati, Maha Lakshmi and Maha Kali are discussed with their avatars in details. In India there are other goddess like Gayatri goddess, Aditi goddess, Prithvi goddess, River goddess which are discussed in detailed. Some lesser known goddess in Indian Hindu mythology like Vac, Usha, Ratri, Mariamman, Aranyani, Manasa, Kotravai are discussed in brief in this paper. Paper discusses importance of different goddess worshipped in different parts of India, Avatars of Tri Devi i.e. Maha Saraswati, Maha Lakshmi and Maha Kali along with their mantras.

Keywords – Mother, Goddess, Indian Literature, tri devi, Maha Saraswati, Maha Lakshmi, Maha Kali

Paper No. 14.39: Sanskrit Literature

भोजप्रबन्धस्य अध्ययनप्रयोजनम्

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ABSTRACT

धारानगरस्य राज्ञः सिन्धुलस्य पुत्रः भोजः कथं महाराजः आसीत्, तस्य शासनं कीदृशम् आसीत्? इत्यादि विशेषैः युक्ता इयं कथायाः मुख्यभूमिका । भोजः महान् संस्कृतज्ञः काव्यरसिकः स्वयं काव्यज्ञः च आसीत् । तस्य संस्कृतकविषु महान् आदरः आसीत् । तस्य आस्थाने बहवः कवयः विद्वांसः प्राज्ञाः च आसन् इति तस्य काव्यस्य अध्ययनेन ज्ञायते । भोजराजस्य कवौ कालिदासे महती प्रीतिः विशेषादरश्च । सः कविं कालिदासमेव "कवीनां चक्रवर्तीति" मन्यते स्म । तस्मात् बहवः अन्ये कवयः कालिदासाय असूयन्ति स्म । तदा भोजः भिन्नभिन्नसमस्याः दत्त्वा, परीक्षाभिः च तेषां समाधानं कारयति स्म । एवं अस्मिन् भोजप्रबन्धे बह्व्यः मनोहारिण्यः कथाः निर्दिष्टाः सन्ति । तासाम् अध्ययनम् अस्माकं सामाजिकानां कृते बहु लाभाय भवति इति मदीयः अभिप्रायः अस्ति ।

भोजस्य काव्यरसिकता बहु प्रख्यता तत्काले । उत्तमकवीन् भोजः आस्थाने स्वगतीकरोति, तेभ्यः पुष्कलं धनं ददाति इति प्रसिद्धिः सर्वत्र प्रसृता आसीत् । तस्य काले सामान्यजनाः अपि स्वपाण्डित्येन कवितां विरचय्य महाराजात् पुरस्कारं प्राप्नुवन्ति स्म । भल्लालदेवेन लिखितः भोजप्रबन्धः अतिप्रसिद्धः । तस्मिन् काव्ये भोजस्य गुणाः के तस्य काव्यशैली कीदृशी इत्यादीनाम् अध्ययनं कृत्वा तस्य काव्यस्य विमर्शं लेखितुम् अहं उत्सुका अस्मि ।

Keywords: भोजस्य काव्यशैली, काव्यरसिकता, भोजप्रबन्धः, स्वारस्यपूर्णाः कथाः च

Paper No. 14.40: Sanskrit Literature

संस्कृतसाहित्यकाराः/ संस्कृतग्रन्थकाराः

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आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्याकाशेऽग्रेसरः, व्याकरणालङ्कारपण्डितः, राष्ट्रपतिप्रशस्तिपुर
स्कृतः, सुधर्मासंस्कृतपत्रिकायाः गौरवसम्पादकः विद्वान् डा॥ एच्. वि. नागराजराव्
महोदयस्य संस्कृतज्ञानं, प्रतिभा, वाक्पटुता च सर्वेषां सुपरिचितैव । अनेन महाभागेन
वैशिष्ट्यपूर्णाः शतकग्रन्थाः विरचिताः । तेषां ग्रन्थानां प्रकटनं मैसूरुनगरस्थिते
विश्वमान्यसुधर्माप्रकाशनद्वारा कारितमस्ति । तेषु कवेः 'निन्दास्तुतिशतकम्', 'दृष्टान्तशतकम्'
, 'नागराजशतकम्', 'सज्जनशतकम्', 'दुर्जनशतकम्', 'श्रीरामचन्द्रशतकम्',
'कलिविमर्शनशतकम्' इत्यादयः ग्रन्थाः सुपरिचितास्सन्ति । एतेषु ग्रन्थेषु अनन्यविचाराः,
अपूर्वसङ्गतयः, सन्मार्गः, सत्यसङ्गः, आदर्शजीवनमौल्यानि, धार्मिकनितिः, निःस्वार्थता,
विश्वभ्रातृत्वम्, सहनाशीलता,

नागराजकवेः ग्रन्थेषु न केवलं पाण्डित्यपूर्णं भाषाज्ञानं, साहित्यानुभूतिरेव विज्ञायते;
अपि तु लौकिकालौकिकविषयानाञ्च परिचयः सम्यक् अवगम्यते । यथोदाहरणार्थम्, काक-
पिकयोः विषये बहवः सुभाषितश्लोकाः संस्कृतकाव्येषु उपलभ्यन्ते । तथैव कविना काक-
पिकयोः जीवनशैलीमधिकृत्य; तयोर्मध्ये शिशूणां पालन-पोषणभेदानुद्दिश्य एवं वर्णितम् ।

*मुख्यशब्दाः- शतकसाहित्यम्, कलिविमर्शनशतकम्, कलिविडम्बनशतकम्, नीतिविषयकाः,
जीवनमौल्यानि, लोकज्ञानम्

Paper No. 14.41: Sanskrit Literature

भिन्नकाव्येषु सुन्दरकाण्डस्य सामान्य परिचयः

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ORCID ID : 0000-0003-4238-5001[E Mail: shantalavishwas@gmail.com](mailto:shantalavishwas@gmail.com) Contact No. 9480503411**ABSTRACT**

रामस्य अयनं (चरितं) रामायणम् । रामायणमादिकाव्यं सर्वेषां काव्यानां जीवातुभूतं च भवति । रामायणं महाभारतवत् कश्चिदितिहासग्रन्थो भवति । संस्कृतसाहित्ये रामायणवत् प्रसिद्धः लोकप्रियश्च अन्यः ग्रन्थः नास्तीति वक्तुं शक्यते । नीतिदृष्ट्या काव्यात्मकदृष्ट्या लोकोपकारकदृष्ट्या च रामायणस्य महत्त्वं वर्धते । पितृपुत्रधर्मस्य पतिपत्नीधर्मस्य भ्रातृधर्मस्य तथा अन्यकौटुम्बिकधर्मस्य च आदर्शभूतो अयं ग्रन्थः। आदिकाव्यस्य रामायणस्य कर्ता श्रीमद्वाल्मीकिः । रामायणे न केवलं युद्धमात्रं प्रत्युत सकलालङ्काराणां प्रकृतिसौन्दर्यस्य धर्मस्य च यत्र तत्र वर्णनं दृश्यते ।

रामायणमादिकाव्यम् इति प्रसिद्धम्। इतिहासग्रन्थः इत्यपि भाव्यते एतत्। एतस्य ग्रन्थस्य रचयिता वाल्मीकिः। तमसानदीं स्नानार्थं गच्छन् वाल्मीकिः व्याधेन मारितं क्रौञ्चं पश्यति। तदा शोकाकुलः सः – 'मा निषाद प्रतिष्ठां त्वमगमः शाश्वतीः समाः' इति व्याधं शपति। ततः नारदमुखात् रामस्य कथां श्रुत्वा सः रामायणं रचयति। सीतारामयोः वियोगः रामायणस्य मुख्यं कथावस्तु। पाणिनेः अष्टाध्याय्याम् अपि कैकेयीकौसल्यादयः शब्दाः दृश्यन्ते। रामायणं कदा आसीत् इति विषये मतभेदाः बहवः सन्ति। रामायणे २४००० श्लोकाः सप्तकाण्डेषु विभजिताः सन्ति। ते बालकाण्डः, अयोध्याकाण्डः, अरण्यकाण्डः, किष्किन्दाकाण्डः, सुन्दरकाण्डः, युद्धकाण्डः, उत्तरकाण्डः इति ।

रामायणस्य प्रतिसहस्रतमस्य श्लोकस्य आदौ गायत्रीमन्त्रस्य एकैकम् अक्षरं प्राप्यते। पाठभेदादयः न भवेयुः इति उद्देशेन एवं कृतं स्यात् कविना। रामायणं सर्वासु भारतीयभाषासु बह्विधेषु विदेशीयभाषासु च उपलभ्यते। एतस्मात् रामायणस्य जनप्रियता ज्ञाता भवति। वाल्मीकेः शैली ललिता सरला सुन्दरी च।

श्रीरामस्य धर्मनिष्ठा, सीतायाः सौशील्यं, भरतस्य भ्रातृवात्सल्यं, लक्ष्मणस्य कर्तव्यनिष्ठा, आज्ञनेयस्य कार्यदक्षता, सुग्रीवस्य सौहार्दभावः इत्यादयः अंशाः अतिरमणीयतया चित्रिताः तेन। संस्कृतसाहित्यनिर्माणे वाल्मीकिः शकपुरुषः इत्यत्र न अतिशयोक्तिः। रामायणं अधिकृत्यैव अनेके ग्रन्थाः रचिताः सन्ति। विशेषतः रघुवंशम्, रामचरितम्, जात्रकीहरणम्, रघुवीरचरितम् इत्यादि ग्रन्थाः रचिताः। तत्रापि सुन्दरकाण्डः सामान्याति सामान्यान् मोहयति। तत्र सुन्दरकाण्डस्य भिन्नत्वं, वैशिष्ट्यं किम्, कीदृशाविषयाः अत्र वर्णिताः इति विविच्यते।

Keywords : श्रीरामस्य धर्मनिष्ठा, सीतारामयोः वियोगः, अष्टाध्याय्याम् अपि कैकेयीकौसल्यादयः

Paper No. 14.42: Sanskrit Literature

DHVANISIDDANTAH IN SANSKRIT AND OTHER LANGUAGES : AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The subject thesis has been written to bring out the clarifications on Dhvanissiddantam. “ Dhvani" means sound. But here Dvani is not merely the sound but the sounds of words received and heard by the user while reading or listening to the writings. Acharya Anandavardhana (9th C E) is said to have discovered the usage of “Dhvani” principles for reading and understanding the writings of distinguished Writers. One may ask, whether before 9th C E the dhvani principles had not been used by the Poets of earlier periods? The answer is a Big No!! Such usages have been widely used by various distinguished Poets of not only Sanskrit, but by Great Poets of other Languages (like Tamil &Telugu). While I have personally read Poets’ writings in Sanskrit and Tamil and to a certain level in Telugu languages, I am not very familiar with Kannada and other language literatures. It is my misfortune perhaps. Let us take a small example from which, one may understand the Dhvani even in one’s household. “ A Father sees his sons/daughters busy watching a cinema in the drawing room. The father sees this and says , ” Very good. You are going to get high marks in the exams because all the questions are going to be about this film”. And what is the response from the sons/daughters? The sons/daughters quietly close the cinema and start preparing for the ensuing examinations!! Thus Dhvani Siddhantam is quite welcome by one and all !!

Paper No. 14.43: Sanskrit Literature

मध्ये मध्ये पानीयं समर्पयामि

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सकलगुणपरिपूर्ण ईश्वरो जगत्कर्तास्ति । तत्र प्राणिनां सृष्टिर्नाम, आत्मनो देहप्राप्तिरेव । मानवो देहद्वारेणैव धर्म-अर्थ-काम-मोक्षरूपान् पुरुषार्थान् प्राप्नोति । एतेषां प्राप्तिरेव मानवस्यान्तिमं लक्ष्यम् । कर्मणैव मानवस्य पुरुषार्थप्राप्तिर्भवति । न खलु कायाभावस्य जीवस्य कर्म कर्तुं शक्यते । अतोऽस्ति कायस्यापि प्राधान्यम् । उक्तञ्च "शरीरमाद्यं खलु धर्मसाधनम्" इति कालिदासेन । शुद्धाहारवाय्वम्बवादीनां सेवनेन शरीरे वृद्धिः, बलम्, स्वास्थ्यादिकं च सम्भवति । आहाराद्यभावे वृद्ध्याद्यभावः । भावमिश्रपण्डितोऽवदत् -

अन्नेनापि विना जन्तुः प्राणान् धारयते चिरम् ।
तोयाभावात्पिपासार्थः क्षणात्प्राणैर्विमुच्यते ॥ इति ।

अन्नाभावेऽपि मानवः चिरं जीवति । किन्तु जलाभावे तृषितः मोहं प्राप्य, प्राणान्विमुञ्चति । अतः जलस्य "जीवनम्" इत्यन्वर्थपदम् । किन्तु अस्मिन् कालखण्डे उदकपानविषये मनुष्या भ्रमाक्रान्ता इव दृश्यन्ते । यतः अत्यम्बुपानम्, भोजनान्तिमे जलपानम्, भोजनात्पूर्वकाले जलपानम्, बुभुक्षितकाले जलपानादिकं च बहुत्र बहुजनैः क्रियमाणं दृश्यते । एतैर्निदानैरेव वर्तमानकालेऽनेके रोगास्समुद्भवन्तस्सन्ति । दृष्टान्तर्जालः पुरुष एतदसाधवाचरणमाधुनिकविज्ञानस्यैव योगदानमिति अवगच्छति ।

किन्तु आयुर्वेदकर्तारो भिषजो भिन्नाभिप्रायिन एव दृश्यन्ते । यतः "अत्यम्बुपानं रोगनिदानम्" इति वाग्भटस्याभिप्रायः । अतः तृषितसमये तृषानिवृत्तिपर्यन्तमेव जलपानमारोग्यकरम् । नाधिकम् । तथैव कदा जलपानं करणीयमिति सुश्रुतोऽवददष्टाङ्गहृदये - भुक्तस्यादौ जलं पीतमग्निसादं कृशाङ्गताम् । अन्ते करोति स्थूलत्वमूर्ध्वमामाशये कफम् । मध्ये मध्यं गतं साम्यं धातूनां जरणं सुखम् । इति । भोजनादौ जलपानेन जठराग्निर्नश्यते । कायः कृशो भविष्यति । अजीर्णसमस्याप्युद्भवति । भोजनान्ते जलपानं शारीरस्थौल्यं वर्धयति । आमाशये कफमुत्पादयति । तथैवाजीर्णनिमित्तकं रोगादिकमुद्भवत्येव । तथैव बुभुक्षितसमये जलपानं, तृषितसमये भोजनकरणञ्च कफादिरोगमुत्पादयत्येव । अतः "मध्ये चामृतं वारि" इति वचनानुसारेण, भोजनस्य मध्ये मध्ये एवोदकपानमारोग्यकरं भविष्यतीति ज्ञायते । तथैवाग्निः जीर्णक्रियायां समर्थः भवति, तेन सप्तविधधातूनामुत्पत्तिर्भवति । धातुभिः शरीरे आरोग्यबलाद्यभिवृद्धिर्भविष्यति । तेन मनुष्यस्वस्थो भवति । अतो मध्ये मध्ये एव पानीयसेवनमारोग्यकरम् ॥

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ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನ ಋತುಸಂಹಾರ - ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯ ವರ್ಣನೆಯೇ ಮೂಲಾಧಾರ**DR. NARENDRA B S****SANSKRIT LECTURER****TUNGA MAHAVIDYALAYA ,THIRTHAHALLI SHIVMOGGA -****MOB- 9449251850****Gmail - narendrabs50@gmail.com****ABSTRACT**

ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯದ ಮಹಾಕವಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕವಿಕುಲಗುರುವೆಂದೇ ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧನಾದ ಕಾಳಿದಾಸ ಅಗ್ರಗಣ್ಯನೆಂದು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಮತ್ತು ಪಾಶ್ಚಾತ್ಯರಲ್ಲರ ಒಮ್ಮತದ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನು ತನ್ನ ಯುಗದ ಮಾದರಿ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಿ ಅದರ ಸ್ವರೂಪವನ್ನು ತನ್ನ ಕೃತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿಬಿಂಬಿಸಿರುವನು. ಇತರ ಕವಿಗಳು ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಯ ಒಂದೊಂದು ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಚಿತ್ರಿಸಿದರೆ ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಸಮರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ವರ್ಣಿಸಿರುವನು. ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮ ಭಾವನೆ ನೀತಿಗಳ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಪ್ರತ್ಯಕ್ಷಗೋಚರವಾದ ವಸ್ತುಗಳ ವಿಷಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಆಕರ್ಷಕ ಅಂಶಗಳು, ಪರೋಕ್ಷ ವಿಷಯಗಳಲ್ಲೂ ಮನೋರಂಜಕ ಜ್ಞಾನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಅವನಿಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಗೋಚರವಾಗುತ್ತಿದ್ದವೆಂದರೆ ಅತಿಶಯೋಕ್ತಿಯಾಗಲಾರದು.

ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯ ವರ್ಣನೆಯೊಂದಿಗೆ ಕಾಲಕ್ಕನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಆಗುವ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಮುಖ್ಯೋದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನಾಗಿಟ್ಟು ರಚಿಸಿದ ಕಾವ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನ ಋತುಸಂಹಾರ ಮೊದಲನೆಯದು. ಋತುಸಂಹಾರವೆಂದರೆ ಋತುಗಳ ಸೇರುವಿಕೆ ಅಥವಾ ಸಮೂಹವೆಂದರ್ಥ. ಈ ಕಾವ್ಯವು ಯಾವ ಕಥಾಭಿತ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಆಶ್ರಯಿಸದೆ ಭಾರತವರ್ಷದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಗೋಚರಿಸುವ ವಸಂತ, ಗ್ರೀಷ್ಮ ಮೊದಲಾದ ಆರು ಋತುಗಳ ವರ್ಣನೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿರುವುದು ಗಮನಾರ್ಹವಾದ ವಿಷಯ.

ಋತುಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸಿ ಕಾವ್ಯವೂ ಆರು ಸರ್ಗಗಳನ್ನೂಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಒಂದು, ಎರಡು ಮತ್ತು ಆರನೇ ಸರ್ಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದೊಂದರಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತಮ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳೂ, ಮೂರು, ನಾಲ್ಕು ಮತ್ತು ಐದನೇ ಸರ್ಗಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕ್ರಮವಾಗಿ ೨೬,೧೮,೧೬ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳೂ ಇವೆ. ಪಾಠಭೇದದಿಂದ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಸರ್ಗದಲ್ಲೂ ಒಟ್ಟು ಕಾವ್ಯದಲ್ಲೂ ಇರುವ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳ ಸಂಖ್ಯೆಯು ಭಿನ್ನವಾಗಿರುವುದು.

ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯ ಸೊಬಗನ್ನು ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನು ವರ್ಣಿಸುತ್ತ ಹೊರಟರೆ ಬಗೆಬಗೆಯ ಆರಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಆರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಬಿಟ್ಟು ಶಿಶುವಿನಂತೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಕಾವ್ಯ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭವಾಗುವುದು ಗ್ರೀಷ್ಮಋತುವಿನ ಬೇಸಿಗೆಯ ವರ್ಣನೆಯಿಂದ, ಮನುಷ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಮೃಗವಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಆಗುವ ಅದರ ಪರಿಣಾಮದ ಶಬ್ದಚಿತ್ರಗಳಿಂದ. ಬಿಸಿಲಿನ ತಾಪ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾದನೆಲದಿಂದ ಕಂಗೆಟ್ಟ ಸರ್ಪಗಳು ನವಿಲಿನ ನೆರಳನ್ನಾದರೂ ಆಶ್ರಯಿಸುವುದು. ಸಿಂಹಗಳು ಬಾಯಾರಿಕೆಯಿಂದ ಬಳಲಿ ಶಕ್ತಿಗುಂದಿ ಸಮೀಪದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಆನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೊಲ್ಲುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಕಾಡು ಹಂದಿಗಳು ಬತ್ತಿದ ಕೊಳದ ಬದಿಯನ್ನು ತಿವಿಯುತ್ತಾ ನೆಲದಲ್ಲೇ ಅಡಗಿರುವಂತೆ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತವೆ. ಬೇಗೆಯೇರುತ್ತಾ ಕಾಡುಗಿಚ್ಚಿನ ದಳ್ಳುರಿ ಹಬ್ಬುತ್ತದೆ. ಗಾಳಿಯ ಉದ್ರೇಕ ಇದರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸೇರುತ್ತದೆ. ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಜೀವಜಂತುಗಳ ತಳಮಳ ಧಾರಾಕಾರವಾಗಿ ಮಳೆಸುರಿಯುವ ವರ್ಷಋತುವಿನೊಂದಿಗೆ ಕೊನೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಕಾಳಿದಾಸನು ಮಾಡಿರುವ ವರ್ಣನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿದಾಗ ನಮಗೆ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಕಾಲದಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಭಾರತೀಯರು ಕಾಲಕ್ಕನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಆಗುವ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅರಿತು ಅದಕ್ಕನುಗುಣವಾದ ಜೀವನಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳನ್ನು, ಆಹಾರ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯಿಂದುಂಟಾಗುವ ರೋಗರಜನಗಳಿಗೆ ಗಿಡಮೂಲಿಕೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಕೊಂಡು ಅಲ್ಪಾಯುಷಿಗಳಾಗದೆ ದೀರ್ಘಾಯುಷಿಗಳಾಗಿ ಸುಖಸಂಮೃದ್ಧಿಯಿಂದ ಜೀವನ ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದರೆಂದು ತಿಳಿಯಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತದ ಶಾಖೆಯಾದ ಆಯುರ್ವೇದದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು ಇದನ್ನು ದೃಢೀಕರಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

Paper No. 14.45: Sanskrit Literature

SANSKRIT LANGUAGE AND INDIAN CULTURE

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ABSTRACT

It is an attempt to activate ourselves to re-look at our enormous wealth of Sanskrit literature and inherited Indian culture from time immemorial. It is to inculcate among Indians in every ways to imbibe as well as propagate the richness of Language Sanskrit as it connects to Indian culture . We also see attempts to alienate and beguile Indians with disputable presumptions in every walk of their live and digress the natural models of Indianess in other word SanathanDharma (Ancient) My write-up is to restore confidence in Sanskrit language and Culture. The objective of the title gives ample scope to find adequate means, support and proof to stop degeneration among misinformed people. My research method leans on books of recognised authors in this field.

To know the true meaning of Literature, and the origin of Sanskrit Language.

The source of Indian Knowledge is VEDA. It is not created or man-made during any span of time. It describes every branch of science – e.g., it vividly analyses far off planets, stars and deep seas which cannot be easily accessed . Innumerable topics such as general science and metaphysics are elaborately discussed- the predominant Indianness that provides methods to ponder over life beyond earth. Interestingly all these are in Sanskrit Language. Sanskrit and Indian Culture are inseparable.

Paper No. 14.46: Sanskrit Literature

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ABSTRACT

प्रायः सर्वेषां महाकाव्यानां प्रारम्भे कालिदासः स्तुतिषु श्लोकान् लिखितवान् अस्ति शिवेश्वरं तस्मात् शिवभक्तं विद्वांसः । केवलं इति एकं पठनम् रघुवंशमतः अमूर्ताः केचन श्लोकाः तस्य एकेश्वरी इति मूल्याङ्कनं कर्तुं शक्यते शिवं परमं यथार्थं प्रत्यय भगवतः पात्रैः सह यथा महान् धार्मिकपरम्परासु चित्रितम् । तथापि यदि अहं तत् निर्दिष्टं अभिलषामि तर्हि प्रभुः अस्ति तत्र प्रकृतिरूपेण वा पर्यावरणरूपेण तस्य सत्ताभिः च सर्वत्र जगतः यत् सः उपमानां सर्वं साहित्यिकं उत्कृष्टतां समर्पयति। इत्यस्य महत् प्रभावः वेदस्य च पुरुषसूक्तं श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणं च यत् सम्प्रदायान्तरानुगतम् वेदान्तं भिन्नभिन्नं च सनातन्याः श्रद्धाभ्यासेन च लोकप्रियम् हिन्दु। तस्य महाकाव्यानां विचारधारायां तरामः चेत् सम्यक् अवलोकयितुं शक्यते। वयम् रघुवंशमस्य दशमध्याये अतीव सुन्दराणि श्लोकानि प्राप्नुवन्तु ।

तत्र चित्रयति द्रष्टृणां देवतानां च समागमः विष्णुना सह । ते भगवन्तं प्रार्थयन्ति स्म विष्णुः तान् रक्षितुं रावणस्य खलनायकस्य आसुरीदीपानां रामायणः । प्रार्थयन्ते ते भगवन्तं अविभाज्यम् इति सम्बोधयन्ति, अप्रत्यक्षं च किं वयं प्रकृतिकेन्द्रितरूपेण परिणमयामः ? निश्चितरूपेण प्रकृतेः नियमाः न परिवर्तन्ते यावत् दुष्टः मानवीयः हस्तक्षेपः शोषणं च भवति। प्रकृतिः जीवति, परिवर्तनं स्वीकुर्वति जीवितस्य कृते, किन्तु तत् पुनः प्रकृतेः नियमाः ये तस्य विशिष्टत्वेन योग्यतां धारयन्ति स्वभावः। स्वस्वभावं परिवर्तयितुम् इच्छन्तः मानवाः इव अस्मान् कदापि न व्याप्नुवन्ति यथा तेषां सुविधानुसारम्। मानवकौशलं प्रशिक्षितं संवर्धितं च भवति, एतत् प्रशिक्षणं च... संवर्धनं उद्देश्यपूर्णं भवति यत् एकस्मिन् एव व्यक्तितः काले काले च भिद्यते व्यक्ति। यदि वयं अशुभरूपेण अस्माकं इच्छानुसारं प्रकृतौ परिवर्तनं आनयामः तर्हि तत् भविष्यति विकृतः । मानवस्वभावेऽपि वयं प्रायः प्रकृतिः च इति सुभाषितस्य प्रयोगं कुर्मः हस्ताक्षरं न परिवर्तते किन्तु वयं व्यवहारे सर्वदा अस्माकं दुष्टानुसारं अन्येषां परिवर्तनं कर्तुं प्रयत्नशीलाः स्मः प्रचन। तथापि मानवस्य इच्छा अस्ति यत् अन्येषां सर्वेषां परिवर्तनं तेषां उपमानुसारं च... अरुचिः प्रकृतेः परस्परसम्बद्धतायाः विषये तेषां अज्ञानस्य उत्पादाः सन्ति अन्तः बहिश्च तत् च स्वस्य मानसिकसामाजिकसांस्कृतिकवातावरणस्य हानिं करोति परितः च । मानवस्वभावः यस्मिन् परिवेशे निवसति तस्य निर्माणं भवति, तस्मिन् च संवर्धनेन एव केचन प्रकरणाः यत् अवलोकितेन सह तुलनायाः मानकरुतं यावत् उत्कृष्टं भवति बहिः प्रकृतौ पूर्वं उत्कृष्टता। तस्मात् एव मानवजीवनं विवक्षितं भवति यथा विकारप्रक्रिया । यत् प्रक्रियाधीनम् अस्ति तत् वस्तु भवितुम् न शक्नोति तुल्यम् यतः अद्यापि तस्यैव सिद्धिः आवश्यकी अस्ति। विभवाः गुणाः च प्रकृतेः कार्यं तुलनायाः मानकं, तदनुरूपाः मानवगुणाः च सन्ति **be compared or liked** (उपमेय) तेन तुलनामानेन सह तुल्यन्ते प्रकृतौ पूर्वं अवलोकितम् (उपमानम्)। एवं सिमिल्स् एकप्रकारेण मानकरूपेण कार्यं कुर्वन्ति तुलनायाः यत्र प्रकृतिः परिभाषा इव तिष्ठति मानवगुणाः च वर्णाः पूर्वाधारेण तुलनात्मकरूपेण परिभाषितव्याः पदार्थाः इति।

Paper No. 14.47: Sanskrit Literature

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ABSTRACT

अस्यां जगत्यां अनेके देशाः सन्ति खलु , तेषु देशेषु “ इयं भरतभूमिः ” अन्यतमा ।इयम् भरतभूमिः “ कर्मभूमिः ” इति सुप्रसिद्धा ।देवतानां सिद्धभूमिः । तपस्वीनां तपोभूमिः ।भारतीयानां भाग्यभूमिः ।अस्यां भरतभूमौ अनेके महापुरुषाः जन्म प्राप्य , स्वसाधनकार्यं भगवत्पूजारूपेण संसाध्य , सिद्धपुरुषाः अभवन् । सिद्धपुरुषाणां साधनं तु स्वस्वगुरुमार्गदर्शनेनैव भविष्यति । अतः मनुष्याणां जीवने “ गुरुः ” मुख्यः भवति ।कः गुरुः इत्युक्ते – न केवलं चैतन्यपदार्थाः चैतन्यभिन्नपदार्थाः अपि गुरवः भवितुमर्हन्ति ।अस्योदारहणं लभ्यते भागवतएकादशस्कन्धे – श्रीकृष्णः उद्धवं प्रत्युपदिशति ।सैव उद्धवगीता इति प्रसिद्धा ।तस्यां उद्धवगीतायां अवदूतगीता इति कश्चन भागः ।सतु – यद्वदधूतसंवादकथनरूपः ।यदुमहाराजः अवदधूतस्य लोकविलक्षणजीवनपद्धतिं दृष्ट्वा अपृच्छत् – कथं साध्यते एतत् ।अवदूतः वदति । हे राजन्- “ सन्ति मे गुरवो राजन् बहवो बुद्धयुपाश्रिताः ।यतो बुद्धिमुपादाय मुक्तोल्तामीह तान् श्रुणु ॥ मे चतुर्विंशतिगुरवः सन्ति । ते तु – “ पृथिवी वायुराकाश आपोलग्निश्चन्द्रमा रविः ।कपोतोल्जगरः सिन्धुः पतङ्गो मधुकृद् गजः ॥ मधुहा हरिणो मीनः पिङ्गला कुररोल्भकः ।कुमारी शरकृत् सर्पः ऊर्णनाभिः सुपेशकृत् ॥ एते मे गुरवो राजन् चतुर्विंशतिराश्रिताः । शिक्षावृत्तिभिरेतेषामन्वशिक्षमहं ततः ” ॥ एवं अवधूतः चतुर्विंशतिगुरुणा अधीतविषयं यदुं प्रति निरूपयति ।

Paper No. 15.01: Sangeetha Shastra

* ರಾಗಕಲ್ಪದ್ರುಮಾಂಕುರ : ಒಂದು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ

ರೋಹಿಣಿ ಭಟ್ಟ

ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಕರು-ವಿದ್ವಾನ್ ಡಾ.ಕೆ.ಗಣಪತಿ ಭಟ್ಟ,ಧಾರವಾಡ/ಕುಮಟಾ

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ: ಗತಶತಮಾನದ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತ-ಸಂಗೀತ ವಿದ್ವಾಂಸರು, ಮಹಾರಾಷ್ಟ್ರದ ಪರಲಿ ಗ್ರಾಮದ ಕಾಶೀನಾಥ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಅಪಾತುಲಸಿ ಎಂಬವರು ರಚಿಸಿದ ಕೃತಿಯೇ 'ರಾಗಕಲ್ಪದ್ರುಮಾಂಕುರ'. ಸಂಗೀತದ ಕ್ರಾಂತಿಕಾರ ಪಂ. ವಿಷ್ಣು ನಾರಾಯಣ ಭಾತಖಂಡೆಯವರು ಕ್ರಮಿಕ ಪುಸ್ತಕ ಮಾಲಿಕೆ ಎಂಬ ಗ್ರಂಥ ರಚಿಸಿ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂಗೀತಕ್ಕೆ ವಿಶೇಷ ಯೋಗದಾನ ಮಾಡಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇವರ ಸಮಕಾಲೀನರು ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾನಶೀಲರಾದ ಕಾಶೀನಾಥರು ಶಾರ್ದೂಲವಿಕ್ರೀಡಿತ, ಸ್ವಗ್ಧರಾ, ಪೃಥ್ವೀ, ಮಂದಾಕ್ರಾಂತಾ, ವಸಂತತಿಲಕಾ ಮುಂತಾದಂಥದ್ರುಮಾಂಕುರ(ವೃತ್ತ)ಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ೧೨೪ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳಿಂದ ೨೮೨೮ ಶಬ್ದಗಳಿಂದ ರಚಿಸಿದ ಪದ್ಯಮಯ ಈ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಗ್ರಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಭೈರವದಿಂದ ಭೈರವಿವರೆಗಿನ ಎಲ್ಲ ಹತ್ತು ಥಾಟಗಳ ೧೨೦ ರಾಗಗಳ ಪರಿಚಯ ಅಡಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ರಾಗವೆಂಬ ಮಹಾಕಲ್ಪವೃಕ್ಷಕ್ಕೆ ಅಂಕುರ(ಮೊಳಕೆ)ರೂಪವಾದದ್ದೇ ಈ ಲಘು ಪುಸ್ತಕ. ವಿಕ್ರಮ ಸಂ. ೧೮೩೩ ರಚೈತ್ರಮಾಸದಲ್ಲಿ(ಯುಗಾದಿ)ರಚಿಸಲ್ಪಟ್ಟಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಅವರೇ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಹಸ್ತಪ್ರತಿಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಮೂಲಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ಅದೇ ವರ್ಷದಿಂದ ಇಷ್ಟು ೧೯೧೧ ರಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾತಖಂಡೆಯವರು ಮುಂಬಯಿಯ ನಿರ್ಣಯಸಾಗರ ಮುದ್ರಣಾಲಯದಿಂದ ಪ್ರಕಾಶನಗೊಳಿಸಿದರು.

ಉದ್ದೇಶ: ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಸಂಗೀತವೆಂಬ ಪ್ರಾಸಾದವನ್ನೇರಲು ರಾಗಲಕ್ಷಣ ಪದ್ಯವೇ ಪ್ರಥಮ ಸೋಪಾನ. ರಾಗಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದ ಥಾಟ-ಜಾತಿ-ವರ್ಜ್ಯಸ್ವರ-ನ್ಯಾಸಸ್ವರ-ವಾದಿ-ಸಂವಾದಿ-ರಸ-ಸಮಯದ ಪರಿಚಯ ಅದರಲ್ಲಿರುತ್ತದೆ. ರಾಗಗಳ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ಇಲ್ಲದೇ ರಾಗಪ್ರಸ್ತುತೀಕರಣದ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ. ಲಕ್ಷಣಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಕೆಲವು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಳು ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾಣಿಸಿಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳಿಗೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನ ಇಲ್ಲದ ಕಾರಣ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗೀತೆಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ತುಲನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಇದರ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ.

ಲೇಖನದ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿ: ನೂರಾರು ರಾಗಗಳಿದ್ದರೂ ೨೫೦೦ ಶಬ್ದಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾದ ಈಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ 'ರಾಗಕಲ್ಪದ್ರುಮಾಂಕುರ' ಗ್ರಂಥದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಹತ್ತು ಥಾಟ, ಹತ್ತು ಸಮಯಚಕ್ರಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನುಗುಣವಾಗಿ ಹತ್ತು ರಾಗಗಳ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ರಮಿಕ ಪುಸ್ತಕ ಮಾಲಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಹತ್ತು ಲಕ್ಷಣಗೀತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾತ್ರ ಆಯ್ದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವು ಯಾವುದೆಂದರೆ ಭೈರವಭೈರವ ಥಾಟ-ಭೈರವರಾಗ, ಆಸಾವರಿಥಾಟ-ಜೇವನಪುರಿರಾಗ, ಕಾಫೀಥಾಟ-ಭೀಮಪಲಾಸಿರಾಗ, ತೋಡಿಥಾಟ-ಮುಲ್ತಾನಿರಾಗ, ಕಲ್ಯಾಣಥಾಟ-ಭೂಪಾಲಿರಾಗ, ಖಮಾಜಥಾಟ-ಜಯಜಯವಂತಿರಾಗ, ಭೈರವಿಥಾಟ-ಮಾಲಕಂಸರಾಗ, ಮಾರವಾಥಾಟ-ಲಲಿತರಾಗ, ಪೂರ್ವೀಥಾಟ-ಸಂಧಿಪ್ರಕಾಶಕ ಶ್ರೀರಾಗ, ಬಿಲಾವಲಥಾಟ-ಸಾರ್ವಕಾಲಿಕ ಮಾಂಡ ರಾಗಗಳು.

ಅನುಸಂಧಾನ ಪದ್ಧತಿ: ಇದು ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಭಾಗಗಳೆರಡರಲ್ಲೂ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವಿವಿಧ ವೃತ್ತಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳ ಅನ್ವಯಾರ್ಥ ಮತ್ತು ವಿವಿಧ ತಾಳಗಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗೀತೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗಿದೆ. ವೃತ್ತಗಳ ಲಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವರಲಿಪಿಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯೂ ಇದೆ. ಶ್ಲೋಕಕ್ಕೆ ರಾಗ-ಸ್ವರಸಂಯೋಜನೆ ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಇದನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹಾಡಿತೋರಿಸಲಾಗುವುದು.

ಫಲಿತಾಂಶ: ಸಂಗೀತ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿರುವ ರಾಗಲಕ್ಷಣಗೀತೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೊರತಾಗಿ ಸಾಧಕಗಾಯಕರು ಸಂಗೀತ ಕಛೇರಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ರಾಗಕಲ್ಪದ್ರುಮಾಂಕುರದ ಶ್ಲೋಕಗಳನ್ನು ಆಲಾಪ ಪೂರ್ವಕವಾಗಿ ರಾಗಧ್ಯಾನದ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಅದರಿಂದ ಶ್ರೋತೃಗಳಿಗೂ ಸ್ಥೂಲರೂಪವಾಗಿ ರಾಗದ ಪರಿಚಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಸಂಗೀತ ಅಭ್ಯಾಸದಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗುವ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಾಭ್ಯಾಸಿಗಳಿಗೂ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಗೀತದ ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣತೆಗೆ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುವ ಸಂಗೀತಸಾಧಕರಿಗೂ ಈ ಲೇಖನ ಪ್ರೇರಣೆ ನೀಡುವುದು. ರಾಗಧ್ಯಾನಸ್ತೋತ್ರ ರೂಪವಾಗಿ ರಾಗಮಾಲಿಕೆ ರೂಪದಲ್ಲಿ ಹಾಡಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

Paper No. 15.02: Sangeetha Shastra

कर्नाटकशास्त्रीयसङ्गीतसाहित्ये अद्वैतवेदान्तप्रमेयांशाः

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ABSTRACT

दर्शनिष्वन्यतमं वेदान्तदर्शनम् । तत्राप्यन्यतमं शाङ्करं दर्शनम् । आत्मा एक एव स च नित्यः इति वदद्भिः भगवत्पादैः जगतः मिथ्यात्वं प्रतिपादितम् । सिद्धान्तस्यास्य विस्तरेण प्रतिपादनार्थं, सुगमतया अवगमनार्थं, युक्तिभिः तस्य स्थिरीकरणार्थं च अनेकैः विद्वद्भिः अनेके ग्रन्थाः रचिताः । एतेषामध्ययनमेकं साधनम् आत्मनः यथार्थज्ञानार्थम् । एतदतिरिक्तं वेदान्तार्थबोधनसमर्थं साधनं विद्यते सङ्गीतम् । वेदान्तस्य परिचायने सङ्गीतस्यापि योगदानं महत् विद्यते । अनेके वाग्गेयकाराः वेदान्तविचारयुक्ताः कृतीः रचितवन्तः येन जनाः सङ्गीतमास्वादयन्तः वेदान्तमपि ज्ञातुं प्रभवेयुः । यदा सङ्गीतसाहित्ये अद्वैतदर्शनमित्ययं विषयः विचार्यते तदा आदौ स्मृतिपथमायान्ति सदाशिवब्रह्मेन्द्रयतिवर्याः, मुत्तुस्वामिदीक्षिताः, त्यागराजादयः । तत्र स्वयं संन्यासिनः सदाशिवब्रह्मेन्द्रयतिवर्याः अत्यन्तं स्पष्टरूपेण वदन्ति “स्वप्रकाशशिवम् अद्वयमभयं । निष्प्रतर्क्यमनपायमपायं ब्रह्मैवाहं किल गुरुकृपया” इति ।

योऽर्थः “अहं ब्रह्मास्मि”(बृहदारण्यकोपनिषत् – १.४.१०) इति महावाक्येन प्रतिपाद्यते स एवार्थः अत्र सदाशिवब्रह्मेन्द्रयतिभिरपि शब्दान्तरैः उक्तः इति स्पष्टम् अवगम्यते । अस्यामेव पङ्क्तौ विद्यमानः गुरुकृपया इति शब्दः वेदान्तोक्तम् – “ आचार्यवान् पुरुषो वेद”(छान्दोग्योपनिषत् – ६.१४.२) इति वाक्येन प्रतिपादितमेवार्थम् अनुवदति । तस्यामेव कृतौ अग्रे पुनः इत्थं वदन्ति –“चिन्मयबोधानन्दघनं तद्ब्रह्मैवाहं किल” इति । यद् सच्चिदानन्दस्वरूपत्वम् आत्मनः वेदान्तेषूक्तं“सत्यं ज्ञानमनन्तं ब्रह्म” (तैत्तिरीयोपनिषत्- ब्रह्मानन्दवल्ली.१) इत्येवमादि तदेवात्रापि प्रतिपादितम् वर्तते । मुत्तुस्वामिदीक्षितास्तु तेषां द्वितीयायां नवावरणकृतौ इत्थं वदन्ति – “कल्पितमायाकार्यं त्यजरे” इति । एषा दीक्षितोक्ता पङ्क्तिः शङ्करभगवत्पादानां जगन्मिथ्यात्वमेव प्रतिपादयति इति स्पष्टम् एवावगम्यते । तेषां सङ्ग्रहणपुरस्सरं वेदान्तसिद्धान्तप्रसारणे कर्नाटकशास्त्रीयसङ्गीतस्य योगदानं किमिति प्रतिपादनम् अस्य लेखस्य उद्देश्यम् वर्तते ।

Keywords – अद्वैतवेदान्तः, कर्नाटकशास्त्रीयसङ्गीतम्, ब्रह्म, वाग्गेयकाराः

Paper No. 15.03: Sangeetha Shastra

Rhythmic - Soundings during Sloka Narration

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Each form of sloka - oriented meditation has its own ethnicities and rehearses. **Sloka - oriented meditation encircles** intended rheostat of responsiveness and perceptive processes, unemotional, non - evaluative consciousness of fragmentary understanding and programmed transcending. This is a representative of an assemblage of rehearses where contemplation is focused toward solitary object such as breath. There are two primary brain regions involved in focus; Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC) and Default Mode Network (DMN). Anterior Cingulate Cortex sits in Frontal Lobes and connects Cortex, Parietal Lobe, Thalamus of brain to embryonic, sensation centered unswerving differences in Prefrontal Cortex and body consciousness expanses centers of Limbic System.

Aim: This paper presents research observations on some experiments on neuro - rhythms in sloka - oriented meditation. The sloka - oriented meditation methods adopted are ‘Sohum’, meaning ultimate reality and ‘Bhastrika’ meaning bellows.

Methodology: One single subject (small - *n* designs = 01) was elected so as to function as his own control and facilitate prediction, verification and replication. Methodology adopted was obtaining vital statistics (temperature, urine sample and blood sample before and after administering ‘Sohum’ and ‘Bhastrika’ exercises. Event Related Potential (ERP) provided a continuous measure of processing between a stimulus and a response, making it possible to determine which stage (s) are being affected by a specific experimental manipulation. The timing of these responses is thought to provide a measure of judgement of brain's statement or timing of evidence processing. EEG was taken after exercises were administered to examine neural connections via. Theta Waves.

Results: It is observed that there is a significant drop in impressions of vital statistics and a normal EEG (electrical brain wave action) after ‘Sohum’ and ‘Bhastrika’ exercises. Study provides lead for recommending ‘Sohum’ and ‘Bhastrika’ as neuro - physiological apparatus towards management of stress.

Conclusion: Study proposes replication studies in future to further experiment with neurofeedback models.

Keywords: EEG, Neuro - Rhythms, Event-Related Potential (ERP), Theta Waves, ‘Sohum’ and ‘Bhastrika’

Paper No 16.01: Women, Education, and Sanskrit

(स्कृतसाहित्ये आदर्शनार्यः)

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कूटपदानि - मन्त्रद्रष्टारः ऋषिकाः, ब्रह्मवादिन्यः, पञ्चकन्याः सत्याकामजाबाला गार्गी सीता सावित्री
मदालसा

यद्यदाचरति श्रेष्ठस्तत्तदेवेतरो जनः। स यत्प्रमाणं कुरुते लोकस्तदनुवर्तते॥

महाजनो येन गतः स पन्थाः। इत्यादीनि सुभाषितानि समाजे आदर्शनराणां प्रभावं
कीर्तयन्ति। वैदिकलौकिकवाङ्मये आदर्शनार्यः नैकाः दरीदृश्यन्ते। वैदिकवाङ्मये
सत्यकामस्य जननी जाबाला गार्गी मैत्रेयी ऋषिकाः ब्रह्मवादिन्यः आदर्शनार्यः सन्ति।

मन्त्रद्रष्टुषु नार्यः अपि आसन्निति वैदिकवाङ्मयानुशीलनेन स्पष्टीभवति। ऋग्वेदस्य
दशममण्डले नैकाः ऋषिकाः दरीदृश्यन्ते।

घोषा गोधा विश्ववारा अपालोपनिषन्निषत्। ब्रह्मजाया जुहूर्नाम अगस्त्यस्य स्वसादितिः ॥ इन्द्राणी
चेन्द्रमाता च सरमा रोमशोर्वशी। लोपामुद्रा च नद्यश्च यमी नारी च शश्वती ॥ श्रीर्लाक्षा सार्पराज्ञी वाक्
श्रद्धा मेधा च दक्षिणा। रात्री सूर्या च सावित्री ब्रह्मवादिन्य ईरिताः ॥ इति बृहद्देवता नाम्नि ग्रन्थे
ऋषिकाः उल्लिखिताः।

पुराणवाङ्मये मदालसादयः कीर्तिताः याः मातृणाम् आदर्शरूपाः सन्ति। स्वयं वाल्मीकिः
नारीषु उत्तमा वधूः सीता इति स्तौति। रामस्य दयिता भार्या नित्यम् प्राण समा हिता ॥१-१-२६॥
जनकस्य कुले जाता देवमायेव निर्मिता ।
सर्वलक्षणसंपन्ना नारीणाम् उत्तमा वधूः ॥१-१-२७॥

तस्याः खुरन्यासपवित्रपांसुमपांसुलानां धुरि कीर्तनीया ।
मार्गं मनुष्येश्वरधर्मपत्नी श्रुतेरिवार्थं स्मृतिरन्वगच्छत् । । २.२ । ।

श्लोकेस्मिन् दिलीपपत्नीं सुदक्षिणां सुन्दरैरुपमानैः ललितललितपदैः कालिदासः वर्णयामास।
नारीमणीनां गुणगणाः ये कविभिः संस्कृतसाहित्ये संस्तुताः कीर्तिताश्च ते समाजे बहुधा प्रभावं
जनयन्ति। रामादिवत् वर्तितव्यम् नतु रावणादिवत्इति यं मम्मटः आदर्शपुरुषरूपेण
रामं कीर्तयति।

Paper No 16.02: Women, Education, and Sanskrit

ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ: ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಭಾರತದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ

ಡಾ.ದೇವಿಕ.ಎಸ್.ಎಂ, ಡಾ. ರಾಜೇಶ್ ಬೆಜ್ಜಂಗಳ.೨

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ABSTRACT (ÁgÀÉĀR)**ಷೀಠಿಠೆ:**

ಸಾಢಿರಾರು ಲಢುಗಲ ಇತಿಹಾಸಲನ್ನು ಹೂಂದಿರುವ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಪರಂಪರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಹಾಗೂ ಲಲಳ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣಕ್ಕೆ ಲಿಶೇಷಲವಾದ ಸ್ಥಾನಲೂನಲಿದೆ. ಲಿಶ್ಲದ ಉಲಿಲೆಲ್ಲ ದೇಶಗಲಿಗಿಂತ ಭಾರತ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ, ಪರಂಪರೆ ಢುತ್ತು ಜ್ಞಾನದ ಲಢುಯದಲಿ ಅಗ್ರಲೂನಲವಾಗಿದ್ದು, ಲನುಕರಣೀಯಲವಾದ ಸತ್ಲವನ್ನು ಲಿಡಲ ಸಿರೂಂದಿದೆ. ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ದ ಲಢುಯಲೂ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಹೂಂಠ 'ಲ. ಭಾಯ 'ದ' ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಇತಿಹಾಸಲನ 'ು ಢೂಡಿಲರೆ ಢುಹಿಲೆಯರೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಲಗ್ಗೆ ಲಗ್ಗೆ ಇದ್ದ ಪೂರ್ಲಗ್ರಹಗಲು ದೂರಲಾಗುತ್ಲಲೆ. 'ನ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಸ್ಲತಂತ್ಯಲೂಹತಿಲೆ', 'ನ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಲಿದ್ಯಾಲೂಹತಿಲೆ' ಂಬ ಢೂತುಗಲು ಹಲಲೆಲೆ ಲಳಕೆ ಇದ್ದರು ಢುಹಿಲಾ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಲಾತುಲರ್ಲ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದನಿಂದಲೂ ಅಕೆಯ ಲರ್ಲತೆ ಢುತ್ತು ಯೂಗ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಂತ್ತಿ ಹಿದಿಯುತ್ಲದೆ. ಲೇದ ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತುಗಲ ಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣಲೂ ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಢಿಕ ತಳಹದಿಯ ಢೇಲೆ ರೂಪಿತಲಾಗಿ ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಹೆಸರಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಅರಿಲಿನ ಪೂರ್ಣ ಯಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಇದರ ಜತೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಹೆಣ್ಣನ್ನು ಸಢು ಸಢೂಜದ ನೆಲೆಯಿಂದ ಲಿಲಜಿ ಸಿ ಶೂದ್ರ' ರ' ರೂಪಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಸೇರಿಸಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಿಂದ ಲಲಳನ್ನು ಹೂಂಠ' ಡ' ಲ' ಹುನ್ನಾರಲೂ ಸಢು ರಜದಲಿ ಸುಪ್ಲಲಾಗಿ ಲಡಗಿದೆ.

ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಢುತ್ತು ಲ್ಯಾಪಿ: "ಯತ್ರ ನಾರಿಯಂತು ಪೂಜ್ಯಂತೆ ರಢಂತೆ ತತ್ರ ದೇಲತಾಃ" ಂಬ ಸೂಕ್ತಿಯಂತೆ, ಹೆಣ್ಣಿನ ಸ್ಥಾನಲೂನ ಢುತ್ತು ಅಕೆಯ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ಲಕ್ಕೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದಂತೆ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿ ಢುತ್ತು ಪರಂಪರೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪೂಜ್ಯನೀಯ ಸ್ಥಾನಲಿದೆ. "ಹೆಣ್ಣೂಂದು ಕಲಿತರೆ ಶಾಲೆಯೂಂದು ತೆರೆದಂತೆ" ಢುನೆಗೆ ಢೂದಲ ಪಾಠಶಾಲೆ ತಾಯಿ ಢೂದಲ ಗುರು 'ಂಬ ನಾಣ್ಣದಿಗಲೇ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಢುಹತ್ಲವನ್ನು ಸಾರುತ್ಲಲೆ.

ಸಢೂರೂಪ:

ಒಟ್ಟಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರತೀಯ ಸಢೂಜದಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಢುಹತ್ಲ ಹಾಗೂ ಲಿಲೂಗಲಿಂದ ಅದ ಪೂಯೂಜನಗಲನ್ನು ಚರಿತ್ರೆಯಿಂದ ದಾಖಲಿಸಲೂದು. ಇದರಿಂದ ಢುಹಿಲಾ ಸ್ಥಾನಲೂನದ ಲಗ್ಗೆ ಢುತ್ತು ಲಲಳ ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ಲದ ಲಗ್ಗೆ ನಿಜ ಸ್ವರೂಪಲನ್ನು ಅರಿಯಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯಲಾಗುತ್ಲದೆ. ಇಂದಿನ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಲಾದಿ ಲಿಂತನೆಗೆ ಅಂದಿನ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಹೇಗೆ ನೆರಲಾಗಿದೆ ಂಬುದು ಸುಪ್ಲಕಲಾಗಿ ಗೂಚರಲಾಗುತ್ಲದೆ.

ಂಚ್ಛಿತಿಲಿಡಿ: ಧಾರ್ಮಿಕ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಲೇದಗಲ ಕಾಲದ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಉಪನಿಷತ್ತು ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಪೂರ್ಣಗಲಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ, ಶರ್ಣರ ಸ್ತ್ರೀ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಲರಢುನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ತ್ರೀಶಿಕ್ಷಣ

Paper No 16.03: Women, Education, and Sanskrit

Womens' contribution in social work

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ABSTRACT

यत्र नार्यस्तु पूज्यन्ते रमन्ते तत्र देवताः इति यत् वाक्यम् उच्यते तत् मनुस्मृतौ दृश्यते ।

स्त्रीषु अवस्थात्रयं वर्तते । कन्या, पत्नी, माता चेति । स्त्री शब्दस्य बहवः पर्यायशब्दाः सन्ति । स्त्रीयोषिदबला योषा नारी सीमन्तिनी वधुः । प्रतिप्रदर्शिनी वामा वनिता महिला तथा ॥ इति। वयमत्र भारतस्य सामाजिककार्ये स्त्रीणां योगदानम् इत्यस्मिन् विषये चर्चा कुर्वन्तः स्मः । सामाजिककार्यं नाम किं ? कीदृशं वर्तते ? कथं कार्यं करणीयम् ? इत्यादि विचाराः अत्र वर्तन्ते ।

वस्तुतः आधुनिकभारते सामाजिककार्ये इत्युक्ते महिलाः निरन्तरं पुरुषसमानाः भवेयुः इति भावना वर्तते । परन्तु भारतीयमहिलानां मानसिकता तथा नास्ति । अत्र अध्यात्मस्य धर्मस्य च आधारेण सर्वाणि कार्याणि भवन्ति । अतः अत्र भारते सामाजिककार्यं नाम सहजतया मनसा क्रियमाणं कार्यम् इति अर्थः ।

भारते आर्थिक-राजनैतिक-धार्मिक-शैक्षणिक-कृषि-विज्ञानम् इत्यादिषु क्षेत्रेषु स्त्रियः प्रमुखरूपेण आसन् सन्ति च । वैदिककाले ३० अधिकाः मन्त्रद्रष्टव्यः अविद्यन्त । भारतं कुटुम्बप्रधानं वर्तते । कुटुम्बस्य पालनेन रक्षणेन च स्त्रियः सामाजिककार्ये निरताः आसन् इति तु सत्यम् । स्त्रियः कुटुम्बस्य सर्वान् पोषयन् सामाजिकानां सेवायां भवन्ति स्म इति अनेकैः उदाहरणैः ज्ञायते । वेदसाहित्येषु, काव्येषु, नाटकेषु इत्यादिषु एतादृश्यः महिलाः दृश्यन्ते । भारते प्रातःस्मरणीयानां महापुरुषाणां सङ्ख्या महती अस्ति । तेषां मातरः गृहकृत्यानि कुर्वन्त्यः एतेषां बौद्धिकवर्धने विकासे च महत्पात्रम् आवहन् । अध्यात्मदृष्टिः अस्मिन् देशे विद्यते इति कारणतः महिलानां सहभागः सामाजिककार्ये दरीदृश्यते ।

भारतीयसंस्कृतौ सभ्यता वर्तते यत् त्यागः, तपश्च । त्यागेनैकेन अमृतत्वमानशुः इति महानारायणोपनिषदः सारः । शिक्षणक्षेत्रे तु बह्व्यः स्त्रियः कार्यं कृतवत्यः अपि । वैदिककाले स्त्रीणामपि शिक्षणमासीत् इति तु दृश्यते । ब्रह्मवादिनी सद्योवधुः चेति द्विविधम् । ब्रह्मवादिन्यः स्व-अध्ययनानन्तरं शिक्षणक्षेत्रे अनुवर्तन्ते स्म । सद्योवधुः विवाहं कृत्वा पतिगृहं गच्छन्ति स्म । वैदिककालतः स्वातन्त्र्यप्राप्तिपर्यन्तं बह्व्यः महिलाः सामाजिककार्ये संलग्नाः आसन् । तासु काश्चन गार्गी-मैत्रेयी-विश्वामित्रा-अपाला-सुलभा-लोपामुद्रा च ऋषिकाः । किन्तु राज्ञी चेत्रम्मा, केळदि चेत्रम्मा, अहल्याबायी होळ्कर, । भक्तिमार्गे अपि मीराबायी, शारदादेवी । जीजाबायी, भुवनेश्वरी देवी, सावर्कर महोदयस्य प्रजावती इत्याद्याः । कर्णाटकस्य वचनसाहित्ये अपि अक्कमहादेवी, गंगाम्बिका, नीलाम्बिका इत्याद्याः । राजा अशोकः बौद्धधर्मस्य प्रसारार्थं प्रेषितवान् । संघमित्रा तस्य पुत्री प्रथममहिला विदेशप्रवासं कृतवती आसीत्

एवम् आहत्य भारतस्य सामाजिककार्ये स्त्रीणां योगदानं महत् वर्तते सर्वक्षेत्रेषु ।

Paper No 16.04: Women, Education, and Sanskrit

STATUS OF WOMEN IN ANCIENT INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Women make up the majority of the population in India, which means they account for a significant proportion of the modern and ancient part of our nation's history. In ancient times, Women were honoured and treated with respect. There are many elements that influence the position and role of women in ancient India. Social structure, cultural norms, value system and social expectations are few of them. The cultural, aesthetic, moral, and spiritual development of society is also mirrored the role of women in ancient times. Women were treated with honour and made substantial contributions to government and politics as well. Yet, considering the current situation, women must be given greater power and integrated into society in this modern India. The value placed on women in ancient cultures should be thoroughly examined and applied to the advancement of women in modern society. The main objective of this study is to obtain the understanding of the status of women in ancient India. Women endowers plays an important role in the strengthening of human civilization and made rapid progress in the globe since ages

Keywords: Ancient India, Education, status of women, Family

Paper No 16.05: Women, Education, and Sanskrit

WOMEN EDUCATION IN ANCIENT INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In the recent years, worldwide, gender equity and women empowerment is mostly discussed issue. Most of the discussions on women are centered around human resource development. Women empowerment issues had more concern in the ancient India which are reflected in Sanskrit literature and educating women was the strategy even in ancient time. To empower women, specific roles to women in Indian traditions are assigned to manage the households. Indian ancient knowledge provides a direction through a value system for gender equity and women empowerment so that women can be comfortable and in welfare. Therefore, there is a need to probe into Sanskrit literature to understand the traditions of women education, thereby their empowerment. This would help us to develop a suitable strategy for the gender equity and women empowerment. Such an attempt is made in this paper.

Objectives: The main purpose of this paper is to analyses the women education and their social status in the ancient India. The specific objectives are;

- To review the women education in the ancient India.
- To understand the Strategy of women empowerment that Indian ancient knowledge provides.

Description: This paper is descriptive in nature and based on reviewing ancient literature. Women education, status of women in ancient society as reflected by Sanskrit literature are discussed in the paper.

Keywords: women education; status of women, women empowerment; Ancient India

Paper No 17.01: Contemporary Influence of Sanskrit on present & Future Generations

CONTEMPORARY SANSKRIT LITERATURE

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भूमण्डलस्य यस्मिन्कसिन्मपि भागे निवसतां सर्वेषां मानवानां कृते संस्कृतवाङ्मयस्य प्रभूतं महत्वमस्तीति सुविदितमेव। कृषिशास्त्रं पशुशास्त्रं वाणिज्यशास्त्रं स्थापत्यशास्त्रम् आयुर्वेदशास्त्रम् इत्यादिनी अनेकानि शास्त्राणि वर्तन्ते। वेदवेदाङ्गस्मृतिः पुराणेतिहासदीनि धर्ममीमांसा ब्रह्ममीमांसादीनि नीतिशास्त्रं प्रशासनशास्त्रं धनुर्वेदशास्त्रं तर्कशास्त्रं पदार्थशास्त्रं साङ्ख्यशास्त्रं योगशास्त्रं इत्यादिनी शास्त्राणि च संस्कृतवाङ्मये सन्ति। तेषु संस्कृते काव्यसम्पत्तिः सागरवत् अपारा अमूल्या च वर्तते। तत्र अस्माकं सनातनज्ञानराशिः तदात्मकं जीवनं प्रतिबिम्बितं वर्तते। मानवजीवनरहस्यान्वेषणे संस्कृतवाङ्मयस्य सर्वोच्चकारकत्वमपि सुविदितमेव। भारतम् अति प्राचीनम् अति विशालं च। भारतस्य वाङ्मयमपि तथैव प्राचीनं प्रशस्तरं सुमहत् च। सृष्टिकर्ता भगवान् एव भारतीयानां सकलविद्यानां उत्सः इति सिद्धान्तः शास्त्रेषु। भारतस्य सुजाते अल्पजाते अजाते च इतिहास वाग्विनिमयस्य माध्यमं संस्कृतमिति सुविदितं समेषाम्। प्रदीर्घं अस्मिन् भारतेतिहासे यानि शास्त्राणि समुद्भूतानि यत् चिन्तनं प्रावर्तते, ये भावाः प्रकटिताः तत्सर्वमपि संस्कृतभाषाभाण्डारे निबद्धमस्ति। अस्य भाण्डारस्य आकारः कियान् गम्भीरः मूल्यं कियत् अधिकं इति निर्धारणे कोऽपि न समर्थः तेषु सर्वशास्त्रेषु साहित्यशास्त्रं अवलोकयामयः। वेदः प्रभुसम्मितः इत्युच्यते। पुराणं मित्रसम्मितं इत्युच्यते काव्यं हि कान्तासम्मितं भवति। महाकविः भासकालिदासादिप्रणीताः काव्यनाट्यकथाख्यापिकादिरुपा ललितकलाप्रधाना नानाविधासिद्धान्तगता अनेके ग्रन्थाश्च संस्कृतवाङ्मये सन्ति। संस्कृतसाहित्यं अत्यन्तं प्रफुल्लं विकसितमासीत् पूर्वतनकाले। अस्माभिः यः ग्रन्तः पूजनीयः अस्ति सः आदिकाव्यनाम्ना प्रसिद्धः। जगति प्रथमः परिपूर्णकाव्यावतारो नाम बाल्मीकिविरचितं रामायणम्। रामायणात् परं विरचितं महत् काव्यं नाम महाभारतम्। महाभारतं परं कालिदास-भास-अश्वघोषादयः बहवः कवयः उत्कृष्टानि महाकाव्य-नाटकाद्यनेकप्रकारकाणि काव्यानि विरचितवन्तः। तदनन्तरं भारवि माघ बाणभट्ट- भवभूति-श्रीहर्ष कुमारदासप्रभृतयः नैके कवयः सहस्रशः काव्यानि विरचितवन्तः। तेन काव्यलोकः अत्यन्तं विकासं प्राप्तवान्। अत एव बहुनि महाकाव्यानि, खण्डकाव्यानि, नाटकानि, चम्पूकाव्यानि, गद्यकाव्यानि इत्येवं नैके काव्यप्रकाराः समजायन्त। अद्यापि संस्कृतकाव्यप्रपञ्चः वर्धमान एव दृश्यते। अतः अद्य संस्कृतकाव्यलोकस्य इयन्तागणना असम्भवा एव जाता। एतस्मिन् विषये लेखितुं प्रयतिष्ये।

Paper No 17.02: Contemporary Influence of Sanskrit on present & Future Generations

A Sociosemantical Description of Courtesy Expressions found in formal conversations of Sanskrit and a few other Modern Indian Languages

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ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt to find out the courtesy expressions found in formal conversations of Sanskrit and a few other Modern Indian Languages. The purpose of the study is to analyse and appreciate this type of contribution by the ancient Indian linguistics to honour the human dignity and respect for the individual. It also analyses semantically, the strategies adopted thereby to express the respect and regards, with suitable syntactical variations. As per the current status only a few studies are available in this regard which is on Sanskrit Language only. So, this paper is works over the gap of extending the results of these studies over to few other languages, to achieve more features of convergence, between the genres of Indian Languages. The researcher followed the method of Sociosemantics Linguistic Analysis. As a main agenda of the study, secondary sources from previous Sanskrit studies are used, and conversations related to other languages were analysed. Hence, the major objective of the present study is to take up a simple Sociosemantics description of courtesy related strategies found in Sanskrit few other Indian Languages like Hindi, Konkani, Kannada, Malayalam, Tamil, Telugu etc.

From the result of the analysis, it is found that languages belonging to both the genres of Indo Aryan and Dravidian, show similar expressions of courtesy-politeness, to a recognizable extent. The Study employs some basic ideas of previous studies, but major part of analysis with respect to other languages is fully original.

Keywords: Sociosemantical Description, Courtesy expressions in Konk, Courtesy expressions in Kannada

Paper No. 18.01: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama

Significance of the spiritual instructions from the Vishnu Sahasranama and its impact on coping with life situations.

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ABSTRACT

Vishnu Sahasranama comes in the Anushasana Parva of the epic Mahabharatam. It is a conversation wherein 6 poignant yet simple questions are asked by Yudhisthira to Bheesmacharya. His answers signify the spiritual instructions imparted to serve as a spiritual guide for mankind. In this paper, we trace the spiritual instructions given in the Vishnu Sahasranama from the aspect of coping. How these mantras have the power of positivity which helps us cope more effectively with different life situations. How regular chanting has helped people in their difficult times. The main objective therefore is to highlight the significance of spiritual instructions as a coping guide for one and all.

A qualitative survey with sample size of 150 (random -heterogeneous group) was included for the study. No priming was done of respondents who answered it where they had to write their thoughts & experiences on Vishnu Sahasranama and coping. More than 60% respondents agreed on the efficacy of chanting Vishnu Sahasranama as a coping mechanism which was effective for them. More significantly 85% respondents believe in the power of any mantra recitation & repetition in healing the body and the mind. Some respondents from the mental health profession confirmed recommending chanting of mantras especially Vishnu Sahasranama to their clients based on their inclination and orientations. Some respondents from the medical profession are giving reference of jwara chikitsa of Charaka where he mentions chanting of Vishnu Sahasranama as one of the remedies.

Keywords: Vishnu Sahasranama, coping, mantra, chanting, mental health, healing.

Paper No. 18.02: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतादेवीमाहात्म्यञ्च - एतयोः ग्रन्थयोः वैशिष्ट्यम्
Śrīmad Bhagavadgīta and Devī Māhātmyam:
A comparative analysis

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ABSTRACT

संस्कृतवाङ्मये श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतादेवीमाहात्म्यञ्च सनातनधर्मप्रतिपादकौ प्रसिद्धौ ग्रन्थौ वर्तते। श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतामहाभारतस्य भीष्मपर्वणिविद्यते। देवीमाहात्म्यं मार्कण्डेयपुराणस्य उत्तरभागे वर्तते। अस्य सप्तशतीचण्डी इति च नामनीस्तः। समाजे बहवः जनाः ग्रन्थौ पृथक्पृथक् पठन्ति, द्वौ ग्रन्थौ ज्ञात्वा अपि विमर्शनं कुर्वन्ति। तत्तु विरलतया परिदृश्यते। तस्मात् एतयोः ग्रन्थयोः उपोद्घातविषये प्रतिपादनीयमिति मया चिन्तितम्।

गीतायां देवीमाहात्म्ये च उभयोः ग्रन्थयोः भागत्रयमिति जनाः कल्पन्ते। षट्कानुसारं विभागत्रयम् इति भगवद्गीतायां यत्र वेदमहावाक्यस्य प्रतिपादनं सूक्ष्मरूपेण क्रियते। यथा “तत्त्वमसि” इति महावाक्यं त्रिषु षट्केषु संयोजितम्। एवमेव देवीमाहात्म्ये प्रथमचरित्रं, मध्यमचरित्रम्, उत्तरचरित्रञ्च विद्यते। उभयोः ग्रन्थयोः मध्ये उपदेशबोधनम् अपि च प्रश्नोत्तररूपेण संवादः प्रवर्तते। श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतायां श्रीकृष्णः अर्जुनम् उपदेशं बोधयति यत्सञ्जयः, अपि च राजा धृतराष्ट्रः अपिशृणुतः। देवीमाहात्म्ये मुख्यतया ऋषिः मेधाः देव्याः अद्भुतचारित्रं राजानं सुरथम् अपि च वैश्यं समाधिं वर्णयति।

ग्रन्थयोः अनेकवारपठनेन एतत्कार्यसाधितम्। अत्र साम्यं किम्? भेदः कः? इत्येव मनसि निधाय लेखोऽयं लिख्यते। उभयोः ग्रन्थयोः रचयिता महर्षिः वेदव्यासः। उभयोः मध्ये सप्तशतीसङ्ख्यासु विख्याता। कस्मिन्सन्दर्भे, केषां पात्राणि वर्तन्ते, को उद्देशः, प्रक्रियाका, किं बोधितम् इत्येतेषां प्रश्नानां समीक्षा अत्र प्रस्तुता।

Keywords: Bhagavadgīta, Devī Māhātmyam, Comparative Analysis, Hindu scripture

Paper No. 18.03: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Emotional Intelligence in Sāṅkhyayoga of Bhagavadgītā

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ABSTRACT

Emotions play an important role in people's lives, especially in relationships and decision making. If emotions are not kept in check, they can lead to disorders like anxiety and depression. Lack of emotional management also leads to an increase in violence in the society. Hence, it is necessary to know how emotions work and how to control them. Emotional Intelligence or EI is a term popularized by psychologist Daniel Goleman. EI is the capacity to be aware of, control, and express one's emotions, and to handle interpersonal relationships judiciously, and empathetically. Many psychologists claim that high EI indicates a better chance of a successful life, even more than a high IQ (cognitive intelligence). While the IQ generally remains unchanged throughout the life, Emotional Intelligence can be learnt, cultivated, and enhanced.

Although the concept of EI was put forth in the 1990s, many Western and Indian schools of philosophy have acknowledged the fact that emotions should be controlled. Among the philosophical books, *Bhagavadgītā* has encompassed every psychological tendency and metaphysical principle. In many of its verses, the *Bhagavadgītā* establishes the importance of controlling the emotional mind. The preliminary teachings of Krishna can be found in the second chapter of the *Bhagavadgītā*, titled 'Sāṅkhya-yoga'. This chapter covers many important topics like the human mind, emotions, transmigration of soul, and the ultimate truth. In this research paper, efforts have been made to unravel the concepts of Emotional Intelligence that can be found in the *Sāṅkhya-yoga* which may guide people toward a fulfilling life.

Keywords: Emotions, Emotional Intelligence, Bhagavadgita, Psychology, Philosophy

Paper No. 18.04: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

The Viṣṇu Sahasranāma and its Correlation with Ancient and Early Medieval Vaiṣṇava Iconography

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ABSTRACT

The Viṣṇu Sahasranāma forms a part of the Anusāsana Parvan of the Mahābhārata and unfolds as a dialogue between Bhīṣma and Yudhiṣṭhira. The Viṣṇu Sahasranāma enshrines the essence of the Vedas, Upaniṣads and the Śrīmad Bhagavad Gītā and can be chanted by persons of variegated religious persuasions. Among the thousand names of Viṣṇu, there are certain names which are related to his tangible form- i.e. the *mūrtis* or *vigrahas*. The purpose and objectives of this research paper are to ascertain the exact significance and role of the certain *nāmas* of Lord Viṣṇu in the Sahasranāma in connection with the Viṣṇu Vigrahas along with their textual descriptions. One of the most complete modern works on the Viṣṇu Sahasranāma is the one by Dr. H. Janardana Acharya (1968) apart from the *bhāṣyas* of philosophers like Ādi Śaṅkarācārya, Parāśara Bhaṭṭa and ŚrīSatyasandhatīrtha of the Uttarādimaṭha.

The research methodology incorporated for this study is both analytical and descriptive research complemented by textual studies and analysis of actual Vaiṣṇava Mūrtis. The aimed results will centre around determining the symbiotic relationship between the Viṣṇu Sahasranāma and the development of Vaiṣṇava Iconography. The findings would be related to the visual culture which the Sahasranāma emphasizes on to bolster the focus on the form of Viṣṇu and the associated dhyāna with the ultimate goal of spiritual awakening. The link between the Viṣṇu Sahasranāma and ancient and early medieval Vaiṣṇava icons warrants deep exploration and it is exactly this gap that the present study endeavours to fill.

Keywords: Viṣṇu Sahasranāma, Ancient, Early Medieval, Vaiṣṇava Icons, Visual Culture, Dhyāna

Paper No. 18.05: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

BHAGAVAD GITA INSIGHTS FOR THEREINFORCEMENT OF CO-OPERATIVE IDENTITY

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ABSTRACT

The cooperative identity embodying ten cooperative values and seven principles unites us to work for the common good and for rebuilding sustainable cooperative communities (ICA, 2021). This cooperative ideology is the essence of Bhagavad- Gita and the reinforcement of the same is paramount to uphold cooperatives' relevance and overcome multitude of global and cooperative specific challenges. There is a vast repository of knowledge and accumulated experience in India explicating management principles and lessons from Bhagavad Gita (Arikrishnan,2014; Bhattathiri, 2010; Juneja,2022; Mahadevan, 2008), leadership development(Muniapan, 2015), and conceptualization of wisdom and values(Jeste and Vahia, 2008).There has been a dearth of previous research done in this direction.

To fill the research gap, this study examines the concept of cooperative identity in the light of Bhagavad Gita and explains its significance in reinforcing the cooperative identity.To substantiate the theory, it also provides the glimpses of the key cooperatives in India that institutionalized the co-operative values and principles and achieved the greatest good for greatest number of people, which is the core of Bhagavad Gita. The study is based on theoretical research and employed hermeneutics, which is a qualitative methodology used for interpreting and presenting cooperative values fromBhagavad-Gita. Both primary, secondary sources of data, inferences drawn from researcher's previous empirical studies and other documentations are used in the study.

Originality -The findings provide cooperative practitioners and policy makers novel insights for operationalising cooperative values and principles impacting cooperatives affirmatively in multiple manifestations.

Keywords: Bhagavad Gita, cooperative, Identity, Values, Reinforcement

Paper No. 18.06: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

गीताकासार्वभौमिकएवंसार्वकालिकनैतिकदर्शन

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सार

गीतास्मृतिप्रस्थानमेंहोनेपरभीसम्पूर्णउपनिषदोंकासारसरलतमएवंसंक्षिप्तरूपमेंप्रकटकरजनकल्याणकामहनीयकार्यसम्पन्नकरतीहै। अतः महाभारतकारइसे 'सर्वशास्त्रमयी' कहतेहैं। श्रीकृष्णकेनैतिकचिन्तनएवंदर्शनकोअधिगतकरनेमेंमहाभारतोक्त *गीता* (भीष्मपर्व 25-42) परमप्रमाणमानीजातीहैजिनमेंमानवजीवनकेउच्चतमनैतिकचिन्तनएवंव्यावहारिकजीवनदर्शनकोसुस्पष्ट करतेहुएचरमलक्ष्यमुक्तिकेसहजमार्गकोशास्त्रीयविधिसेविनिर्दिष्टकियागयाहै। यहसत्यहैकिगीताशास्त्रसम्पूर्णविश्वकानीतिशास्त्रहै। यहकर्तव्यकीशिक्षा, समत्वकापाठ, ज्ञानकीभिक्षातथाशरणागतिकाउपदेशदेकरसम्पूर्णमानवजगत्काअपूर्वकल्याणकरताहै—

कर्तव्यदीक्षांचसमत्वशिक्षां, ज्ञानस्यचभिक्षांशरणागतिंच।

ददातिगीताकरुणार्द्रभूता, कृष्णेनगीताजगतोहिताय।।

भगवद्गीतासार्वकालिकएवंसर्वभौमिकनैतिकतत्त्वोंकाविमर्शप्रस्तुतकरतीहै। गीताकेनैतिकचिन्तनका मूलाधारकर्मयोगकासिद्धान्तहै।

संन्यासऔरकर्मयोगदोनोंनिःश्रेयस्करहैपरन्तुइनदोनोंमेंकर्मसंन्यासकीअपेक्षाकर्मयोगहीअधिकश्रेष्ठहै। कर्मयोगकीसैद्धान्तिकस्थापनाहेतुश्रीकृष्णजीनेगीताकेदूसरेअध्यायमेंअनेकप्रबलएवंअकाट्ययुक्तियोंकापरिस्फुटनकियाहै। सारतः समझसकतेहैंकिबिनाकर्मकेस्वातन्त्र्यलाभनहींहै। कर्मसंन्याससेसंन्यासकीभीसिद्धिनहींहोतीहै (गीता3.4)। क्षणमात्रभीमनुष्यअकर्मीनहींरहसकताहै(3.5)। शरीरयात्राभीबिनाकर्मसम्भवनहींहै(3.8)। कर्मसृष्टिकानियमहैजोइसकाउल्लङ्घनकरताहैवहवृथाजीताहैऔरलोकसंग्रह(सामाजिकव्यवस्था)केलिएभीकर्मआवश्यकहै(3.20)। परमात्माभीकर्मइसलिएकरताहैउसकोदेखकरहीअन्यजनउनकाअनुकरणकरतेहैं। सभीमनुष्यअकर्मीहोतोयहसमाजहीनष्टनहोजाये। कर्तव्यपालनकीदृष्टिसेकियागयाकर्महीकर्महै। इसीमेंलोकसंग्रहनिहितहै। अन्यइच्छाओंसेकियागयाकर्मसच्चाकर्मनहींहै। समुचितकर्तव्योंकाआचरणहीवास्तविककर्महै।

बीजशब्द—सार्वकालिकनैतिकदर्शन, कर्तव्यदीक्षा, समत्वशिक्षा, ज्ञानकीभिक्षा, कर्मयोग, लोकसंग्रह।

Paper No. 18.07: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

भगवद्गीतायाः महत्त्वं, मुनुकुलंप्रतिमहदुपकारश्च IMPACT AND INFLUENCE OF BHAGAWAD GITA ON HUMANITY

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“श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता” इत्युक्ते श्रीकृष्णार्जुनसंवादः, अर्जुनस्य भीतिः, युद्धात्विमुखी भवितुं प्रयत्नः, श्रीकृष्णस्य अर्जुनप्रत्युपदेशः इत्येते विषयाः मनसि प्रकटीभवन्ति। किन्तु न केवलं अर्जुनप्रतिकृष्णस्य उपदेशः वर्तते,

परन्तु मनुकुलमात्रं प्रति तदुपदेशः गीतायां वर्तते। यतो हि अयं ग्रन्थः “भगवद्गीता” ख्यः। भगवतः गीता इयम्। कृष्णः अर्जुनप्रत्येव न भगवान्, किन्तु जगन्मात्रस्य भगवान्। तथापि भगवद्गीताग्रन्थः पुरातनग्रन्थः, आधुनिकप्रपञ्चे तस्य ग्रन्थस्य तद्गतविषयस्य प्रस्तुतिः युक्तानवाइति जिज्ञासायां, इयं शोधपत्रिका समाधानं ददाति। आधुनिकप्रपञ्चेऽपि आधुनिकसमस्यानामपि परिहारोपायाः गीतायां निरूपिताः सन्ति। न केवलं देहसम्बद्धसमस्यानां, किन्तु मानसिकसमस्यानां, मरणादुत्पद्यमानसमस्यानां, तदतिरिक्तभूतायाकापिसमस्याभवतुतासां सर्वासां समस्यानां परिहारः कृष्णेन गीतायां उक्तः।

उक्तं च व्यासमहर्षिर्विषये “व्यासोच्चिष्टं जगत्सर्वम्” इति, तैः रचितमहाभारतविषये च “यदिहास्ति, तत्सर्वत्र, यत्रेहास्ति, न कुत्रचित्” इति। तदुक्त्यनुसारेण अस्यां शोधपत्रिकायां महाभारतस्य प्रमुखाङ्गभूतगीतायां सकलसमस्यापरिहारः निरूपितः इति निरूप्यते।

अस्याः शोधपत्रिकायाः विशेषस्तु विशेषसन्दर्भान् चित्वा तत्र जायमानविशेषसमस्यानां गीतोक्तदिशा वि- शेषपरिहारनिरूपणम्। अनेन अद्यापि गीतायाः प्रस्तुतिः युक्ता इति भवति। अस्याः शोधपत्रिकायाः अध्ययने सम- स्यापीडिताः सर्वेऽपि, जिज्ञासवश्च अधिकारिणः। प्रयोजनं तु लौकिकस्तरे स्मस्यापरिहारादिकम्, अलौकिकस्तरे आत्मज्ञानादिकम्।

Keywords: भगवद्गीतामहत्त्वम्, मुनुकुलौपकारिकः, विशेषसमस्यानां विशेषपरिहाराः, दैहिक- मानसिकसमस्यानां परिहारः

Paper No. 18.08: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Leadership Lessons from Bhagavad Gita

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ABSTRACT

Leadership is a powerful enabler of organizational capabilities to perform the best. But bad leadership leads the organization to destruction. One of the critical challenges is leading the organization to achieve the goal of the vision under a volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous environment. However when the spiritual teachings are to be applied within a given context or when customizing to the Bhagavad Gita verses, it requires mature understanding. When a phenomenal understanding is to be elicited, it could reflect the problem of representing the union of externalities and internal leadership attempts to work for the welfare of state and people. In this context, how a leadership can work towards obtaining appropriate solutions or decisions is what can be attempted by going through the rigorous understanding of Bhagavad Gita and by self inquiring to fetch the interpretations for various verses present within the scope of Bhavad Gita primarily. However, some of the relevant theories are also discussed and deliberated from multiple perspectives.

Keywords: Artha Nareeswara Tatvam, Bhagavd Gita, Leadership Lessons, Principal-Agent Theory, Leadership from Spiritual knowledge

Paper No. 18.09: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Śrīdhara's concept of Bhakti: A study of *Subodhinī* commentary on *Bhagavadgītā*

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ABSTRACT

Śrīdhara, a non-dualist of Śāṅkara's order, is renowned for commentaries, *Bhāvārtha Dīpikā* on *Bhāgavata Purāṇa*, *Subodhinī* on *Bhagavadgītā* and *Ātmaprakāśa* on *Viṣṇu Purāṇa*. Other extant works include two stotras. Unlike Madhusudan Sarasvati, his independent works on Advaita and Bhakti are unavailable. The reconciliation of Advaita and Devotion in his commentary needs to be researched. The impact of his commentaries on Bhakti literature and the influence of *Bhāvārtha Dīpikā* as a foundational text for the *Gauḍiya* Vaiṣṇavism, which is antagonistic to absolute monism, indicate their importance. Scholars have studied his commentary on selected verses or have noted observations while studying other Vaiṣṇava literature, but Śrīdhara's distinct philosophical standpoint is still unclear. This paper attempts to fill the gap in research concerning the critical study of his commentary in specific. The angle of Devotion in his writings might have significantly contributed to the developmental stage of Advaita Vedanta. The socio-religious conditions, his religious practices and beliefs are reflected in his commentaries.

The scope of this research paper is limited to *Subodhinī* commentary on the selected verses in *Gītā*, which reflect Śrīdhara's distinct devotional perspective. He demonstrates that pure Devotion to the Lord alone is the means to Liberation. Pure literary research with textual and comparative analysis of commentaries of Śāṅkara and Śrīdhara shows how Śrīdhara integrated the devotional aspect with Śāṅkara's non-dualistic commentary on *Gītā*. It appears that he tries to maintain Śāṅkara's supremacy while inserting devotional interpretation with the influence of *Bhāgavata Purāṇa*.

Keywords : Śrīdhara, *Subodhinī* commentary, Bhakti

Paper No. 18.10: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Vishnu Sahasranaama and Spirituality

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Sri Adi Shankaracharya's one of the Advaita Siddhanta says,

“ब्रह्मसत्यं जगन्मिथ्या जीवो ब्रह्मैव न परा” ||

The above line conveys that the being that has taken birth on this Earth, is not different from that of the Supreme. The realization of this ultimate truth can be coined as SPIRITUALITY. Spirituality is a process to unite self with the Supreme soul to come out of the web of cycle of births and deaths called MOKSHA and to enjoy the state of BLISS - the happiness which is not culminated with calamities. There are many ways such as Yoga, meditation, pranaayama, Bhakti, performing pooja to lord and many more wisdoms to move in the path of spirituality for the purpose of Self Realization. One of the most powerful and popular light in the path of Spirituality is Vishnu Sahasranaama (V.S)

V.S is the thousand names of lord Vishnu found in Anushaasana parva {verse 14 to 120} of Mahaabhaarata epic composed in Deva Bhaasha, Samskritam language. Yudhishtira asks Bheeshmaachaarya.

किम् जपन् मुच्यते जन्तुर्जन्मसंसार बन्धनात्

In which way does the जन्तु, human being gain moksha. Acharya replies

स्तुवन्नामसहस्रेण पुरुषः सततोत्थितः

Any मुमुक्षु, the seeker of moksha, if chants V.S shall be released from the whirlpool of births and deaths.

Keywords: Salvation, Hindu, Shankaracharya, Vishnu Sahasranaama, Spirituality

Paper No. 18.11: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Contribution of Sri Madhvacharya in Bhakti Yoga

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ABSTRACT

The contribution of the great Sri Madhvacharya, the 13th century saint is a vast in Bhakti Yoga. The Acharya is well known as a Vedantist and a reformer of Hindu philosophy, and an Acharya of Prasthanatraya – the Brahmasutra, Upanishads and Bhagavad Gita but not many are aware of his contributions are of Bhakti Yoga. This study is to provide some understanding of the Acharya and his valuable hard work of Dvaita School for the world.

The very famous Sri Mahabharata Tatparya Nirnaya is a great work of the Acharya which provides a vast knowledge of Bhakti Yoga to all the devotional practitioners. Although the book was named as Mahabhatata Tatparya Nirnaya but the study includes the past-times of Lord Sri Rama and full of information about Bhakti Yoga can be found in this book. The Sarva Moola Grantha is a collection of about 37 hard works and the contributions of the Acharya in Philosophy, Bhakti, Jyana, Karma, etc; and Mahabharata Tatparya Nirnaya is one of the Grantha. One would be able to understand and receive some knowledge of the Acharya, his contribution, philosophy, teachings, etc. to Bhakti Yoga by the study of Sri Mahabharata Tatparya Nirnaya itself.

Keywords: Madhvacharya, Mahabharata, Upanishads, Sarva Moola Grantha, Bhagavad Gita, Philosophy, Dvaita, Bhakti Yoga.

Paper No. 18.12: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतायां ज्ञानभक्तिकर्मणां संगमः

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ABSTRACT

भारतदेशे बहुविधाः ग्रन्थाः सन्ति। प्रत्येकं ग्रन्थः कञ्चित् विषयं वा प्रकर्षेण वदति। खण्डनखण्डखाद्यग्रन्थः ज्ञानाधारितः ग्रन्थः। नारदभक्तिसूत्रम्, शाण्डिल्यभक्तिसूत्रं च एतौ ग्रन्थौ भक्तिप्रधानौ स्तः। मीमांसाग्रन्थाः कर्म कथम्प्रधानम् इति वदन्ति। परन्तु भगवद्गीतायां ज्ञानभक्तिकर्मणां समन्वयः अस्ति।

वयं केवलकर्मयोगम् स्वीकुर्मः चेत् भावविरहितकर्मरुक्षं भवति, ज्ञानरहितः पुरुषः कुशलतया कर्मकर्तुम्न शक्नोति। यदा बुद्धेः उपयोगम् अकृत्वा भक्तिकुर्मः तदा एषा बुद्धिरहीता भक्तिवैदिकधर्मः न मान्यते। भक्तौ कर्म अपि आवश्यकम्। यदा भक्त्याः अधिष्ठानम् विना ज्ञानं प्राप्नुमः तदा तु ज्ञानी गर्विष्ठः भविष्यति। ज्ञानी कर्मन करोति चेत् ज्ञानमिच्छति। भविष्यति।

अतः केवलं ज्ञानं केवलकर्म अथवा केवला भक्तिः न सम्पुर्णा। त्रयः घटकाः आवश्यकाः। तेषां समन्वयनं भगवद्गीतायां द्रष्टुं शक्नुमः। तेषां कथं समन्वयनम्, अर्जुनेन कथं प्रेरणा प्राप्ता इति अस्मिन् लेखे स्पष्टीकर्तुम् इच्छामि।

Keywords: नारदभक्तिसूत्रम्, शाण्डिल्यभक्तिसूत्रं, कर्मयोगम्भक्तिः, ज्ञानम्

Paper No. 18.13: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

विष्णुसहस्रनाम-पारायणेन फलम्

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ABSTRACT

चतुर्वेदाः भारतीयतत्वशास्त्रस्य हिमालयपंक्तयः इति कथ्यते। उपरिउपरिगच्छन्तः वयं उपनिषत्-शिखराणि पश्यामः। उपनिषदः मानवेभ्यः मर्त्यलोकात् अमृतत्वम् आरोढुम् उपयुक्तं सोपानम् इत्यपि कथ्यते। उपनिषत्सु नैकसिद्धान्ताः सन्ति। एकं सत्यं बहुधा पश्यन्ति अत्र। सर्वैः अनुभूतं सत्यं भविष्यज्जनाङ्गस्य उद्धारार्थं म्योग्यशिष्येभ्यः उपदिष्टमस्ति अत्र। सादेव गङ्गा इव अद्यापि उपनिषत्सु प्रवहन्ती अस्ति। यः कोऽपि अत्रागत्य सात्वापुनीतः भवेत्।

विना भगवद्गीतां,

विष्णुसहस्रनाममहाभारतं तु केवलं एका एतिहासिककथा एव भवति। एतन्महाभारतं विभागत्रयेण अवगन्तुं शक्यते। प्रथमतस्तस्य

“साहित्यिकरूपं” कौरवपाण्डवकथा, द्वितीयं तस्य

“मनोवैज्ञानिकरूपं” अर्जुनस्य अकालिकमोहपरिहारार्थं विश्वस्य प्रथममनोचिकित्सावैद्येन उपदिष्टा भगवद्गीता, अन्तिमं तस्य

“आध्यात्मिकरूपं” विष्णुलोकगमनसहायकं विष्णुसहस्रनामस्तोत्रम्। अत्र कृष्णस्य साहाय्येन एव पाण्डवाः विजयं प्राप्तवन्तः,

कृष्णस्य विरुद्धं युद्धं कृत्वा कौरवाः हताः।

महाभारते सर्वपदानि अपि विष्णुना मानि एव। यथा भारतीयतत्वशास्त्रेषु महाभारतं श्रेष्ठं तथैव सकलस्तोत्रेषु विष्णुसहस्रनाम एव अतिश्रेष्ठम्। अतः यदा भक्त्याः पठन्ति तदा एतन्नाम्नां दतरङ्गेण रोगपरिहारः भवति इति तु सिद्धमेव। अत एव अस्य फलश्रुतौ उच्यते

“रोगार्तो मुच्यते रोगात्” इति। ‘क्यान्सर्’

सदृशाः भयङ्कररोगाः अपि अस्य पारायणेन निवार्यन्ते इत्यत्र संशयः। विष्णुसहस्रनामपठनेन अस्माकं विश्वासः आत्मविश्वासः पवर्धते। गृहेऽस्मिन् साक्षात् विष्णुः सकलदेवदेवतासहितः आगत्य निवसति। तस्मात् अस्माकं धनकनकादिसंपत् आरोग्यं चलभ्यते। कलियुगे भगवतः नामस्मरणेनैव महत्तपः। तेन च मोक्षः इति कथ्यते। “भक्त्या सङ्कीर्तनं विष्णोः न दोषः परिभूयते” इत्यत्र विष्णुसहस्रनामपारायणस्य

भक्तिः एव मूला,

एतत्स्तोत्रगङ्गा इव पवित्रम्। स्वाश्रितान् भक्तान् अपि पवित्री करोति, दैहिकमानसिकबाधाः स्तोत्रपारायणेन निवारिताः इति सत्यामृतसिद्धान्तानुभवं करोति।

Keywords: महाभारतम्, विष्णुसहस्रनाम, भगवद्गीता, आध्यात्मिकरूपम्

Paper No. 18.14: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

आचार्यत्रयगीताव्याख्यान औचित्यं

Research Scholar – Pavan K

Guide : Dr.Shrikantha R Balthillaya

सहस्रस्येतिहास्येतिहासपुराणवेत्तारः विदितमेवेदं ज्ञाने तिरोहिते उत्तमज्ञानमार्गात् भ्रष्टे सज्जने सर्वोत्तमः भगवान् नारायणः श्री वेदव्यास सत्त्वेन अवतीर्य वेदार्थनिर्णायकानि ब्रह्मसूत्राणि अष्टादशपुराणानि महाभारत च अरचयत् । अत एव “व्यासोच्छिष्टं जगत्सर्वं” इति वाक् सुप्रसिद्धा व्यासः साक्षात् विष्णुरेव । तथा च श्रीमन् महाभारते

–
“कृष्णद्वैपायनं व्यासं विद्धि नारायणं प्रभुम् ।

को ह्यन्यः पुण्डरिकाक्षात् महाभारत वृद्धवेत् ॥” इति ।

महाभारत –

महाभारत गात्रेण अर्थेन च श्रेष्ठः ग्रन्थः । अस्य च भावं विशेष च यो जानाति सः सर्वपापविमुक्तो भवतीति महाभारतवचनम् ।

“महत्वात् भारवत्वाच्च महाभारतमुच्यते ।

निरुक्तमस्य यो वेद सर्वपापैः प्रमुच्यते ॥”

इति ।

सर्वशास्त्रेषु श्रीमन्महाभारतग्रन्थः अत्यन्तश्रेष्ठः इति प्रतिपादितः । भारतं पञ्चमो वेदः इत्युक्तदिशा महाभारतस्य पञ्चमवेदत्वं प्रसिद्धम् । एतादृशे श्रीमन्महाभारते अष्टादश पर्वाणि सन्ति, लक्षाधिकक्षलोकाश्च विद्यन्ते । 2

भगवद्गीता–

„भारतपारिजातमधुभूताम्” इत्यनया वाचा भगवद्गीतायाः महत्त्वं अवगम्यते । „भारते गीतिका वरा”, „विष्णोः

सहस्रनामाऽपि ज्ञेयं पाब्जं च तद् द्वयम्” पौरुषेयनिर्णयशास्त्रेषु यदा महाभारतग्रन्थः श्रेष्ठः तदा भगवद्गीता

विष्णुसहस्रनामस्तोत्रं च । अन्यत्र एवं वर्णितम् –

“सर्वोपनिषदो गावो दोग्धा गोपालनन्दनः ।

पार्थो वत्सः सुधीर्भोक्ता दुग्धं गीतामृतं महत् ॥”

इति ।

सर्वो उपनिषदः गोस्थानीयाः । श्रीकृष्णपरमात्मा दोग्धस्थानीयः । अर्जुनश्च वत्सस्थानीयः । क्षीरस्थानीयं च गीतामृतम् । इदं अमृतं सर्वे सज्जनाः पिबन्तु ।

श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता सर्वेषामपि जनानां उत्तमजीवनाय मार्गदर्शिका एतस्य अर्थविवरणय न केवलं

अस्मदेशीयव्याख्यानानि अपि तु पाश्चात्यदेशीयानि व्याख्यानानि च उपक्रान्तानि ।

पुराणेष्वपि गीतायाः महात्वं वर्णितमस्ति–

“गीतायाः पुस्तकं यत्र यत्र पाटः प्रवर्तते ।

तत्राहं निश्चितं पृथ्वि निवसामि सदैव हि ॥”

इति वराहपुराणे ।

Paper No. 18.15: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Psychotherapeutic Techniques in Bhagavad-Gite

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Current lifestyle is pressurizing more on one's mental health. Today everyone is result oriented and needs the result in short span of time. Today man has become greedier. To add upon his target-oriented lifestyle, he is using all sorts of technology, market, financial risks etc. which will spoil his mental health by increased work pressure. The result of which is issues related to physical health as well as mental health. Today major health issues in educated working-class people are mental health. More and more people go to the psychiatric department for treatment. The major treatment in the psychiatric department is counselling wherein the expert and the consultant are discussing in a room to solve the problem. The paper here highlights the discussion between Lord Srikrishna and Arjuna as expert and consultant, wherein all sorts of psychiatric problems and solutions are discussed. The paper also depicts the implementation of the Chapter 2 of Bhagavadgeethe on psychiatric consultations. The paper tries to correlate the meanings of some slokas of the second chapter and tries to give the current relevant meaning to the current psychiatric techniques which are currently used and some new proposal for the consultation.

Methodology/Approach: Study and explanation of slokas from fifty-four to seventy-two. Analyze the meaning of each sloka to the current relevance. Suggestion for the implementation of the above techniques in psychiatry.

Findings/Results: The findings from this paper clarifies the implementation of chapter 2 of the Bhagavadgeethe in psychiatry and clarifies the lifestyle to be followed to lead a better healthier life.

Originality/Value: *Implementation of ancient knowledge in the current environment.*

Paper Type: *Conceptual Research.*

Keywords: Bhagavadgeethe, Sthithaprajna, Desire, Divine consciousness, Life satisfaction

Paper No. 18.16: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

ಕೃಷ್ಣಾರ್ಜುನ ಸಂವಾದ ಗೀತಾಸಾರ

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ABSTRACT**कृष्णार्जुन संवाद गीतासार****ಕೃಷ್ಣಾರ್ಜುನ ಸಂವಾದ ಗೀತಾಸಾರ**

ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತಾ ಮ್ತುಳ್ತಾರಿ ಕೃಷ್ಣ ಅನಿ ಅಜುನಾನ ಯುದ್ಧಭೂಮಿಂತು ಕೆಲ್ಲೆ ಸಂವಾದ ಮ್ತುಣಚೆ ಅಮಕಾ ಸರ್ವಾಂಕ ಕಳಿತಾಕ ಅಸ್ತಾ. ಅಟ್ರಾ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಾಚೆ ಹೇಂ ಪವಿತ್ರ ಗ್ರಂಥಾಂತು ದೋನ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಮಧೆಂ ಚೆಲ್ಲೆ ಭಾಸಾಭಾಸ ಶೋಭಿತ ರೀತಿರ ಚಿತ್ರ ಕಲ್ಯಾ. ಸುರವೆಕ ಹ್ಯಾ ಗೀತಾ ಸಂವಾದಾಂತು ಭಗವಾನ್ ಶ್ರೀಕೃಷ್ಣ ಸ್ವಷ್ಟ ಕರತಾ...

ಗೀತಾಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಮಿದಂ ಪುಣ್ಯಂ ಯಃ ಪಠೇತ್ಯಯತಃ ಪುಮಾನಾ|

ವಿಷ್ಣೋಃ ಪದಮವಾಪ್ನೋತಿ ಭಯಶೋಕಾದಿವರ್ಜಿತಃ||

ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತಾ ಮ್ತುಣಚೆ ಹೇಂ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಖಂಯಚೊ ಮನೀಸ್ ಸಾಂಗತಾಕಿ, ತಾಕಾ ಮೋಕ್ಷ ಮೆಳತಾ ಅನಿ ತೋ ಭಯ-ಶೋಕ ಅಸಲೆ ಬಾಧೆನ ತ್ರಾಸ ಕಾಣು ಘೇನಾ. ಅಮ್ಮಿ ಅಜುನಾಲ್ ಜಾಗೆರ ಅಸ್ತುನು ಚಿಂತನಾ ಕೆಲ್ಲೆರಿ ಅಮಗೇಲೆ ಮನಾಂತು ಉದ್ವಪ ಜಾವಚೆ ಖೂಬ ಸವಾಲಾಕ ಗೀತಾ ಜವಾಬ ದಿತ್ರಾ. ಬೇಜಾರ ಜಾಲ್ಲೆಲೆ ತೆದಾನಾ ಕೃಷ್ಣಾನ್ ಅಜುನಾಕ ಸಾಂಗಿಲೆ ಬೋಧ ಮನಾಕ ಘೆತಲೆರಿ ಅಮಗೇಲೆ ಜೀವನಾಂತು ಯವಚೆ ಹಜಾರಭರ ಸಂಕಷ್ಟಾಕ ಪರಿಹಾರ ಮೆಳತಾ. ಅಮಗೇಲೆ ಮನಸ್ವಯಂ ಚಡತಾ. ಅಟ್ರಾವೆ ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಾಚೆ ಅಖೇರಿಕ ಕೃಷ್ಣ ಪರಮಾತ್ಮ ಅಶಿ ಸಾಂಗತಾ.

ಯತ್ರ ಯೋಗೇಶ್ವರಃ ಕೃಷ್ಣೋ ಯತ್ರ ಪಾರ್ಥೋಽ ಧನುರ್ಧರಃ|

ತತ್ರ ಶ್ರೀವಿಜಯೋ ಭೂತಿಧ್ರುವಾ ನೀತಿಮತಿಮಮ||

ಖಂಯ ಯೋಗೇಶ್ವರ ನಾರಾಯಣ ಅಸ್ತಾ ಧಂಯಿಚ ಧನುರ್ಧರ ಪಾರ್ಥ ಉರತಾ. ಧಂಯಿಚಿ ನೀತಿ ಅನಿ ಸಗಟ ಚಾಂಗ ವಿಚಾರ ಅಸ್ತಾ ಮ್ತುಣಚಿ ಕೃಷ್ಣಾನ್ ಸಾಂಗಚೆ ಸಂದೇಶ ಸಕ್ರಾಂಕ ಬರೆ ವಾಟ ದಾಕಯ್ತಾ.

ವಜ್ರೋತಿಥಿಜ್ಞಃ

ಶ್ರೀಕೃಷ್ಣ, ಅಜುನ, ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತಾ, ಗೀತಾಸಾರ, ಸಂವಾದ

कृष्णार्जुन संवाद गीतासार

भगवद्गीताम्ह्यारीकृष्णानीअर्जुनानयुद्धभूमिंतुकेलिलेसंवादम्हणचेआमकासर्वाककळीताकआस्सा . अट्राअध्यायाचेहेपवित्रग्रंथातूदोनव्यक्तीमधेचलिलेभासाभासशोभीतरीतीरचित्रीतकेल्या.

सुरवेकह्यागीतासंवादातूभगवानश्रीकृष्णस्पष्टकरता...

Keywords: श्रीकृष्ण, अर्जुन, भगवद्गीता, गीतासार, संवाद

Paper No. 18.17: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणे मानवकल्याणाय वर्णितं योगत्रयी

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(तासिका तत्त्वेन) संस्कृत प्राध्यापिका

बाबाजी दाते कला आणि वाणिज्य महाविद्यालय, यवतमाळ, महाराष्ट्र

भ्रमणध्वनी क्र. ९४०५७०९३६७ / ७०२०७२११७५

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प्रस्तावना :-

भारतीयज्ञानपरम्परायां पुराणग्रन्थाः गौरवान्विताः मन्यन्ते | यथा वेदाः ईश्वरस्थाने विद्यन्ते तथैव पुराणग्रन्थानीश्वरस्य निःश्वास प्रचक्षते | न्यायादर्शनुमते – “इतिहासं पुराणं पञ्चमं वेदानां वेदम् |”^१ भारतीयप्राचीनपरम्परायाः विचारान् संमुखी कर्तुम् पुराणशास्त्रम् विद्यमानमस्ति | ‘यस्मात् पुरा भवति तत्पुराणम् |’ इति पुराणस्य परिभाषा | स्कन्दपुराणे उक्तमस्ति - “श्रुतिस्मृती तुनेत्रेद्वेपुराणं हृदयं स्मृतम् |”^२ श्रुतीस्मृत्योः एकस्याज्ञानी काणा, द्वयोः अज्ञानी अन्ध तयं पुराणस्य ज्ञानं नास्ति स तु हृदयहीनः कथ्यते | पुराणस्य आद्याक्षरेण पुराणस्य सङ्ख्या देवीभागवतेकथितमस्ति |

मद्वयं भद्वयं चैव ब्रत्रयं वचतुष्टयम् | अनापलिङ्गकूस्कानि पुराणानि प्रचक्षते ||^३

मद्वय – (१) मत्स्यपुराणम्, (२) मार्कण्डेयपुराणम्

भद्वयं – (३) भागवतपुराणम्, (४) भविष्यपुराणम्

ब्रत्रयं – (५) ब्रम्हपुराणम्, (६) ब्रह्माण्डपुराणम्, (७) ब्रह्मवैवर्तपुराणम्

वचतुष्टयं – (८) विष्णुपुराणम्, (९) वराहपुराणम्, (१०) वायूपुराणम्, (११) वामनपुराणम्

अनापलिङ्गकूस्कानि – (१२) अग्निपुराणम्, (१३) नारदपुराणम्, (१४) पद्मपुराणम्, (१५) लिङ्गपुराणम्,

(१६) गरुडपुराणम्, (१७) कूर्मपुराणम्, (१८) स्कन्दपुराणम्

मर्यादा एवं च व्याप्ती :-

मुख्यपुराणानां सङ्ख्याष्टादश सन्ति एवञ्चवर्णविषयाः अपि बहवः | तथैव योगः अपि बहुविधोऽस्ति | अस्मिन् शोधनिबन्धे श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणे उक्तभक्तियोगकर्मयोगज्ञानयोगानामभ्यासात्मकं विचारः विद्यते |

उद्दिष्ट्यम् :-

- कर्मयोगभक्तियोगज्ञानयोगानां मानवकल्याणाय भागवतपुराणाधारे अभ्यासः
- जीवने भक्तिकर्मज्ञानेभ्यः महत्त्वपूर्णः एवं च श्रेयस्करयोगस्य शोधः

संशोधनपद्धतिः :-

प्रस्तुतशोधनिबन्धाय विश्लेषणपद्धतेः उपयोगः क्रियते |

भागवतपुराणस्य महत्त्वम् :-

श्रीमद्भागवतपुराणम् संस्कृतसाहित्यस्यानमोलनिधीः अस्ति | एतद् निर्मलकल्पतरुः अमृतमयफलं वर्तते | बल्भाचार्येण भागवतं तु महर्षिव्यासस्य सामाधीभाषेत्युक्तम् | भागवतस्य गुढार्थं म्वक्तुं वैष्णवसंप्रदायेन स्वमतानुकुलं व्याख्या कृतातासु प्रमुखतया सुदर्शनसूरी, पदरत्नावली, सिद्धान्तप्रदीप सुबोधिनी, श्रीधर, हरीभक्तरसायन एतेषामाचार्याणां भाष्यग्रन्थाः प्रसिद्धाः सन्ति | सर्ग, प्रतिसर्ग, वंश, वंशानुचरितम् एवं मन्वन्तरमेते पुराणस्य पञ्च लक्षणानि सन्ति | भागवतपुराणस्य द्वे स्कन्दे अल्पशः शब्दभेदेन पुराणस्य दश लक्षणानि कथितानि |

अत्र सर्गो विसर्गश्च स्थानं पोषणमृत्युः | मन्वन्तरे शानुकथा निरोधो मुक्तिराश्रयः ||^४

Paper No. 18.18: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Impact and Influence of Bhagavad-gita on Humanity

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सन्तुष्टःसततयोगीयतात्मादृढनिश्चयः।

मय्यर्पितमनोबुद्धिर्योमद्भक्तःसमेप्रियः॥२(१४)॥

Bhagavan Shri Krishna, in Shrimad-Bhagavad-gita, Bhaktiyoga-chapter 12, verse 14, says that, “when a human being is free from all his hatredness, shows friendly nature and kindness towards all and surrenders all senses and mind to me is my favourite human”, this is how he describes HUMANITY.

But in the present, humans are being opposite to what they had to be and in the name of modernising, developing, being dynamic, competitive etc, are getting cruel, not-merciful, disrespectful, enmity and so on, have forgotten that humanity does exist on earth.

Also Shri Krishna in Moksha-sanyasayoga-chapter 18, verse 71, tells how Shrimad-Bhagavadgita can Impact and Influence the mankind when read or listened with faithfulness, can achieve पुण्यकर्मणां means good deeds and शुभान्लोकान्-better world to live.

This paper focuses mainly on 2 aspects, they are as follows:

1. Societal influence
2. Individual impacts and changes

Keywords: Impact, Humanity, Influence, Mankind, Shrimad-Bhagavadgita, Shri Krishna.

Paper No. 18.19: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

Nutritional Psychiatry Concepts in the Bhagavad Gita and their implications for individual and societal well being

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ABSTRACT

Food is the integral need for human existence, and has deep-rooted impacts on healthful living. The roles of food influencing mental health in varied aspects are much known and have been supported by recent & strong scientific evidences which gave momentum to advanced nutrition concepts like nutritional psychiatry. Nutritional Psychiatry, an emerging field of psychiatry, nutrition and dietetics has gathered much research interest due to recent evidences of nutritional interventions on psychiatric state. Links between nutrition and health are well established and dated long back in Indian cultures and texts from vedic times like sushrutasamhita, ashtangahridyam, etc., in all of which ancient/traditional Indian Medicine systems like Ayurveda, siddha, etc. Another ancient Sanskrit scripture which has lately attracted research interest, particularly during pandemic times, due to psychotherapeutic concepts in it is the Bhagavad Gita which consists of 700 verses or shlokas divided across 18 Adhyayas.

In the present paper, the researchers have identified & indicated specific citations of Bhagavad Gita indicating psychiatric outcomes due to consumption of certain types of foods in diet, which can be considered as strong evidences of nutritional psychiatry concepts. The link between *aahara* and *swabhaavah* had been identified 5000 years ago by Sri Krishna. Sri Krishna's revelation for behaviour modification and unearthing of diet control impacts on mental health holds great significance to humankind, societal well-being, especially the research community interested in the application of Indian knowledge systems for healthcare. This paper can contribute in advancing healthcare researches.

Keywords: Bhagavad Gita, Nutritional Psychiatry, Sri Krishna, mental health, diet control, Indian knowledge systems

Paper No. 18.20: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

ಗೀತೆಯೆಂಬ ಅಮೃತ

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ABSTRACT

ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆನಮ್ಮ ಇತಿಹಾಸದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಹಳ ಮಹತ್ವದ ಗ್ರಂಥ .ಪ್ರಾಚೀನರು ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ ಯನ್ನು ವೇದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳಿದ್ದಾರೆ .ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಸರಿಸಾಟಿಯಾದ ಕೃತಿ ಇಲ್ಲ .ಇದು ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಸಾರವಿರುವ ಗ್ರಂಥ .ಸನಾತನ ಧರ್ಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಋಗ್ವೇದ ,ಯಜುರ್ವೇದ,ಸಾಮವೇದ,ಅಥರ್ವವೇದಎಂದು ಬಹುಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ನಾಲ್ಕು ವೇದಗಳಿವೆ ಮತ್ತುಉಪನಿಷತ್ ನ್ನು ಪಂಚಮವೇದ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತಾರೆ .ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯು ಗೀತೋಪನಿಷತ್ ಎಂದು ಪ್ರಸಿದ್ಧವಾಗಿದೆ .ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ ಯಲ್ಲಿ ಧರ್ಮ ,ಆಸ್ತಿಕಭಕ್ತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಯೋಗದ ಆದರ್ಶಗಳು ಮೋಕ್ಷದ ವಿಚಾರಗಳು, ಜ್ಞಾನ,ಭಕ್ತಿ,ಕರ್ಮ ,ಮತ್ತು ರಾಜ ಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯು ಹಿಂದೂ ಗ್ರಂಥದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಶ್ರೇಷ್ಠವಾಗಿದೆ.ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯು ಈಶ್ವರ,ಪ್ರಕೃತಿ, ಕಾಲ,ಕರ್ಮ ಎಲ್ಲವನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ .ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ ನಾವು ಯಾರು ,ನಾವು ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಇರಬೇಕು, ನಮ್ಮ ಜೀವನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ,ಮನೋಧರ್ಮ ಮತ್ತು ಆಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ.

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಈ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿರುವ ತತ್ವಗಳನ್ನು ನಮ್ಮ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತುಧರ್ಮ ಕರ್ಮಗಳು ಬದುಕನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವ ಕನ್ನಡಿಯಾಗಿದೆ ಎನ್ನುವುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕಿರುನೋಟವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.ವೈದಿಕ ಜ್ಞಾನದಿಂದ ,ಕರ್ಮದಿಂದ ಮೋಕ್ಷ ಸಾಧನೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಬಹುದು .ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಳಿರುವ ತತ್ವಗಳನ್ನುಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಕ್ಕೆತರುವುದರಿಂದ ಮನುಷ್ಯನು ತನ್ನ ಬದುಕನ್ನು ಪರಿಪೂರ್ಣ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಬದುಕಿನ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಶಾಶ್ವತ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬಹುದು ಎನ್ನುವುದನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ .

Keywords: ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ, ಅದರ ಮಹತ್ವ ,ಇಂದಿನ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಅದರ ವಾಸ್ತವಿಕತೆ

Paper No. 18.21: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

कर्मयोगः

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ABSTRACT

“न हि कश्चित् क्षणमपि जातु तिष्ठत्यकर्मकृत्। कार्यते ह्यवशः कर्म सर्वः प्रकृतिजैर्गुणैः (३.५)” इति गीतावचनम्। सर्वैः सदाक्रियमाणम् इदं कर्म। किं तत् कर्म? यत् क्रियते तत् कर्म[कृत+मनिन्]। श्रेयः प्राप्तये यथा ज्ञानमार्गः सहकारी तद्वत् कर्मणः अपि वर्तते एव अपेक्षा। नित्यनैमित्तिकादीनियानि कर्माणि तानि फलाभिसन्धिवर्जितया क्रियमाणानि चित्तशुद्धिहेतूनि भवन्ति। चित्तशुद्धिश्च ज्ञानप्राप्त्युपकारिका। श्रेयससाधनवत् व्यवहारदशायामपि अत्यन्तापेक्षा कर्मणः विद्यते।

“गहना कर्मणो गतिः” इति उक्तत्वात् कर्म-अकर्म-विकर्मणां ज्ञानापेक्षा वर्तते। किं कर्म किं च अकर्म? इति आकांक्षायां ज्ञानप्राप्त्युपायभूतानि फलाभिसंधिरहिततया क्रियमाणानि यानि तानि कर्म। फलाकांक्षया क्रियमाणानि अकर्म इति एकः निरूपणप्रकारः। अपरस्तु देहादीनां या चेष्टा तत् कर्म, तूष्णीं भावः अकर्म इति। द्वितीयः क्रमः तमंशमादाय एव “कर्मण्यकर्म यः पश्येत् अकर्मणि च कर्म यः। स बुद्धिमान् मनुष्येषु स युक्तः कृत्स्नकर्मकृत्(४.१७)” इति निरूपितं गीतायामेव। किमिदं विकर्म? इति चेत् प्रतिषिद्धं एव तत्। कर्मेन्द्रियादिकं नियम्य बाह्यचेष्टामकृत्वा, मनसा एव इन्द्रियार्थान् विषयान् कामयन् यः आस्ते तस्य तादृशं कर्म मिथ्याचारः इति पण्डितैः कथ्यते। इह तु कर्म शरीरपोषणार्था। कर्म अकुर्वतः शरीरपोषणमपि न सुलभम्। कीदृशेन वा कर्मणा इदं साधयामि इति चिन्तनमपि असाधु। तथा मया क्रियमाणेन कर्मणा इदमेव फलमग्रे प्राप्तव्यं इत्यपि एतादृशः निर्णयः जीवने दुःख-क्रोधादीनां उपायो भविष्यति। किं तर्हि कदलीवृक्षमारोप्य कदलीफलं मे भवत्विति आकांक्षा न कार्या वा? इति सामान्याः एतादृशाः सन्देहाः। लक्ष्यं अनादाय न कोपि कर्मणि प्रवर्तते। क्रियमाणे कर्मणि या श्रद्धा सा लक्ष्यप्राप्त्युपायिका एव। किन्तु कदाचित् निर्दिष्टं यत् फलं तद् काले एव यदि नैव प्राप्यते तर्हि ततः लक्ष्यादेव विरक्तिः स्यात्। अतः कर्मफलाफले समत्त्वबुद्धिः स्यात्। तदा लक्ष्यप्राप्तिरपि सुगमा भविष्यति। एवं लोकि अस्मिन् कर्मणः महत्त्वम्। एवं प्रबन्धे अस्मिन् कर्मणः स्वरूपं, माहात्म्यं, विभागाः, इहपरोभयप्राप्त्युपायत्वमित्यादयः विषयाः निरूप्यन्ते।

Keywords- कर्मस्वरूपम्, इहपरोभयप्राप्त्युपायत्वम्, कर्मणः महत्त्वम्।

Paper No. 18.22: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

ಶ್ರೀವಿಷ್ಣುಸಹಸ್ರನಾಮ-ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆ

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ABSTRACT

ಲೇಖನದಸಾರಾಂಶ

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ :-

ಶ್ರೀಮನ್ಮಹಾಭಾರತದ ಅನುಶಾಸನಪರ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಪಿತಾಮಹಭೀಷ್ಮಾಚಾರ್ಯರ ಮುಖಕಮಲದಿಂದ ಹೊರಬಂದಿರುವ ಶ್ರೀವಿಷ್ಣುಸಹಸ್ರನಾಮ ಸ್ತೋತ್ರವು ಸಕಲರಿಗೂ ಅಭೀಷ್ಟಪ್ರದಮಂತ್ರ ಮಾಲಿಕೆ ಎಂಬುದಾಗಿ ಭಗವಂತನಲ್ಲಿ ತಮ್ಮನ್ನರ್ಪಿಸಿಕೊಂಡ ಭಾವುಕರ/ಭಕ್ತರ ಅನುಭವ.

ಪ್ರತಿನಿತ್ಯ ಶ್ರದ್ಧೆಯಿಂದ ಈ

ಸ್ತೋತ್ರವನ್ನು ಪಾರಾಯಣಮಾಡುವ ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಪ್ರಾಚೀನಕಾಲದಿಂದಲೂ ಬಂದಿದೆ.

ಇದು ಮಹಾಭಾರತದ ಭೀಷ್ಮಪರ್ವದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಂದಿರುವ ಶ್ರೀಮದ್ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಂತೆ ಸಾರವತ್ತಾದ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ಮುಕ್ತಿಪ್ರದ ಸ್ತೋತ್ರವೂ ಹೌದು.

ಗೀತೋಪದೇಶವು ಕುರುಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಯುದ್ಧದ ಅವಸರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅರ್ಜುನನಿಗೆ ಉಂಟಾದ ಸಂದಿಗ್ಧ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕ್ಷಾತ್ಯಗವಂತನವದನಾರವಿಂದದಿಂದ ಹೇಗೆ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಿ ತೋಹಾಗೆಯೇ ಈ

ಸ್ತೋತ್ರವೂ ಯುದ್ಧಾನಂತರದಲ್ಲಿ ಯುಧಿಷ್ಠಿರನಿಗೆ ಉಂಟಾದ ಧರ್ಮಸಂದೇಹದ ನಿವಾರಣೆಗಾಗಿ ಭೀಷ್ಮಾಚಾರ್ಯರ ಮುಖಕಂಜದಿಂದ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಿದೆ.

ಇಲ್ಲಿಯಾದರೂ ಸಕಲ ಭಗವದ್ಭಕ್ತರ ಎದುರಿನಲ್ಲಿ,

ಶರಮಂಚದಲ್ಲಿ ಪವಡಿಸಿರುವ ಭೀಷ್ಮಾಚಾರ್ಯರ ಶರೀರದಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಶೇಷ ಸನ್ನಿಹಿತನಾಗಿ ಪರೋಕ್ಷವಾಗಿ ಭಗವಂತನೇ ಧರ್ಮೋಪದೇಶವನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿರುವನು.

ತನ್ನ ಆಯುಷ್ಯದ ಅಧಿಕಭಾಗವನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಜನೆಗೆ ಮೀಸಲಿಟ್ಟು ಸಂಪಾದಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವ ಭೀಷ್ಮಾಚಾರ್ಯರ ಜ್ಞಾನನಿಧಿಯನ್ನು ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸುಭಕ್ತರಿಗೆ ನೀಡುವುದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಸುಮಾರು ಐನೂರು ಅಧ್ಯಾಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಧರ್ಮೋಪದೇಶಬಂದಿದೆ.

Keywords: Sahasranama, Mahabharata, Narayana

Paper No. 18.23: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

A STUDY ON SRI VISHNU SAHASRANAMA IN SANSKRIT

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ABSTRACT

According to Upanishads, Vishnu means a great positive power a strong positive vibrations which is present everywhere even in very particle, people can feel his positive power and vibrations through Sri Vishnu Sahasranama. Sri Vishnu Sahasranama means 1000 names of Lord Sri Maha Vishnu, The 1000 names are in the 108 slokas are segregated and recited individually. Sri Maha Vishnu is considered as one of the main forms of God of Hinduism and he is the supreme god for Vaishnavas. Mantras are impulses which create vibrations in each cell of our body and influence brain strongly. It said that in sanskrit “Manana Trayate iti mantra” which means that Mantra saves us from worries. In this Vishnu Sahasranama is the strong mantra, which is like a Pranayam exercise and after chanting it you feel energised, we have observed the effectiveness of chanting Vishnu Sahastranama every day has lot of health benefits like it controls Depression, Anxiety, stress and cortisol was significantly decreased and blood pressure was regulated within normal limits. It has had great experience and changes in many people’s life. This study provides preliminary evidence for beneficial effects of Sri Vishnu Sahasranama Chanting and recommend further detailed studies in this area to recommend practicing Sri Vishnu Sahasranama Chanting regularly. The aim and intention are to bring the inner meaning of every ritual and practices to focus; so that the new generation understands the values and continues to follow the Vedic principles and mantras.

Keywords : Sri Vishnu Sahasranama, Quality of life, Stress Management, Pranayama

Paper No. 18.24: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

भगवद्गीतायाः प्रभावः परिणामः च

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ABSTRACT

सर्वोपनिषदो गावो दोग्धा गोपालनन्दनः।

पार्थोवत्सः सुधीर्भोक्ता दुग्धं गीतामृतम्महत्॥

अनेन वचनानुसारेण सर्वोपनिषदसारः गीतायाम् अस्ति इति ज्ञायते। उपनिषत् वेदस्य अन्तिमभागः। अतः वेदस्य ज्ञानम् गीतायाः प्राप्तुम्शक्यते। तत्र जीवनमौल्यानि, अस्माकम् संस्कृतिम्, उत्तमवर्तनानि च विवृतम्भवति। एतादृशस्य ज्ञाननिधेः सारः भगवद्गीतायाम् अस्ति। अस्याः प्रभावः तथा परिणामः सर्वत्र प्रत्यक्ष अप्रत्यक्ष रूपेण भवति एव। किमर्थमित्युक्ते भगवद्गीता सर्वदा प्रायोगिकरूपेण चिन्तयति सम्स्यान्परिहरति च। तस्याम् विवृताम्श अनुसरणे सर्वेषां व्यक्तित्व विकसनः निश्चयेन भवति।

सर्वेषां कृते यदा कदापि मनसि आगच्छेत् यत् किमर्थम् कार्यम् करणीयम्? , किमर्थम्

कर्तव्यम्पालनीयम् ?इति। तदा एकम् सुभाषितम् स्मरामि यत्

आहारार्थं कर्मकुर्यादनिद्यम् कार्यादाहारं प्राणसन्धारणार्थम्।

प्राणाः सन्धार्याः तत्त्वविज्ञानहेतोः तत्त्वविज्ञेयं येन भूयो न जन्म॥

तन्नाम कार्यम् कृत्वा आहारं संपाद्य खादित्वा च प्राणस्य रक्षणम् करणीयम्। पश्चात् यत्र मानव जीवनस्य साफल्याय चतुर्विध पुरुषार्थान् सूचितमस्ति, तत्र अन्तिमः मोक्षः तन्नाम भूयः जन्म नास्ति इति, तस्य प्रापणे तत्त्वज्ञानं प्रापणीयम्। तत्तु सर्वोपनिषदसारः भगवद्गीता सुलभतया सरलतया च विवृणोति सर्वोपनिषदसारत्वात्।

इत्यनुसारेण मानवः विषयं वा वस्तुं चिन्तयति। तस्य प्रापणाय सङ्गम् करोति। ततः

कम, क्रोधा, सम्मोहः, स्मृतिविभ्रमः, बुद्धिनाश, पूर्णनाशादि कार्याणि सम्भवति। एतेषां निवारणार्थं

चञ्चलमनसः निग्रहः अवश्यकः। तत्तु अभ्यासेन वैराग्येण च सिद्ध्यन्ति। तदा एव अस्माकम् जीवनम्

सहलम् भवति। एतद् रीत्या बुद्धिनाशः कथम्? तस्य परिहारः कथं इति दृष्टवन्तः। अस्य पालनेन

अवश्यम् जीवनम् सुन्दरं भवति।

Keywords: Impact and influence of Bhagavadgita

Paper No. 18.25: Bhagavad-Gita & Vishnu Sahasranama.

अष्टावक्र गीतायाः अध्ययनम्

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ABSTRACT

राजा जनकस्य , अष्टावक्रस्य च मध्ये यः संवादः अभवत् सः 'अष्टावक्र गीता ' इति कथ्यते। भगवद्गीता, उपनिषद्, ब्रह्मसूत्र एतेषां समानमेव अष्टावक्र गीता अपि एकः अमूल्यः ग्रन्थः इति कथने कापि अतिशयोक्तिः नास्ति। अष्टावक्रः एकः महान् सन्तः, आत्मज्ञानी च आसीत्। जनक महाराजः अष्टावक्रं त्रीन् प्रश्नान् पृच्छति।

कथं ज्ञानमवाप्नोति कथं मुक्तिर्भविष्यति ।
वैराग्यं च कथं प्राप्तमेतद्ब्रूहि मम प्रभो, ॥

गमनीयः एकः विशेषः अंशः अत्र एषः अस्ति- यः प्रश्नं पृच्छन् अस्ति, सः एकः प्रसिद्धः राजा अस्ति स्म, यः आत्मज्ञानं सदृशं अति जटिलं विषयं बोधनं कुर्वन् अस्ति सः केवलं द्वादशवर्षीय एकः बालकः अस्ति स्म ।

अष्टावक्र गीतां अधिकृत्य ये अध्ययनं कर्तुं इच्छन्ति, तेषां कृते अध्ययनयोग्याः अनेकाः विषयाः अत्र सन्ति। अत्र मनोवैज्ञानिकता अस्ति, आध्यात्मिकता च अस्ति। अनुक्षणं मुक्तिप्राप्तिः कथं भविष्यति, गर्भस्थ शिशुः स्वस्य पितरं एवं बोधनं करोति इति अतीवकौतुकभरिताः, अध्ययन योग्याः च विशिष्टविषयाः सन्ति। एतान् सर्वान् विषयान् अवगन्तुं न केवलं बुद्धिः ज्ञानं अपितु एका अन्तर्दृष्टिः अपि आवश्यकता एव।

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Keywords: 14.2 Hindu Religious Literature

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ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸರಬಂಧಿತ ಕೇಶ್ ಸೃಷ್ಠಿಸ್ಥಾನದ ಜೀವನ ಪಾಠಗಳು:

ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆ: ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ವಿವಿಧ ಅಯಾಮಗಳು

ಡಾ. ಸತೀಶ್. ಎ.ಪಿ.¹, ಡಾ. ರಾಜೇಶ್ ಬೆಜ್ಜಂಗಳ್.²

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ರಚನಾಕಾಲ (ಸಾರಲೇಖ)

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ಮಹಾಭಾರತದಂತಹ ಮಹಾಕಾವ್ಯವು ಜನರನ್ನು ಜೀವನದ ನಾನು ತೊಂದರೆಗಳಿಂದ ಪಾರು ಮಾಡುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿದೆ. ಕೃಷ್ಣನು ತನ್ನ ಉಪದೇಶದ ಮೂಲಕ ಅಜ್ಞಾನನಿಗೆ ನೀಡಿದ ಜ್ಞಾನವು ಇಂದಿಗೂ ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯ ಸತ್ಯ, ಪ್ರೀತಿ, ಮದುವೆ, ಕರ್ಮ, ಜೀವನ, ಜನನ - ಮರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಇನ್ನು ಮುಂತಾದ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾಗಿ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಸಾರುತ್ತದೆ. ಅನೇಕ ಅನುಯಾಯಿಗಳ ಅನಂತ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯನ್ನು ಗಳಿಸಿರುವ ಕೃಷ್ಣನು ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವಿಶೇಷವಾದ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹತ್ವದ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಹೇಳಿರುವ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವನ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ವಿವಿಧ ಅಯಾಮಗಳು ಎಂಬ ಶೀರ್ಷಿಕೆಯ ಮೂಲಕ ಇಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ವಚಿಸಲು ಬಯಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿ: ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಪ್ರೀತಿಯನ್ನು ಜೀವನದ ಕೇಂದ್ರ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿ ಚಿತ್ರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಒಬ್ಬರ ಅಧ್ಯಾತ್ಮಿಕ ಪ್ರಯಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರಾಣಯಕ ಅಂಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಗೀತೆಯ ಪ್ರಕಾರ, ದೈವಿಕತೆಗೆ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ಭಕ್ತಿಯ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುವುದು, ಅದು ಅಂತರಿಕ ಶಾಂತಿ ಮತ್ತು ವಿವಿಧತೆಯನ್ನು ತರುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕಾರಣಗಳಿಂದ ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆಯು ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ಮುಖೇನ ಮನುಷ್ಯನಿಗೆ ನೀಡಿದ ಜೀವನಾನುಭವದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನಿಸಿ, ಜೀವನಾನುಭವಗಳ ವಿಸ್ತರಣೆ ಹೇಗೆಲ್ಲಾ ಸಮಾಜದ ಸರ್ವತೋಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಆವರಿಸಿದೆ ಎಂಬ ಸೀಮಿತ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಈ ಲೇಖನ ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿರುತ್ತದೆ.

ಸಮಾರೋಪ:

ಕೊನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ ಭಗವದ್ಗೀತೆ ಜೀವನ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕಲಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಗೀತೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯು ವ್ಯಾಪಕವಾದ ಅರ್ಥಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಒಬ್ಬರ ನಿಜವಾದ ಸ್ವಭಾವ ಮತ್ತು ಉದ್ದೇಶವನ್ನು ಅರಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಕಡೆಗೆ ಒಬ್ಬರ ಪ್ರಯಾಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮತ್ತೊಬ್ಬರು ಪ್ರೀತಿಯ ಕಾರಣಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಅಂಗವಾಗಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರೂ ಪ್ರೀತಿಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಅಂತರಿಕ ಶಾಂತಿ, ಬುದ್ಧಿವಂತಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿವಿಧತೆಯನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸಬಹುದು.

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